

**Analyzing the Success Factors in the development of absorptive
capacity in Service Sector SMEs based in Nigeria**

Submitted by

Olakunle Jamiu Agboola

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Abstract

Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) have been identified as the catalysts and builders for economic growth and national development for both developed and developing countries, particularly Nigeria. To sustain their competitive advantage in a highly competitive landscape, SMEs, in spite of their limited resources, need to effectively learn and use new knowledge to innovate. Therefore, this study, through critical exploration of existing success factors within service sector SMEs based in Nigeria, attempts to highlight the requirements for the effective development of absorptive capacity in these small and medium scale enterprises.

This descriptive qualitative study will be underpinned by the two theories : Absorptive Capacity Theory and Social Exchange Theory. Research questions for this study include how do the SME owner's perception of knowledge exchange and the quality of relationships within small business networks contribute to the development of absorptive capacity, What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve knowledge exchange with other SMES for absorptive capacity development and how do SME owners build and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners in Nigeria.

Questionnaires, Interviews and a focus group were deployed to achieve these research objectives. The questionnaire part had 60 SME owners participating, out of which 20 were handpicked for the interview stage and 6 participants for the focus group. Analysis of Data was done through a thematic analysis. The results revealed five overall themes which are engaging in knowledge exchange, knowledge exchange participation, factors of absorptive capacity, influence of personality, and relationship building. The results indicated the participants received support from engaging in exchange of knowledge and building relationships and that engaging in these activities of knowledge exchange and relationship building help keep SME owners focused in achieving goals.

Keywords: Knowledge exchange, building relationships, absorptive capacity development, SME owners, Absorptive Capacity Theory, Social Exchange Theory

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Chapter 1

1.1 Introduction

Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) are important segment of the economic system, this sector has being identified as catalyst and stimulant for Economic Growth and National Development of either a developed economy, emerging economy or developing economy. The SME sector is known to be the largest employer of labor, it provides the teeming population with business opportunity which can be pursued diligently for the actualization of dreams and vision as an employee or entrepreneur (Memili, Fang, Chrisman, & De Massis, 2015).

Entrepreneurship activities contribute immensely to the economic growth and also help in engaging the business owner productively in economic activities. Apart from job creation, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) bring about healthy competition and provide consumers with large choice of goods and services within the market (Memili et al., 2015). Considering the importance of SME's in the economic growth, ensuring continuous success of the sector becomes very crucial and a critical topical issue.

One of the factors contributing to the increasing success of SMEs is the development of Absorptive Capacity. In line with the study conducted by Turner and Endres (2017), Absorptive Capacity development and effective implementation of the acquired innovative ideas for the success of the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) through the network of numerous stakeholders in the sector was largely classified as very essential.

Absorptive Capacity is the recognition of the importance of innovation through technological and scientific breakthrough, comprehend such innovation and implement it in a brilliant way and also make it an essential part of the organization's process, procedure, practice and organizational mission statement (Cohen and Levinthal 1989, 1990; Zahra and George 2002).

Memili et al. (2015) postulated that SMEs can easily adjust and adapt to economic changes faster than large corporations; further to this, the ability to easily adjust and adapt requires high level technological and managerial know-how.

Absorptive Capacity development in SMEs assist the sector by providing the business with the ability to be prepared and positioned to take advantage of innovation, invention, technological and scientific breakthrough, comprehend and implement effectively and profitably. This essential quality of an entrepreneur was considered an organizational absorptive capacity. The general belief is that absorptive capacity is connected to a set of company's procedures and operational processes which form the bedrock of the company's technological advancement acquisition which they seems to have comprehended, mastered and effectively implement and become very proficient on the skill acquired.

One of the center-point of this study was how SMEs in the service sector cope with the challenges of absorptive capacity development. Skills acquired through Absorptive Capacity development are only beneficial when the SMEs implement effectively to solve existing organizational problems which later had a resultant effect in improving current condition progressively. Absorptive Capacity development posed a great challenge to service sector SMEs thereby hindering them to benefit from technological advancement and managerial development (Yoo, Sawyerr, & Tan, 2016).

The major obstacle in the development of Absorptive Capacity amongst service sector SME's is inadequate resources (man, material and financial) effective implementation and efficient utilization of the acquired innovative idea (Yoo & et al., 2016). The readiness of these SMEs to embrace innovative idea comes with its attendant limitation (Yoo & et al., 2016).

The study is concerned with how development of Absorptive Capacity contributes to the success of service sector SMEs in Nigeria. The study was executed with the use of qualitative descriptive analysis, the information required will be elicited by gathering primary data from the major stakeholders in the service rendering segment of the Nigerian SME sector. Well-structured questionnaires was designed for information gathering, Interviews was conducted for respondents and a focus group was formed to achieve the desired objective of research. The questionnaires was served on 60 (sixty) SME's out of which 20 was randomly selected for the interview stage, 6 (six) emerged from the pool of 20 as the focus group.

Analysis of data was executed using thematic analysis; thematic analysis generated detailed information about the success of Absorptive Capacity development amongst service sector SMEs in Nigeria. The information generated through Thematic Analysis will help in encouraging and incentivize other SME sectors to give absorptive capacity development consideration for an enhanced innovative advancement.

This chapter (Chapter 1) attempts to introduce and justify the need to explore the success of Absorptive Capacity development amongst service sector SMEs in Nigeria. The latter part of the chapter dealt with the background of the Absorptive Capacity Development in the service sector of the SME's in Nigerian SMEs using well-structured questions to elicit fact, useful data and information from the major stakeholders in the service sector of the SME's.

The criteria for adopting a qualitative descriptive study were highlighted, definitions of key terms were provided, assumptions, limitation, and delimitations of the study were touch- lighted. Understanding success of Absorptive Capacity development will help to generate more effective innovation within the real sector of the Nigeria economy.

1.2 Background of the Study

Development of absorptive capacity and its effective implementation is very crucial to the profitability and sustenance of an organization (Sawang & et al., 2016). It is very essential that development of Absorptive Capacity should be one of the mission statements of every SME for it to succeed as a business entity. According to some of the available literature in respect of the history of absorptive capacity, it was reported that this topical issue became very popular among scholars and researchers in the later part of the 20th century. Some critique of this assertion, believed that, absorptive capacity theory was much earlier than the reported period. The criticism was supported with additional notable evidence that Robert Hal carried out a study on factories within the pig iron industry in Cleveland, United Kingdom and discovered that organizations engaged in Absorptive Capacity development in respect of production technique and architectural or engineering design plan as far back as the 17th century (Benkler, 2017).

Through the development of Absorptive Capacity, remarkable growth and success were recorded in the activities of SMEs. Through effective development of Absorptive Capacity and successful implementation of innovative idea, the promoters of SMEs have succeeded in strengthening and bringing SMEs to high level of efficiency. Several definitions of an SME have been put forward by several scholars, the differences in definition have been attributed to varying position and perspective from which each writer approaches the issue. The only generally and widely accepted definition of an SME is given as a business that is privately owned by an individual or partners (Kuckertz & Mandl, 2016). In economics literature, definition of SME's are related to size, such as the number of employees, sales turnover, profitability, net worth etc.

In Nigerian context different scholars have proffered varying definitions of SME. These include the definitions given by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Nigeria Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI), National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND), Centre for Industrial Research and Development (CIRD), National Council of Industries (NCI). The difference in their definitions is related to the stance of their individual policies. In spite of the numerous definition proffered by different agency and regulatory authority, the definition that is being applied for the purpose of an SME in Nigeria is one given by the Bankers Committee of the Central Bank of

Nigeria (CBN). The Bankers Committee of the CBN define SME as any business entity with a maximum asset base of N200million (Two Hundred Million Naira) excluding land and working capital and with the number of employees of the enterprise not less than ten (10) and not more than three Hundred (300), the definition is susceptible to periodic review by the Bankers Committee (CBN, 2001).

It is worthy to note that, an SME is not determined solely by the number of employees in the organization. The level of success recorded is also an important criterion that is being used in the classification; this is basically because SMEs are the largest employer of the Nigeria labor force. With SME's being the engine for economic growth and development, a clearer and safer pathway to survival must be charted. Kuhn and Galloway (2013) found that: "As owners or promoters of SME's synergized within the business network, relevant capacity will be absorbed when there is trust among the owners of the SMEs, this will assist the entrepreneur to be successful. To further improve the success rate, owners of SMES should engage professionally with the veterans within the industry networks. Absorptive capacity development is rewarding only if SME owners assimilate and effectively implement to generate innovative idea.

The study focused on development of Absorptive Capacity and the strength of relationships among the promoters of SME's in Nigeria as it relates to effective implementation of capacity absorbed into innovative idea and success of the SME's. Development of Absorptive Capacity relates to the acquisition of innovative knowledge by the owners of SME through relationship with other owners of SME within the industry network and effective implementation of the strategies for the purpose of the SME (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990; Yoo & et al., 2016). The ability of the entrepreneur to develop absorptive capacity is greatly affected b the relationship strength between SME owners which subsequently translates to assimilation and effective implementation of business strategies for the success of the SME (Olaniran, 2017). When a promoter of SME has built confidence and has trust in other promoters of SME and each member of the network has developed high level of Absorptive Capacity and there is willingness and desire to exchange innovative idea mutually, the strength of the relationships is improved, and capacity absorption is more effective (Olaniran, 2017).

Not much is yet known about the perception of SME's owners regarding knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship within the industry network as regards the development of Absorptive Capacity (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo & et al., 2016). Several research studies carried out in the past suggested that there is need for more research work to be carried out on the effects of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships on effective development of Absorptive Capacity (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo & et al., 2016). Probing into how Absorptive Capacity development is affected from the perspective of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships among the SME's owners in Nigeria will result into an in-depth understanding of effective implementation of the acquired innovative idea and the benefits of building strong synergy among the industry stakeholders (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang et al., 2016). An in-depth understanding of these factors from the perspectives of SME owners will facilitate and guide decision making.

1.3 Personal Motivation

“In an economy where the only certainty is uncertainty, the one sure source of lasting competitive advantage is knowledge” (Nonaka, 1991, page 96)

“Innovation for absorptive capacity is not a new notion; neither is it a phenomenon restricted only to modern times. An analysis of the world today acknowledges the fact, that we live in an environment of constant change. Baumol (2002) contends that the larger part of the economic growth that has ensued since the eighteenth century, is, in great part, attributed to innovation. Change, opportunity, and innovation are all harvested by the entrepreneur and exploited for commercial gain (Burns, 2011). We are living in an era characterized by fierce competition and constant change - a very challenging business environment, where only the best and most versatile survive (Baggio and Cooper, 2010; Fasnacht, 2009).

Firms no longer aim and aspire to achieve sustainable competitive advantage at the local or national level only, but many have their sights set on the global sphere, as it is only in this manner, that they can mitigate the difficulties posed by this modern ecosystem. In this context, innovation is seen as an indispensable tool at the hand of entrepreneurs, a tool that will enable them to exploit change (Drucker, 1993). Policy makers see a very important correlation between innovation and business and economic growth (Baumol, 2002, 1985; Oke, Burke, Myers, 2007; Porter and Ketels, 2003). Innovation puts the firm in a position where it can carry on enjoying existing advantages, whilst endeavouring to create new ones.”

“Innovation is the only source of sustainable competitive advantage that equips the firm to compete successfully with other firms (Morris, 2013; Porter, 1990). Indeed, Porter (1990, page125) concedes “invention and entrepreneurship are at the heart of national advantage.” “By this, Porter ties together two important aspects of national success: primarily, that there is a relationship between invention and Introduction 21 entrepreneurship, as it is, fundamentally, the entrepreneur who takes an invention to the market; and, secondly, that there is a positive correlation between invention, entrepreneurship and national advantage. With the above assertion, Porter is in support of Schumpeter (1934), one of the earliest scholars to associate these three concepts of entrepreneurship,

innovation, and growth. Innovation is very closely dependent upon the market: it gravitates around the entrepreneur's ability to identify and ably penetrate and enable a new market to grow, as much as it depends on the entrepreneur's ability to preserve an already established and mature market. Innovation is measured by the firm's ability to commercialise new products. This feature is not limited only to goods, but it extends also to embrace any organization's capability at developing services.

This clarification is specifically relevant in today's economic scene, where, particularly in developed countries, the services sector dominates the economy, both in terms of value and growth (Uppenberg and Strauss, 2010). In fact, data from the World Bank reveals that the services sector has contributed between 72%-74% of the Gross Domestic Product of the European Union for the period 2005-2014, a proportion that is in excess of the world average, which stands between 66% and 68% for the same period (World Bank, 2017). Indeed, Fasnacht (2009) reveals that the service sector accounts for in excess of 70% of the gross domestic product across the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (Gallouj & Djellal, 2010; Gallouj & Windrum, 2009).

The services sector is also responsible for as much as 75% of cross country differences in economic growth across individual European Union (EU) countries. The rationale of innovation to embrace also services is, therefore, of great relevance to the modern economies. It is imperative for small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) to embrace innovative practices, if they wish to remain competitive and secure their market position (OECD, 2014). SMEs are the pillar of an economy and should not be overlooked when assessing the relevance different-sized firms play in the economy. As many as 70-95% of all firms can be classified as micro enterprises (i.e. employing fewer than ten employees) in countries across the OECD (OECD, 2014), revealing the importance of SMEs in generating wealth Introduction 22 and creating employment across economies. Unfortunately, across the OECD, innovation activities are in the main part carried out by larger firms, in contrast to SMEs, affirming that due priority must be given to the innovative capacity of small and medium sized firms in order to fuel economies and enhance competitiveness.

The innovative SME is recognised as the engine that will fuel this new post modernist knowledge-era (Warren, 2008). Thanks to their size and flexibility, SMEs are more agile than large firms, and therefore, are better

positioned to respond to market changes more speedily than larger firms. Indeed, radical innovation is a vital entrepreneurial activity, and is considered to be the lifeblood of SMEs (Oke, Burke, Myers, 2007; Simon, Houghton, Savelli, 2002). There is no doubt that competitive pressures on all organizations are increasing significantly, particularly, from low-cost developing nations. This, in itself, is rendering the corporate environment an increasingly more challenging one.”

1.4 Research Problems

Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) have been identified as the catalysts and builders for economic growth and national development in Nigeria. The SME sector of the economy provides employment opportunity for the teeming Nigerian population. The inability of the Nigerian government to adequately provide for its teeming population in a way encourage lots of people to embrace SMEs in the pursuit of self-employment, job security and financial freedom (Spremo & Mičić, 2015). Ability to set up an SME provides owners the potential to create wealth based on his/her capabilities and acquired skill (Spremo & Mičić, 2015).Whereas, If the survival rates of SME's fail to improve persistently, there will be decline in the job creation which then creates an adverse effects for the economy (Small Business and Entrepreneurial Council, 2016).

Not much is yet known about the perception of SME's owners in respect of knowledge exchange and the strength of relationships within their business network as it contributes to the development of Absorptive Capacity (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo & et al., 2016). Target population for this research included service sector small business owners in Nigeria. To select SME owners for the sampling, the researcher identified SME's owners' with much experience in knowledge sharing activities through the chambers of commerce in Nigeria and the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME). Small business owners within this sampling provided greater insight into the challenges impeding the development of Absorptive Capacity with special focus on the role of knowledge exchange and strength of the relationships with other SME owners. The insights provided strategies to overcome challenges in absorptive capacity development and cultivating impactful relationships with other small business owners:

The research problems are numbered below:

1. Researching into the techniques the owners of service sector SMEs employ in developing Absorptive Capacity within the industry's network offers a blueprint to be adopted by new entrants into the sector for quick growth and result oriented performance. The new entrants and the less experienced SME owners

will be confronted with challenges on how to effectively implement the innovative idea acquired for the success of the business with their inadequate available resources.

2. Another challenges required to be surmounted by new entrants is building confidence and trust in the acquired capacity also ability to express the challenges being faced by the business freely without holding back among other owners of the SME within the industry's network (Hui-Ru, Min, & Pian-Pian, 2016). Developing formidable techniques for Absorptive Capacity through the strengthening of the synergy among the owners of SME's can successfully assist in navigating through those challenges.
3. Exploring into the development of Absorptive Capacity, and the strengthening of the synergy among owners of SME's is responsible for quick growth stability and performance driven ability of the less experienced owners of SMEs, this is made possible by developing formidable strategies for capacity absorption. Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) stipulated that owners of SME's can absorb capacity and disseminate same within the industry's network only with the owner's willingness and desirability.
4. The development of the Absorptive Capacity will be effective only if the SME's has ability to efficiently implement and take advantage of the innovative idea acquired (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). If the owner of SME's failed to see the value and benefits of developing Absorptive Capacity and strengthening of the relationship among the owners of SME's within the network in the right perspective, the process will be less effective because of non-existence of confidence and mutual trust (Olaniran, 2017). Social Exchange Theory (SET) identifies that strengthening of synergy among the owners of SME's depends mainly on trust and desires of the SME owners to engage effectively on the industries network (Blau, 1986).

The study offered two basic advantages, the first include bolstering the ability of newly established service sector SME owners to develop strong absorptive capacity through quality relationship with other SME owners. The second include increasing the ability to effectively implement innovative ideas to proffer solutions to some fundamental problems typically associated with SMEs in Nigeria thereby leading to the growth of SMEs. The

aforementioned advantage of the study provided an in-depth understanding of absorptive capacity which support the implementation of an efficient support system for service sector SME owners and while also ensuring stronger synergy for an enhanced absorptive capacity development.

There are two forms of Absorptive Capacity development; explanatory study conducted by Yoo & et al. (2016) postulated that technical and non-technical type of Absorptive Capacity development, directly impact the effectiveness of innovative idea implementation. The frequencies and consistency of participation in Absorptive Capacity development process by the owners of the SME through effective synergy with other owners of SME was statistically responsible for its success (Yoo & et al., 2016). The more the owners of service sector of the SMEs engaged consistently and continuously in Absorptive Capacity development process with the same set of SME owner in the industry network, the greater the confidence, trust and familiarity improved (Yoo & et al., 2016).

Where there is absence of trust among SME's owners in the network, the readiness and desire to develop Absorptive Capacity will be low (Olaniran, 2017). The owners of SME's that are involved in the development of Absorptive Capacity must be ready to establish a mutually beneficial relationship.

This study attempts to probe into the shortcomings of developing Absorptive Capacity among service sector of the SME owners facilitates the in-depth understanding of how to effectively implement innovative idea absorbed for the success of the SME (Yoo et al., 2016). In addition, the study dwelt on the perceptions of the strength of the relationship among the owners of the service sector of the SME's (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016). The study employed the use of a well-structured questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group, this method of data collection facilitated the identification of the themes indicating how the owners of SME's take advantage of Absorptive Capacity development within the industry's social network.

The data elicited from the explanatory study provided detailed information on the previous quantitative research by highlighting the experiences and perceptions of service sector of SME's (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo & et al., 2016). SME owners will be better able to comprehend the tactics to be adopted for

successful development of absorptive capacity through the evaluation of the themes that came up in the analysis part. Effective implementation of Absorptive Capacity development process has a successful impact on the performance of the SME. Through the development of Absorptive Capacity, owners of SME's through mutual exchange of ideas overcome the shortcomings of the industry.

Absorptive Capacity development is fast turning out to be an important must-do for the SMEs in the service sector. This concept depends heavily on the strength of the relationship among the owners of SME's (Man-pil, Bongihn, & Joon-ho, 2017). Development of Absorptive Capacity becomes very useful when there is existence of positive relationship among the owners of SME's within the industry network and there is high level of confidence and trust which will encourage every SME owners to mutually contribute to the pool without holding back any fact (Olaniran, 2017).

1.5 Research Aim and Objectives

The principal aim for carrying out this qualitative descriptive research study is to examine how SME's owner's perceived knowledge exchange and the strength of relationships within industry's social network as it contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity amongst service sector of the SME's in Nigeria.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) represent a substantial percentage of Nigeria's economy, presently these SMEs create the bulk of the employment opportunity in the country. Similarly, SMEs have helped in the promotion of entrepreneurship and utilization of indigenous technology thereby acting as agent and promoter of Import substitution policy.

The objectives of the research study include to:

- 1) Gain an in-depth understanding in respect of the experience of SME's owners' with knowledge exchange and perceptions of relationships with other SME's owners through a questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group discussion.
- 2) Identify the strategies adopted by SME's to develop Absorptive Capacity through effective knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships.
- 3) Expand the current research by evaluating the ability of SME's owners in the appropriate utilization of knowledge exchange which is a form of collective learning technique for SME owners to achieve success.
- 4) Recommend a framework on how small business owners leverage resources such as time and technology to exchange knowledge and cultivate impactful relationships with other small business owners.
- 5) Contribute to Absorptive Capacity Theory and Social Exchange Theory as well as also advice policy makers and Service Sector SME owners on the development of absorptive capacity.

Knowledge exchange among SME owners is a system which is often called "collective learning" (Sawang & et al., 2016) which has been shown by previous studies to improve comprehension and rate of assimilation in an

organizational set up (Sawang & et al., 2016). Submissions from previous research revealed that collective learning improves organizational learning and its success (Sawang & et al., 2016). Collective learning afforded the owners of the service sector of the SME the opportunity to synergize profitably with other owners in the network for the purpose of the SME growth and improved performance.

To broaden the scope of the current research, this study explored how owners of SME have developed Absorptive Capacity within the industry network which is a form of collective learning for effective implementation and efficient utilization of the innovative idea for the purpose of the SME. (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo & et al., 2016). Collective learning is an important learning technique for the owners of SME to enhance credible performance for the growth and success of the SME. The increase in the awareness about the importance of SME and entrepreneurship in the institutions of higher learning and among the professional (employees) at different cadre of employment lay emphasis on the need to provide infant SME and their owners with resources to develop Absorptive Capacity and also encourage mutual synergy among the owners of the SME's (Infants and the Veterans) in order to enhance the operations of the SME (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). Exploring deeper into Absorptive Capacity development and how credible relationship are built among the owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria can assist the infant SME owners to understand the nitty-gritty of the industry based on the past experiences shared. The process of developing Absorptive Capacity and ability to enhance the synergy among the owners of SME provide a guideline for the study and allows a deeper understanding of the perception of SME owners in Nigeria.

1.7 Research Questions

The following research questions will provide the required guidelines for this study:

- ❖ RQ1: How does SME owners' perception of knowledge exchange and quality of relationships with other SME's aid the development of absorptive capacity?
- ❖ RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve knowledge sharing with other SMES?
- ❖ RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners?

RQ1 is the major focus of this study which also underpins RQ2 and RQ3. RQ1 was very useful in understanding how the ability of SME owners in absorbing and transferring knowledge back into the business affects the development of absorptive capacity. RQ1 also provided personal insights into participant perception of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship with other SME owners which helped to understand how knowledge exchange and quality of relationships affects the development of absorptive capacity.

RQ2 was helpful in describing approaches deployed by SME owners towards improving the capitalization of knowledge exchange opportunities. SME owners that were interviewed came from differing backgrounds with varying personalities which helped to get a broader image of the many obstacles being faced in the process of knowledge exchange as well as the different approaches SME owners use in tackling these obstacles.

An in-depth understanding of factors affecting the development of absorptive capacity will reveal other factors besides perception of knowledge exchange. Strength of the relationships is another factor that affects the absorptive capacity development for SME owners. RQ3 was instrumental in exploring how quality of relationship with other SME owners affect the development of Absorptive Capacity by enabling the collection of data on the impactful nature of relationships as well as approaches used by SME owners to initiate and/or develop relationships with other SME owners.

RQ1 and RQ2 are both connected to the Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT). Through RQ1, data was

collected which showed how each participant in the study identify opportunities to engage in knowledge exchange. RQ2 on the other hand delved into the ability to transfer knowledge back to the organization as well as the attendant obstacles. Between RQ1 and RQ2, an image is created of the perception of knowledge exchange by each participant as well as approaches deployed to tackle knowledge exchange challenges towards the development of Absorptive Capacity.

RQ1 and RQ3 on the other hand are linked to the Social Exchange Theory (SET). Strength of the relationships is another highly influential factor in the development of Absorptive Capacity. SET made it possible to examine how each participant navigates the process of cultivating relationships. Through Research Question 1 (RQ 1), strength of the relationships are considered to be very essential in the building of trust in respect of the sources of the knowledge to be exchanged. Research Question 3 (RQ 3) provided different experiences of the SME owners in deploying resources such as technology and time to develop relationships with other SME owners. The Social Exchange Theory provided the background for the elucidation of individual experiences from RQ1 and RQ3.

Collectively; RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3 jointly filled the long existing void in the literature. This vacuum in literature was identified as exploring how small business owners' perception of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). By using the three research which were the signal board for the research study, individual experience of the SME's owners were elicited in respect of Absorptive Capacity development through knowledge exchange and dependable relationships.

1.7 Researcher's Contribution and Significance of the Study

Previous research carried out by scholars have failed to examine the involvement of the service sector of the SME's in Absorptive Capacity development and the strengthening of the synergy with other owners of SME in the network. Working to fill the void will provide insights into the varying experience of the individual owner of SME and its attendant benefits; it will also make available scholastic material in respect of the literature (Turner & Endres, 2017). The research carried out by Turner and Endres (2017) opined that future research study should focus on Absorptive Capacity development process in the multivariate sector of the SME's (Turner & Endres, 2017). Interestingly, Turner and Endres (2017) covered only coffee shop owners in his work, therefore involving other sectors of the SME will provide detailed insights into Absorptive Capacity development.

The absence of adequate literature was identified and this formed the basis for evaluating how owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria were able to effectively develop Absorptive Capacity and strengthen the relationships among others owners of the SME for the success of the SME (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). Data gathering among individual owners of service sector SMEs in respect to developing effective Absorptive Capacity through exchange of knowledge and strengthening the relationship with other owner of the SME's was made possible through the research questions developed.

By examining SME with a varying number of employees, less experienced owners of SME's highlighted different techniques adopted for improving Absorptive Capacity development. Developing Absorptive Capacity does not connote automatic innovation. Development of Absorptive Capacity and the strengthening of the relationship among the owners of SME's are the main contributing factors for successful implementation of innovative idea (Sawang & et al., 2016; Yoo et al., 2016). A good number of less experienced owners of service sector of the SME in Nigeria are unaware that innovative idea in an organization develops through socialization, externalization, and internalization (Wipawayangkool & Teng, 2016). To develop organizational capacity effectively, the owners of service rendering segment of the SME must be ready to surmount the limitations and barriers hindering development of Absorptive Capacity.

Yoo & et al. (2016) carried out quantitative study adopting Absorptive Capacity technique and the relationships of owners of SMEs as the main contributing factors to successful implementation of innovative idea for the growth of the SME. The study carried out by Yoo & et al also identified the level of technical and managerial know-how as an important factor in developing Absorptive Capacity among the owners of SME's (Yoo & et al., 2016). It should be noted that relationship factors, such as confidence and trust in the process and also the willingness and desires of the owners of the SME to effectively implement acquired innovative idea (Yoo & et al., 2016). The research by Yoo & et al pointed it out that future research should be directed on the study of how Absorptive Capacity development and the strengthening of the relationship among SME's owners and as it positively impact effective implementation of innovative and the general success of the alliance (Yoo & et al., 2016).

Previous study concluded declared that, development of Absorptive Capacity is only effective when the innovative idea acquired perfectly fit the requirement of the owners of the SME in the network (Sawang & et al., 2016). For Absorptive Capacity development to be effective it must accommodate specific needs of owners of the SME's in the network. External capacity absorbed by individual owner of the SME'S and the ability of the owner of the business to effectively implement the absorbed capacity for the success of the business, this stimulates organization learning (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017).

By evaluating the experiences and perceptions of the owners of SME's, this research has been able to contribute to the available literature and fill the long existing void by making available qualitative data with rich industry value which can proffers solutions to curtail the challenges confronting the development of Absorptive Capacity and the existing relationship with other owners of the SME's within the network.

Two main theories propounded to serve as the bedrock for this research work are the Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) as well as the Social Exchange Theory (SET). Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) is propounded by Cohen and Levinthal (1990), the theory described Absorptive Capacity development as the ability to absorb knowledge. Through Absorptive Capacity development, knowledge exchange is said to occur in two stages. The first stage has to do with the individual expressing willingness to absorb external knowledge (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). This is immediately followed by the second stage; the second stage is the ability of the SME's to absorb

knowledge from the individual SME's owners (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). The first stage may be influenced by relationship factors while the second stage might be influenced by technological resources. By jointly evaluating Absorptive Capacity development alongside the role of strength of the relationship, the two stages of knowledge exchange will be examined through the experiences shared by the SME's owners. This study intends to contribute to Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) through the examination of how SME's owners overcome the challenges associated to the development of Absorptive Capacity.

The Social Exchange Theory (SET) established by Peter Blau provides the second background for this study. Peter Blau, was credited with creating the framework for the behavior and interaction of individuals in a social setting (Blau, 1986). He subsequently discovered that the reason for interaction and how much individuals end up interacting is a function of trust and a mutual desire to share with both factors helping to cultivate better relationship (Olaniran, 2017). This research aspires to contribute to the Social Exchange Theory (SET) by reviewing how SME owners perceive relationships as regards to knowledge sharing experiences.

1.8 Research Methodology Rationale

The type of research design adopted for this study is qualitative descriptive study. Quality data, sourced primarily is required in the study to exhibit the individual experience of the owners of service sector SME's. Qualitative descriptive research study method explained the main reasons behind the statistical data generated by quantitative study (Yin, 2014). A good evaluation and comprehension of the results presented in previous researches carried out by different scholars' facilitates the creation of guidelines for SME owners to develop Absorptive Capacity and also strengthen the quality of relationships with other SME owners within the network.

Qualitative descriptive study provides a detailed description of the experience of every individual owner of the SME within the industry network. The void in the scholastic literature forms the guiding principle in selecting the methodology for this study. Several quantitative studies carried out had failed to probe into individual experience of owners of SME's in the development of Absorptive Capacity through role played by quality relationships with other SME owners within the network (Park & Park, 2016). Qualitative study on the other hand recognizes the experience of individual owners of SME's which provides adequate data to enlarge the horizon of the previous quantitative research.

The experiences of each SME owner vary based on how the particular SME had succeeded in adapting to limitations and barriers to the development of Absorptive Capacity. The collation of varying degree of experiences provided by the owners of the SME to identify what activities have helped the SME with a detailed understanding. With the aid of the reports, the less experienced SME owners can benefit extensively for the success of the SME. For the reasons stated above, a qualitative descriptive study was most desirable.

Qualitative descriptive research method was adopted for the purpose of this study; qualitative research measures human nature and experiences (Colorafi & Evans, 2016). Good understanding of human behavior and experiences in developing Absorptive Capacity and strengthening of the relationship among the owners of SME's within the network is very important in finding solution to issues raised in the research questions.

A qualitative descriptive study creates room for the exploration and the exhibition of the individual experience of owners of SMEs. This study presented an open-ended questionnaire, well-articulated interview questions to capture every individual SME owners' perception and experiences. Through well-articulated and or unstructured questions, qualitative research is very effective in obtaining detailed facts (Park & Park, 2016). The open-ended questionnaire and the well-articulated interview questions formed the basis which guided the owners of SMEs in responding appropriately to the questions by giving the participants' the honour of using their discretion in the course of the discussion (Yin, 2014).

The research study captured and displayed the experience of the SME owners and the innovative idea acquired within the network. Social Exchange Theory (SET) asserted that being opened and willingness to share individual experiences by SME owners contributes towards development of Absorptive Capacity and the cultivation of better relationships amongst SME owners in the network (Blau, 1986). This study recognized how SME owners surmount the limitations and barriers confronting development of Absorptive Capacity (Yoo et al., 2016).

The desire for deeply rich data means that a quantitative approach is not suited for this particular study. The use of Quantitative research has to do with testing if a hypothesis is true or not by making use of structured questioning (Yin, 2014). Correlations have been found by past quantitative research amongst knowledge sharing, developing relationships and absorptive capacity. However, the quantitative research cannot explain the vacuum in the literature as to the experiences of the SME owners in respect of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships among the SME's owners and its effects Absorptive Capacity development.

1.9 Research Design Methods for the Study

This qualitative study adopted the use of descriptive study design to examine how SME owners' perceived knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships within the owners' network and its contribution to the development of Absorptive Capacity. The qualitative descriptive study provides detail analysis of the individual SME owners' representation of a population (Colorafi, & Evans, 2016). Questionnaires involve the sampling of 60 SME owners, the questionnaires sample size serve as the selection pool where the SME's owners that participated in interview sessions and focus group discussion were randomly selected. A focus group provided a detail explanation of the challenges and strategies adopted in curtailing the challenges of participating in Absorptive Capacity development through the guided discussions among SME owners.

The convenience sampling method provides the selection process of SME's owners for the interview participant who had some level of experience in Absorptive Capacity development. The convenience sampling is the result of the researcher selecting participants who adequately represents the general population (Yin, 2014). The selection consisted of 30 participants that portrayed the characteristics that offered quality and reliable data required for the success of the research study (Yin, 2014). However, saturation for the interview participants occurred around 25 interview sessions (Yin, 2014). Selecting 30 SME's owners to participate in the interview session ensured saturation without repeating the selection process. The qualitative descriptive study employed the use of questionnaire, interview, and focus group to collate the required data for the research study. The unit of measurement for the qualitative descriptive study is SME owner. If the SME's ownership structure is not a sole proprietorship, only one director or partner of the SME will participate in the interview.

Grounded Theory is not appropriate for the purpose of this research study because the objective of the research study is not to develop a new theory (Morse et al., 2016). A narrative qualitative study provides information about only one individual owner of the SME's (Smith, 2015). A narrative research design was not selected because it has limitations in area of depth and quality of the data, a narrative research design excludes the response of other respondent to the questionnaire or the interview. A phenomenological qualitative research design focuses on the

actual experience of an individual and goes further to offers a subjective interpretation for the experience of the individual (Smith, 2015).

The research work focus mainly on the development of Absorptive Capacity through the roles of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship among SME owners. A qualitative descriptive study provided the instruments needed to collate detailed data by exploring the development of Absorptive Capacity through the roles of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship among SME owners (Yin, 2014). The questionnaire make allowance for the researcher to engage the owners of the SME's to participate in external Absorptive Capacity development as well as to evaluate the factors that contribute to the strengthening of the synergy among the owners of SME within the network. The questionnaire encourages the gathering of data which displayed the patterns of participation of individual owners of the SME (Yin, 2014).

The interviews covers the details of the updates provided by individual owner of the service sector of the SME's in the development of the Absorptive Capacity, the questionnaire provided useful data in establishing the perceptions of individual owners of the SME's in the development of Absorptive Capacity process. The questionnaire also offered insights on the owners of the SME's self-perceptions of their personality.

The interview allowed the researcher to observe the perception, countenance and posturing of individual owners of the SME's (Yin, 2014). The focus group creates room for the collection of quality data within a smaller sample size of the owners of the SME's. By including a focus group, the possibility of engaging in a mutual discussion of Absorptive Capacity is ensured (Yin, 2014).

The thematic analysis of the focus group discussion provided additional data to support the report of the interviews. Additionally, the data provided information in respect of the individual SME owners engaging professionally in the development of Absorptive Capacity and the strengthening of the synergy among owners of SMEs.

1.10 Terms of Reference

Using search engine optimally in internet based education requires a good understanding of the communication technology and the terminologies being put to use in delivering messages

There are different definition in respect of terminologies used in this research study, for the purpose of the research study, the following definitions is applicable. Definitions of terms will be elaborately discussed in chapter two of this study.

For the purpose of this research study, the following terminologies were put to use:

Absorptive Capacity: This is explained as the SME owner's ability to absorb knowledge and capacity as well as the desire to implement same for the success and improved performance of the SME's (Yoo & et al., 2016) which is dependent on variables like the SME's financial, human capital or technical resources.

Competition: Competition is the situation in which people or business competes with each other for share of the market which that are limited in size or in quantity.

Outsourcing: Outsourcing is the process whereby a part of organization economic activities is contracted or ceded to another organization for execution; it is done to either save production cost or time. Outsourcing relied on principle of comparative advantage, where the SME resources are directed to the production of goods and services they can provide efficiently and contracting the the production of the goods and services that will strain the SME's resources to another SME.

Knowledge Exchange: Knowledge exchange is refers to as the collaborative learning within the context of SME's owners networks, knowledge exchange is the process whereby SME owners desire to work together and exchange individual experiences (Sawang & et al., 2016).

Small and Medium Enterprises (SME): A small and Medium Enterprises (SME) is any enterprise with a maximum asset base of Two Hundred Million Naira (N200million) excluding land and working capital, and with

the number of personnel employed by the enterprise not less ten(10) and not more than (300). This definition is however subject to periodic review by the Bankers Committee of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2001).

Small and Medium Enterprises Owners' Network: Tunde & Endres , 2017 explained that “Networking is the social connections made among individuals with common interest and goals. Within the SME’s industry, the SME’s owner networking is the process of creating connections essential to the growth and sustainability of the SME”. The strength of the relationships within the network of SME owners’ can boost formation of innovative ideas while also increasing the rendering of useful advice based on individual SME’s owners’ experience (Sawang & et al., 2016).

Strength of the Relationship: The strength of the relationship is the quality of relationship with another individual owner of SME (Ismail, 2014). In addition, the relationship strength is the ability of the organization to progressively carry on developing relationships with other SME owners (Ismail, 2014). Building strong relationships among SME owners improves the productivities of the SME’s (Ismail, 2014).

1.11 Assumptions, Limitations, Delimitations

In this section, assumptions, limitations as well as delimitations are defined and the rationales for all the axioms are provided after each definition.

1.11.1 Assumptions:

The definition of an assumption is an unproven belief in research but is necessary in order to conduct the research (Simon & Goes, 2015). The reliability of research cannot merely depend with the belief in assumptions being true (Simon & Goes, 2015). Research reliability depends with addressing how assumptions will be addressed (Simon & Goes, 2015).

The research study is based on following assumptions:

1. It was assumed that the questionnaire respondents in this study are truthful and very honest in answering questions posed to them and that the
2. It was assumed that SME owners provided answers in utmost good faith and to their best ability.
3. Owners of service sector SMEs with less experience have been confronted with similar obstacles and challenges as opposed to owners of SME with much and vast experience
4. Another assumption made is that this research work represents an accurate picture of how Absorptive Capacity development is affected by knowledge exchange as well as strengthening of the relationship among the owners of service sector SMEs within the industry's network.

1.11.2 Limitations:

These are the factors which negatively impact the study and are out of the control of the researcher (Simon & Goes, 2015). For a qualitative study, reliability and validity present more limitations than in quantitative studies (Simon & Goes, 2015). Limitations for a case study consist of the behaviors of individual owner of the SMEs (Simon & Goes, 2015).

1. Focus group may not be proper representative of the larger population.
2. Irrelevant discussions may consume focus group time.
3. Owners of service sector SMEs may not complete the questionnaires appropriately.
4. In developing the interview guidelines, there could be bias in the questions presented.

1.11.3 Delimitations:

The choice of the problem by the researcher creates the first delimitations (Simon & Goes, 2015). Delimitations arise from the decision to select one possibility over another possibility (Simon & Goes, 2015). Delimitations can exist in the objective, theoretical framework, and even the selection of participants (Simon & Goes, 2015).

1. Delimitation to this study is that interview participants selection was restricted to the response provided by the questionnaire participants.
2. The number of the selected participants for the questionnaire is an insignificant representation of the general population of the service sector SMEs. This is further trimmed down for the purpose of the interview sessions thereby making a smaller representation.
3. Delimitation of questionnaire participants was selected by the researcher from the list of SME owners culled from The Chamber of Commerce directory for both the Nigerian American Chamber of Commerce (NACC) and the Nigerian British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC)) as well as the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME).
4. The scope of evaluating the importance of developing of Absorptive Capacity and the strengthening of the synergy among owners of SME were only two factors influencing effective implementation of the acquired innovative idea.

Other factors that influence effective implementation of the acquired innovative idea include factors like topic relevancy, the experience and qualifications of the knowledge provider, the source of the knowledge, and frequency of participating in Absorptive Capacity development process.

1.12 Summary and Presentation of the Remaining Parts of the Study

This qualitative descriptive study aims to evaluate how SME owners perception of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships within SME's industry's network contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity in service sector SMEs in Nigeria. Absorptive Capacity development in SME's can be traced to the 19th century, during the pre-industrial revolution era, Robert Hall carried out a researched study on factories within the pig iron industry in Cleveland, United Kingdom, through the study, Robert Hall discovered that companies were known to have being involved in the exchange of important information in respect of manufacturing techniques and facility design plans as early as the 1850s (Benkler, 2017). Absorptive Capacity development provided SME's owners unrestricted accessibility to up to date innovation idea and experiences from other SME owners.

Absorptive Capacity development helps in strengthening SMEs. The research design of this study is to evaluate the two principal factors affecting effective development of Absorptive Capacity in the service sector of the SMEs in Nigeria. The vacuum created in the literatures and the need to evaluate how SME's owners' perceived knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships among SME's owners within the SME's industry's social network and its contribution to the development of Absorptive Capacity (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016).

The Absorptive Capacity Theory as well as the Social Exchange Theory served as the guideline and framework for the research study. SET is significant in explaining how individual SME interact within social settings and the influence of trust and confidence in gaining acquiring innovative idea (Blau, 1986). ACT provides insight as to how SME's seeks to absorb capacity (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990).

Chapter 1 introduced the research topic by establishing the problem statement and gap in literature. Factors such as relationships, the type of knowledge and the level of participation influence effective implementation of the acquired innovative idea for the success of the SME (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). Previous studies carried out revealed that relationships influenced development of Absorptive Capacity. The current research attempted to fill the existing void by evaluating the development of

Absorptive Capacity and the strengthening of the relationships among the owners of service sector of the SME's in Nigeria.

The targeted population size includes the owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria. A qualitative descriptive study was used to collect data using a questionnaire, in-depth one-on-one interviews, and a focus group. Participants for the questionnaire were culled from The Chamber of Commerce directory for the Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce (NACC), the Nigerian-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC) and The Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME).

The participants for the interviews were selected using a convenience sampling through their responses on the questionnaire. Questionnaire responses also provided the participant selection pool for the focus group. The questionnaire sample included sixty (60) owners of service sector SMEs. Twenty (20) SME owners participated in one-on-one interviews out of which Six (6) owners went on to participate in the focus group. The data collected was analyzed using thematic method of analysis.

The basic assumptions for this study is that questionnaire respondents are truthful and not deceptive with their answers and that the participants answered questions with utmost good faith, honesty and to the best of their ability, this research is an accurate representation of Absorptive Capacity and the impact of the strengthening of the relationships among service sector of the SME owners. Owners of the SMEs with less experience are likely to have been confronted with similar impediments and challenges as opposed to owners of the owners of SME's with much experience.

The delimitations of the study has to do with the fact that selection of the interview participants were made from the pool of the questionnaire respondents. Also, sample size of the selected participants for the questionnaire represents an insignificant percentage of the general population size of the service sector owners of the SME's

Another important delimitation of the study is that the questionnaire participants were selected from the Chamber of Commerce websites of the Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce (NACC), the Nigerian-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC) and the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME).

The research limitations include focus group which may not be an appropriate representative of the larger population, irrelevant discussions, incomplete questionnaires, and existence of bias in the questions presented.

Chapter two of the study focused on the literatures which presented the importance of SMEs to the economy in Nigeria and the support structures currently in place to help in stimulating the success of SME's. The literature review outlined how SME's develop Absorptive Capacity and the impact the strengthening of synergy among the owners of SME's with other owners of SME's for effective implementation of the acquired innovative idea for the success of the SME.

Previous research has shown that Absorptive Capacity development and the strengthening of the relationship among service sector of the SME's owners' serves as the bedrock for effective implementation of the acquired innovative idea for the success of the SME (Yoo et al., 2016). Olaniran (2017), this suggests that Absorptive Capacity development depends on positive relationships built on confidence, trust and openness. The current study was supported by prior empirical research which recommended the exploration of how SME owners' perceived knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships among the SME's owners in the industry's social network and its contribution to Absorptive Capacity development (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016)

Chapter three presents the research methodology adopted for use. A qualitative descriptive study was identified as the appropriate approach to examine the process of the small business owner's knowledge sharing, quality of relationships and absorptive capacity. According to Yin (2014), qualitative research explores the phenomenon conducted in natural settings. Techniques such as interviews, observations, individual experiences, introspection and productions provided the data for qualitative research (Yin, 2014). Data validation in qualitative research relies on triangulation using multiple sources of data (Yin, 2014). A questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group

provided the required data for this study. Yin (2014) states that triangulation provides quality data and its validity allows the researcher to obtain detailed perspective of the process.

Chapter 4 provides an analysis of the collected data using thematic method of analysis. A thematic analysis is presented in Chapter 4.

Chapter 5 provided the researcher's interpretation of the study based on the result from the thematic analysis while Chapter 6 presents the conclusion and recommendation as well as a summary of assumptions, limitations, delimitations, and suggested future research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Chapter Introduction

The main purpose of this qualitative descriptive research was to examine how owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria perceive knowledge exchange and the strength of relationship with other SMEs as contributing to the development of Absorptive Capacity (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016).

“Irrespective of the size and nature of business, firms now have to contend with global competition (Barrett and Peterson, 2000). Innovation is the catalyst which firms need to adopt to thrive in today’s modern aggressive business environments. Innovation is not a new notion, neither is it a phenomenon restricted only to modern times. Indeed, history reveals to us that there seems to be a constant inherent quest by mankind to execute things in a new, improved and better manner. One has but to analyse the world we live in today to acknowledge the fact, that, indeed, we live in an environment of constant change.” According to Drucker, (1993), “innovation is the specific tool of entrepreneurs, the means by which they exploit change as an opportunity for a different business or service.” (page 20). Porter (1990) agrees and reiterated, “national prosperity is created not inherited”.

Truly, the basis of a competitive economy is recognized as innovation (Porter and Ketels, 2003). A lot of reliance is therefore placed on how organizations internally manage processes of innovations (Balachandra and Friar, 1997; Rothwell, 1992) as the adoption of new processes, markets and technologies bring about increased competitive advantage for organizations. The “core renewal process” inside of an organization is Innovation (Tidd and Bessant, 2009), which allows entrepreneurs to achieve a turnaround of ideas into reality as well as secure value from the organization. ‘Innovation’ as a term is a multifaceted one as it involves many variables such as new markets, new products and services, new opportunities. Innovation often times relate to the creation of totally different and new opportunities. Innovation very much depends on the market as it centers on the entrepreneur’s ability with regards to a new market identification, able penetration and growth including an entrepreneur’s preservation ability of a market that’s already matured and established.

One factor needed by firms to enjoy a competitive advantage that is sustained is Innovation (Hadjimanolis, 1999, Damanpour and Gopalkarishnan, 2001; Mei, Arcodia and Ruhanen, 2012; Nicolau and Santa-Maria, 2013; Paget, Dimanche and Mounet, 2010; Tseng, Kuo and Chou, 2008) and there exist a strong connection between Innovation and enhanced organizational performance and firm growth (Freeman, 1982). Firms with an encouraged sense of innovation are much better able to withstand the volatile and dynamic nature of modern market conditions (García-Zamora, González-Benito and Muñoz Gallego, 2013; Jansen, Van den Bosch and Volberda, 2006).

Nowadays, the competition in the business environment is much more rooted in the possession of knowledge (Lane and Lubatkin, 1998). One very important strategic asset for a firm is now being increasingly identified as Knowledge (Grant, 1996; Kogut and Zander, 1992; Spender, 1996; Teece, Pisano, Shuen, 1997) which is said to be the only reliable way to achieve a competitive advantage (Nonaka, 1991); it drives innovation (Dobni, 2006) and is tightly related to the capability of the firm to achieve a competitive advantage that is sustainable (Bhatt, 2001; Fiol, 1996; Grant, 1996; McEvily and Chakravarthy, 2002; Teece, 2001). It should be noted that an organization's core strategic asset is not the actual knowledge, but rather the steps taken by the firm to internalize the knowledge itself (Grant, 1996). Knowledge can be categorized into tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge (Nonaka and Takeuchi, 1995). An example of explicit type of knowledge is formalized knowledge which is often seen in recorded formats such as manuals. This type of knowledge is methodically collected and stored which makes it to be easily transferred and shared within an organization (Nonaka, 1994; Gorman, 2002). This is quite different in comparison to tacit form of knowledge which evolves from participation, learning experiences, personal contact and know-how thereby making its transfer very difficult (Afiouni, 2007; Nonaka, 1994; Polyani, 1957). Absorptive Capacity (measure of how prepared a firm is to absorb and exploit new intake of knowledge) and Knowledge Management (KM) thus become an important management process which is very much linked to the innovative capability and subsequent financial success of firms (Kostopoulos, Papalexandris, Papachroni, Ioannou, 2011). Researchers (Squier and Snyman, 2004; Wiig, 1993) insist that a critical challenge for management is the exploitation of this important resource in order to benefit the firm thru management of

employees' knowledge. Further research also show (Enz and Walsh, 2006) that firms often neglect to take cognizance of the knowledge possessed by service support staff for example in the retail or hospitality sector. Service support workers mostly in retail and tourism are often viewed to be easily replaced , hence attention is more focused on the investment in professional workers' intellectual capital. Researchers also claim that innovation focused research are usually based on large firms (Damanpour, 1988, 1991; Kim 1980; Kimberly and Evanisko, 1981), while smaller firms are simply classed as larger firms miniatures (Durst and Edvardsson, 2012). Importantly, there is a lack of enough research focusing on frameworks related to management of knowledge, especially SME related ones (Ergazakis, Ergazakis, Flamos and Charalabidis, 2009).

This chapter focuses on two related themes. Firstly, there will be a discussion centered on how the Absorptive Capacity (ACAP) concept has developed. The measurements, dimensions, and antecedents of Absorptive Capacity literature arguments will be presented and contrasted. This chapter also features a systematic review. A representation of the different themes of the Absorptive capacity literature is presented in this analysis. This chapter also show a map of the literature which visually illustrates the development of the various aspects of Absorptive capacity study. In the second part of this chapter, there will be an adoption of a more focused approach, which will be based on the themes' development that emerged from the literature map, including the development and adoption of absorptive capacity by service sector SMEs, with a particular focus on Nigeria for the purpose of this study.

2.2 A Systematic Review and Literature Map of Absorptive Capacity

Meta-analyses and systematic reviews are very useful tools being used by social sciences researcher (Davis, Mengersen, Bennett, Mazerolle, 2014). A systematic review has to do with locating and analyzing the relevant and available literature on a theme allowing for previous research comprehensive study, which allows a deep comprehension of the problem and how different researchers will interpret it. A systematic review is a simple statistical representation aggregated from the various studies in the systematic review. Initially, meta-analyses were specifically designed to be used in the social sciences, especially psychology, (Glass, 1976), but other fields soon adopted the technique, including the medical field (Davis, Mengersen, Bennett, Mazerolle, 2014).

Through Meta-analysis, literature over a stated period are illustrated help. It also help to understand how different researchers have viewed a concept or problem as well as the integration of findings from previous researchers. Systematic review helps the establishment of a rigorous procedure and structure to the research process as well to summarize the research findings (Möser and Schmidt, 2014), which have been previous research outcomes (Card, 2012). Readers have often found systematic reviews very useful to help in the evaluation and review of research results (Stanley, 2001) and, they are also very useful to combine prior research evidence for the purpose of informing and directing new research (Davis, Mengersen, Bennett, Mazerolle, 2014).

The systematic review of the extant literature on Absorptive Capacity aims to provide a systematic representation of the sourced research papers in a statistical, simplified and systematic way, which was published with a focus on Absorptive Capacity (or Knowledge Management) theme. Through the research process of this study, there have been referencing of many of these research papers. The purpose of this review is the summarization, evaluation, as well as the analyzing of the empirical research on the theme in focus.

In order to carry out the systematic review as well as provide a foundation to the literature review on Absorptive Capacity, the author has undertaken an analysis of the peer reviewed research on Absorptive Capacity (sourced on the Google Scholar platform), starting with the seminal works published by Cohen and Levinthal (1989, 1990, 1994), Zahra and George (2002) Lane, Koka and Pathak, (2006) and Todora and Durisin (2007). Then in a top

down way, the author then carried out the review of literature that centered on the various perspectives of the Absorptive Capacity construct adopted by individual researchers. These were gotten by searching on the Google Scholar platform. While evaluating the meta-table, there was an indication that the published research has put more of a focus to define and conceptualize Absorptive Capacity; including the various components of Potential and Realized Absorptive Capacity as well as the antecedents and measurements of Absorptive Capacity.

“The process of thematic analysis of the two hundred and forty-four, peer-reviewed papers from 1973 to 2018, revealed a balanced volume of literature around several facets of Absorptive Capacity: Identification of knowledge, Implementation of knowledge, transfer, perception, creation/acquisition/generation, utilization of knowledge, exploitation and transformation; unidimensional, quantitative measures of ACAP, the measurement of intellectual capital, the extent of the relationship of management and leadership structures on ACAP and the extent of the organization’s strategic orientation on the effectiveness of ACAP. However, there was very little attention focused on any of these variables from the specific direction of SME’s. All firms are rather assumed to belong to a homogeneous sample of large firms. The analysis revealed that only two of the papers reviewed had size of firm under consideration as a variable in their analysis. The systematic review further revealed a higher interest in the area of Realized ACAP (i.e. those aspects related to exploitation of knowledge and transformation) compared to the number of papers in the area of Potential ACAP (i.e. aspects of assimilation and acquisition of knowledge), with the highest research interest coming from the single area of transfer of knowledge. Evidence of equitable research interest is evidenced in the realms of absorptive capacity measurement and conceptualization, although antecedents of Absorptive Capacity especially the internal, more controllable antecedents. Contemporary interest in the study of absorptive capacity in emerging countries was revealed by the study, as well as how social media acts as an absorptive capacity facilitator.”

Figure 2.1 is a Literature Map, presenting the association and connection of absorptive capacity concepts. Mapping of Literature is used to show the patterns that abound in the published research. It is described as a pictorial summary of the literature (Creswell, 2008). A literature map is of benefit as it can be of help to visualize the development traced by the construct and indicate the main participants at each stage point.

Figure 2.1: A Map Depicting Absorptive Capacity Literature Development

Source: Personal Collection

2.3 The Theoretical Foundations and Conceptual Framework: The Development of the Construct of Absorptive Capacity and its Definition

Absorptive Capacity organizational phenomenon has seen an increasing interest amongst all management fields (Koka and Pathak, 2008; Lane and Lubatkin, 1998; Teece, Pisano, Shuen, 1997). Cohen and Levinthal (1990) provided an explanation into the proactiveness of firms enriched Absorptive Capacity capabilities towards market opportunities, whereas organizations with lower Absorptive Capacity capabilities merely adopt a reactive approach to market conditions. Scholars (Hamel and Prahalad, 1994; Liao, Welsch and Stoica, 2003; Volberda, 1998) have recognised the importance of organizational proactivity as a necessary condition for firms to cope with unstable economic and business environments. “However, despite the heightened attention being dedicated to the construct, a considerable extent of ambiguity and divergence of definitions features around this area of management (Zahra and George, 2002) resulting in a substantial degree of obscurity when discussing Absorptive Capacity”

“Kedia and Bhagat (1988) first coined the term Absorptive Capacity (ACAP), in their study on international technology transfer.” “However, the work of Cohen and Levinthal (1989, 90) is generally accepted to mark the origin of this construct. Absorptive capacity represents ‘the firm’s ability to identify, assimilate and exploit knowledge from the environment... a firm’s ability to imitate new process or product innovations’ (Cohen and Levinthal, 1989, page 569).

“In their initial article on the theme, scholars Cohen and Levinthal related ACAP closely to the Research and Development (R&D) efforts of the firm, arguing that ‘our model postulates that a firm’s capacity to absorb externally generated knowledge depends on its R&D efforts’ (page 571). In subsequent research conducted by the same authors, Cohen and Levinthal (1990) refine their ACAP model to include other vital factors, which determine this construct, such as, the firm’s existing knowledge base, its learning experience, and prior related knowledge. The refined ACAP model is now defined, not simply as the firm’s ability to acquire and assimilate information, but more importantly, to exploit this information to commercial ends. Indeed this is the whole scope of business in the first place. In this new scenario, it becomes imperative to evaluate also the firm’s problem

solving abilities and communication processes for knowledge sharing and knowledge transferring, as, under the refined definition, these abilities have a strong bearing on the firm's ACAP.”

“In a study published in 1994, Cohen and Levinthal argue that their ACAP models thus far were incomplete, as a firm's ability to exploit new knowledge for commercial aims also depends on variables such as, past behaviour, uncertainty, and competitive interaction. They examine the extent to which firms invest in enhancing their knowledge base and processes, even though the return of their efforts may be unknown.

Welch (2001) argues that firms reap benefit as a result of the speed with which workers learn, transfer their knowledge across the firm, and act upon the newly acquired knowledge; all three processes being very difficult to forecast with any degree of accuracy. Firms can never anticipate the return that their investment in intellectual capital will render, because it is always challenging to manage (identify, record and retrieve and share) knowledge held by workers. Cohen and Levinthal proceed also to analyse the effect that different competitive environments have on a firm's investment in knowledge acquisition and assimilation, and argue the case of spillovers. They claim that employees' mobility between firms causes the spillover of acquired knowledge by the original firm to the receiving organization. Another form of spillover is also considered in this ACAP model: the knowledge that other firms acquire of a firm's expected return on investment in new technology. This analysis of absorptive capacity also considers the effect of the degree of market competition on the firm's investment in learning and ACAP. It is argued that market competition may result in an underinvestment in ACAP, especially in the case where learning has a rather non-cumulative nature, and, where it is mostly restricted to an updating of knowledge”

“Other scholars (Arbussà and Coenders, 2007) have extended Cohen and Levinthal's (1994) evaluation of the effect of spillovers on ACAP. They disclose that firms will invest in increased R&D activities when they are able to reduce outgoing spillovers, by reverting to appropriation regimes, such as, patents, trademarks, copyright (Antonelli, 1999; Buzzacchi, Colombo and Mariotti, 1995). Such instruments give firms the assurance that their investment benefits are not being illicitly transferred to other firms in the industry, as workers move from one firm to another. Further, they establish that the impact of incoming spillovers on a firm's innovation, is industry specific, varying greatly between two groups of firms: on the one hand, manufacturing and high tech industries

and, on the other hand, service firms and low tech industries; and again, is more substantial for those firms that invest in appropriation regimes, as once the knowledge has filtered into the organization, it cannot be replicated by other firms, and gives the original incumbent a competitive advantage.”

Figure 2.2 : A model for Absorptive Capacity

Source: Todorova and Durisin (2007), adapted from Cohen and Levinthal, (1989,90,94)

“Figure 2.2 illustrates the ACAP model based on the research done by Cohen and Levinthal. The model shows the final development of the authors’ theory, with the variables in the firm’s environment which play upon the firm’s ability to manage firm’s knowledge; the firm’s practice of relying on regimes of appropriability to secure its investment in knowledge acquisition; absorptive capacity with its three dimensions of knowledge identification,

knowledge assimilation and knowledge exploitation and, finally, the outcome of the firm's investment in knowledge, i.e. enhanced firm performance and sustainable competitive advantage. The pioneering model of ACAP presented by Cohen and Levinthal (1989,1990,1994) was subsequently revisited several times with different researchers adding their own specific perspective and interpretation of the phenomenon.”

“Heely (1997) was one of the first scholars to revise the initial model proposed by Cohen and Levinthal. He proposed to decompose ACAP into three main components: external knowledge acquisition, intra-firm knowledge dissemination, and technical competence, thereby, contrasting with Cohen and Levinthal's ACAP dimensions of knowledge identification, knowledge assimilation and knowledge exploitation. Heely contended that the acquisition of new knowledge is, on its own, irrelevant, and relies on the internal sharing and dissemination of the new knowledge for the benefit of the firm. Technical competence, Heely explains, emanates mainly from previous activities in R&D.”

Lane and Lubatkin (1998) were also among the first researchers to reconsider the original ACAP model. Their main argument was that relevant knowledge is generally contextual and inlaid in what they refer to as ‘specific knowledge processing systems’ (Lane and Lubatkin page 473, cited in Leonard-Barton, 1992; Spender, 1996; Teece and Pisano, 1994). In their analysis of ACAP they transfer the focus of the model from being solely on the firm, to what they refer to as the ‘learning dyad’ (page 462), i.e. the learning couple: the learning firm and the teaching firm. It is in this way that Lane and Lubatkin's interpretation of ACAP differs from that presented by both Cohen and Levinthal and Heely (the latter only focused on the factors in the firm's environment). Lane and Lubatkin distance themselves from the model, which simply presents the ‘learning, or knowledge-receiving organization’, but, instead, prefer to focus on the context that exists between the learning firm and the firm from whom the knowledge is being learnt, i.e. the teaching firm, and they coin this as Relative Absorptive Capacity. The authors argue that the ability of an organization to acquire and assimilate external knowledge is not only reliant on the characteristics and features of the firm itself, but rather also depends upon an additional three factors, which enrich the context of the analysis of the ACAP framework. Lane and Lubatkin (1998) posit that the form and nature of the knowledge being transferred, as well as the affinity between the processes and structures of

the learning and teaching firm, together with the firm's appreciation of the context within which the original knowledge emanated from (i.e. compensation policies and familiarity with organizational problems), all impact on the level of ACAP of the learning organization. In general, the authors argue, that the greater the relative similarity between the characteristics of the learner and the teacher, the greater is the learning firm's relative absorptive capacity.

Zahra and George (2002) focus on the relevance of the dynamic capabilities (Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000; Teece, Pisano and Shuen, 1997; Raff, 2000; Sun and Anderson, 2010) of firms, as it is such competences that equip the firm to realign its knowledge base and enable it to respond effectively to the ever changing competitive business environment, thus being better positioned to secure its sustainable competitive advantage. Zahra and George redefine the ACAP framework to reduce its ambiguity by recognising it as a firm's ability to acquire, assimilate, transform and exploit knowledge and proceed by saying that this ability is engrained in a firm's own processes and routines. They therefore reconfigure Cohen and Levinthal's three-dimensional model into a four-pillar model. Furthermore, the authors propose that the four components of ACAP (acquisition, assimilation, transformation and exploitation of knowledge) are complementary and support the firm in developing its dynamic capability. Zahra and George's definition of ACAP, indeed, incorporates definitions by other researchers (Cohen and Levinthal, 1989,1990, 1994; Kim, 1998; Mowery and Oxley, 1995) and relates each of these differing versions of the ACAP definition to one of the four components of the construct. This indicates that Zahra and George embrace the work of prior scholars and moreover, they enhanced upon it by discussing the complementarity of the ACAP dimensions and the importance and the link between ACAP and firm processes and routines. Mowery and Oxley's (1995) and Kim's (1998) definition focuses on the acquisition of knowledge, whilst Cohen and Levinthal's definition features the acquisition and exploitation dimensions, whereas Kim's version highlights the firm's ability to problem solving, hence, illustrating the transformation dimension of ACAP. Zahra and George present a model, which, at its origins, brings together previous literature on the construct of ACAP."

Figure 2.3: A Revised Model of Absorptive Capacity

Source: Zahra and George (2002)

“This model focuses on knowledge flows within organizations, giving the construct a process-like perspective, dynamic rather than static. The model also highlights the antecedents of ACAP; activation triggers (Walsh and Ungson, 1991; Winter, 2000) i.e. events that compel the firm to act to stimuli in its environment; knowledge mechanisms, which enable employees to learn from one another, and which also enable problem solving (Garvin, 1993, Sheremata, 2000) besides driving knowledge exploitation (Chaudhuri and Tabrizi, 1999). Other studies (Liao, Fei and Chen, 2007) bear evidence to the fact that knowledge sharing, enhanced by social integration mechanisms, enables absorptive capacity and innovation capability. Social integration mechanisms are new elements to the ACAP construct, one, which had not been considered by earlier scholars and, which puts the focus

on the extent and quality of communication with which employees engage. The model also includes the firm's use of regimes of appropriability. Zahra and George (2002), like Cohen and Levinthal (1994), and Lane and Lubatkin (1998) before them, show how, when substantial regimes of appropriability are in place, the payoff from ACAP will be greater, as firms can better protect their knowledge assets and generate profits from them (Anton and Yao, 2000).

Zahra and George posit that the four dimensions of knowledge acquisition, assimilation, transformation, and exploitation are complementary and correlative. They propose further similarities between them. They argue that the aspects of knowledge acquisition and assimilation can be regarded as Potential ACAP (PACAP), whilst those of knowledge transformation and exploitation can be considered as Realised ACAP (RACAP). PACAP positions the firm to be responsive to external knowledge acquisition and assimilation, whilst RACAP is a measure of the firm's ability to use its knowledge transformation and knowledge exploitation capabilities to its advantage. The authors use the ratio of RACAP to PACAP to measure the absorptive capacity efficiency, i.e. the rate at which the firm is capable of exploiting its acquired knowledge to create sustainable advantage. Zahra and George (2002) contend that firms cannot incorporate (assimilate) new knowledge into their firm, unless they have first acquired the said knowledge. Moreover, even when firms have developed processes to acquire and assimilate knowledge, they do not necessarily have the ability to transform and exploit this knowledge to commercial advantage, an element that had been overseen by previous scholars. Therefore, the four components of the model are complementary to each other. The authors claim that firms, which have well developed PACAP capabilities, are well positioned to continually update and renew their stock of knowledge, and to identify market trends to compete in changing markets.

A further development in the model for ACAP is that proposed by Lane, Koka and Pathak (2006). Following a detailed analysis of previous studies on the theme, Lane Koka and Pathak (2006) develop a definition of ACAP that encompasses three sequential processes: exploratory learning, transformative learning, and exploitative learning. Figure 2.4 illustrates these processes and the interaction between each phase and element. The model is presented with the antecedents of ACAP, which are categorised into (a) those variables determining the breadth,

depth, and ease of understanding, and (b) those, which drive the incentive for developing ACAP feeding into the ACAP process, which consist of exploratory, transformative and exploitative learning. Other elements, such as the firm members' mental models, the firm's structures and processes, as well as the firm's strategies are also seen to impact on the process of ACAP. The exploitation of knowledge drives the production of knowledge and commercial outputs, which impacts on the firm's performance and success. In turn, the knowledge outputs created by the firm will shape the mental modes of the firm members and the structures, process and strategies adopted by the firm, which in turn will again drive the exploratory, transformative and exploitative learning. This learning process is illustrated in Figure 2.4 below.

Figure 2.4 A Further Revised Model of ACAP source: adapted from Lane and Pathak (2006)

Lane, Koka and Pathak, (2006), therefore define ACAP as the ‘firm’s ability to utilize externally held knowledge through three sequential processes: (1) recognizing and understanding potentially valuable new knowledge outside the firm through exploratory learning; (2) assimilating valuable new knowledge through transformative learning, and (3) using the assimilated knowledge to create new knowledge and commercial outputs through exploitative learning’ (page 856).

The above model is one of the first to distinguish between internal and external drivers of ACAP. The internal antecedents include factors such as internal organizational structures, strategies and processes, and the mental models of the organization’s members. Only a few other researchers (Lane and Lubatkin, 1998; Lane, Salk and Lyles, 2001; Van den Bosch, Volberda and De Boer, 1999) include this perspective in their studies. The external antecedents include an evaluation of the firm’s alignment between the internal knowledge and the new knowledge that needs to be learnt, the environmental conditions within which the firm is operating, as well as the cultural, structural, strategic and compensation fit between the firms.

Jansen, Van den Bosch and Volberda (2006) explain ACAP as emanating from a triad of combinative organizational capabilities, or building blocks: coordination capabilities, systems capabilities and socialization capabilities (Van den Bosch and Volberda, 1999), these being regarded as the antecedents to ACAP. In addition, they argue that ACAP is the antecedent to the organization’s adaptation and performance. Here, the authors are inspired by previous work (Verona, 1999), which linked a firm’s ability to absorb external knowledge as being closely linked to management structures, procedures and systems as well as social mechanisms. The authors prove that the success of a unit at exploiting both the potential and the realised aspect of ACAP depends on the combinative organizational mechanisms. They show how, coordination capabilities, such as, those associated with job rotation and participation, enhance PACAP. They argue, that different coordination capabilities will enable diverse aspects of ACAP, revealing how, for example, participation can only enable the acquisition of knowledge, but not its assimilation. Organizational socialization mechanisms, on the other hand, reinforce realised absorptive capacity. They reveal how different organizational units possess different abilities at managing PACAP and RACAP, and support the claim that the capabilities required to transform knowledge are different from those

essential to exploit it. They contend that tight networks within work units encourage employees to support and help each other, thus enabling RACAP in the form of the assimilation, transformation and exploitation of new external knowledge.

Todorova and Durisin (2007) present a further definition of ACAP, wherein they contend that presented by Zahra and George in 2002. Todorova and Durisin argue the importance of learning and innovation in the ACAP framework. Zahra and George (2002) argue that firms transform already assimilated knowledge, whereas Todorova and Durisin (2007), contend this, and propose a different viewpoint. Calling on extensive research on innovation and learning, Todorova and Durisin propose that knowledge is transformed when it cannot be assimilated. This happens when the new knowledge cannot be adapted to 'fit' with the already existing knowledge base. They thus present knowledge transformation as an alternative, not a sequence of knowledge assimilation. Furthermore, the model suggests that knowledge may bounce back and forth several times between assimilation and transformation mechanisms, before it is adapted and ready for exploitation.”

Figure 2.5 A Refined Model of Absorptive Capacity source: Developed by Todorova and Durisin, (2007), page 776, adapted by Author.

“The above illustration in Figure 2.5 shows the model of ACAP as proposed by Todorova and Durisin (2007) proposing changes to the contingent factors presented in the seminal work of Zahra and George (2002). Others, namely, Amit and Shoemaker, (1993); Dierickx and Cool, (1989); Grant, (1991, 1996); Prahalad and Hamel, (1990) show how social interactions enhance the capabilities of the resources working together. Here, it is argued that social integration mechanisms must affect all the components of ACAP, and not only the process between PACAP and RACAP, as proposed earlier. Cohen and Levinthal (1990) establish that a relationship exists between levels of appropriability and incentives to invest in knowledge. They show how markets, where low appropriability regimes exist, experience lower returns to knowledge. The new proposed model provides for a

deeper understanding of the moderating effect of the regimes of appropriability on the outcome of ACAP. The authors propose to measure the relationship between the antecedents of ACAP and the absorptive capacity itself and again between ACAP and its outcomes. A third contingent factor, power relationships, is also included in this redefined model of ACAP. Research (Contu and Willmott, 2003; Dosi, Levinthal and Marengo, 2003) shows that power relationships, i.e. the nature and type of communication engaged into by actors to enable them to achieve their desired objectives (Pfeffer, 1981), are influential on learning and capabilities in an organization. An understanding of how power structures impact on ACAP better equips researchers to understand why some firms are superior than others at exploiting knowledge.

Other scholars (Camisón and Forés, 2010) develop the ACAP model proposed by Zahra and George (2002) and introduce the dimension of knowledge transformation into the framework. Camisón and Forés advance a two dimensional ACAP model, with measures of PACAP and RACAP. Camisón and Forés, are in agreement with the interpretation of PACAP and RACAP used by Zahra and George (2002) in their model. PACAP describes the firm's ability to value, acquire, and assimilate new, external knowledge, whereas RACAP aims to integrate and reconfigure already existing external knowledge with the newly acquired knowledge as well, so as to enable knowledge transformation activity through the firm's activities, systems, procedures and routines. Camisón and Forés (2010) show how RACAP is the main influence on innovation outcomes; PACAP being the essential element to continually renew the firm's knowledge base to secure sustainable competitive advantage. They improve the firms' understanding of ACAP by designing a measurement instrument that is both valid and reliable. This measurement instrument presents ACAP as two subsets, PACAP and RACAP, containing various processes, capacities and organizational procedures and routines.

Other scholars (Biedenback and Müller, 2012; Kim, Akbar, Tzokas and Al Dajani, 2013; Schleimer and Pedersen, 2013) have evidenced the role of the transformative capability of the firm as being complementary to the firm's exploratory and exploitative learning processes. Since the situation in developing markets does not allow that firms immediately exploit the knowledge that they would have assimilated, it becomes necessary for the organizations to store their knowledge and retrieve it, ready for commercial use at the appropriate time. This,

therefore, implies that the ability of the firm to transform knowledge links to the firm's ability to explore and exploit that knowledge, as these learning processes are dependent upon one another and ultimately affect the firm's innovation capability.

More recently, researchers (Cepeda-Carrion, Leal-Millán, Martelo-Landroguez, Lean-Rodriguez, 2016; Valentina and Passiante, 2009) have evaluated ACAP to identify its relevance for stakeholder value creation. Valentina and Passiante (2009) argue that firms' participation in networks, positions the firms more favourably for value creation. This is more strongly felt the smaller the size of the firm. Small and medium sized firms (SMEs) are, generally, expected to face extensive innovation challenges than their larger counterparts, particularly owing to their resource limitation (Freel, 2000; Hadjimanolis, 1999). The smaller the size of the SME, the stronger the relationship and ties with the owner-manager's style of thinking and doing. Therefore, in SMEs, much of the innovative capability of the organization lies within the remit of the owner manager (Lynskey 2004; Webster, 2004). Research reveals the inverse relationship between the size of organizations and the motivation for firms to network for knowledge enriching purposes (Rothwell, 1991).

Despite the fact that SMEs possess attributes that constrain their ability to innovate, (particularly resource availability mentioned earlier), they are also characterized by behavioural advantages, such as closeness to customers, learning and flexibility, which enable them to be agile and successful at innovating, as they find it easier to listen to their customers' opinions and act accordingly, given that the locus of decision making is a relatively short one (Dutta and Evrard, 1999; Salavou, Baltas and Liukas, 2004). Valentina and Passiante, (2009) and Cepeda-Carrion, Leal-Millán, Martelo-Landroguez, Lean-Rodriguez (2016) argue that ACAP is a necessary causal factor for value creation, as it affects knowledge application both directly and indirectly. Furthermore, the researchers show that knowledge storage in itself has a limited effect on value creation. However, the combined effect of knowledge application and knowledge storage has a complementary impact on value creation.

To accomplish the objectives of this study, development of theoretical framework is required so that further conclusion can be made. Although there are endless debates on the precise dimensions of absorptive capacity theory, it was clear that number scholars applied Zahra & George (2002) and Todorova & Durisin (2007)

dimensions of absorptive capacity. Knowledge acquisition, assimilation, exploitation, and transformation have been subjected to many studies to relate the main absorptive capacity theory with a competitive advantage. For example, Da Silva & Davis (2011) adopted Zahra & George (2002) construct of absorptive capacity to link creativity and innovation in academic settings. Also, Ojo et al. (2014) applied the four dimensions of absorptive capacity and suggest a specific level of each dimension. There are other studies used similar dimensions as well such as Delmas, Hoffmann, & Kuss, (2011), Lowik et al. (2017), Wuryaningrat (2013), Xie, Zou, & Qi (2018) and many more. Summarily, numerous studies that employed these four dimensions demonstrate its relevancy in this framework. Provided that absorptive capacity is influenced by existing, prior and source of knowledge, connecting knowledge management to the antecedents of absorptive capacity are consistent with the initial concept's.

Denoting definition of knowledge management with prior knowledge concept in absorptive capacity theory, recognizing existing knowledge asset is core pillar in knowledge management. According to Davenport & Prusak (2000), knowledge management is “to identify, manage, and value items that the organization knows or could know” indicating pertinent role of knowledge identification. To some extent, this knowledge identification may include broad-spectrum knowledge about specific development in the field that is crucial for learning processes (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990; Massingham, 2014a) and identifying future opportunities (Shepherd & DeTienne, 2005).

Thus, knowledge identification is first antecedents of absorptive capacity which conceal current knowledge resources before obtaining external knowledge. On the other hand, apart from knowledge identifying process, Rowley (2000) proposed that knowledge access is one of the essential concepts in knowledge management. Knowledge access concerns on the ability of persons to attain required knowledge within the organization either in tacit or explicit form (Valentim, Lisboa, & Franco, 2016). The ability to obtain current, precise and complete knowledge of the organization's environment will enhance their knowledge capability. However, the existence of knowledge access does not necessarily indicate the efficient knowledge transfer practice because knowledge transfer only occurs at certain conditions (Inkpen & Tsang, 2005) like trust and culture (Tsang, 1997).”

Thus, knowledge distribution is a significant aspect of knowledge management concepts. Knowledge distribution refers to the process by which information from different sources are shared (Gonzalez & Martins, 2017) such as knowledge repository, subject matter expert, organizational memory and others. Adopting Rowley (2000) diversified concept of knowledge management, knowledge identification, knowledge access and knowledge distribution covered all other definitions of knowledge management from processes, value, and technological aspects.

Furthermore, innovation undoubtedly is the main pillar of competitive advantage. At an individual level, innovation is appropriately reflected by personal characteristics (Agarwal & Prasad, 1998; Mun, Kirk, & Jae, 2006) rather than innovation outcome or post-facto which could be time-consuming and partly biased (Hurt, Joseph, & Cook, 1977). Innovativeness is an important determinant of organization's performance (Garcia & Calantone, 2002) either in financial, operation or products aspects. Absorptive capacity original concepts also disclosed the distinctly pivotal role of innovation in advancing organization's competitive advantage. Hence, innovation capability is regarded as an outcome of individual absorptive capacity. Therefore, based on previous discussion, proposed theoretical framework is as shown in following figure:

Theoretical Framework

2.4 Problem Background

Consistent and steady growth is required for SMEs in the service sector to continually contribute to the success of the national economy more importantly in creation of employment opportunities for the teeming Nigerian population. Between the periods of 2009 to 2013, the Telecommunication and Information Technology sector which is sub-sector of the service sector in Nigeria created well over 60% of the new jobs (Nigeria Employers Consultative Association (NECA), 2016). The improved performance of SMEs in the service sector encourages more self-reliance and entrepreneurship (Spremo & Mičić, 2015).

Encouragement of entrepreneurship amongst SMEs in the service sector in Nigeria provided young school leavers, the retirees, and the unemployed a window of opportunity to create wealth and earn decent source of livelihood (Spremo & Mičić, 2015). If there is decline in the failure rate of SME, there will be a significant increase in number of newly created jobs, which will have a positive impact on the national economic growth (National Bureau of Statistics, 2016).

Based on research, several definitions of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) have been put forward by varying number of authors.

For the purpose of this study, the definition provided by the Bankers Committee of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) define a Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) as any enterprises with a maximum asset base of Two Hundred Million Naira (N200million) excluding land and working capital and with the number of personnel employed by the enterprise not less than ten (10) and not more than Three Hundred (300). This definition is subject to periodic review by the Bankers Committee (CBN 2001).

The establishment of National Directorate of Employment (NDE) which is an agency under the ministry of Labor and Productivities in Nigeria shows the recognition and attention the federal government of Nigeria is given to SMEs. The National Directorate of Employment (NDE) was founded in 1986 in order to promote and support self-employment. Under the scheme; two credit guarantee instruments provide assistance to SMEs. The two credit schemes are: The Graduate Job Creation Loan Scheme (GJLS) and the Matured People's Scheme (MPS). The two

schemes were complemented by an Entrepreneur Development Program (EDP) which is mandatory before one qualifies for any of the scheme.

Based on the latest report of National Bureau of Statistics, there exist about 5.73 million SMEs in Nigeria which has successfully created well over 20million jobs, this successfully mean that SMEs in Nigeria is a significant factor in the building of the economy.

Further to role of SME to the growth of the Nigeria economy, it is very pertinent to chart the path to enhance continuous improvement of the sector. Kuhn and Galloway (2013) posited that, “As service sector SME owners strengthened the relationship with one another within the network with confidence and trust, the owners will access to updated information and create a level ground for all the stakeholders in the industry. Also, it will bring about effective knowledge sharing that will enable the SME’s to be more competitive leading to the success of the SME” (p. 593).

To improve the survival rate of the service sector of the SME’s in Nigeria, the owners of the SME’s’ should endeavor to strengthened the relationships for better knowledge exchange which results in Absorptive Capacity development within the industry. The less experienced owners and the veterans in the industry should build a formidable relationship that will ensure cross experience sharing.

The involvement and participation of individual owner of the service sector of the SME in effective knowledge sharing is very important and fundamental to the success of SMEs (Sawang et al.,2016). Knowledge sharing and on the job training must be taken more serious and given a topmost attention in the service sector SMEs for an enhanced performance and improved growth.

It is widely believed that knowledge exchange became a very notable topical issue for research in the early 1980 (Benkler, 2017). Although research carried out by Robert Hall amongst pig iron factories in Cleveland, United Kingdom produced results that show these companies as far back as the 1850’s to have been sharing information about techniques of manufacturing and plans for facility design (Benkler, 2017).

By engaging in knowledge exchange and also through the strength of the relationship amongst owners of the service sector SMEs leading to the development of Absorptive Capacity, SMEs will have greater prospect to grow and succeed. With the aid of effective knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship among the owners of SME's in the service sector, the strength of the SME's in innovation is enhanced because knowledge exchange promotes innovation and invention.

This research probed into how owners of the service sector SMEs engage in effective knowledge sharing and build quality relationship for the development of absorptive Capacity. The research identifies the two factors which contribute to successful development of Adoptive Capacity in service sector SMEs.

The process of development of Absorptive Capacity comprises the acquisition of knowledge, transfer of knowledge as well as tactics to develop innovation (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990; Yoo et al., 2016). Development of Absorptive Capacity is determined by how the owners of the service sector of the SME view the importance of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship among individual owners of SME (Olaniran, 2017). The strength of the relationship among SME's owners involves having trust and confidence to discuss personal experience in respect of the performance and activities of the SME within the industry network without holding back facts and details.

Previous research on the topic is yet to determine the perspective of service sector SME owners in regarding knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship with other owners within the network as a major factor contributing to the development of Absorptive Capacity for the success of SME's. (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). Prior studies regarding knowledge exchange and relationship building has recommended future research into how owners of service sector SME's in Nigeria perceived knowledge exchange and the relationship among SME owners' as the critical success factor for development of Absorptive Capacity. (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016).

Based on the findings of this research study, the owners of service sector of the SMEs can confidently attempt to strengthened the relationship among SME's owners and enhance knowledge exchange with high level confidence and trust to develop Absorptive Capacity for the success of the SME's (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang et al., 2016).

Having a clear cut idea about how owners of the service sector of the SME's attend to the issue of factors that contribute to the development Absorptive Capacity through the contribution of knowledge sharing and building of quality relationship within the industry's network. The process will help in guiding the less experienced owners of the SME's in decision making this will improve the survival rate thereby leading growth of the business and improved performance of the business.

The research evaluates two main factors that impacts and contribute to the success of developing Absorptive Capacity. It should be noted that each business unit have varying degree of limitation as to the development of Absorptive Capacity which may include inadequate resources which will afford individual owner of the SME to participate effectively in the industry's networking which was as a result of strengthening the relationship among other owners of the SME and to implement strategies gained from the quality relationship and knowledge exchange (Yoo et al., 2016).

The study evaluates the techniques adopted in finding solution to the limitations confronting infant and newly established SME's in the development of Absorptive Capacity to encourage innovative ideas within the network of the industry (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). In addition, development of Absorptive Capacity depends on mutual relationships built on confidence and trust to share personal knowledge/ experiences (Olaniran, 2017). Ability to develop and strengthened the relationships among the owners of service sector of the SMEs will encourage participation and good level of individual owner's involvement in the process. Focusing on these two important success factors will help owners of service sector of the SMEs to adequately benefit from the development of Absorptive Capacity.

2.5 Identification of the Gap

Development of Absorptive Capacity has been identified as a significant resource in curtailing the challenges within the service sector SMEs in Nigeria. Knowledge exchanged through quality relationship within the industry's network availed the owners of SMEs the opportunity to be exposed to new and efficient production and operation techniques.

Kuhn and Galloway (2013) postulated that, "...knowledge is a form of primary resource that can positively influence the growth and success of SME's outcome and give it a competitive edge" (p. 572). Limited and scarce financial resources can be a major constrain for appropriate acquisition of formal professional training and skill acquisition. Development of Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship among owners of the service sector of the SME's is cost effective and a cheaper form of acquiring practical knowledge which is a good alternative to formal training and skill acquisition.

This research is focused on examining the two success factors that contributes to the development of the Absorptive Capacity; it gives clearer view on how to leverage on the importance of this concept for benefit of SME's.

In the literature review carried out using Meta-Analysis technique which covered the periods of 2010 to 2015 by Muhammad and Sadia (2016), it was reported that the concept of Absorptive Capacity development depends mainly on trust and confidence the owners of the service sector SMEs built on the effectiveness of the process. This was reiterated in year 2011 that the process of developing Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships is built mainly on trust and teamwork, this make trust and teamwork the central theme of the whole process(Muhammad & Sadia, 2016). The Meta-analysis carried out in year 2012 highlighted trust and cultural values as the central themes (Muhammad & Sadia, 2016). In year 2013 and 2014, social relationships and the strength of the relationship among the owners of the service sector of the SME's within the industry's social network were highlighted as the major themes contributing to the development of the Absorptive Capacity (Muhammad & Sadia, 2016).

The central theme from literature reviewed carried out year in 2015 according to (Muhammad & Sadia, 2016) recognized effective communication as a major contributive factor to the development of Absorptive Capacity which results to innovation and technological advancement. The focus of research has since now shifted to the methods of knowledge exchange and relationship strength as contributing to the development of Absorptive Capacity with trust being the bedrock and the most consistent theme. Table 1 review some of the previous research work in this area including the research context and the methodology.

Author	Context	Methodology
Cohen and Levinthal (1990)	Development of absorptive-capacity in Manufacturing Companies in America	Quantitative
Szulanski (1996)	Exploring Internal Stickiness: Impediments To The Transfer Of Best Practice Within The Firm	Quantitative
Lane and Lubatkin (1998)	Relative Absorptive Capacity and Interorganizational Learning	Quantitative
Zahra and George (2002)	Absorptive Capacity: A Review, Reconceptualization And Extension	Conceptual
Lane et al. (2006)	The reification of absorptive capacity: A critical review and rejuvenation of the construct	Conceptual
Nooteboom et al. (2007)	Cognitive distance in and	Quantitative

	between SME's and firms: Where do exploitation and exploration take place, and how are they connected?	
Easterby-Smith et al. (2008)	Absorptive capacity: A process perspective	Qualitative
Mcadam, R, et all 2010	Development of absorptive-capacity based innovation in Construction sector of the SMEs in UK	Mixed
Vasudeva and Anand (2011)	Unpacking absorptive capacity: A study of knowledge utilization from alliance portfolios.	Quantitative
Steve Onyeiwu 2011	Does Lack of Innovation and Absorptive Capacity Retard Economic Growth in Africa?	Quantitative
Ceccagnoli and Jiang (2013)	The cost of integrating external technologies: Supply and demand drivers of value creation in the markets for technology.	Quantitative
Omoriegbe, U. (2015)	A Developing Country's Absorptive Capacity: The Link between FDI and Economic	Quantitative

	Growth in Nigeria	
Ade Abdulquadri Bilaul et al. (2015)	Review of Absorptive Capacity in Small and Medium Sized Construction Firms in Nigeria	Conceptual
Kehinde Medase. (2018)	Investigation into how specialized capabilities including absorptive capacity and marketing capabilities influence innovation commercialization in manufacturing and service firms in Nigeria	Quantitative
Gabriella Cappellari et al 2019	Development of absorptive capacity in Metal Mining companies in Brazil	Qualitative
Shirley A. Souza et al 2019	Development of absorptive capacity in Textile Manufacturing companies in Brazil	Qualitative

The target of this study is to carry out an intensive examination of the perception of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships among the owners of the service sector of the SME's on Absorptive Capacity development. Knowledge exchange and the relationships formed the nucleus for the successful development of Absorptive Capacity. (Yoo & et al., 2016). In addition to the two main contributive factors,

factors such as man hour, financial resources, and cultural value are also itemized as an important factor in developing Absorptive Capacity. Close examination and evaluation of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships among the owners of the SMEs provided detailed insight as to the influence the two contributive factors posed on development of Absorptive Capacity.

The limitation confronting individual service sector of the SME is distinct in terms of the ability to develop Absorptive Capacity effectively, these limitations include inadequate resources to participate in the process and also lack of manpower to effectively implement innovative idea acquired from the relationship and knowledge exchange (Yoo et al., 2016). Also according to prior quantitative studies by (Yoo et al., 2016), technical knowledge was found to decrease Absorptive capacity while absorptive capacity is increased with non-technical knowledge

Exploring the techniques employed to curtail the challenges of developing Absorptive Capacity by encouraging innovative ideas amongst less experienced and newly established service sector SMEs (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990), Absorptive Capacity development is strengthened through a mutual and beneficial exchange among owners of the SME's within the industry's social network. According to (Olaniran, 2017), absorptive Capacity development depends on the strength of relationships which are based mainly on trust and confidence before participating in knowledge exchange or experiences .Olaniran in his quantitative studies also stated that when individuals engage in mutual relationship as regard knowledge exchange, trust and confidence improves this further enhanced the desires and willingness of the owners of SMEs to share personal experiences in respect of the individual service sector of the SME (Olaniran, 2017). To be successful in building trust and confidence amongst owners of SME's, quality relationships and good rapport among the owners of the service sector of the SME's is necessarily required, (Kuhn & Galloway, 2013). Unhealthy competition in the industry might be a major barrier, however having solid trust and confidence in the process will assist SME owners to have great belief that every participant in the process are genuine and not opportunist (Kuhn & Galloway, 2013). By creating quality relationships with other owners of the service sector of the SME's, developments of Absorptive Capacity will

more successful (Man-pil et al., 2017). The empirical studies emphasized on the merit of developing Absorptive Capacity and building quality relationships.

The purpose of this study is to fill the void in respect of dearth of available literatures as regards the perception of SME's owners on knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships with other owners within the network and how this contribute successfully to the development of Absorptive Capacity in Nigeria (Sawang & et al., 2016; Yoo et al., 2016).

This study provides detailed information about how service sector of the SMEs were able to surmount the limitation and obstacles around the development of Absorptive Capacity. The research study also emphasized the importance of strengthening the relationships with other SME owners within the network. Through this study, the owners of the SME were able to develop tactics to develop Absorptive Capacity. Two theories formed the bedrock for this study; Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET) which will be discussed in the next section.

2.6 Review of the Literature

This section presents a review of literatures that form the bedrock for this study. Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) are very important to the success and growth of the Nigeria economy. Development of Absorptive Capacity provides opportunities for SME owners to engage in knowledge exchange and strengthen the relationships with other owners in order to improve the survival rate of the business and enhance its growth. The literature review provides detailed insights into how the owners of the SME's perceived the contribution of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship on development of Absorptive Capacity

2.6.1 Importance of SMEs to the Nigeria Economy

Economic growth is an important indicator that expressed the health status of a country. A country's economic growth is influenced by the level of increase in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Memili et al., 2015). The establishment of large business corporation is taxing and more challenging than the creation of SMEs. Ifekwem & Adedamola, 2016; Memili, Fang et al., 2015 was of the opinion that the consistent success and sustainable growth of SMEs in Nigeria in recent time more especially service sector SMEs has helped in the rapid growth of the economy. Supporting and embracing entrepreneurship and Small Medium Enterprises has resulted in visible and sustainable improvement in the development of the Nigeria geographical space. The Nigeria economy is presently benchmarked on the success of the privately driven Small and Medium Enterprises sector.

The essential features and characteristics of SMEs has given the sector a remarkable recognition by the government based on its contribution to the national economic growth. These characteristics bring about healthy competition in the industry and provide the consumers with choice of goods and services (Neagu, 2016). SME's are more flexible in adjusting to changes in the marketplace, also it cultivates the ability to be creative and innovative in order to be very competitive and have an edge (Neagu, 2016). Large Corporation on the other hand are confronted with the challenges of administrative and bureaucratic bottlenecks in adopting these essential characteristics.

Faems and Madhok (2019) explained that an SME can record a landmark technological success on an idea a large corporation will consider insignificant. The owners of service sector SME's have higher tendency to perceived the success of small projects as a breakthrough than large corporation's (Faems & Madhok, 2019). Often times, small projects will be unattractive to a large corporation for investment, while service sector SME owners will be motivated and attracted to all forms of revenue generating business activities (Faems & Madhok, 2019).

The flexibility feature of SMEs and their innovative pursuits positioned them on a level to provide larger corporation with important solutions, as a result the larger corporations outsourced some section of their operations to SMEs to manage (Neagu, 2016). Out-sourcing some operation and productive activities to the SME's by the large corporation increased the client base of these SME's and also increase their revenue, in addition the SME's will have direct relationship with large corporation thereby having indirect access to some sophisticated technologies.

In view of the significant and impressive contribution of SMEs to the economy, most of the problems and challenges confronting SME's are caused by unfavorable economic policies and downturn in economic growth. In spite of the ability of these SME's to adapt easily to market changes, adverse economic cycles, the effects of the challenges are more drastic and easily noticeable on the activities of the SMEs than large corporation.

(Ghosal & Ye, 2015). Ghosal and Ye (2015) concluded that Small and Medium Enterprises, who have less than 300 personnels, experienced the effects of a negative economy policy 4.5 times more than large firms. To improve the survival of SMEs in the face of economic downturns, the owners of service sector SME's must be willing to employ sustainability techniques.

Geographical locations of SMEs also have effect on their ability to maintain the sustainability technique during economic downturn. SMEs located in the rural areas are more prone to the adverse impact of the economic downturn than SMEs located in the urban region (Johnson, Faight, & Long, 2017).

In evaluating the contribution of SMEs to the growth of the national economy, the SMEs located in the rural areas provides a clear view of the importance of SMEs. Owners of service sector SMEs located in the rural area depend

on other SMEs to provide support service like, logistics, transportation, warehousing for survival of their own business (Johnson et al., 2017) therefore creating sustainability must be strategic.

Sub-urban regions more especially the remote areas in Nigeria lack the infrastructural development and economic stability offered by urban areas. Rural areas struggle in attracting larger corporations, especially manufacturing which has the capability and facility to employ a larger number of personnels (Johnson et al., 2017). These challenges encourage the residents of the sub-urban region to embrace entrepreneurship in order to be self-dependent in job creation and income earning.

In rural areas, such as Iseyin (a sub-urban area in Oyo state South-West Nigeria), creation of employment opportunities by the natives is higher due to high employment levels (Svaleryd, 2015). Compared to urbanized areas, there might be varied options for individuals to decide whether to set up a business or seek employment (Svaleryd, 2015). Where there is a situation in which an economy is experiencing deficit term of trade where increase in imports result in unemployment, the rational economic policy and strategy to be put in place is the strengthening of the SMEs and encourage Import Substitution to create a viable solution for foreign exchange earnings for the national economy and the correction of the imbalance in the term of trade (Liang & Goetz, 2016).

A strong national economy provides a higher level of sustainability and growth for the organization. Government schemes and programs can be put in place to strengthen SMEs. To help improve the sustainability and growth of SMEs, programs such as fiscal incentives (like Import Duty Draw Back, Export Development Fund, Export Credit Guarantee Insurance Scheme, Tax Relief on Interest Income Manufacture in-bond), Industrial Development Centre (IDC), Industrial Training Fund (ITF), Youth Enterprise With Innovation In Nigeria (YouWIN) N-Power . Each scheme opened window of opportunities for youth empowerment, youth training and skill acquisition for the participants to create sustainability and growth for SMEs. Since the commencement of some of these programs in Nigeria, there has been notable increase in the sustainability of SMEs. The young graduate and school leavers who have acquired entrepreneurship training find it easier to establish SMEs (Ifekwem & Adedamola, 2016; Svaleryd, 2015). The efforts and seriousness of the government in providing the support structure to serve as a testimonial to the importance of these SMEs to the growth and development of the national economy.

Embracing entrepreneurship and establishing SMEs is much more than a desire to achieve self-sufficiency or simply satisfying the unemployment problems. Spremo and Mičić (2015) stated that “Since SMEs are characterized by easy absorption of capacity, innovation, flexibility, and easy adaptability to unstable economic conditions, SMEs have succeeded in contributing immeasurably to the provision of employment for the workforce and increasing of economic growth”. Examining how important SMEs are to the economy is of great help in laying a strong background to explore how service sector SME owners maximize the benefits accruing to development of Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and the strength of relationships with other SME owners. The study will examine the development of the Adoptive Capacity among owners of service sector SMEs within industry’s network.

Absorptive Capacity provides an alternative method of learning for the owners of the service sector SMEs. The development of Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships give the less experienced and less educated owners of SMEs to have access to other experienced and educated owners, thereby having access to updated information and latest innovative idea in the industry.

2.6.2 Small Business Support

There exist numerous government agencies (Ministry Department and Agency-MDA's), private and Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) that are involved in providing support for the owners of SMEs as SME activities has been recognized to be a major contributor to sustained economic growth. Small and Medium Industries Development Agency (SMIDA) is a federal government agency created to initiate and articulate ideas for the SME's and also to provide and facilitate technical and managerial training to SMEs.

To assist in stimulating the growth of the economy through an improved revenue generation for SMEs, the local contents Act of the Nigeria government has made it mandatory for every governmental agency to award a significant number of their surplus sales and contracts to the indigenous SMEs. This has helped improve the success of SMEs and strengthen the survival rate.

The SMIDA's primary function has been to link SMEs to sources of finance, technology, technical skill development and management, it was observed that providing the SMEs with finance alone does not resolve the challenges of SMEs, it only provides relief for the short run and thereby postponing the inevitable (Grose,2013).

After critical review of the survival rate of SMEs, SMIDA concluded that owners of the SMEs with poor managerial and technical skill required assistance (Grose, 2013). Therefore, provision of technical and Management assistance became the area of concentration of SMIDA. This paradigm focus shift represent a signal as to how important it is for SME owners to be educated in business operations in order to drive business success.

The technical and management assistance program was a formal establishment for development Absorptive Capacity for owners of service sector SMEs. The Small and Medium Industries Development Agency (SMIDA) main function is capacity building in the SME sector, it also provide access to industrial infrastructure including industrial estates and layouts and incubators.

The efforts by the SMIDA signaled the initial effort of becoming a valuable resource center for the owners of service sector SMEs. The support for SME owners for better operational management is one of the earlier forms of

Absorptive Capacity development. SMIDA which was established purposely to coordinate the activities and policies concerning SMEs works with the Industrial Development Centers (IDCs) to provide adequate advisory and consultancy services among other support service for effective operation of SMEs.

Another support for owners of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) for effective operational activities is the Industrial Development Centers (IDCs), the Nigeria's Ministry of Industry maintains this network for the provision of technical and managerial assistance to the owners of SMEs. The workers at the IDCs are expected to offer advice to SMEs in project conception, packaging, equipment sourcing, installation, and maintenance. The Industrial Development Centre have the characteristics of an extension service, a training institution and product development Centre for the SME sector. In addition to the technical and management service being rendered by IDC's, the government also established agency like Federal Institute for Industrial Research Oshodi (FIIRO), Project Development Agency (PRODA) and the Raw Materials Research and Development Council (RMRDC).

The 2015 Gallup HOPE index provided a statistic that 0.5% of people have the rare and quality genius-level for entrepreneurship (Martin, 2017). It is often that the idea of setting up a business may no longer be an option by the time the individual is finishing school and deciding on a career path. The orientation that sharpens the entrepreneurship ability of individuals' take-off with exposure to entrepreneurship training which help to enhance creative abilities. The creative abilities provide the opportunity to create entrepreneurial opportunities (Martin, 2017). The Industrial development Centers (IDCs) which is otherwise known as incubators provided a cost effective take-off point to harness the opportunities.

The universities provide educational platform for students to learn how to develop Absorptive Capacity within the four walls of the classroom and outside of the classroom. The classroom provides the professor and other educational instructor with platform to introduce the concepts of entrepreneurship to the student (Thatcher, Alao, Brown, & Choudhary, 2016), assignments, projects, and case studies provide the student with opportunities to acquire additional knowledge (Thatcher et al., 2016).

Additionally, through quality relationships with other owners of SMEs within the industry's network, the university faculty can place the students on internship or Short Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) with the SMEs for projects aimed at resolving challenges confronting the SMEs and their owners (Thatcher et al., 2016). The study carried out by Katimertzopoulos and Vlados (2017) confirmed that larger number of SME owners desired to consummate quality relationship with local universities and other institutions of higher learning. The partnership between most university faculties' and owners of service sector SMEs provides benefits for the students' educational advancement and skill acquisition, the SMEs also benefit by having access to cheaper manpower and equally bring about economic growth and development of the small business (Harrington & Maysami, 2015).

Universities have the resources to provide the student with an integrated approach to the development of Absorptive Capacity process. The students benefit extensively from SME owners by having the opportunity to learn from their actual-life experiences (Thatcher et al., 2016). The partnership between the university and SMEs is very important because it afforded the student the opportunity to have first-hand experience about the operations and challenges confronting SMEs. From this initiative, the student will be able to learn from the SME owners' realistic experiences (Thatcher et al., 2016). This partnership between SME owners and the university is one of the ways to develop Absorptive Capacity for both parties as they exchange ideas mutually (knowledge exchange) and establish quality relationships (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Harrington & Maysami, 2015). The mutual collaboration provided the students with benefits which is absent and non-existent in traditional classrooms.

Owner of SMEs also benefit by having unrestricted access to fresh innovative ideas and educational resources which are not available prior to this partnership (Thatcher & et al., 2016). These owners also have the luxury of being exposed to an outsider's point of view which will assist them to have a different view and perception on how the business is operating. The exposure and accessibility to current knowledge will mean that SME owners are provided with a competitive advantage with a resultant fact that SME owners are better able to evaluate diverse solutions to challenges confronting their SMEs (Thatcher & et al., 2016). The development of the

Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and cultivation of quality relationships between the university students and SME owners serves as a source of capacity in form of support for SME owners.

In the presence of abundance of external resources, SME owners are very careful and selective in seeking external knowledge (Mole, North, & Baldock, 2016). Mole et al. (2016) in his industrial study of SME owners carried out in England found out that male SME owners are less willing to get external knowledge compared to female owners. They also discovered that the management team orientation is another important factor affecting the decision to seek for external support.

Managers who believe Absorptive Capacity can be developed through knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships are more willing and show desire to seek knowledge and support from external sources compared to their counterparts who did not (Mole et al., 2016). The involvement in the development of the Absorptive Capacity process is based on the individual SME owner's perception about development of Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and building of credible relationships for the success of SMEs.

Strong and healthy economies depend on the success of and improved performance of SMEs. For institutions of higher learning such as universities which depend on strength of the national economy for its subventions, the enthusiasm for the success of SMEs is very paramount (Hopson, Miller, & Lovelace, 2018).

2.6.3 Knowledge Exchange

A broader definition of knowledge exchange and knowledge management is important; “knowledge is the careful harmonization of contextual information with experience (Ramayah, Yeap, & Ignatius, 2013)”. Knowledge management encompasses the identification of knowledge sources, accessing the knowledge, assimilation, transfer, and effective utilization of the knowledge to enhance SME growth and development (Ramayah et al., 2013; Schenkel, Farmer, & Maslyn, 2019). As stated by Ramayah et al., 2013, knowledge exchange is the principal factor of knowledge management. They further stated, “...knowledge exchange can be referred to as the exchange of knowledge between at least two parties in a reciprocal process allowing reshaping and sense-making of the knowledge in the new context”. Effective exchange of knowledge is a form of mutual exchange.

Knowledge exchange is very beneficial to SME owners. Through knowledge exchange, owners of service sector SMEs improve the performance and profitability of SMEs, it also helps in sustaining the growth of the business while also encouraging building of credible relationships with other SME owners to create innovative ideas (Turner & Endres, 2017). Owners of SMEs are more likely to benefit from multiple sources of knowledge including family and friends, educational institutions, collaboration with other SMEs within the industry's network (Howard, Steensma, Lyles, & Dhanaraj, 2016).

Knowledge brings about creativity, efficiency, and self-development. Cerezo, et al. (2019) in their study explained that it's very important to know the difference between self-perceived knowledge and objective knowledge. They also found that how an individual perceives knowledge may be different from the perception of another individual. The knowledge an individual believes he has is known as self-perceived knowledge while managerial or technical training and experience is known as objective knowledge (Cerezo, et al., 2019).

He found that objective knowledge does not always encourage acceptance of an idea, self-perceived knowledge is receptive and willing to accept an idea (Cerezo, et al., 2019). The level of confidence an individual has about his knowledge strengthens his creativity and self-development.

Creativity and self-development stimulates innovation and invention. Research has shown that an individual who innovates possess high level of creativity and self-development as creative self-efficacy is a byproduct of the knowledge of an individual's knowledge (Bei and Yidan 2016) . They further postulated that increased knowledge implies that there is an increase in creative self-efficacy resulting into an increase in innovative ideas (Bei & Yidan, 2016). Bei and Yidan (2016) developed hypothesis which confirm that knowledge exchange among employees increases innovation while carrying out research on creative self-efficacy and innovation

For SMEs in the service sector, development of Absorptive Capacity had great influence on the business entrepreneurial development. Being entrepreneurially oriented comprises the innovativeness of the organization, risk appetite, responsiveness as well as pro-activeness in finding solution to problems (Arash & Mahsa, 2016). They also hypothesized that entrepreneurial collaboration and development of Absorptive Capacity improved the entrepreneurial orientation of the SME organization. This upholds how important building credible relationship and knowledge exchange is to developing Absorptive Capacity. The entrepreneurial orientation of SMEs is positively impacted by the formation of joint ventures, merger and strategic alliances (Arash & Mahsa, 2016).

As the owners of service sector SMEs cultivate credible relationships and exchange knowledge with other owners, innovative ideas are passed from one SME to the other thereby boosting the process of creative thought (Arash & Mahsa, 2016; Ziemiańczyk et al., 2017). Bei and Yidan (2016) also pointed out this in their study when they said that innovation is stimulated by creativity.

The recognition of how important development of Absorptive Capacity is, is not only beneficial to the SME owners alone, management within the SMEs corporate structure also benefits as well. Management supports development of Absorptive Capacity in three distinct ways (Al Saifi, Dillon, & McQueen, 2016). Firstly, the SME's managers must encourage and allow the personnel participate in the process (Al Saifi et al., 2016). Secondly, service sector SMEs must design organizational goals to include the development of Absorptive Capacity as an highlight on the SME's vision statement (Al Saifi et al., 2016). Thirdly, the topmost management level should expressly and openly declare support for the development of Absorptive Capacity in the SME (Al Saifi et

al., 2016). Al Saifi et al. (2016) concluded management's active support for development of Absorptive Capacity has positive effects in encouraging effective communication, learning, and team building.

A supportive environment begins with management's commitment; the enabling environment created by the management will positively influence the development of Absorptive Capacity. To support an environment that promotes Absorptive Capacity development which in turn improves the strength of the relationships and knowledge transfer among the owners of the service sector SMEs (Tavani, Sharifi, Soleimanof, & Najmi, 2013), it is of high necessity for the management to have good understanding about how Employee-Organization Relations (EOR) contribute to the successful development of Absorptive Capacity within SMEs (Hui-Ru & et al., 2016). They made use of a 2-factor EOR framework to assess the relationship between the SME and the employee with regards to the motivating factor for employee to absorb capacity effectively.

The main factors of the framework comprises the contribution of the employee and the incentives the organization offers to the employee (Hui-Ru & et al., 2016). How strong the conceptual framework is depends mainly on the manager's action and in-actions and his relationship with the employees.

SME's Managers play a significant role in the development of Absorptive Capacity through the strength of the relationships and knowledge exchange. Hui-Ru & et al. (2016) hypothesized the potential contributions made by SME managers would impact positively on the development of Absorptive Capacity. Research has shown that Absorptive Capacity development enhance the performance of SMEs (Hui-Ru & et al., 2016; Tavani et al., 2013). They agreed to the fact that the benefits of developing Absorptive Capacity is proportional to the strength of the relationship between the SME's managers and the employees and the ability of the managers to effectively engage in knowledge exchange. The contributions of the SME's manager to the development of Absorptive Capacity depends on the managers' motivational package. The incentives package for the SME's managers to engage in the development of Absorptive Capacity can either be narrow or broad (Hui-u et al., 2016).

Material rewards are classified as Narrow incentives, while broad incentives can be non-material rewards like opportunities for personal development to material rewards (Hui-Ru & et al., 2016). With regards to incentivized

motivation, Hui-Ru & et al. was of the opinion that the better the incentives package offered, the more the manager's desires and willingness to engage in developing Absorptive Capacity (Hui-Ru & et al., 2016). Conversely, the manager's enthusiasm and desires to embark on the development of the Absorptive Capacity will be low where there is no incentive package in place for the SME's managers (Hui-Ru et al., 2016). The employees' engagement in the development of Absorptive Capacity is promoted by the strength of the relationship between the managers and the employees and the ability of the managers to effectively share knowledge.

In year 2016 Hui-Ru & et al. posited that the level of incentive packages presented to SME managers increase the expected contributions by management to internal development of Absorptive Capacity through the strength of the relationships and knowledge exchange with employees. They went on to conclude that good incentives package will encourage the manager of the SME to actively go after fulfilling the expectations seamlessly. They further explained that long term relationships within the Employee-Organization-Relation bring about increased success rates for the development of Absorptive Capacity and that benefits of absorptive capacity is maximized by the enabling environment created by mutual relationships .

The owners of service sector SMEs are motivated to participate in the development of Absorptive Capacity through the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge exchange as the desire to remain competitive increased (Silva, Rocha Dacorso, Barreto Costa, & Di Serio, 2016). Development of Absorptive Capacity through external exchange of knowledge is therefore a reflection of internal knowledge exchange; as internal knowledge exchange aids the setting of the precedent to pursue the exchange of external knowledge. Sawang & et al., 2016 stated that organization learning (OL) is referred to as the exchange of knowledge within the context of SMEs. The process of organization learning depends on the skills and experiences of the organizational members to bolster the SME'S overall performance (Sawang & et al., 2016). This method of group learning will be greatly advantageous and effective if the learning experience is designed to meet the participant's needs (Ramezani & Ava, 2017). Business consultancy which offers learning opportunities for the owners of service sector SMEs appears to be better effective to deliver educational content thereby encouraging innovation by taking cognizance

of the participant's needs (Sawang & et al.,2016). Internal exchange of knowledge has the benefit of designing knowledge exchange experiences to meet the need of the owners of SME's, external knowledge exchange on the other hands provides other form of benefits for service sector SME owners. External knowledge exchange expanded the access to resources for the organization.

Prior study has evaluated the impacts of external knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships for the development of Absorptive Capacity. In 2016 Sawang & et al. carried another study which further supported the previous research which established that SME's owners that engage in exchange of knowledge externally experience higher success levels compared to non-participants. By engaging in learning collectively and exchange of knowledge externally, participants are better able to detail real life skills and experiences in a less formal setting with other SME owners (Sawang & et al., 2016). When SME owners participate in the knowledge exchange experience, information are shared in a manner to improve the profitability of the SMEs within the local market and how to collaborate with other SME owners within the industry through social networking (Turner & Endres, 2017).

The two main knowledge forms are explicit and tacit. Olaniran, 2017 classified knowledge gained from experience as Tacit Knowledge. An example of Tacit knowledge was presented by Turner and Endres (2017) as the live and realistic experiences the much experienced owners of the SMEs shared with the new entrant in the industry and the less experienced owners. The process of exchanging tacit knowledge increased the self-efficacy and creativities of the owners the SME's (Wipawayangkool & Teng, 2016). In spite of the fact that, self-efficacy is a motivating factor required in engaging in mutually beneficial knowledge exchange, it is worthy of note that, individuals are not solely motivated by self-efficacy to share their knowledge (Wipawayangkool & Teng, 2016). Mutual exchange is often the motivating factor for beneficial and successful exchange of knowledge, particularly tacit knowledge.

The study carried by Olaniran in 2017 presented the barriers that hinder effective exchange of tacit knowledge. He first and foremost said, personal values can impede the desires of the SME's owners not to engage in tacit knowledge exchange . Personal values consist of the personality traits with the disposition that is incompatible with cultural or

knowledge superiority where a lower value is placed on one culture by another (Olaniran, 2017). The perception of SME owners involved in the knowledge transfer will hinder the development of Absorption Capacity (Olaniran, 2017).

Secondly, Olaniran discovered that the dearth of quality relationships in the industry social networking can prevent the transfer of tacit knowledge. Lastly, he said the culture of individual organization can lead to conflict as tacit knowledge is transferred. Lack of team cohesion creates resistance to innovative ideas and differing perception.

Further to the technological advancement, SMEs need to embrace development of Absorptive Capacity as nucleus part of their operational routine and procedures. Identifying the success factors, as well as the challenges is the first step to developing Absorptive Capacity process. However, the SMEs will be required to take a step further by building credibility relationships and effective implementation of knowledge (Asiedu, 2015). To adequately support development of Absorptive Capacity, management of the service sector SMEs must be ready to construct facilities and create conducive environment that encourages and enables the employees' of the SMEs development process (Asiedu, 2015). The success of developing Absorptive Capacity process commenced with the strong support from the management and subsequently drop down to the employees'.

2.6.4 Personality traits

As hypothesized by Rajput & Talan, 2017, SME managers may not be motivated naturally to support development of Absorptive Capacity. The intellectual capacity that an individual possess is his/her personal asset which aids the creation of competitive advantage for the individual. The idea of desire and willingness to exchange knowledge may be taxing and difficult for some set of individual SME's owners.

Personality traits influence the process of developing Absorptive Capacity and the ability of the individual to exchange knowledge. The influence of the individual's personality cannot be de-emphasized in the process of developing Absorptive Capacity. In a research conducted on Absorptive Capacity development among educational instructors, the individual's personality traits contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity (Zhang, Zhou, & Zhang, 2016). Quan, Di, & Lan, 2015; Rajput & Talan, 2017; Zhang et al., 2016 further said that individuals who exercise higher levels of extroversion, conscientiousness and were more agreeable will freely participate better in the process.

The study on personality traits influence is in agreement with prior research which suggested that effective exchange of knowledge is a function of the willingness of the participant to share their individual experiences (Sawang et al., 2016). In developing Absorptive Capacity through quality relationships and knowledge exchange process, the personality traits of the participants cannot be discounted. There exist different ways each individual will be motivated to participates in the process.

Development of Absorptive Capacity involves strength of the relationships and the knowledge exchanged based on mutual exchange between participants. It should be noted that all five personality traits have its distinct contribution to the development of Absorptive Capacity process; agreement between the participants contribute positively to the process (Quan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2016). Another important contributory factor in the development of Absorptive Capacity through quality relationships and knowledge exchange to bring forth innovative ideas is willingness and openness to exchange experience (Quan et al., 2015). Building trust and

confidence between partners in a relationship is another important contributory factor that must be considered in the development of Absorptive Capacity when trying to imbibe the habit of openness in sharing.

2.6.5 Trust

This emerges from the conceptual framework of Social Exchange Theory (SET). Trust emanates from two main roots; firstly trust can be grown from building a relationship that's personal and close (Blau, 1986). Secondly, trust can be grown from the mutual exchange in a relationship as well as the social exchange network (Blau, 1986). "The principle of reciprocity according to Social Exchange Theory (SET) asserted that participants will receive mutual contributions from the relationship (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Lioukas and Reuer (2015) proposed that as each participant contributes to the development of Absorptive Capacity through the strength of the relationships and knowledge exchange process because of seeking a mutual benefit rather than fulfilling a self-serving intention and trust will grow. Originally, trust begins with mutual exchanges. The study carried out by Lioukas and Reuer (2015) concluded that trust does not exist automatically because of social exchanges. Trust is cultivated over time.

Over time, individuals build strong and credible relationships through continual positive interactions among the owners of SMEs. As individuals established rapport with each other, trust grows out of the formation of close personal relationships (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Previous interactions and commitments within the social network create historical details of synergy between owners of the SMEs thereby leading trust. Trust can exist through caring about the other member(s), this type of affect-based trust will help strengthened the alliance and encourage development of Absorptive Capacity through quality relationships and knowledge exchange which will occur naturally (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). As exchanges occur, affections begin to grow thereby creating a strong connection in the alliance.

Building credible relationships cannot break the natural boundaries that exist among owners of SMEs. Lioukas and Reuer (2015) study showed that there exist certain boundaries within affect-based trust between owners of SMEs. The research suggested that when business owners are in less direct competition, the affect-based trust will

be stronger (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Trust will grow more easily when owners of SMEs are not directly competing for the market shares; also through less fear there exists competitive advantages (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). The identification of such boundaries is important when seeking to form relationships with other owners of SMEs.

The influence of personality traits helps to uncover the challenges in building credible relationship. An individual's personality traits contribute to individual's approach to placing trust on others and allowing trust to strengthen relationships (Rajput & Talan, 2017). Trust, quality relationships, and understanding of the role personality plays important role in developing Absorptive Capacity which help to increase the knowledge exchange of the participants. Trust enabled individuals to be more opened in the knowledge exchange process.

The personality trait which is made up of the Big Five Model includes extroversion, agreement, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and intellect.

Extroversion is the tendency of the individual owner of the SME's to be sociable, adventurous, energetic, and assertive (Zvolensky, Taha, Bono, & Goodwin, 2015).

Agreement is the ability to feel at ease around other owners of the SME's and the ability to be compliant and cooperative (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Conscientiousness is the ability to be self-aware, self-disciplined, and organized (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Emotional stability is involved with the ability to assess and express emotion (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Intellect is the desire for innovative learning, creativity, and new ideas (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Personality trait is the distinct expressions of the individual.

2.6.6 Propensity for relationships

The motivation to establish credible relationships varies among owners of SMEs. The literature review earlier pointed it out that owners of SMEs will establish credible relationships for knowledge exchange. However, there are other factors that may encourage the owners of SME's to seek and establish quality relationships.

The literature review section will evaluate factors that influenced the owners of SMEs to develop credible relationships with other owners of SMEs within the industry's social network. By having good understanding of the motivational factors, owners of SMEs can form alliance towards developing quality and meaningful relationships with other SME's owners.

Cultivating credible relationships with other owners of SMEs provide connections with other owners of SME's who face similar challenges previously. Absorptive Capacity process creates more than an opportunity to learn new concepts. The involvement of the owners of the SMEs in external knowledge exchange creates an intangible asset known as social capital. Social capital is the product of cultivating relationships which add value to the owners of the SMEs that participates in the process (Moyes, Ferri, Henderson, &Whittam, 2015).

Social capital enables owners of SMEs to take advantage of the resources to increase innovation and improve the efficiency in the operations of the SMEs (Moyes et al., 2015). The bridge which connects owners of the SMEs to collaborate and form alliance in the exchange of resources is trust (Moyes et al., 2015; Yoo et al., 2016). Social capital is a dynamic process through which owners of the SMEs recognized the potential in developing credible relationships (Moyes et al., 2015). Owners of SMEs are encouraged to develop credible relationships with other SME owners to basically to create social capital.

The literature review has successfully identified other factors which influenced SME owners to develop credible relationships in order create opportunities to learn (Silva et al., 2016). Man-pil et al. (2017) stated conscientiousness and agreeableness were two of the personality traits exhibited by managers which influenced building of credible relationship and organizational learning.

It should be noted that agreeableness is the only personality traits found to directly impact performance (Man-pil et al, 2017). As owners of SME's are being careful and vigilant in their relationships with other SME owners and seek to develop strong and credible relationships, the potential for the development of Absorptive Capacity improves (Man-pil et al., 2017). Relationships strengthened the development of Absorptive Capacity.

Cultivating credible relationships with other SME's owners is important to increase the knowledge base within the SMEs (Silva et al., 2016). To be innovative, SME owners need to embrace learning (Bei & Yidan, 2016; Silva et al., 2016). Development of Absorptive Capacity creates opportunity for informal learning (Bei & Yidan, 2016; Silva et al., 2016). Through developing quality relationships, mutual exchange of knowledge becomes seamless (Bei & Yidan, 2016; Silva et al., 2016). Cultivating credible relationships with other SME owners is a continuous process built on trust. Successfully engaging in external knowledge exchange depends on trust, credible relationships, and learning.

The market situation is very dynamic, therefore the market conditions shift periodically, and the relationships will need to be re-aligned for the owners of SMEs to benefit from knowledge relevant to prevalent market conditions (Silva et al., 2016). For an SME owner who is well motivated to develop credible relationships for the development of Absorptive Capacity, the process of re-aligning relationships become very fluid and dynamic (Silva et al., 2016). However, the owners of SME who is less motivated to strengthen the relationships, the process of re-aligning the relationships will be retrogressive and static (Silva et al., 2016). It is worthy of note that not all relationships consummated by the SME's owners directly relate to business activities of the SMEs.

2.6.7 Absorptive Capacity

This section of the literature review will provide detailed perception about Absorptive Capacity. A basic definition of Absorptive Capacity is provided, in order to provide a detailed view, all the essential phases of Absorptive Capacity will be elaborately discussed with the components and dimensions of each of the phase. The detailed view of Absorptive Capacity will help to broaden the understanding of how the SMEs receive knowledge and transform the knowledge into innovation and invention.

Absorptive Capacity is the ability to identify external source of knowledge, comprehend the knowledge provided, the ability to transfer the knowledge to service sector SME owner and its employees', and the SMEs ability and desire to capitalize the knowledge provided (Garrido, Parente, Gonçalo, & de Vasconcellos, 2017). This definition established Absorptive Capacity as the mediator between the past performance and achievement of the SMEs and the projected future performance (Garrido et al., 2017). It is important to note that the process involved in the development of Absorptive Capacity is not as simple as its basic definition.

Absorptive Capacity involves more than absorbing knowledge. Cohen and Levinthal (1990) described Absorptive Capacity as the ability of an SME owner to absorb knowledge effectively. Further study carried out on Absorptive Capacity by Oumaya and Gharbi's (2017) defined Absorptive Capacity by identifying and recognizing all the dimensions. Cohen and Levinthal's primary measurement of Absorptive Capacity was based on the outcome of Research and Development (R&D) activities.

However, Oumaya and Gharbi (2017) defined the measurement of Absorptive Capacity through knowledge assimilation; knowledge transformation, valorization capacity, and knowledge application. The detailed definition of the Absorptive Capacity model increases the ability of the owners of SMEs to accurately identify the challenges confronting the SMEs. The multi-dimensional focus of Absorptive Capacity creates a model for a detailed understanding of the Absorptive Capacity development process.

Understanding the contributory role of each dimension of Absorptive Capacity assists in the creation of the platform through which the research can provide detailed insights into the overall Absorptive Capacity development process.

Knowledge assimilation is the ability of the individual to comprehend new knowledge (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). Knowledge transformation occurs as the individual shifts from receiving external knowledge to transferring the knowledge to the SMEs (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). Valorization capacity is the ability of the SME's to improve the value of the knowledge (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017).

Innovation occurs as the SMEs applies the knowledge to find solutions to the problems and challenges confronting the SMEs (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). The two phases of Absorptive Capacity classified the dimensions.

2.6.8 Absorptive Capacity Phases

Absorptive Capacity development is divided into two-phase. Firstly, SME owners must be able to identify the sources of external knowledge exchange and understand the knowledge so that the owners of the SME's can transfer the knowledge acquired back to the employees' of the SME's (Garrido et al., 2017). Absorptive Capacity depends on the technical knowledge of the individual owners of the SME's to understand and the share knowledge (Yoo et al., 2016).

Garrido et al. stated, "The capability to acquire knowledge is an essential internal component of the innovative process" (p. 561). Understanding knowledge is fundamental to the ability to transfer knowledge back to the SMEs. Secondly, the owners of the SMEs must have the ability to absorb the knowledge and be able to effectively apply the knowledge for innovative solutions (Garrido et al., 2017). It should be noted that, possession of the knowledge without the ability to effectively transform and applies is insufficient if the knowledge is only to strengthen the competitive advantage of the SME's (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). To absorb the knowledge, organizational resources, such as human capital, are essential for the implementation of the techniques for creating innovative ideas (Yoo et al., 2016).

The two phases involved in the development of Absorptive Capacity consists of identifying the potential knowledge and the transformation of the knowledge into innovation. The two phases of Absorptive Capacity are known as Potential Absorptive Capacity and Realized Absorptive Capacity. The Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC) is the ability to identify external sources of knowledge and the ability to understand the knowledge (Garrido et al., 2017). The PAC is classified into assimilation of knowledge and knowledge transformation (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). The Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) is the transfer and capitalization of the knowledge gained (Garrido et al., 2017). The RAC phase of Absorptive Capacity is made up of Capacity valorization and Innovation dimensions (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). A detailed definition of Absorptive Capacity reveals a clearer path from knowledge acquisition to innovation

2.6.9 Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC)

The PAC phase begins with the perception of the SME owner as regards participation in knowledge exchange. The owners of SMEs are the main influencer of the Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC) (Garrido et al., 2017). The SME owner's cognitive and behavioral process determines how Absorptive Capacity process is developed (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). Cognitive processes are those in which the individual SME owner identifies external knowledge exchange opportunities (Garrido et al., 2017; Yoo et al., 2016).

Factors which drive the cognitive processes are past experiences of the SME owners, standard of education, and problem-solving experience (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). Where cognitive processes are external to the SME owners, behavioral processes are internal to the SME owners.

The behavioral process compliments the cognitive process, the behavioral process influences how the owners of the SMEs cultivate credible relationships with other participants during course of engaging in external knowledge exchange (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). Yoo et al. (2016) identified the formation of relationships between professionals as alliances. He maintained that, as the relationships grow and strengthened, the relationships become relational capital (Yoo et al., 2016).

Relational capital is the value placed on the relationships with other allied members within the industry's social network (Yoo & et al. 2016). Relational capital increases as the quality of the relationships grow through trust and mutual contributions to knowledge exchange (Yoo et al., 2016). The impact of the cognitive and behavioral processes on the Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC) highlights the role of personality traits in the development of the Absorptive Capacity. Relational capital is very important to the knowledge assimilation dimension.

2.6.10 Intellectual capital and PAC

A principal factor for knowledge assimilation is intellectual capital, intellectual capital is comprised of the collective knowledge and relationships of the SME owners and their employees' (Cassol, Goncalo, & Ruas, 2016).

Relational capital is a component of intellectual capital which coincides with the overall level of Absorptive Capacity (Cassol et al., 2016). In other words, Cassol et al. (2016) suggested that increase in the level of investment in the development of credible relationships results in increase in Absorptive Capacity.

Knowledge assimilation is partly based on the trust and the credibility of the existing relationships with the source of the knowledge (Cassol et al., 2016). Developing quality relationships strengthen the success of the SMEs overall Absorptive Capacity development. Intellectual capital is an intangible asset of SME's, Cassol et al. (2016) concluded that the greater the intellectual capital of SME's, the higher the SMEs ability to innovate. Intellectual capital is a factor that facilitates the ability to assimilate knowledge. The dimension in Potential Absorptive Capacity process is intellectual capital, the increase in intellectual capital increases the Absorptive Capacity of the SME's (Cassol et al., 2016;Tavani et al., 2013).

For knowledge to flow effectively from the PAC phase to the RAC phase, owners of the SMEs must be ready and willing to transfer the knowledge to SMEs employee's through organizational learning process (OL) (Nouri, Ghorbani, & Soltani, 2017). Organizational Learning (OL) with active support of the management of the SME's (Hui-Ru et al., 2016). Higher level of Absorptive Capacity facilitates smooth and hitch-free progression from the PAC phase to the RAC phase.

2.6.11 Organizational learning and RAC

Transition from Potential Absorption Capacity (PAC) to Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) shifts from the SME owners to the SME employees. As SME owners transfer knowledge to the SME's employees' through internal knowledge exchange known as organizational learning (OL) (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). Nouri et al. (2017) defined organizational learning (OL) as "...the change of the knowledge and values of the SMEs so that problem-solving skills and new operational capacities can be created" (p. 198). One of the challenges of the organizational learning (OL) process is that some owners of the SME'S may not perceived the benefits and value in acquiring external knowledge (Nouri et al., 2017; Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). The process of placing value on the knowledge by the owners of the SME's and their employees' reflects the valorization capacity dimension (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). Improvement in organizational learning (OL) will improve the Absorptive Capacity of the Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) phase.

Three major elements supporting the effectiveness of the organizational learning (OL), this three elements include motivation to learn, the capability to comprehend, and the openness to receive new knowledge (Yoo et al., 2016).

Motivation for the development of Absorptive Capacity identifies the behaviors behind the owners of the SMEs seeking external source of knowledge. This type of knowledge shared influences the ability of the SME owners to comprehend (Yoo & et al., 2016). As the participants in the development of Absorptive Capacity build trust with each other, the openness to absorb and share knowledge increases (Yoo & et al., 2016). The key elements serve as the bedrock for organizational learning (OL) (Yoo & et al., 2016). The trust and mutual exchange of knowledge among the owners of the SME's improves the organizational learning process (OL).

As organizational learning (OL) improves, there will improvement in Absorptive Capacity. In connecting the three main elements of OL with Absorptive Capacity, Yoo & et al. (2016) found that in learning, the first element has a positive relationship with both Absorptive Capacity and relational capital. Higher levels of desires and willingness to participate in learning activities will have a positive impact on the willingness of owners of the SME's to absorb knowledge for capital gain of the SME's and increase the credibility of relationships with other

owners of the SME's within the industry's social network (Yoo & et al., 2016). Intention and desire to learn is a necessary element for the elevation of Absorptive Capacity and effective organization learning (OL).

In evaluating the capacity to learn, the second main element of organizational learning (OL) as identified by Yoo & et al. (2016) as being either technical or non-technical. Absorptive Capacity development improves with higher level of technical knowledge than with non-technical knowledge (Yoo & et al., 2016). As Oumaya and Gharbi (2017) noted that Absorptive Capacity is enhanced when the prior experience of the SME owners adequately relates to the knowledge exchanged. Newly established service sector SMEs owners are more well exposed and comfortable with technology than the old time SME owners within the market in which the SME operates. The lack of adequate experience presents an obstacle to knowledge absorption (Yoo & et al., 2016).

The final basic element of organizational learning (OL) is the openness to absorb knowledge. The openness of the owners of the SMEs depends on the strength of the relationships the owners of the SMEs established with other owners within the industry's social network. For the owners of the SMEs, alliance learning provides the owners with the opportunity to gain external knowledge (Yoo & et al., 2016). The results of the study concludes that owners of SME's who engaged in the alliance learning exhibited higher Absorptive Capacity than those who seek external knowledge without desires to participate in alliance learning (Yoo & et al., 2016). These results are supported by the first step in the Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC) phase which is to identify the sources of the external knowledge (Garrido & et al., 2017). The lack of intentions to seek external sources of knowledge reduces the SMEs Absorptive Capacity development (Yoo & et al., 2016). To help improve organizational learning (OL) and enhance the value of knowledge, previous research carried out identified key elements and factors of the Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) phase.

2.6.12 Realized Absorptive Capacity

A critical review of the Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) phase identifies the principal factors and elements which are responsible to control how knowledge flows in this phase of Absorptive Capacity. Tavani et al. (2013) presented an in-depth view on Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) phase of absorptive capacity. As demonstrated in Figure 1 below, the RAC phase consists of five main elements (Tavani et al., 2013). The measurement of each main element was in terms of financial and/or non-financial impact of innovation (Tavani et al., 2013). The five main elements is comprised of the previous and relevant knowledge of the SME manager, the prior and relevant knowledge of the employees’, the communication network, the communication climate, and knowledge scanning (Tavani et al., 2013). The five elements help in having a clear view about the four organizational factors which control the Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) phase.

Figure 2.5 : Phases, Key elements, and factors of Absorptive Capacity.

The four determinants influencing knowledge exchange in RAC include the organization’s structure, gatekeeper position, Research and Development (R&D, and interface position (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch, Volberda, &

de Boer, 1999). Each Determining factor influence how the SMEs absorb knowledge from the Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC) phase. With the good understanding of determinant factor by the management, the benefits of the Absorptive Capacity will be maximized.

The organizational structure consists of three major forms, the forms are; divisional, functional, and matrix. The divisional form of organizational structure involves structuring the organization by product grouping or grouping by a strategic pairing of products within the SME's production line (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). The divisional form of organizational structure promotes strategic alignment in operations; it helps in the development of Absorptive Capacity. The SME owners and employees' of the division filter the knowledge (Tavani et al., 2013) as it directly relates to the goals and objectives of the division rather than how the knowledge can benefit the SMEs (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999).

The narrow focus of the knowledge does not consider how other sources of external knowledge could enhance the division in a way which the goals of the SMEs is supported (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). Out of the five main element of potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC), previous knowledge and knowledge scanning of the SME managers and the employees' serve as filters for new knowledge transferring from the PAC phase to the RAC phase (Tavani et al., 2013). A divisional form of the organizational structure affects the development of Absorptive Capacity moderately.

The second form of organizational structure is the functional form, the functional form include the groupings within the SME's based on specialized knowledge and activities (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). The focus on specialized skill and activities creates an environment for higher efficiency in production. However, the focus on specialized knowledge reduces the development of Absorptive Capacity in the SME's (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). Meanwhile, lower level Absorptive Capacity development as a result of the SME's adopting functional form of organizational structure is not suitable for business environments which are dynamic in operations. Matrix form of organizational structure is known to the structure that supports operational dynamism

The matrix form of organizational structure is a hybrid structure that combines the characteristics of the divisional form with the functional form of organizational structure (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). The need for specialization lowers the operational efficiency but has a higher level of absorptive capacity development (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). The forms of organizational structure adopted by the owners of the SME's determines how new knowledge will be absorbed and used. For effective transfer of knowledge from Potential Absorptive Capacity (RAC) to Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC), the gatekeeper position plays a significant role.

The knowledge scanning process filters new knowledge based on the goals and needs of the SME's. The gatekeeper position scans the external knowledge in relation to the need of the SME's (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). The responsibility of this role is to supervise the external environment for the development of the absorptive capacity, knowledge exchange opportunities and facilitates the connection of the knowledge back to the innovators. Having the owners of the SME's holding mediator role helps in reducing the narrow approach created by the divisional form of the organization structure (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999; Van den Bosch et al., 1999).

The gatekeeper influences the development of absorptive capacity of the SME's by recognizing the sources of external knowledge and facilitating the transfer of external knowledge back to the SME's (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). The desire to facilitate knowledge transfer helps to open communication channel within the SME's and industry's social network.

The SME owners open the channels of communication between management and the employees', effective communication channels enable discussion as to the criteria for knowledge scanning (Tavani et al., 2013).

Promotion of open communications at all levels of the SME's start with management (Tavani et al., 2013). To maximize the knowledge scanning process and to create a higher value for the external knowledge, communication serves as the backbone for the valorization capacity dimension within the phase of Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC).

Opening of functional communication channels support healthy Research and Development (R&D) functions. Research and Development (R&D), the third factor in the RAC phase, transform new knowledge into innovation through the open communication and communication network elements (Duchek, 2015; Tavani et al., 2013). As Research and Development (R&D) develops innovative solutions, new knowledge blends with existing knowledge (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). The harmonization process transforms the new knowledge into a form which aligns with the current operational goals and objectives while improving existing knowledge (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017).

As the harmonization take place, SME's owners engaged in the Absorptive Capacity development process to share ideas to find the best application of the acquired knowledge (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). The successful harmonization of the process culminates into an increased knowledge and innovation for the SME's, increased investment in research and development (R&D), provide the SME's with competitive advantage (Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017). The harmonization of the process promotes innovation through the assimilation of knowledge and idea generation (Cassolet al., 2016; Oumaya & Gharbi, 2017; Tavani et al., 2013). Transformation of knowledge into capital requires the owners of the SME's to effectively implement the innovative idea.

The interface position provides the last SMEs factor of the Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) phase. The interface position fills the void between research and development (R&D) and manufacturing as the two engage in implementation of the innovative idea (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). The interface position opens communication channels and facilitates collaboration between R&D and manufacturing (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch et al., 1999). By serving as the mediator between the two groups, the SME's experiences a reduction in the negative impact of decentralization of knowledge while encouraging and efficiently facilitating Absorptive Capacity development (Duchek, 2015; Van den Bosch & et al., 1999). Development of Absorptive Capacity through effective knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships improve the SME's ability to create innovative solutions.

Effective knowledge exchange in both phases of absorptive capacity (PAC & RAC) requires the SME owners to strengthen the credibility of the relationships among the owners of SME's within the industry's social network.

On the other hand, credible relationships depend on trust and desire to share business experiences (Yoo & et al., 2016). SME owners may be competing for market shares within the same market, nevertheless it is beneficial to develop trust on each other so that knowledge can be freely shared and received (Yoo et al., 2016). Absorptive Capacity development through effective knowledge exchange leads to the building of credibility relationships which encourage collaboration, sharing ideas, and innovation (Yoo & et al., 2016). Even when the SMEs are competing in the same market, owners of the SMEs increase the growth potential by understanding the phases and factors of Absorptive Capacity while engaging in external knowledge exchange.

2.7 Challenges Faced by SMEs to develop Absorptive Capacity

2.7.1 Knowledge Exchange Engagement for Absorptive Capacity Development

Absorptive Capacity is a foundational concept for organization learning theory. According to this theory, organizational learning is a function of an organization's absorptive capacity, defined as the ability of the firm to evaluate, assimilate, and utilize outside knowledge for commercial ends. Absorptive capacity requires learning capability and develops problem-solving skills. Learning capability is the capacity to assimilate knowledge (for imitation), whereas problem-solving skills represent the capacity to create new knowledge (for innovation) (Cohen & Levinthal 1990).

Absorptive Capacity was first described in academic literature in the fields of management and organizational science as a construct for consideration at the organizational level by Cohen and Levinthal (1990). Cohen and Levinthal (1990) proposed the original measure for absorptive capacity as "Research and Development (R&D) intensity," which was formulated as business unit-funded R&D expenditure expressed as a percentage of business unit sales and transfers. While Cohen and Levinthal (1990) suggest that the cognitive abilities of individual members are critical to Absorptive Capacity at the organizational level, absorptive capacity is generally regarded as an organizational-level construct (Lane et al., 2006; Todorova & Durisin, 2007; Zahra & George, 2002).

With the common and pervasive nature of knowledge in the organizations, the rapid convergence and diffusion of computing, communications, and content technologies offered the organizations significant opportunities to enhance organizational Absorptive Capacity (Roberts et al., 2012). Nonetheless, Zahra and George (2002) acknowledge that, while there is a diverse use of reference for Absorptive Capacity in the literature, there is also much ambiguity in the description of its measurement, definitions, components, antecedents, and outcomes.

Absorptive Capacity is an important theory in information Systems (IS) research. Organizations are dedicating more of their budgeted expenditure to services, software, infrastructure, and human resource enhancement with the aim of developing Absorptive, retentive, and exploitative capabilities to use with acquired knowledge.

Organizations are therefore able to achieve and sustain their competitive advantage (Armstrong and Sambamurthy, 1999).

This applies both to the organization's understanding of its operations, in terms of process and the management of its product and service offerings, as well as to its understanding of the "state of the art" in Information System. Being close to the cutting edge of Information System, through continual research and investment in technological assets and capabilities, will enable the organization to continually learn and absorb external knowledge to improve its absorptive capacity. Understanding how researchers observe and explain the extent of organizational absorptive capacity and its relationship with various aspects of information system is critical to the ability to prescribe methods and constructs that organizations can utilize to develop this capability."

2.7.2 Participating in Knowledge Exchange for Absorptive Capacity Development

Participation in Absorptive Capacity development process can often times be confronted by challenges.

Inadequate Resources Affect Absorptive Capacity Development

Inadequate resources is a major challenge that affects absorptive capacity development, time availability is a factor that affects ability to participate in direct physical capacity development activities, time is a very scarce and limited resource that hindered the participants from participating in the capacity development process, however technology advancement had provides the facilities and platform that has helped the participants to conveniently participate in absorptive capacity development process with limited time resources.

Apart from the time scarcity challenge, technology has also helped in combating other challenges affecting participating in Absorptive Capacity development process, this includes lack of office coverage, and direct physical participation in capacity development process is affected by the inability of the participant to leave the work space. Technology provides an alternative method for participating in Absorptive Capacity development.

Relevancy of the Content

Inadequate resources is not the challenges inhibiting participation in Absorptive Capacity development process, the content and relevance of the capacity is another important challenge that the participants considered when deciding either participate in the activity or not.

The quality of the content serves as a motivating factor to engage in Absorptive Capacity development process, the content must be focused in providing solution to a prominent business problem or as an idea for innovation.

Individual's Perceptions About The Importance of Participating

The importance of the perceived importance of participating in Absorptive Capacity development activities cannot be overemphasized. Lack of perceived importance of the process may prevent the ability of the participant to be opened and transparent during the capacity absorption process.

Individual's Previous Experience About The Process Influence Current Approach

Previous experience about Absorptive Capacity development process influence participation in future engagement. Substantial amount of revenue could be lost due to time taken away from the business. The Absorptive Capacity development opportunity must be in high quality to motivate the SME's owner to participate. The previous experiences in Absorptive Capacity development influenced continued participation based on the quality of the content.

Socializing improved Absorptive Capacity development experience

The established credible relationships motivate participants to engage in Absorptive Capacity development, the attempt to be thorough and detail on Absorptive Capacity development experience revealed reliance on trust and the credibility of the responses provided by the SME's owners. Some SME's owners make use of absorptive capacity activities as a primary method of operation.

Credibility is built through cultivating of quality relationships; the confidence to mutually participate in Absorptive Capacity development depends on the credibility of the source of the capacity. An established credible relationship helped in building credibility in the source of knowledge and motivates the SME owners to participate.

2.7.3 Knowledge Exchange Factors of Absorptive Capacity

Contributive factors that influence absorptive capacity development demonstrated the organization attempts to absorb the external source of knowledge. Absorptive Capacity developments represent the attempts by SME owners to capitalize on external knowledge exchange. The individual experiences of SME owners' attempt to implement advice from other SME owners reflected varying degrees of difficulty.

Negative Experience of Knowledge Exchange Impedes Participation

Having trust on the source of knowledge is very important for SMEs. Owners who received misleading information may developed apprehension and might not make effective use of important information provided in future that can lead to the growth of the SME. Regardless of the intention behind the information, misguided advice will discouraged future participation in Absorptive Capacity development.

Positive Experience of Knowledge Exchange Facilitates The Strengthening of The Operations

Positive experiences on knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development generated the opportunities to overcome inadequate resources. Inadequate funds can prevent a business owner from being able to start a new business in an actual office space as opposed to the home. The poor business location presented a challenge in attracting high net worth and credible clients.

This reflects that Absorptive Capacity development activities have both positive and negative impacts on businesses. Knowledge absorption is influenced by many factors such as trust, inadequate resources, marketing, and the pressure to succeed, and misguided advice

2.7.4 Quality Relationship Factors of Absorptive Capacity

Prior discussion of absorptive capacity development has highlighted ways in which credible relationships influenced Absorptive Capacity development as it relates to Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT).

Participating in Absorptive Capacity development process is influenced by established by the strength of the relationship, the established relationships helped in strengthening the trust and confidence of small business owners in the capacity development process. Building of credible relationships is essential for the ability to trust the shared knowledge. Trusting the source of knowledge increased confidence in participating in the Absorptive Capacity development process, increased and improved Absorptive Capacity development stimulate innovation.

A mentor is an important resource for SMEs

Relationships with other SME owners are very important to the development of Absorptive Capacity. The importance of quality relationships was observed through the discussions of accountability and finding solutions to problems. One specific type of relationship often mentioned is the mentor/ mentee relationship.

The motivation to be a mentor is the interest in rendering assistance to other SME owners that struggling with their SME business activities. Mentorship is considered as being informal, when an SME owner is aware of the needs of others who have challenges in their business. On other hand, a formal mentorship is when specific needs of the SME is being handled by a professional business coach. Mentoring can occur either through the voluntary engagement of other people or through a formal professional engagement of clients. Mentoring created more definition of the role of Social Exchange Theory (SET) within the activity of Absorptive Capacity development. Both the ACT and SET provides the guidance in establishing a solid foundation for the growth of the SME business. Strategically engaging other SME's owners is important.

Mentoring provided opportunity to help other SME owners, the owners of newly established SME's struggles with the business take-off or commencement. Mentoring provided the opportunity to listen to what the much

experienced SME's owners have experienced while trying to stabilize and grow their business. Mentoring results in improving the success and improved performance of the SME.

2.7.5 Relationship Building

Strategies that are employed in cultivating quality relationships for the SME's owners include the below:

- 1) Consistency in meeting people with similar goals and values.
- 2) Trust is the result of established relationships and improves the Absorptive Capacity development experience.
- 3) Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person.

Consistency in meeting people with similar goals and values, a simple statement sums up the interview responses, which provides answer to the questions on how to cultivate credible relationships.

Intentionality in getting to know other SME owners cultivated credible relationships. A simple phone call can help in the establishment and strengthening of credible relationships. The individual experiences shared by the participants corroborate this fact

Intentionality is often a common topic when discussing strategies to cultivate quality relationships, cultivating quality relationships required SME owners to be intentional in connecting with other SME owners. Most business owners preferred meeting outside of the business in an informal, casual setting. An activity as simple as meeting for coffee or going out to lunch play important role in establishing quality relationships.

Trust is the result of established relationships and improves the Absorptive Capacity development experience. The reciprocation of business was another strategy identified by SME owners in cultivating credible relationships, relationships are strengthened by sending referrals to other SME's owners. The reciprocation established loyalty and built trust between SME owners. The overall effect results is an improved Absorptive Capacity development.

Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person business activities. The third strategy often talked about is volunteering in the local community. Volunteering in the community provided an opportunity for the community to get to know the SME owners and the team personally. Volunteering provided the community with extra help to meet a need, through meeting this need, the community will develop a greater awareness of the SME services and brand.

2.7.6 Personality of the SME Owner

The influence of the individual SME owners' personality in respect of their approaches to Absorptive Capacity development through the contribution of quality relations and knowledge sharing are clear and common among SME owners.

The type of personality influences how relationships are established and cultivated

Relationship is a powerful two-way tool for SME owners. For the introverted business owner, the cultivation of relationships is avoided due to the type of personality. The challenge of being an introvert prevents such individual from intentionally engaging in cultivating credible relationships.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) was illustrated through the influences of the SME owners' personality, the quality and reliable data revealed that the success of the business is factor that improves the personality of the owners that influences the approach for cultivating credible relationships. Different personality types cultivate credible relationships and engage in Absorptive Capacity development easily than other personality types.

2.8 Methodology and Instrumentation.

The study make use of qualitative descriptive design to examine how service sector SME owners in Nigeria develop Absorptive Capacity for the growth and success of the SME's through the contribution of credible relationships and knowledge exchange.

The study provide a detailed understanding on the perception of owners of service sector SMEs to improve the credibility of the relationship and knowledge exchange within the industry's social network to enhance the development Absorptive Capacity. The study also provided insights into the influence of credible relationship on Absorptive Capacity development.

The qualitative descriptive study provide detailed information on the study through the SME owners' experience, and report from the previously concluded research on Absorption Capacity development through knowledge exchange and credible relationships.

Previous empirical research on Absorptive Capacity development, knowledge exchange and strength of the relationships provided a void that led to the need to embark on this study. The identified vacuum calls for the need to examine how the SME owners in the service sector in Nigeria develop Absorptive Capacity through the contributory factor of knowledge exchange and strength of the relationship within the industry's social network (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016).

In year 2016, Sawang & et al conducted a quantitative analysis of Absorptive Capacity development and its effectiveness in the SME's advisory programs. Turner and Endres (2017), identified Absorptive Capacity as a valuable resource for the owners of the service sector SME's.

Turner and Endres (2017) identified three major themes for the success of the SMEs in service sector. The first notable theme was the owners' networking and creating space for customer networking (Turner & Endres, 2017). Another important theme identified by Turner and Endres (2017) was the SME's business plan's effectiveness in identifying and addressing challenges.

Turner and Endres also identified achieving marketing differentiation as theme. The research by Turner and Endres concluded by suggesting future research study to include qualitative descriptive study on one of the identified themes and including SMEs in multiple industries (Turner & Endres, 2017). Other empirical studies included research on Absorptive Capacity; Absorptive capacity became an important concept in understanding the success of developing Absorptive Capacity. Yoo & et al. (2016) hypothesized Absorptive Capacity and relational capacity had a positive relationship with learning. Yoo & et al. (2016) stated: “Thus, it would be interesting to investigate the roles of Absorptive Capacity and relational capital in acquiring tacit and explicit knowledge in alliance learning” (p.250). The establishment of credible relationships and effective knowledge exchange and its ability on the development of Absorptive Capacity.

Elaborating on the previous study, a qualitative descriptive study create rooms for the exploration of the experience of service sector SME owners in respect of the development of Absorptive Capacity through contributory factor of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016).

With the use of well structured questionnaires, interviews and focus group, the research questions captured detailed and up to date data in respect of each respondent regarding their individual experiences.

Suggested future research encourages evaluation of Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships among owners of the SME’s (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016).

The well-structured researchquestionnaires established a baseline for service sector SME owners of involvement in the development of Absorptive Capacity through the use of effective knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships with other SME owners in different industries and varying backgrounds of experience (Turner & Endres, 2017).

To expand the scope of the previous research on Absorptive Capacity as suggested by Sawang & et al. (2016), evaluating factors that influence the development of Absorptive Capacity has assisted the owners service sector

SMEs to establish detailed understanding of Absorptive Capacity development as it relates to organizational learning (OL)

Questions relating to strategies used in curtailing the challenges and limitations of Absorptive Capacity development expanded the previous research conducted by Sawang & et al. (2016) on Absorptive Capacity development.

2.9 Chapter Summary

Chapter 2 presented the elementary requirements of developing Absorptive Capacity for SMEs in the service sector. Knowledge transfer is a fundamental element for the success of the SMEs in the service sector (Sawang & et al., 2016). It is recommended that continuous learning must be an active part of SMEs mission statement as well as the development and expansion plan. Benkler (2017) pointed it out that Absorptive Capacity was popularized by research carried out by Robert Hall in the early 20th century. Robert Hall, who researched factories within the pig iron industry in Cleveland, United Kingdom, found that companies were known to have shared information regarding manufacturing techniques as well as facility design plans as early as the 1850's (Benkler, 2017). Through development of Absorptive capacity, the SME's business experienced to growth and improved performance.

Using Social Exchange Theory (SET) and Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) as the theoretical foundations, Absorptive Capacity development among service sector SME owners is important for the growth and sustainability of SMEs. Sawang & et al. (2016) suggested expanding the scope of the research by examining the experience of the SME's owners with the knowledge gained, including working with limitations in the resources required to implement and capitalize the knowledge. Yoo & et al. (2016) suggested future research to include the study of how knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships influence Absorptive Capacity development.

The outline for the literature review is comprised of the importance of SME's for the growth and development of Nigeria economy, Small Medium Enterprise (SME's) business support the importance of Absorptive Capacity

development for the SME's owners in the service sector, knowledge exchange, social capital, Service sector SME owner's experience and, strength of the relationships, and healthy competition.

To study the major themes in the literature, the design of this study was a qualitative descriptive study. A descriptive study added to existing literature by examining the experience of the owners of service sector SMEs.

Chapter 3 covered the problem statement, research questions, methodology, research design, population, sample, sources of data, trustworthiness, data collection, and data analysis using thematic analysis, ethical concerns, limitations, and assumptions. Chapter 3 completed the foundation for conducting a qualitative descriptive study.

Qualitative research study provides quality and reliable descriptive data which is necessary for obtaining feedback from the owners of service sector SME's regarding the development of Absorptive Capacity through knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships with other SME owners within the industry's social network (Yin, 2014). A qualitative descriptive study allowed a general overview of service sector SME's owners perception of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships with other SME owners within the social network towards the development of absorptive capacity.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This study researched into how SME owners' perception of critical success factors such as knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships with other SME's owners contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity in service sector SMEs in Nigeria. Apart from knowledge exchange being the bedrock for informal learning, it also facilitates promotion of innovation in the SME's (Bei & Yidan, 2016). More importantly, the knowledge exchange experience is further enhanced by forming credible relationships with other SME owners. (Silva & et al., 2016). Examining the perception of SMEs owners about how knowledge exchange and relationship quality affects Absorptive Capacity will provide very useful strategies for the SME's owners.

Due to the nature of the objectives of this research study, a descriptive qualitative approach is seen as the best research design. Through the use of a descriptive approach, one is able to deploy an investigative strategy by the adoption of questionnaires, interviews, and a focus group of SME owners thereby providing a detail evaluation of the research questions by providing quality and credible descriptive data are able to be collated from individual experiences (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). In this Chapter, the selected methodology will be presented in detail which will cover the research questions, research design and methodology, the sample and population, research instrumentation, the trustworthiness of the research method, collection and management of data as well as its analysis, ethical concerns, and of course limitations. The chapter is concluded with the detailed summary.

3.2 Research Methodology

Osuala (1982) defined research as the process of arriving at reliable solutions to problems and challenges through the planned and systematic collection, analysis and interpretation of data. Research is the most important tool for knowledge advancement, promoting progress and for enabling man to relate more effectively with his environment.

Ezejelue and Ogwu (1990) defined research as a scholastic or scientific, as well as diligent investigation or inquiry in seeking facts or principles. Research is the systematic and controlled approach for providing answers to questions. Generally, research is a systematic process of investigation designed to seek solution to practical problem confronting mankind.

3.2.1 Types of Research Methodology

Research may be basic or applied. A research is basic when it deals with relationship between two or more variable and its purpose is the development of theory or model.

Applied research on the other hand, tests the product of basic research findings. The aim is to test theories, model or concepts derived from basic research in real problem situation.

Basic Research is otherwise known as Pure or Fundamental Research while Applied Research is also known as Demonstrative Research.

Fundamental or Pure Research

This is also called Basic Research; this type of research has to do with the construction and development of theories which may lead to formulation of principles and generalization that will enhance understanding. Basic Research is starting from nothing to something, moving from the unknown to create a path for the known, discovering new ground and establishing new principles to organize nature. Basic or fundamental research is characterized by a very rigorous and well-structured types of analysis.

Applied or Demonstrative Research

This is the application of basic knowledge or established principles to specific problem situation either in the laboratory or in the social or industrial setting. Theories are tested with regards to their effectiveness in different area of human endeavor. The established theories in the natural science are tested and applied for the production of certain products for use by man. Also in management, theories are tested and applied to explain, describe and understand some phenomenon in human environments. Applied Research can be sub-divided into the below:

Action Research

This is a localized applied research which is usually small scale in nature and designed to address restricted local problems, for example problem of poor customer are addressed by such organizations through action research aimed at improving performance.

Evaluation Research

Evaluation research is usually engaged in by owners of business (SMEs) when they need to know the functional effectiveness of their business. Evaluation research could be referred to as an assessment of return on investment by owners of business (SME's), it is employed to ensure the success or failure of various educational programs. Evaluation research is not quite popular because all researches are evaluated and project performances are always assessed as routine not necessarily for research purpose.

Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is the type of research in which information about a phenomenon are expressed through verbal symbols.

Quantitative Research

Quantitative research is the type of research when information collected are expressed through mathematical symbol i.e. data collection and analysis.

Researches are also classified according to the methodology, some of the well-known research methodologies are:

- i) Survey research method
- ii) Experimental Research method
- iii) Causal comparative method
- iv) Historical research method
- v) Case study research method

The appropriate research design that fits the objectives and goals of this research is the qualitative descriptive design. The use of qualitative descriptive research for the study create room for investigative strategy to be deployed which provides detailed information about the research questions through the gathering and collation of relevant qualitative data from the experience of the owners of service sector SMEs (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016) through the use of questionnaires, interviews, and a focus group .

3.3 Research Approach

This study takes an inductive approach and does not involve formulation of hypotheses. An inductive research approach was selected, as this is concerned with building understanding from the context in which the events are taking place, and uses the flexible structure of qualitative data sources when the researcher can be part of the research process. An inductive approach can contribute to new theories and generalizations. It starts with a research question/s, aims and objectives to derive findings from the collected data and its analysis, to provide valid answers at the end of the research process.

3.4 Philosophical Underpinning

“Several studies have identified different research philosophies that have shaped social science research and their implications on the design and interpretation of such investigations (Creswell, 2003; Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2007; Crotty, 1998; Denzin and Lincoln, 1998; Guba and Lincoln, 2005; Howe, 1988; Neuman, 2000; Puhch, 1998; Tashakkory and Teddie, 1999, 2009). Throughout this study the researcher has maintained a pragmatic worldview of knowledge. Pragmatists claim that knowledge arises out of situations, actions and consequences,

rather than being an antecedent condition. The pragmatist researcher is not conditioned by any one system of philosophy or reality, and this works well particularly for methods research. Researchers are given the freedom to choose which methods or research procedures best suit their purposes. Pragmatists like mixed methods researcher, do not see absolute unity, and consider many different possibilities for collecting and analysing data. Creswell (2003) argues that the philosophical stance taken by researchers has implications in regard to the position the researchers take throughout their study, in terms of the ontological, epistemological, axiological and methodological perspectives, as well as the nature of the rhetoric adopted to report the findings.

This research adopted a pragmatist worldview of knowledge and embraced a qualitative method of enquiry to achieve its objectives. Pragmatism is favoured as a philosophical position as it allows the researcher on embracing the methodology that works best for the problem at hand. Alternative worldviews of knowledge prioritize the method over the problem. The researcher wants to adopt a knowledge philosophy, that allows him the freedom to choose the research method, technique, and procedures, best suited to the situation at hand. Pragmatism allows this degree of freedom, considering that it is not tightly connected to any one single method or technique, but allows the use of what works within a given context. Pragmatism has been identified as being the most commonly adopted philosophical rationales for mixed methods studies (Biddle and Schafft, 2014; Bryman, 2007; Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2011;

3.5 The Research Design Framework

The design of this research study is based on the research framework as affirmed by Creswell (2003, page 5) and associates three different facets of research: (a) the theoretical perspective and philosophical considerations (ontology, epistemology, axiology) underpinning the study; (b) the strategies of inquiry; and (c) the distinct phases of the research process. These three dimensions of the research are all considered with the research objectives in the background. This implies that the research is designed purposely to reach the objectives it set out to attain. Here Creswell (2003) argues that primarily the researcher needs to decide on the epistemology informing the research, such as, positivism, post positivism, constructivism, advocacy, or pragmatism.

With this position to the philosophical view of knowledge in mind, the researcher can proceed to determine which approach to research best suits his/her philosophical world view, and his/her research objectives: qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods. At this point the researcher's planning can be translated into practice, with the design of the research process itself: the research instrument, the data collection and capture; the data analysis and evaluation; the write-up and validation of the results.

Source: Adapted from Creswell, 2003

Figure 2 : The interconnection of philosophical worldviews, strategies of inquiry and research stages”

3.5.1 Justifying Choice of Research Methodology

Research designs are approaches of carrying out research studies to enable the study to achieve the objectives of the research studies. The researcher used a qualitative descriptive design to collect the quality and credible data from the strategies adopted by the SME owners' to develop Absorptive Capacity. The qualitative descriptive study also collected data on the self-perceptions of relationships. The qualitative descriptive study design allowed the exploration of how SME's owners' cultivate credible relationships with other owners within the industry's network through knowledge exchange as it contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity.

3.5.2 Rationale for adopting Qualitative Methodology

“Quantitative researchers are intent that ‘hard, generalizable ... data’ (Sieber, 1973, page1335) offers a preferred level of analysis, and affirm that research should be free from ‘time and context generalisations’ (Nagel, 1986). They adopt a positivist approach to their work, and believe that the observer is distinct from the subjects that he is observing. Advocates of qualitative research methods, on the other hand, refute positivism. They argue that both ‘time and context-free generalisations’ are undesirable and impossible, and profess the superiority of ‘deep, rich and observational data’ (Sieber, 1973, page 1335).

They affirm that research is ‘value-bound’, and that it is impossible to keep the knower and the known separate and distinct from one another (Guba, 1990). Qualitative research offers rich data and allows for comparison across cases, whereas quantitative methods do not permit. Quantitative research, when used independently of any other method, suffers from a number of shortcomings. The researcher’s categorization of data or theories used may differ from those accepted and understood by the researched. Also, the output of the research may be considered to be too abstract, while it may be difficult to apply to local contexts and situations. Further, the quantitative researcher may focus so closely on hypothesis testing, that he may completely neglect the actual generation of the theory or hypothesis.

The choice of method is largely determined by the fit between the research objectives and the research methodology. The existing ACAP models are inadequate for small firms in the service sector (Nonsanka & Takeuchi, 1995; Thomas & Wood, 2014). This indicates that exploratory research (i.e. research of a qualitative nature) must be undertaken to address these issues. Furthermore, internal ACAP processes need to be identified, and their effectiveness assessed and evaluated (explanatory research) to allow for recommendations and predictions to be made. A qualitative research design offers a research framework, which better addresses the research objectives outlined in Chapter 1. Qualitative research provides rich descriptive data which is necessary for obtaining feedback from the small business owner regarding small business owner networking (Yin, 2014). A qualitative descriptive study allowed a holistic view of the participants' individual experiences on the development of absorptive capacity amongst small business owners. The individual experiences contributed to prior research by providing rich deep data missing from quantitative research.

3.5.3 Crafting of a definition of SMEs for the purpose of this study

Sixty businesses from the service sector have formed the basis of this study. The features of this sample has been considered and evaluated to determine the precise nature of the participants in the sample and to ensure that the firms in question fall within the category of SMEs, the context within which this research is grounded. At the fundamental part of the analysis, the firms have been classified according to headcount, this being the most commonly used objective (EU Commission 2005; Kushnir, Mirmulstein, Ramalho, 2010; World Bank, 2016).

Following on the recommendations of various proponents of the definition of SMEs (Burrows and Curran, 1989; Curran and Stanworth, 1986; Kushnir, Mirmulstein, Ramalho, 2010) the researcher has also considered a number of other industry-specific variables to refine the definition and reduce the ambiguity surrounding the firm classification. All of the firms in the services sector for this research have been qualified according to size of workforce (based on full-time equivalent number of employees). For the purpose of this study, the target population is owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria with less than 500 employees.”

3.5.4 Survey Research Design

Survey research is that part of non-experimental research design which has been commonly put to use in data gathering, it is a very important and useful research design. Survey are generally conducted in the society in the form of questions directed at different people to ascertain their perspective opinion, beliefs, attitude and general behavioral dispositions regarding an issue (in the context of this study which is looking at the contribution of credible relationships and effective knowledge exchange to the development of Absorptive Capacity).

Survey research study both large and populations by selecting and studying samples chosen from the populations to discover the relative incidence, distribution and interrelation of sociological and psychological variables (Osuala, 1982). Surveys provide information to the administrator, manager or executive from which decision are made, survey gathers data, interpret the data, synthesize and integrate the data to point out the implication and interrelationships. Survey research design is more realistic and factual than experiment because it evaluates process in their natural settings. The survey research design is flexible and versatile.

The followings are the steps taken in this study to design the survey research:

- ❖ Construction of well-structured questionnaire
- ❖ A convenience sampling method was used, 60 owners of service sector SME's were engaged in the survey, from the 60 participants that responded to the questionnaires, a convenience sampling was executed which bring out 20 owners for interviews. A convenience sampling is the result of the researcher selecting participants who will be easy to reach (Yin, 2014). The convenience sampling consisted of participants whose responses indicated he or she best provided the rich, deep data necessary for adding value to this study (Yin, 2014). The 20 owners that emerged from this stage was further scaled down to 6 SME owners who formed the focal group for the study.
- ❖ Thematic analysis method was used in analyzing the data collated from the survey.
- ❖ Qualitative and descriptive method was used in the interpretation of the data collated.

Survey can be differentiated by methods used in obtaining information from the concerned population; these methods include questionnaire method, the personal interview, the telephone and the mail methods.

3.5.5 The Questionnaire

The questionnaire is a survey research instrument designed in question form to obtain feedback information from subjects (Service sector SME owners) with respect to their opinions, attitudes, beliefs and motive regarding the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge exchange in the development of Absorptive Capacity.

The questionnaires is the most widely used survey research technique in sub-Sahara Africa most especially Nigeria. For a well-constructed questionnaire, analysis and interpretation, a good background in text and measurement is required.

Writing question items in a questionnaire involves writing and rewriting items until they are clear and succinct. Principal feature of a good questionnaire are stated below:

- ❖ The number of questions should be kept at the minimum; the questions should focus on the main topic of the study. The questions that are not relevant to research study should be avoided.
- ❖ The question should be short and clear, short and clear questions are easier to answer than long ones
- ❖ Offensive questions should be avoided. A respondent will not be cooperative if offensive questions are asked; questions concerning personal life of the respondent should be avoided as much as possible.
- ❖ Influential or leading questions should not be used, this type of question will influence the thoughts of respondents and thus true answer may not be obtained.
- ❖ Questions should be designed to find facts that respondents are expected to be able to give.
- ❖ Questions requiring reasoning or special knowledge in order to be answered should be avoided.
- ❖ The questions must be organized into coherent and sequential manner.
- ❖ Questions that are vague should be avoided
- ❖ Questions that are ambiguous should be avoided.

60 Questionnaires was deployed for the purpose of this study.

3.5.6 Interview

Interview is a conversation between two people (interviewer and interviewee) where one person asks questions and the other answers. Interview is a target oriented conversation carried out for the purpose of obtaining certain information for use in a research. Out of the 60 respondents for the questionnaire stage, 20 was selected for the interview stage. Through interview, reliable and valid information are collected from the response of the interviewee in line with a planned sequence of questions. There are structured and unstructured interviews.

Structured Interview

The Structured interview consists of rigid set of questions drawn from the specific research problem area. It is less flexible and requires thorough knowledge of the research problem by the researcher or the interviewer. Structured interview is used effectively in order to enable the researcher to structure his survey and devise adequate and precise questions from which deviation can be minimized. Structured interview could be informal of schedule in line with the purpose of investigation.

Unstructured Interview

The unstructured interview is more suited for getting varied response and allows the researcher more access to different dimensions of information concerning the problem area. The unstructured interview is generally used to obtain information at the early stages of a research work.

3.5.7 Stages of Interview

The interview approach in research investigation passes through four stages. The four stages are as follows:

- ❖ Identification of the sample members for the interview
- ❖ Preparation and organization of the interview material and modalities.
- ❖ Interview questioning process is the technical aspect of the interview method in research study. To ensure that the researcher's goals are achieved, the interviewers are expected to ask all the applicable questions as they are given or structured without more explanations and proofing or even variations in the wordings.

In addition, the researcher (interviewer) must not give his own views or explanations of the meaning of the questions as this may not represent the researcher's focus.

- ❖ Recording the responses of interviewee's (owners of the service sector of the SME's) is an important aspect of the interview process. The researcher's should ignore the irrelevant statements made while concentrating on the points relevant to the study.

3.5.8 Mail Surveys

To expand and enlarge the coverage of the survey, questionnaire is usually mailed to the subjects (owners of the service sector of the SME's) and after completing the questionnaire, the subjects return the completed questionnaire to the researcher (investigator). The mailing is through electronic mail (email), the postal and courier services. A follow-up letter could be sent to the respondents as reminder; this will help in increasing rate of return of the questionnaire. Also, follow up telephone and other means of communication will enhance the rate of questionnaire return.

The research survey for this study was carried out with the aid of questionnaires which were delivered through mail survey. The interviews were conducted with the aid of structured and unstructured questions to elicit facts and relevant information from the service sector SME owners in Nigeria. The focus group which is a small group of owners of service sector SMEs that are chosen to discuss and give their perception about the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge in the development of Absorptive Capacity for the success of SMEs. The focus group consisting of six (6) owners of service sector SMEs was drawn from the twenty (20) owners that were initially picked for interview which are also sampled out of the original sixty (60) participants that the questionnaires were served on.

The qualitative descriptive study design is more closely aligned with this study than grounded theory, narratives, or phenomenology. Researchers use grounded theory when developing a new theory, this practice does not meet the objective of creating a detailed understanding of the strength of the relationships and

knowledge exchange in developing Absorptive Capacity (Morse et al., 2016). Going by this submission, narrative design present information about one individual owner, therefore narrative design tends to limit the quality and relevance of the data by excluding the experiences of other owners of the service sector of the SME's (Smith, 2015).

Phenomenological studies present us with the live and realistic experiences of individual SME's owner rather than a specific event (Smith, 2015). The qualitative descriptive study attempt to examine the effects of Absorptive Capacity development being experienced by the owners of the service sector SMEs.

The researcher employed the use of questionnaires to gather information about the self-perceptions regarding the personality traits of the owners of service sector SMEs to identify the personality factors which influence development of Absorptive Capacity. The data collected provides the study with details in respect of the personality traits of SME owners that contribute to the successful development of Absorptive Capacity. (Yin, 2014). The design of the questionnaire makes a provision for each respondent (owners of the SMEs) to scale or rank their self-perceptions as regard of his or her personality.

Structured questions used during the interview provide guidelines for the interviewee (SME owners) to share individual experiences. The use of structured questions in an interview session, avail the interviewees with the opportunity to account for their subjective experiences in the development of Absorptive Capacity through the impact of knowledge exchange and strengthening of quality relationships with other business owners within the industry's social network (Yin, 2014).

Structured research questions serves as a guideline to the owners of service sector SME's in the exchange of their experiences regarding challenges of developing Absorptive Capacity and strategies employed to capitalize on the innovative idea acquired from the process (Yin, 2014).

The unstructured questions used during the interview session provides quality fact and details required to x-ray the challenges of developing Absorptive Capacity through the contributory role of credible relationships and knowledge exchange for the success of the SME's.

It is worthy to note that focus group discussions differ from an interview, interview data provides one line of thought (O.nyumba et al., 2018) while the data collected from the focus group x-ray the challenges faced in developing Absorptive Capacity and the success accruing to the strengthening of quality relationships and effective knowledge exchange among owners of the service sector SMEs within the industry's social network.

3.6 Research Questions

The research questions of the study was premised on the theoretical framework and the literatures that laid the foundation for the development of Absorptive Capacity in the service sector Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The research questions were coined from the Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and the Social Exchange Theory (SET).

The above mentioned theories, postulations and conceptual framework highlighted the under listed issues as it relates to the structuring of relevant and an all-encompassing research questions that will solidify the foundation of developing of Absorptive Capacity in the service sector Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs):

- ❖ Willingness and readiness to absorb knowledge
- ❖ Availability of resources (technical skill) to absorb the knowledge
- ❖ Rigorous nature and difficulty of acquiring the knowledge
- ❖ Existence of quality relationships among the owner of SMEs
- ❖ Willingness and desire to engage in the developmental process
- ❖ Interactive ability of SME owners
- ❖ Trust, mutual willingness, and desire to engage in the development of absorptive capacity.

- ❖ Cultural ethnocentrism and cultural accommodation, this explains a situation where two different individual from different geographical area absorb each and perceive their culture to be at par with other culture.
- ❖ Identification of knowledge gap
- ❖ Identification of external source of knowledge and ability to understand the knowledge.
- ❖ Support of the topmost management for the developmental process.
- ❖ Incentivized and improved motivational package for effective implementation

3.6.1 RESEARCH QUESTION 1

RQ1: How does SME owners' perception of knowledge exchange and quality of relationships with other SMEs aid the development of absorptive capacity?

Research question 1 which was designed to elicit facts about how quality relationships and knowledge exchange contribute to the development of absorptive capacity was premised on the identification of the knowledge gap and identification of external source of knowledge. The owners of service sector SMEs has been able to identify knowledge within the organization and to cushion the effects and acquire the required knowledge, an external source of knowledge was identified. Therefore, in order to benefit and harness from the external knowledge there is to make use of the social network within the industry, and this will only be successful if the quality of relationships with other owners is strengthened.

3.6.2 RESEARCH QUESTION 2

RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve knowledge exchange with other SMEs?

The research question 2 was designed in line with the postulations of absorptive capacity Theory (ACT) which observed that there is slack in the willingness and desire of the owners of the service sector SMEs to absorb knowledge. Also, the rigorous nature of acquiring knowledge was identified. In addition, the incentive and motivational package for the SME managers that will be grossly involved in the implementation of the management policy was also identified. In view of this, it is very important that question that will obtain data and information on the strategies required to be tailored to resolve the challenges should be included in the research questions.

3.6.3 RESEARCH QUESTION 3

RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners?

Research question 3 was developed from the concept of Social Exchange Theory (SET), Personality Traits and the Organizational Learning (OL) principle. It was observed that trust, mutual willingness, and desires to engage in the development of absorptive capacity process to determine the level of interaction, also the personality traits which is the disposition of the owners not to be forthcoming with knowledge as a result of cultural value and superiority was identified as causative factor that impacts negatively on the development of absorptive capacity.

In addition, the level of topmost management involvement and support and the need to design organizational goal to include development of absorptive capacity in the SME was identified as a contributory factor for the cultivation and consistent maintenance of quality relationships. Therefore, there is need to design a question that will elicit response in respect of this vital issue.

The questionnaire designed to elicit data in respect of Research Question 3 (RQ3) is labeled as appendix H (see Appendix H). The questionnaire provides the basis for the owners of service sector SME's to express their views to participate in voluntary social interactions. A rating scale (a rating scale is used to provide a graded response to a question) measured self-perceptions of personality traits, such as being extroverted or introverted. This data helped provide qualitative data to establish the basic foundation for Research Question 1(RQ1) and Research Question 2 (RQ2) by identifying owner's that participated in development of absorptive capacity process within the industry's social network. The answers provided by the participants helped in identifying the participants that qualifies for the interview stage.

The un-structured interview questions (See Appendix J) allowed for detailed understanding of Research Question 1 (RQ1) and Research Question 2 (RQ2) by examining the motivating factors that influences the owners of service sector SMEs to participate in the development of the absorptive capacity process.

With the use of un-structured questions, the interviewer attempt to provide guidelines for the interviewee (owners of service sector SMEs) into being more open about their responses regarding their individual experiences (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The researcher (interviewer) did not make use of structured interview questions because it is less flexible and place some level of restriction on the responses to be provided by the owners of these SMEs to the questions.

To further add value and depth to the interview session, a focus group discussion was also initiated to provide insight as to how owners of service sector SMEs perceived the development of absorptive capacity through the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge exchange activities, as well as how SME's owners cultivate relationships with other owners within the industry's social network. The focus group is made up of both the experienced and less experienced (new entrant) owners. This selection of the focus group discussants assisted in providing insights for the study through mutual discussion from different perspectives.

Responses and facts elicited from the focus group discussion is quite different from the data and information obtained from the interview session. Most of the discussants on the focus group are more reactionary to the submissions of other discussants therefore more and additional information are provided voluntarily.

Thematic analyses of the focus group discussion transcript gave an insight as per the experience on absorptive capacity Development process. The focus group allowed the discussants to initiate and consummate new social connections, engage in mutually beneficial discussion, and learn profitably from one another.

3.7 Population and Sample Selection

Research is concerned with problems which mean that the identification of a problem area for the research is the first step prior to the selection of the research population. The identified research problem leads to the prevalence of the problem which in turn point to the relevant subject of the research. Therefore, further to the identification of the problem, the researcher will have to define the characteristics of the population from where the sample will be drawn.

3.7.1 The Population

The population in a research study is made up of all imaginable components, subjects or observations in a particular research's focus point. Population could be called the universe or the entire group (subject or observation) whose peculiar characteristics or behavioral pattern are to be estimated. The population could be students, market women, stores and company's employee. For the purpose of this study, the population in contention is the owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria.

Population could be very large or small; it should be known that the entire population will very difficult to be studied and investigated in a research study. The practicable strategy is to draw a sample from the population and studied in the research.

3.7.2 The Sample

The research sample is part of the research population, the sample is known to be a sub-set of the population, and it is the sizable members of the population that are subjected to the research study. It is considered rational and economical to study a fractional part of the entire population than studying the entire population. The result or outcome of the study is generalized to entire population.

The process of selecting the sample size is very essential in the research study; varying methods of selecting the sample have been recognized. The process of selecting the sample is sampling.

3.7.3 Sampling

Sampling is the process of drawing up a representative sample from the population. The sampling process is as stated below:

- ❖ Defining the population
- ❖ Making the list of all units in the population
- ❖ Determining the size of the sample in line with all characteristics of the population.
- ❖ Drawing the sample units from the list so that they can adequately represent the entire population.

For the purpose of this study, the target population is owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria with less than 500 employees. According to the data provided by the registrar of Corporate Affairs Commission, collaborated by the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, it was reported that there were well over Five Million (5million) Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria as at 2017 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2016.). With the huge size of the target population, there are known similarities and uniformities as per the features and characteristics among the population which is in line with the research investigation; therefore drawing up a sample along these similarities will give an accurate result of the entire population.

It should be noted the research study employed the use of qualitative research method; qualitative descriptive research does not make use of numerical or statistical tools in identifying the sample size like quantitative

research; in qualitative type of research the sample size is determined by the projected saturation (Yin, 2014). Saturation takes place when there is continuous repetition in the result of the data collected (Dai, Free, & Gendron, 2019; Saunders et al., 2018; Yin, 2014). The level of saturation varies based on the method of data collection adopted. This study employed the used of questionnaire, interviews, and focus group for data collection.

The first method of data collection adopted in this research study is the questionnaire. The questionnaire for this study consisted of a sampling of 60 owners of service sector SMEs in Nigeria in order to attain saturation level. A sample size of 60 participants accounted for attrition in participation and completion of the questionnaire.

The researcher's ability to access the directory of members of the Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce (NACC), Nigeria-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC) and Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME) was facilitated by the secretariats of these Associations. In order to have unrestricted access to the required data in respect of the subject matter, the researcher had to register his company, as a member of the Nigeria-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC), Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce(NACC) and NASME. The decision was helpful in no small measure as it facilitates the access to relevant information and data for this study as well as in the distribution and timely receipt of the completed questionnaires.

The research studies' primary objective is to x-ray the success factors and also design effective framework for the development of Absorptive Capacity in service sector SMEs in Sub-Sahara Africa with focus on Nigeria. The target population is the owners of service sector SMEs less than 500 employees. A convenience sampling method was employed in the selection of the sample for the study. A sampling frame of each of the members of the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME), Nigeria-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC) and the Nigeria-American Chamber of Commerce (NACC) was developed .With a large population, creating a sample representative of the entire population is pertinent.

The websites for the Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce (NACC) and the Nigeria-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC) provides a veritable resource for this study (see Appendix A). The Nigerian-American

Chamber of Commerce (NACC) membership directory consists of approximately 1,800 members, there are 1,661 members in the Nigeria-British Chamber of Commerce' (NBCC) directory. The chamber of commerce provides the SMEs with up to date information in respect of government policy and regulation, it also serves as an interest or pressure group to make demand on behalf of the members from the government. It provides a common front for SMEs owners.

The formal request to use the directories was made through electronic mailing method of communication, which is the acceptable form of contact for every member of the association. The Director of Public Relations approved the use of the Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce' (NACC) directory while the Executive President of the Nigeria-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC) granted approval for the use of the association's directory as well (see Appendix A).

The sample size is made up of individuals identified as owner service sector SMEs in Nigeria with cognate experience in the development of absorptive capacity through the success factor of quality relationships and knowledge exchange. Each member that has a registered functional electronic mail address was contacted and invited to participate in the questionnaire.

The front page of the questionnaire contained the informed consent notifying the participant of privacy protection and the right to terminate participation at any time without penalty (see Appendix C). To account for attrition, another method of recruiting included selecting participants from the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME) with registered membership strength of over Three Thousand (3,000) with just about 1600 active and financial members.

In achieving the required sample size, the sampling selection process carried out involves the selection of equal number of SME owners from each data basket (NACC, NBCC & NASME). The questionnaire invitation was sent to twenty (20) SME owners on the register of Nigerian- American Chamber of Commerce (NACC) and another twenty (20) invitations were sent to the Nigeria British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC). To complete the

sampling selection process, Twenty (20) owners from the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME) were also invited to participate in the questionnaire.

The method of selecting the sample depend mainly on the theme of the study, the theme of the study is how the owners of service sector SMEs perceived the contribution of knowledge exchange and quality relationships in the development of absorptive capacity. A convenience sample comprised of owners of SMEs that are accessible (Yin, 2014). In view of the available resources required in the identification of the owners of SMEs, the study was based on a convenience sampling.

To set up an effective sample requires a well thought-out plan and meaningful process. Yin (2014) recommends using a multi-phase screening process where twelve or more participants are eligible to be selected for the study. The first phase of the selection process is the compilation of the list of members from the chamber of commerce who registered a functional electronic mailing address contact. The first phase consisted of thirty (30) owners of SMEs that are registered member of the Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce (NACC) and thirty (30) owners of the SME's that on the membership roll call of the Nigeria British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC). To complete the selection process of the first phase, thirty (30) SME owners that are members of the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME). The list is made of the sample frame for the recruitment of questionnaire participants.

The second phase for the selection of the participants is the transmitting of electronic mail in respect of Letter of Invitation to the SME's owners to partake in the process by completing the questionnaire (see Appendix P). The letter of invitation transmitted electronically provides details information about the study, the instructions on completing the informed consent and the questionnaire form.

The front page of the questionnaire form has the informed consent (see Appendix C). The informed consent is a non-disclosure agreement and it provide the brief that participation in the process is voluntary and that the participant withdrawal from the process has no legal implication or attract any form of penalty. (Yin, 2014). The

participant is expected to execute the informed consent section by selecting either “I agree” or “I disagree” before progressing.

The questionnaire equipped with the question requesting the participants about their willingness and desires to participate in either an interview or focus group and the preferred method of contact. The list of the SME’s owners that are interested in participating in the interview session or focus group discussion are generated from the sampling process for the purpose of the fourth phase of the selection process.

For the interviews, Yin (2014) stated that saturation typically occurs around thirty (30) interview sessions. To account for attrition, the researcher initially constructed the sample frame to consist of thirty to forty participants, once saturation occurred, that marks the conclusion of the interviews. Saturation took place at Twenty (20) participants.

Once the number of the completed questionnaire reached the required sample size, a listing is made from the response received. The listing is comprised of SME owners that had expressed desire to participate in the interview session. The desired sample size for the interview is Twenty-Five (25) SME owners. Ten (10) SME owners that emerged from each basket of data were invited to participate in an interview. To balance and improve the quality of the data collected, Five (5) male and Five (5) female owners of SME’s were selected. Most researches and report has been able to establish gender’s equality influence on the development of absorptive capacity (Moreno, Ávila, & García-Contreras, 2018). Observing diversity and gender balance bring about varying degree of experiences and perspectives for the study.

A convenience sampling method is used to create the list of participants for the focus group discussion. The sample frame for the focus group is made of the participants that have initially expressed their desires to participate in the focus group discussion at the questionnaire stage of the process.

The focus group sampling guaranteed that the participants are knowledgeable about the subject matter (Pedersen, Delmar, Falkmer, & Gronkjær, 2016). For this study, the experience in the subject matter is the development of Absorptive Capacity through the contribution of cultivating quality relationships and knowledge exchange with

other SME owners within the industry's social network. To ensure varying levels of experience in respect of the subject matter, the sub-sampling method adopted for the focus group is the same as that of the interview sampling.

The focus group is made up of six participants, to achieve a balanced perspective; two owners of the SME were sampled out from each data source for participation. Given the influence of gender equality on absorptive capacity development (Moreno et al., 2018), one male and one female owner of the SME were invited to participate from each of the three data basket. Diversity in perspective and experiences offered quality and detailed data and information during the focus group discussion exercise.

The researcher is duty bound to confirm the readiness of each participant three days before the focus group discussion to manage attrition for the focus group. The early confirmation provides ample time for the researcher to contact alternate participant, where any of the participant is indisposed. The interview and the focus group discussion are conducted with the aid of video conferencing using Zoom.com. Video conferencing provides the capacity for seamless recording of the sessions for both transcribing and reviewing required for the data analysis. By using video conferencing, site authorizations are not necessary.

To maintain anonymity, coding system was put in place. The first part of the code is the abbreviation of NS for National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME), NB for Nigeria British Chamber of Commerce & Industry (NBCC) and NA for Nigerian American Chamber of Commerce (NACC). The second part of the code consists of sequential numbers starting with 001 to uniquely identify each owners of the SME. The third part of the aggregate code consisted of either **I** for Interview or **F** for Focus Group. The aggregate code was assigned while compiling the list of interview and focus group participants.

3.8 Sources of Data and Data Analysis Methods

Qualitative research allows deep examination of the perspectives within a process; the qualitative descriptive approach provided the opportunity for the participant to express their individual experiences and perspectives (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). This qualitative descriptive study utilized three sources of data to collect the quality data and information for further comprehension of how SME's owners engage in the development of Absorptive Capacity. The sources of data include questionnaire, interviews, and the focus group. Three sources of data provided triangulation.

3.8.1 Questionnaire

The questionnaire is commonly used for the collection of primary data, a well-designed questionnaire is very critical for the success of the research project (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The questionnaire is structured questions fashioned to elicit facts and information from the identified participants in a data gathering process (Yin, 2014). The questionnaire (see Appendix H) for this study designed to collect data from the identified service sector SME owners on how individual owners perceived the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge exchange in developing absorptive capacity. The questionnaire served two purposes for this study; firstly the questionnaire was used in the selection of participants for the interview sessions and the focus group discussion. Secondly, the responses received from the questionnaire have strong correlation with the responses from interviews and the focus group. The use of the questionnaire to generate the sample size required for the interview and focus group discussion guaranteed that the participants are owners of SMEs that are knowledgeable on the development of absorptive capacity through the contributory factor of quality relationships and knowledge exchange for the success and growth of the SME's.

The first section of the questionnaire is tailored to obtain data relating to basic demography. The questions are structured to obtain data relating to type of service or product the owner of the SME is producing, number of employees, number of years of experience as owner of an SME, and age. The demographic data helped in ensuring divergence view of the participants. The divergent view improves the quality of the data by providing

varying experiences and perspectives. Absorptive capacity Theory brings about the design of the questionnaire to establish the basis of measurement for the participants' perspective on absorptive capacity development. The participant was asked to rate the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge exchange on Absorptive Capacity development. The questions serve as guide for the selection of participants for interviews who were potentially able to offer divergent opinion on absorptive capacity Development. The answers were rated based on a rating scale of **strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, strongly agree**, or **n/a**. Social Exchange Theory (SET) lead to the development of questions to identify the frequency of knowledge exchange by either giving or receiving knowledge, trust in the source of knowledge received, and willingness to interact with other SME owners. The response to the questions were measured on a rating scale of **less than once a month, once a month, more than once a month, once a week, more than once a week**, or **never**.

To elicit data to x-ray SME's owners' ability to socially interact with other owners, the third section of the questionnaire included structured questions to rate the participants' self-perceptions of their personality. The scales from the International Personality Item Pool (Goldberg et al., 5006) served as measures of the five-factor model. Prior research has shown that personality has great influence on individual's desire to participate within the industry's social networks (Dachner, Ellingson, & Tews, 2017). The five-factor model served as a tool to explore the influences of personality type with absorptive capacity development and cultivating quality relationships with other SME owners. The questionnaire (see Appendix H) is comprised of five sections with six questions in each section to rate the participant's self-perception of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and intellectual imagination (Goldberg et al., 5006). The model was selected as the scales best depict social behavior (Dachner et al., 2017). The six questions are made up of three positive and three negative questions. The rating for the scale followed the instructions for converting IPIP item responses to scale scores. The positive questions were measured on a scale of 1 to 5 with **1 being strongly disagree** and **5 being strongly agree** (Goldberg et al., 5006). The negative questions were measured on a scale of 1 to 5 with **1 being strongly agreed** and **5 being strongly disagree**. The gross values were summed up once all the values had been assigned (Goldberg et al., 5006).The questionnaire responses also assisted in creating the

sample frame for the interview and focus group selection process. The questions aided the identification of the best participants for this study and to corroborate the data collected in the interview and focus group.

The expert panel was engaged to review the questionnaire; the expert panel is comprised of three individuals with terminal degrees (see Appendix V). The first individual's area of specialty is consumer behavior, the member of the expert panel has successfully carried out research on sociology, and the third member of the panel has published guidelines on qualitative research (see Appendix X). Suggestions from the expert panel included the addition of demographic data and to include the rating of more than once a week to the frequency scale. All suggestions from the panel were implemented.

A pilot test provided further validation of the questionnaire (Stake, 1995), it provides the researcher with the opportunity to observe how the research tool will perform (Stake, 1995). For the pilot test, three SME's owners consisting of an insurance agent, marketing consultant, and a health club owner participated (see Appendix G). The pilot test participants had vast experience in Absorptive Capacity development through contributory factor of cultivating credible relationships and knowledge exchange with other SME owners, but they would not have been a part of the target population for the study. The pilot tests resulted in organizing the questionnaire into smaller sections as opposed to presenting all questions at one time. This adjustment helped in keeping the participant focused on the subject matter.

Participants selected from the list of potential participants from the two chambers of commerce and the National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises received the invitation to participate in the questionnaire through electronic mailing communication system upon the approval of the ethical committee of the association. The formal letter provides detail information on the nature of the research study, instructions regarding the informed consent. The informed consent (see Appendix C), on the first page of the questionnaire, required the participant to select either "**I agree**" or "**I disagree**". To proceed to the main questions, the participant is required to select "**I agree**". The questionnaire ended if the participant selected "**I disagree**". The informed consent outlined that participation was voluntary and that participants had the option to quit questionnaire process at any

time without penalty, it also specified the procedures used to safeguard the information provided by the participants. Questionnaire participants provided the sampling for the interviews and focus group.

3.8.2 Interviews

Interviews presents quality and detailed data that enhanced the comprehension of the realistic experience of owners of SMEs in respect of absorptive capacity development through cultivation of quality relationships and effective knowledge exchange with other owners within the industry's social network. A better understanding of the subject topic is derived from analyzing the data from the participant's perspective (Yin, 2014). Empirical analysis provided substantial data through quantitative research which provide support for the fact that Absorptive Capacity development is influenced by the strength of the relationships cultivated (Sawang & et al., 2016; Yoo & et al., 2016). Previous research failed to cover the perception of the owners of service sector SMEs on contribution of credible relationships. Interviews, through the use of structured qualitative research provide a detailed insight that supersedes that provided by quantitative and empirical data (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The qualities of data obtained from the interviews of SME owners afford them the opportunity to learn new strategies on how to improve the development of Absorptive Capacity.

The phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) presents the outline for the interview questions guidelines, the interview question guidelines was developed from the concept of absorptive capacity development in service sector SMEs in Nigeria, identification of the importance of absorptive capacity development, the need for acquiring external source of knowledge, capitalizing on external knowledge. Each guideline is made up of five or six unstructured questions, classifying the interview guidelines into categories mirrored the phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) ensured elaborate discussion of Absorptive Capacity Theory.

The questions within each category were set-out to help the participant to identify how that subject matter influences the success of SMEs, for instance, question 4.1 on acquiring external knowledge required the participants to select the type of knowledge that they required most. The identification of the importance of

external source of knowledge facilitates the development of Research Question 1 (RQ1). The questions transitioned into application of the subject matter. Question 4.4 on acquiring external knowledge required the participants to select the preferred frequency of participating in knowledge exchange. Each category concludes with the questions that require the participants to share the strategies adopted to improve absorptive capacity development. This category of question provides answer to Research Question 2 (RQ2).

The last category of the interview guideline is the importance of the relationship quality in the development of Absorptive Capacity. The unstructured questions were designed to evaluate the importance of personality traits in the strength of the relationships with other owners of SMEs. Social Exchange Theory (SET) brings about the questions that guide the participant to assess the self-perceptions of personality traits with the preferences for social interactions with other owners of SME. The identification of personality traits and social interactions provides strategies required to take advantage of Absorptive Capacity development process. The evaluation of personality and social exchange contributed to Research Question 1 (RQ1) and Research Question 3 (RQ 3).

The guidelines provided for the interview questions were created basically for purpose of this study; the qualitative research instruments used in prior research require validation (Stake, 1995). The validation of the interview guideline was provided by both the expert panel and a pilot test. The members of the expert panel are made up of three individuals with terminal degrees (see Appendix V). Based on the feedback received from expert panel and the pilot test in respect of the length of the first draft of the interview guidelines and the alignment of the questions with the research questions, necessary modifications were made.

The pilot test provides further validation of the instrument prior to the execution of the research study. Pilot tests provide the opportunity for the collection of first-hand evidence of the instrument's performance (Stake, 1995). For the pilot test three SME owners that are major stakeholder in insurance agency, marketing consultant, and a health club were drafted to participate in the pilot test of the interview protocol (see Appendix I). The pilot test participants were not drawn with the use of the sampling method adopted for the study earlier mentioned. Video conferencing over Zoom.com was scheduled for each participant.

Each pilot test provided an effective instrument for the collection of data required for the research study. The first pilot test carried out by the insurance agent resulted in removing questions which resulted in repeated answers. The removal of the questions increased the opportunity for collection quality data. Another issue corrected with the help of the first pilot test was the ambiguous questions. Simplifying the questions helped the participants to comprehend the question seamlessly. Clarity in understanding the research subject matter contributed to the overall quality of the research data. The marketing consultant executed the second pilot test; the participant suggested examples should be provided for questions asked about the conceptual issues; this exposed the study to predetermined responses from the participants. The last pilot test involves the health club owner; the test discovered that the level of experience of the health club owner in the development of Absorptive Capacity was less than the experience levels of the other two participants. The primary objective of the field test is to experience how the actual interviews will take place without the distraction of making notes to modify the instrument. The final draft of the instrument after the third pilot test includes minor adjustments to simplify the interview question by making it very simple.

Zoom.com teleconferencing device was used for the interview sessions, the settings of the Zoom device include audio and video recording. All other settings remained at default setting mode for recording through Zoom.com. The recordings is initially hosted in the Zoom cloud service, the audio was downloaded and stored on a more secured external hard drive. The audio file transcription was carried out with the use of Trint.com. The transcribed interview session provided the document for SME owners to assess the accuracy and make additional comments for clarity. MaxQDA is used in the thematic analysis of the interview transcripts.

3.8.3 Focus Group

Focus groups provide a means to collect additional data that other research methods were unable to capture. The design of the focus group plays an integral role as to what types of data the researcher can collect (Ryan, Gandha, Culbertson, & Carlson, 2014). While on the surface the focus group is a group interview, an advantage of a focus group over a one-on-one interview is that the conversations between participants provide broader contents (Ryan et al., 2014). The broader contents generated from the discussions result from the diversity of the focus group discussants (Ryan et al., 2014). The focus group seek to provide detailed insights on technique to be adopted to surmount the challenges confronting the development of Absorptive Capacity and the perceptions of the personality's influence on relationships. The quality and improved data collected from the focus group helped identify how SME owners improve Absorptive Capacity development.

The focus group guidelines were designed to examine how Absorptive Capacity is developed and the role of quality relationships and knowledge exchange. The unstructured questions of focus group guideline assisted in the assessment of the last phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT), the last phase is the ability of the organization to absorb and capitalize on the absorbed capacity. The questions were designed to stimulate discussion among participants regarding the importance of Absorptive Capacity development in respect of the success and improved performance of the SME's.

The principles of Social Exchange Theory (SET) provide guidance in creating the unstructured questions pertaining to the roles of quality relationships and knowledge exchange in the development of Absorptive Capacity. Social Exchange Theory posited that relationships are rewarding when every participant contribute mutually in the process. Three key questions prompted the discussion of relationships based on Social Exchange Theory. Firstly, the group discussed the perceived value of quality relationships with other SME owners within the industry's social networks. The second question was designed to direct the discussion to share how the established relationships have benefitted individual participants. The relationship discussion is concluded with how the participants have contributed to helping other SME owners to succeed.

The unstructured questions for the focus group guidelines were created for this study to examine the experience of individual SME owners on quality relationships with other owners in the network. Research instruments not used in previous research require validation (Stake, 1995). Expert panel and pilot test were engaged for the validation of the focus group guidelines. Three individuals with terminal degrees served as the expert panel to review the unstructured questions. The objective of the focus group is to provide the research study with additional insights that are not generated from the interviews. The review of the guidelines resulted in removing questions which overlapped with the interview guideline.

The pilot test executed by three service sector SME owners who are into insurance agency, marketing consultant, and a health club owner. The pilot test was scheduled at the convenience of the three participants. The session was conducted over Zoom.com. The pilot test resulted in two key modifications. The modification was necessary because the coordination of individual schedules presented a challenge and multiple communications to set an appointment. The process was modified to present five potential appointment windows for participants to indicate availability and readiness. The second modification is the reduction in the number of questions to be asked. The fluid conversations did not require as many questions to cover the desired subject matter adequately.

The focus group is made up of six participants knowledgeable in the development of Absorptive Capacity in the SME sector. A common occurrence for focus groups is for one or two participants to not show up (O.nyumba et al., 2018). To account for this attrition, the researcher invited eight SME owners. One method of focus group design consists of selecting participants who have established relationships with other owners within the industry's social network (Ryan et al., 2014). However, research has shown that when participants are not familiar with one another, the dialogue is less reserved (Onyumba et al., 2018). The focus group for this research study is made up of owners of SMEs who had expressed their desire and willingness to participate in the focus group discussion while completing the questionnaire.

The focus group discussion takes place after the completion of interview sessions. The researcher served as the focus group moderator. The online focus group was conducted via Zoom.com. A recording of the focus group meeting was stored in the Zoom Cloud which provides the facility to review the session later. Trint.com provided

an automatic transcription of the session. The transcribed documents provide each participant the opportunity to check the response of other member and request revisions for clarity. Participants had ten days grace period to respond to the member check. MaxQDA facilitates the thematic analysis of the interview transcripts.

3.9 Trustworthiness

“Qualitative research lacks the proven scientific and statistical reliability in comparison to quantitative research. Within the construct of qualitative research study, the study must reflect Credibility, Transferability, Dependability, and Confirmability (Yin, 2014). The role of these four tests is to enhance the achievement of high-quality research (Cope, 2014). Qualitative methodology established trustworthiness by utilizing data instruments that have been proven to be very potent through repeated experiments (Cope, 2014). The qualitative researcher must be creative and confident because qualitative research cannot disapprove the outlined assumptions (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Each step involved in establishing trustworthiness in qualitative research is important.

3.9.1 Credibility

The first step required in establishing trustworthiness is credibility. Cope (2014) defines credibility as “...the truth of the data or the participant's views and the interpretation and representation of them by the researcher” (p. 89). Establishing credibility is crucial for qualitative research, because the quality of the research is dependent upon the quality of the data, the major threat to any qualitative descriptive study is the misrepresentation of the participant’s views. Another known threat is the participants’ misinterpretation of the questions. Member checking, triangulation, and researcher notes throughout the data collection process assist in abating the threats.

Member checking only occurs after the transcription of the recorded interviews and the focus group. Member checking credibility was established through the accurate reporting of the interview (Birt, Scott, Cavers, Campbell, & Walter, 2016). When responses were ambiguous, participants will be requested to provide clarification to ensure accurate interpretation. This process ensured that the interpretations of the responses were credible and accurately represented.

A second method of credibility included triangulation, triangulation as described by Yin (2014) is the collection of data through three different instruments. The instruments serve to confirm consistency in results while providing detailed data in understanding the process. This study used questionnaires, interview sessions, and focus group discussions. One example of triangulation in this study is the question No.6 that required the participants to rate the extent to which external knowledge has helped the business. The responses were compared to the interview question which asked the participants to give an example of external knowledge that helped improve the performance of the SME. Within the focus group, participants discussed strategies to overcome the challenges posed by inadequate resources to capitalize and implement on ideas gained from external sources of knowledge.

Lastly, an audit trail was used throughout data collection and analysis. An audit trail provided another strategy to strengthen the credibility (Cope, 2014), the audit trail includes transcripts of interviews and focus group, notes are made throughout the research process, notes on data analysis steps, and final data analysis reports. The audit trail provided reflective feedback in order to ask certain questions which allowed the conversations to be more fluid and natural.

3.9.2 Transferability

The transferability of the study contributed to trustworthiness, transferability occurs when users can apply the information provided by the research for other studies and purpose (Cope, 2014). Transferability includes applying the results to a study with a different population (Cope, 2014). While qualitative research depends on the ingenuity of the researcher in developing research designs to study a phenomenon (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), the ability to transfer the design and results is important in establishing trustworthiness (Cope, 2014). Transferability was addressed in this study by providing a thick description of the phenomenon and using appropriate data collection protocols. The participant discussions presented a threat to transferability.

Inadequate description of the phenomenon is a threat to transferability. Inadequate description occurs when there is insufficient data to accurately describe the phenomenon (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Inadequate description will lack detail individual experiences of the participant. According to Cope (2014) “By providing a description of the strategies and quality data, notable quotes from the participants, the reader can personally criticize the credibility of the study and substantiate the interpretations” (p.90). To reduce the threat of inadequate description, unstructured interview and focus group questions provide the participants with the opportunity to give an account of individual experiences. Individual experiences provide detailed and quality data which creates adequate description of the phenomenon.

To ensure the transferability of the collected data, appropriate protocols were followed, the protocols for this study includes questionnaire, interview and focus group guide. An effective sample size was achieved through convenience sampling. The sample size of 60 questionnaire participants provided sufficient candidates to select 20 interview participants and six focus group participants. Frantic efforts were made to develop detailed and robust account of experiences of data collection so that it would be applicable to other contexts, situations, times, and populations. The established procedures for creating, field testing and using the research instruments ensures transferability to future research.

3.9.3 Reliability

The researcher has dedicated much time and deliberation to craft a research design that not only produces findings which are directly related to the research objectives, but also ensures the credibility of her research results. In this context, the author is abiding by Rogers' (1961) interpretation of scientific methodology, where he asserts that this is a procedure for increasing the credibility and reducing the subjectivity of the research findings.

It is worthy to note that the condition of the research are dynamic, reliability is established through the researcher's account of the research process. Reliability is the ability to replicate the qualitative study in similar conditions thereby producing comparable results which demonstrates Reliability (Cope, 2014). The notes and documentation of the research process provide a demonstration of reliability within the study (Cope, 2014). A threat to reliability is the inability of the future research to reflect the findings of this qualitative descriptive study.

Strategies to enhance reliability included an audit trail, evidence, and records of the data analysis process. Full transcripts and documentation of the research process were preserved as evidence of the steps required to be taken for executing qualitative descriptive research study (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Audit trails provide the documentation of the research process that is required for another researcher to conduct the same research in similar conditions (Cope, 2014). The records of the data analysis process include the codebook used for the thematic data analysis which is supported by samples of data as well as examples from transcripts (Cope, 2014). All coding materials and processes were outlined as part of the audit trail.

3.9.4 Confirmability

Qualitative research depends on the participant's perspective; confirmability is the ability to demonstrate that the data collected and its analysis reflect the view of the participants (Cope, 2014). There are many strategies for improving confirmability, other researchers using the same data and data analysis, the researcher should be able to confirm the originality of the data (Yin, 2014). The major obstacles to confirmability are the potential reflection of bias (Cope, 2014), the integrity of the research depends on the exclusion of personal bias and reporting what has been said or observed during the research process.

The researcher addressed the potential bias by clarifying participants' responses as required, interpretations were supported by references to other literature as specified. Procedural documentation provided a reference to follow throughout the process. Consistency in execution provided a structured approach which assist in minimizing personal bias. Accurate interpretations and minimal personal bias facilitates the in creation of the codebook for this study. The codebook was developed in two steps. The first step was creating the level 1 code-book and the second step created the level 2 code-books.

The first level codes were created by carefully identifying emerging themes, level 2 codes were created through careful review. The codes were reviewed multiple times and grouped by similar attributes. Basic themes within the thematic network emerged from the grouping of codes based on similarity in attributes. The accuracy of the thematic analysis was built on the assumptions of this study.

The researcher assumed that all questionnaire participants were not deceptive in answering questions. It is assumed that the experience of the owners of SME's presents the accurate representation of Absorptive Capacity development, credible relationships and knowledge exchange. It is also assumed that the service sector SME owners with similar levels of experience face similar challenges than those with more experience.

3.10 Data Collection and Management

The target population for this study is the owners of the service sector of the SME's in Nigeria. The target population is the owners of service sector of SMEs with less than 500 employees. A convenient sampling was employed in the selection of the sample size for the study. A sampling frame of each of all the members of the Nigerian Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME), Nigeria British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC) and Nigeria America Chamber Of Commerce (NACC) was developed.

3.10.1 Tools of Data Collection

The data collection tools included a questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group. Multiple methods of data collection ensure the collection of appropriate, quality and, and detailed Data. Detailed and quality data is elusive, abstract, verifiable, and close to the phenomenon (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). Questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group provided the sources of primary data that are close to the process of SME owners that engage in the development of Absorptive Capacity through quality relationship and knowledge exchange with other SME owners.

The data collection and management steps used in the study are detailed below. The steps included expert panel approval, pilot testing, identifying sources for recruitment, recruitment for questionnaire participants, identifying interview participants, conducting interviews, identifying focus group participants, conducting the focus group, transcribing audio files, and storing data. The steps taken for data collection and management ensured consistency and the study can be replicated.

3.10.2 Justification for Multiple Methods of Data Collection

When a research study requires precision and thoroughness with different categorization and stages, one technique of data collection will not be adequate, therefore the combination of different methods will be put to use in order to arrive at accurate and reliable data. The different techniques will certainly be employed at different stages of the study before the final research is achieved.

3.10.3 Expert panel

Members of the expert panel are purposely selected and are used for whatever purpose they are needed. Expert panel is a procedure of repeatedly using the same sample almost like a permanent sample. For the purpose of this study, the expert panel is made up of three individuals with terminal degrees with one having experience in development of Absorptive Capacity (see Appendix V). The first member of the expert panel had a Doctor of Business Administration degree from Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun State South-West Nigeria with a focus on consumer behavior. The second member of the panel holds a Ph.D. in Sociology from Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun State South-West Nigeria. The third member of the panel holds a Ph.D. in History of Science and qualitative research also from Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun State South-West Nigeria (see Appendix V). Each panel member offered insights to improve and streamline the data collection instruments. The feedback assisted in ensuring the interviews and focus group conversations flowed smoothly. The revised documents were used in conducting the pilot test.

The expert panel review occurred before the execution of the pilot test. The questionnaire (see Appendix G) was edited to collect demographic data. The interview guidelines (See Appendix I) were edited to streamline questions. Questions in the focus group guidelines that overlapped questions in the interview guide were edited to collect quality data that are not represented in the interviews. Modifications were made based on the recommendations of the expert panel. Once the final edits were made, a pilot test was conducted on the protocols.

3.10.4 Pilot test

Pilot test was conducted on the data collection tools prior to ethics committee approval. The questionnaire (see Appendix G), interview guide (see Appendix I) and focus group guidelines (see Appendix K) were pilot tested. Three SME owners were invited to participate in the pilot test made up of a brand consultant, an independent insurance agent, and a marketing design consultant. The pilot test participants were not part of the intended population for recruitment. All the three SME owners are drawn outside of the targeted population. The pilot test helped in identifying question repetition, clarity in wording, and a logical flow for conversation. The pilot test provides opportunity for the researcher to sharpen the instruments before the commencement of the actual research. The final revisions of the questionnaire are presented in Appendix H. The revision and modification of the interview guidelines is presented in Appendix J, and that of the focus group is presented in Appendix L.

3.10.5 Data collection: Questionnaire

The selection of the questionnaire tool was guided by the Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and the Social Exchange Theory (SET)

Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) established factors and phases of Absorptive Capacity development. Social exchange theory (SET) identified foundational principles of individuals exchanging ideas and thoughts. The questionnaire served two purposes. Firstly, basic demographic data was collected for each participant. The questionnaire also served as a selection tool for interview and focus group participants by establishing a baseline for Absorptive Capacity development process and a rating of the participant's self-perception of their personality.

The questionnaire (see Appendix H) identified self-perception of personality data as well as data relating to general participation in Absorptive Capacity development through quality relationship and knowledge exchange with other owners of SMEs.

Emails provided the technology to conduct the questionnaire online, the questionnaire availed the participants with informed consent form as the front page of the questionnaire (see Appendix H). The participants were requested to either accept or decline participation in the process. If the participant chose to decline, the questionnaire ended.

The questionnaire is comprised of rating questions to establish the perception of service sector SME owners on the impact of Absorptive Capacity development on external knowledge exchange. In addition, the questionnaire provided rating questions regarding the self-perceptions and personality traits of the owners of the SMEs (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). If the small business owner agreed to participate in either the interview or focus group, the questionnaire provided a prompt on the participant's email address. The questionnaire should be completed in about twenty minutes.

First, using community resources, such as the chamber of commerce and National Association of Small and Medium Enterprises, the researcher identified potential participants who are owners of SMEs to participate in the questionnaire. An invitation to participate in the questionnaire was transmitting through electronic mailing system to the owners of the SMEs (see Appendix P).

3.10.6 Data collection: Interview

“The phases of ACT provided the guidelines in developing the research questions that guide the interview. The phases of ACT outline the questions which explored the participant’s personal experience. SET on the other hand provided the structure for questions that demand detailed and quality of data in respect of the participant’s personality and perceived value of relationships with other owners of the SME’s owners. The interview guidelines provided strategies adopted to improve Absorptive Capacity and cultivate credible relationships.

Enrolment list of questionnaire participants who agreed to participate in the interview provided the sampling frame for the interviews. The interview guidelines provided the direction for the interview process (see Appendix J). The owner of the SME’s received formal invitation for the interview through electronic mailing system (Appendix N). Interviews occurred at the convenience of the owners of the SME’s via Zoom. The interview recordings were initially stored in the Zoom Cloud until it is transcribed; the audio files were downloaded, stored on an external hard drive and kept in a safe when not in use.

The audio files were uploaded to Trint.com for transcription, data collection and analysis will take place simultaneously throughout the data collection phase of the research. Yin (2014) recommended that data analysis should commence as soon as the first interview is completed. Immediately the data is transcribed, the documents will be made available for member checking to test the accuracy and clarity of the process.

Once the interview has been scheduled, an aggregate code is assigned to protect the confidentiality of the participant. The aggregate code was set up using the following procedure; the first part of the code is made up of the abbreviation of **NS** for National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME), **NB** for Nigerian-British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC), and **NA** for Nigerian-American Chamber of Commerce (NACC). The alphabetical tags (formed by abbreviating the alphabet of the first two words) were followed by a sequential number starting with 001 to distinctly tag and identify each owner of the SME. The next step after assigning the sequential number is the aggregate code which comprise of either and **I** for Interview or **F** for Focus Group. An example of the aggregate code is NA0004I.

Each participant signed an Informed Consent for interviews (see Appendix D) and the focus group discussion (see Appendix E) prior to participation. Informed consents were dully signed and transmitted through electronic mailing system for the purpose of the research study. All informed consents were printed and stored in a locked safe for privacy and confidentiality.

The length of the interviews ranged from 30 minutes to 45 minutes depending on the level of social exchanges and interaction from the participant. The responses provided a minimum of five pages of text, single spaced at 12-point Times New Roman font. The data collected from the interviews provided individual experiences in the development of Absorptive Capacity through external knowledge exchange and cultivation of quality relationships.”

3.10.7 Data collection: Focus group

The list of questionnaire participants who agreed to participate in the focus group served as the sample frame. The owners of SMEs that received letter of invitations through electronic mailing system to participate in the focus group (see Appendix O) along with an informed consent. The researcher served as the focus group discussion moderator for this study. The focus group moderator used a focus group protocol to guide the group discussion (see Appendix L). The focus group comprised of six owners of SMEs, the focus group discussion was conducted online and recorded on Zoom.com. The audio recording of the focus group discussion allowed for transcription of the text for coding. The audio file was downloaded from Zoom.com and subsequently uploaded to Trint.com for transcription. Upon completion, the transcription was member checked for accuracy and clarity; the focus group discussion session lasted for 45 minutes. The transcription produced nine pages of text with single line spaced using 12-point Times New Roman font size and type. The transcriptions were securely stored to ensure privacy and confidentiality of the participants to ensure ethical concerns.

“All participants were informed of data security measures taken by the researchers to secure the data and information provided. Data security included downloading the audio file from Zoom.com, downloading all files from Trint.com after transcription, deleting files from all online services, storing aggregate codes of the

participants electronically, encrypting all electronic data, and keeping the data in a locked safe to ensure confidentiality. Appendix M contains a 16- step process map outlining the data collection, storage, replication and destruction:

16 Step Process Map

Step 1	Project approval from University of West Scotland
Step 2	Identify small business owners through local chambers of commerce as well as the National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises and contact via email per UWS approved procedure to participate in the survey. Allow two weeks for a response to participate.
Step 3	Destroy identifying information of small business owners who did not participate. Assign unique identifier to participants. Master list will be kept separate from all other data files in a locked safe. The master list will be the only means to identify participants.
Step 4	Once surveys are complete, select 20 participants to conduct interview based on survey responses
Step 5	Begin conducting interviews using Zoom.
Step 6	After completion of the interview, the raw media file will be transcribed.
Step 7	Begin focus group selection process
Step 8	Begin conducting focus group using Zoom.
Step 9	After completion of the focus group, the raw media file will be transcribed.”

Step 10	<p>Transcript of each interview will be presented to corresponding participants for member checking.</p> <p>The participant will be informed that this will provide opportunity for him/her to edit, clarify, or delete any comments.</p>
Step 11	<p>Transcript of the focus group will be presented to the participants for member checking.</p> <p>The participant will be informed this will provide opportunity for him/her to edit, clarify, or delete any comments.</p>
Step 12	<p>Focus group and interview scripts will be loaded into MaxQDA.</p> <p>Thematic data analysis will be used.</p>
Step 13	<p>Thematic analysis will be conducted on interview and focus group independently first.</p>
Step 14	<p>Notations will be made throughout the analysis process that highlight trends in knowledge exchange, innovations which resulted</p>
	<p>from knowledge exchange, and how the small business owner values relationships with other small business owners.</p>
Step 15	<p>Upon completion, both sets of transcripts will be merged into MaxQDA for a thematic analysis to identify commonalities.</p>
Step 16	<p>Revise/ complete analysis. Complete results write-up. Archive all data for 3 years.</p> <p>Destroy any personal information belonging to the participants and all data after 3 years.</p>

3.11 Data Analysis Procedures

Further to the data generated from the combination of the questionnaire, interview and focus group, the researcher must work on the data by complying with the data analysis procedure. The data analysis elaborate on how Absorptive Capacity is developed through cultivation of quality of relationships and knowledge exchange with other owners of SMEs and its importance to the improved performance and growth of SMEs. To ensure thorough analysis of the research, Yin's (2014) five-phased cycle provided the framework to conduct the thematic analysis. The five-phased cycle guided the formation of a complete picture of Absorptive Capacity development through quality relationships and knowledge exchange.

Data collated from the questionnaire were downloaded into a spreadsheet. Individual questionnaire responses regarding the self-perceptions of personality were reviewed on a case by case basis. Each of the five personality factors consisted of six questions with three positive and three negative questions. The participants scored each item on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging 1 to 5. Based on the scoring presented by Goldber et al. (5006), the positive questions were given a positive value, the negative questions were given a negative value. The scale range values for the positive questions included strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neither agree or disagree (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5) (Goldberg et al., 5006). The scale range values for the negative questions included strongly disagree (5), disagree (4), neither agree or disagree (3), agree (2), and strongly agree (1) (Goldberg et al., 5006). The responses were totaled and scored to provide a rating for the personality factor. The individual questionnaire results provided insights in analyzing discussions in the interview and focus group. The results from both instruments provide quality and detailed the data for analysis.

To ensure thoroughness in data analysis of the interviews and focus groups, the five-phased cycle of data analysis provided guidance in conducting the thematic analysis of the interview and focus group transcripts (Yin, 2014). The phases of the cycle include compiling, disassembling, reassembling, interpreting, and concluding (Yin, 2014). The thematic analysis guided the process of coding segments of the transcripts, arranging the codes into basic themes which were categorized into organizing themes. The themes summarized the organizing themes. Using a structured approach, data analysis procedures must be consistent with the emerging themes.

3.11.1 Compiling Phase

The compiling phase consisted of collecting data from the questionnaire, interviews, and the focus group. Data collected from the questionnaire was summarized by question using SurveyMonkey.com's built in reporting tool. The summarized data provided a benchmark of the participant's engagement in external knowledge exchange. This information was important in creating the framework to construct the thematic analysis. For the interviews and focus group, the compiling phase of the analysis began immediately the session is concluded. Audio files were downloaded from Zoom.com to an external hard drive for secure storage. To create a document for analysis, the audio files were uploaded to Trint.com as part of transcription; the participant was assigned a unique identifier so that anonymity was maintained. The unique identifier consisted of a three-part code. If the participant was selected from Nigerian American Chamber of Commerce (NACC), the code would be NA001IF. NA denotes the source where the participant was selected from. The 001 is a sequential number based on when the participant signed up for the interview or focus group. The I denoted an interview and an F denoted the focus group.

Once transcription was complete, the document is read and reviewed while following the audio recording ensuring a verbatim transcription of the participant's responses. The document was downloaded and sent to participants to be member checked. Once member checking is completed, the document will be exported into the MaxQDA software for analysis. MaxQDA provides the platform to manage the coding process of the transcripts.

3.11.2 Disassembling Phase

The disassembling phase consists of delineating the collated data. Open coding and axial coding were used to identify emerging themes within the open-ended responses. Responses were read multiple times to establish accuracy in translation.

Table 3:

Code Examples

Text	Code
Like I said we use knowledge bases and webinars and video	Methods of knowledge exchange
You have to be open to learning or you wouldn't work for me	Expectations

After initially establishing the codes in the first transcript, the transcript will be reviewed. The codes were checked for redundancy and alignment with the research questions. Reviewing the transcription bring about clarity to the themes represented in the open-ended responses.

Data analysis, conducted with analytical tools in SurveyMonkey.com, based on the questionnaire established the SME's owners' perceptions of external knowledge exchange as well as reflecting the self-perceptions of the small business owner's personality. The perceptions of personality traits and participation in external knowledge exchange through small business owner networking provide data to answer Research Question 3 (RQ3).

3.11.3 Reassembly phase.

The reassembly phase is the grouping of data back together into thematically identify patterns. As coding progressed, over-arching themes became evident. Theme categories were created using the research questions to label the codes. Table 4 demonstrates the development of themes.

Table 4:

Text	Code	Themes
If I if I cannot develop rapport with somebody in a group, I'm not going to return it.	Influences on knowledge exchange	Relationships
They learn about me as a person. They learn about my personality. And then the business comes later, or the referral comes later.	Benefits of relationships	Relationships
Learning continuously is one of our core values in my industry	Frequency	Receiving Knowledge
You have to be opened to learning or you wouldn't work for me	Expectations	Receiving Knowledge

Creating themes differs from coding; themes are the results of coding. Themes are the logical categorization of the codes (Saldana, 2016). As the codes were initially created, the iterative process of evaluating text within the transcript to identified codes, similar groupings were identified. As shown in Table 2, statements regarding quality relationship with other owners of SME's were coded and knowledge exchange as it influence development of Absorptive Capacity created data to answer Research Question 3 (RQ 3) in respect of the quality relationships. The theme of relationships was created to identify groupings of data for Research Question 3 (RQ 3). The process was applied to analyzing all transcripts.

As the process continued through multiple iterations, the codes and themes were refined. Groupings of similar themes are summarized into patterns creating a thematic network (Saldana, 2016). The themes for the network were the individual research questions. Research Question 1 (RQ 1) theme is developed from the influence of quality relationship and knowledge exchange on Absorptive Capacity development. The theme derived from Research Question (RQ2) is focused on the strategies used in addressing limitations confronting Absorptive Capacity development. The influence of quality relationships and knowledge exchange formed the basis for the theme in respect of Research Question 3 (RQ 3). As the themes emerged from coding, the final thematic network was anchored to five themes.

3.11.4 Interpretation Phase

As the thematic network was refined, the network served in answering the research questions. The patterns identified in the text through coding assisted in explaining the themes. The themes were supported using other empirical research which substantiated the results.

Data from the interviews were cross validated with the responses from the focus group and questionnaires. For example, comparing questions from the interview regarding the levels of participation in knowledge exchange to questions from the questionnaire regarding self-perceptions of personality gives detailed insight about the reasons some individuals owners of SMEs may not be willing to participate in different types of external knowledge exchange. When taking similar data from the focus group, triangulation deepens the validity of the data.

3.11.5 Conclusion Phase

In answering the three research questions presented by this study, the results from the interpretation phase were then placed in context with the theoretical framework of SET and ACT. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the questionnaire data regarding age, industry, age of the SME's (starting from the commencement date), and the number of employees.

3.12 Ethical Considerations

The University of West Scotland ethics committee approved the research prior to commencement of this study. Each participant executed the informed consent section of the questionnaire. Questionnaire participants were required to either agree or disagree on the front page within SurveyMonkey.com. Interview and focus group participants were contacted through electronic mailing system. The dully executed agreement was scanned and emailed back before the commencement of either the interview or focus group session..

Aggregate codes kept identities of the participants anonymous and not shared within this study. The participants had the option to withdraw from participation at any time.

The Belmont report provided the framework for protecting the participants in the study. The principles established in the Belmont report include respect for person, beneficence, and justice (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1978). Humility promotes the treatment of all participants with courtesy and respect. The enormous benefits of the process challenge the researcher to minimize the risk to the participant while maximizing the benefit to the study. The principle of justice protects the participant from exploitation, mal-administration of procedures and equal distribution of benefits to the participants (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1978). The study reflects the Belmont principles through scheduling all data collection at the convenience of the participant, providing the participants with the option to withdraw from the study without any punitive measure, not soliciting for data which will exposing competitive advantages the owners of SME's to risk, and applying the same rules for data collection to all participants.

The study is exposed to risk of integrity with the use of open-ended questions which has the tendency to attract negative responses about the SME owners. The interviewer with his expertise used questions to manage the negative conversations as required. Upholding good level of confidentiality in relation to competitive advantages was another ethical concern. To maintain confidentiality, each participant was assigned a unique identification number.

The identification number is assigned to each participant to guarantee anonymity and confidentiality in the study in order to protect the integrity of the owners of SMEs. Interview sessions are conducted via Zoom.com to help ensure a higher degree of confidentiality. The protection of the brand image and the reputation of the SME owners are handled with top priority by the researcher.

The questionnaire contained an electronic informed consent agreement section (see Appendix H). The participants had to click whether they agreed to accept the informed consent. The execution of the e-form connotes an electronic signature of approval. Participants received an email containing the informed consent agreement form prior to the commencement of the interview and focus group session. A locked fire-proof safe is used to store all aggregate codes, transcripts, recorded interviews, focus group discussion, and the questionnaire data. Only the researcher had express access to the fire-proof safe. All materials input and output of the research study will be available for review for up to three years after the official completion of the dissertation at which time all materials can be destroyed. (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979)

3.13 Limitations and Delimitations

3.13.1 Limitations

This study is confronted with some limitations which impacts this research study. A focus group may be intimidating for certain individuals. Conducting a focus group may place individuals with introvert personality types in a position not to be able to share and engage in the exchange freely because of the presence of other discussants. The inability of an individual share freely impact negatively on the quality of data collected. To curb the impact of being introverted, the focus group moderator asked each participant to discuss about their experience in respect of their business.

The research study targeted population is the service sector SMEs with less than 500 employees. The SMEs are likely to have more than 500 employees depending on the industry's operational requirement.

In the course of preparing the interview and focus group guidelines, a bias could exist in the questions presented; the bias would naturally direct the participants to provide answer to the interview questions in a predetermined manner. Inclusion of such bias would diminish the value and reduce the credibility of the research. The interview questions were subject to pilot test by a three-person panel comprised of three owners of the service sector SME that were not originally considered as participants from the targeted sample group. The field test is useful in minimizing the presence of bias.

3.13.2 Delimitations

The principal delimitation to the research study is that the interview and focus group discussion participant's selection is based on questionnaire respondents. Also, the number of participants for the questionnaire was an insignificant fractional representation of the general population size of the service sector SME owners. Another noticeable delimitation of the research study is the reduction in the number of participants for the interview and focus group thereby representing an insignificant representation.

Another delimitation of questionnaire participant selection was that the researcher selected small businesses from two chambers of commerce, and the SME national body. Other small businesses potentially exist outside of these sources. The lesser known small businesses potentially exhibit challenges in developing Absorptive Capacity unknown to the study.

The purpose of the research was to examine the contribution of knowledge exchange and quality of relationships with other owners of the SME's towards the development of absorptive capacity amongst service sector SMEs. It was observed that there exist other factors that impact the success of Absorptive Capacity development, this include factors such as the relevance of the topic, the qualifications of the source of knowledge, and frequency of engagement in knowledge exchange activities. To be able to collect quality and detailed data, the factors researched had to be narrow in scope.

3.14 Summary

This qualitative descriptive study helped in filling the void in the available literatures by providing detailed insights about the perceptives of individual owners of service sector SME's on Absorptive Capacity development through the effective contribution of knowledge exchange and the strength of relationships among owners of SME's. The absence of quality and detailed data to improve understanding of how SME owners perceived the contributions of relationships quality and knowledge exchange with other owners within the industry's social network to the development of Absorptive Capacity summarized the existing void in the literature (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). The following research questions guided the research in providing the required quality data to fill the void:

- ❖ RQ1: How does SME owners' perception of knowledge exchange and quality of relationships with other SMEs aid the development of absorptive capacity?

- ❖ RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve knowledge exchange with other SMEs?

- ❖ RQ3: How does SME owners develop and maintain credible relationships with other owners of the SME's?

The goal of the study is to evaluate individual's SME owners experience about Absorptive Capacity development. The research study employed the use of qualitative descriptive research methodology for the purpose of the study. The researcher made use of questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussion to collect the credible and quality data required to improve on the existing and available literatures. Using the three methods of data collection provided triangulation as prescribed by Yin (2014). Triangulation helped in building high level trustworthiness in the research study.

Other methods employed to establish trustworthiness include member checking and audit trails which helped in strengthening credibility of the research study. Transferability of the researched data is ensured with the quality

and credibility of the data collated (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Sufficiency of the data evidence and proper records of the data analysis process made the research to be dependable (Cope, 2014). Developing and using a codebook during thematic data analysis helped in strengthening confirmability (Cope, 2014). For qualitative research, trustworthiness improves the credibility of the research study.

Data collection depends mainly on the university's approval. Upon the granting of the approval, SurveyMonkey.com provided the platform to conduct the questionnaire.

The enrolment list of the questionnaire participants that confirmed their agreement to participate in the interview provided the sample size for the interview. The interview guidelines provided the direction for the interview process. In the bid to put in place measures for the controlling of COVID-19 pandemic and in compliance with the physical and social distancing directives, the research study were executed remotely, the SME owners received formal invitation for the interview through electronic mailing system. The interview session is held at the convenience of the owners of the SME's via Zoom. The interview recordings were initially stored in the Zoom Cloud until it is transcribed; the audio files were downloaded, stored in external hard disk and kept in a fire-proof safe when not in use.

Upon the conclusion of the interview session, an aggregate code is assigned to protect the confidentiality of the participant. The aggregate code was set up using the following procedure; the first part of the code is coined from the abbreviation of **NS** for National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME), **NB** for Nigerian British Chamber of Commerce (NBCC), and **NA** for Nigerian American Chamber of Commerce (NACC). The alphabetical abbreviation is followed by a sequential number starting with 001 to distinctly tag and identify individual owner of the SME. The next step after assigning the sequential number is the aggregate code which comprise of either and **I** for Interview or **F** for Focus Group. An example of the aggregate code is NB0004I.

Individual participant signed an Informed Consent agreement for the interview and the focus group discussion prior to participation. Informed consents were dully signed and transmitted through electronic mailing system to

the researcher for the purpose of the research study. All informed consents were printed and stored in a locked safe for privacy and confidentiality.

The recorded audio files were uploaded to Trint.com for transcription, data collection and analysis will take place simultaneously throughout the data collection phase of the research. Yin (2014) recommended that data analysis should commence as soon as the first interview is completed. Immediately the data is transcribed, the documents will be made available for member checking for accuracy and clarity.

An expert panel and pilot testing was employed to put the validity of the data collected to test. The expert panel of three individuals with terminal degrees reviewed data collection instruments prior to pilot testing. All the data collected for the purpose of the research, the aggregate codes, and documents were kept in a locked safe for three years after the official completion of the dissertation. All materials will be destroyed three years preceding the year of concluding the research study. All necessary measures were taken to ensure the protection of the participants' privacy.

For the data analysis, thematic analysis is used. Yin's (2014) five-phase cycle of qualitative analysis guided the thematic data analysis. A Level 1 codebook provided the foundation for initial analysis in the MaxQDA software. The researcher progressed by developing the codebook into categorical codes after the data collected had been analyzed. The thematic analysis identified the themes for Absorptive capacity development, credible relationships and knowledge exchange.

The problems and gap were presented in the literature review. The justification for the selected methodology and the alignment for the answering of the research questions provided the foundation for conducting the study.

Chapter 3 also presented limitations, delimitation, ethical considerations, and trustworthiness in respect of the proposed qualitative descriptive study. Further to the completion of the research methodology and data analysis, the researcher presents the results of the analysis in chapter 4.

CHAPTER 4: Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Introduction

The perception of service sector SME owners about the contribution of quality relationships and exchange of knowledge to the development of Absorptive Capacity is yet to be ascertained (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). The purpose of this qualitative descriptive study was to x-ray how SME owners perceive exchange of knowledge and relationship quality within the industry's social network as contributing to the development of Absorptive Capacity amongst service sector SMEs in Nigeria.

The research questions inquired about the perceived influences of exchange of knowledge and relationship quality on innovations within the network of SME owners. A qualitative study allowed for an examination of the phenomenon of knowledge exchange and cultivating relationships to enhance the comprehension about the perceptions of SME owners. This research design provided a comprehensive description of SME's owners' opinions on the contribution of knowledge exchange and relationship quality on the development of absorptive capacity.

The theoretical framework of the research assists in developing and laying the basic foundation for the study. Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET) provided the guideline for examining the perception of SME owners on how exchange of knowledge and relationship quality contributes to Absorptive Capacity development.

The Research Questions were structured and developed based on the guidelines offered by Absorptive Capacity Theory and Social Exchange Theory, the following Research Questions were developed in respect of the qualitative descriptive research study:

- ❖ RQ1: How does SME owners' perceive exchange of knowledge and relationship quality with other SME's as aiding the development of absorptive capacity?
- ❖ RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs?
- ❖ RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners?

Data collection involved using three different method of data collection – a questionnaire, unstructured interviews, and a focus group. The questionnaire provided a selection pool of eligible participants who had experience in Absorptive Capacity development. The first section of the questionnaire comprised of demographic questions to elicit data and information about the size of the SME's, the age of the SME (commencement date). To elicit more data, two additional questions were presented to inquire into SME owners' previous participation in knowledge exchange opportunities and the rating of the SME owners' perception on personality. The last section of the questionnaire inquires about the desire of the SME owners to participate in either the interview session or the focus group discussion.

Chapter 4 presents the general overview of the purpose of the study, the research method, the research questions, data analysis, and results. Chapter four of the study begins with the description of the findings of the population in order to create the basis for the owners of service sector SME's, the age of the business from the commencement of business operation, number of employees, and years of work experience as an owner of a SME. The data collection techniques, data analysis, and triangulation are presented in Chapter 4. The results are summarized and organized by theme to support the research questions. The concluding part of Chapter 4 is the summary section.

4.2 Descriptive Findings

This section provide detail description about the sample, it explained the nature of the data collected in respect of demography, personal (bio-data) data, and the data describing giving insights about the experience of SME owners in respect of Absorptive Capacity development through the contributory influence of cultivating quality relationships and knowledge exchange with other owners of service sector SME's in Nigeria. The descriptive findings section also includes information regarding the data collected and the summary of the participants' responses.

All participants are owners of a service sector SME with age over 18years, the suffrage age in Nigeria being 18years.

All participants experienced the influence of knowledge exchange and quality relationships with other small business owners.

All participants have dully executed and consented to the informed consent agreement electronically before proceeding with the completion of the questionnaire (see Appendix C).

The participants of the interview session and focus group discussion had return the scanned copy of the dully executed informed consent agreement to the researcher before they are qualified and eligible to participate in the research (see Appendix D).

4.2.1 Questionnaire

The questionnaire served as the initial point of contact with the participants. Participants were invited to complete the questionnaire. A total of 60 participants received and completed the questionnaire fully.

4.2.1.1 Participants' Demography

The participants represented 21 different industries such as sales, office equipment repair, sports, real estate, auctions, property management, junk removal, direct marketing, crafts, law, financial advisement, business consulting, bail bondsman, and pharmaceuticals. The researcher ensures that participants from vast diverse business engagement were captured in order to collect quality divergent views about service sector SMEs.

For the owners of these SMEs, involvement and participating in external knowledge exchange opportunities is an unusual process in the sector. The SMEs involves in sales and marketing are more willing to participate in knowledge exchange opportunities for the purpose of networking as compared to SME owners that are into business activities such as pharmaceutical, sports, crafts etc.

From the research survey, a total of 45 participants employed five or less employees. 8 participants employed six to ten employees. There were 5 participants with ten to fifteen employees, and two participants employed more than 20 employees. The ability to participate in Absorptive Capacity development present varying degree of challenges, the prominent among the challenges is the size of the labor force employed. Table 5 below presents the details in respect of the number of employees on the pay roll of owners of service sector SMEs that participated in the process.

Table 5: Number of Employees

Number of Employees	Participant Count
0-5	45
5-10	8
10-15	5
15-20	0
20-25	1
25+	1

The questionnaire identified 28 owners of service sector SMEs that have garnered between 1year experiences to 5years experience as the mode of the demographic sampling data collected. The researcher also captured 11 SME owners that garnered between 10years to 15 years of experience. The survey revealed that 9 SME owners had more than 20years or experience. Only 6 SME owners had between 5years to 10years of experience while 6 owners had garnered between 15years to 20years experience in the business.

Table 6: Years of Experience

Years of Experience	Participant Count
1-5	28
5-10	6
10-15	11
15-20	6
20+	9

The summary of the participants' age class ranges is presented Table 7. The age demographic revealed that 24 participants were in the age range of 45 -54 years, there are 11 participants in the age class of 35years-44years, also the age class range of 55years-64years has 9 participants. There are 5 participants in the class range of 18years to 24 years, three are also 5 participants within the age boundary of 65 years and above, 6 participants' falls into the age class boundary of 25 years-34 years.

Table 7: Age Ranges of the Participants

Age Range	No. of Participants
18-24	5
25-34	6
35-44	11
45-54	24
55-64	9
65+	5

4.2.1.2 Narrative Summary of Data Collected

The questionnaire presented a question about the level of involvement in Absorptive Capacity development and their self-assessed rating. The questions were scaled based on periodic frequencies of **once a week, more than once a week, less than a month, once a month, more than once a month**, and **never** regarding the participants' involvement in the development of Absorptive Capacity with other owners of SMEs with the industry's social network. From the sample size of 60 participants, 8 indicated they had never been involved or participated in Absorptive Capacity development either by receiving or using knowledge from other small business owners.

In knowledge exchange, 4 participants declared they had not offered or provided advice to other SME owners within or outside of their industry's social network. For **more than once a month** periodic involvement in the process, 14 of the SME owners reported that other SME owners have benefitted in the process by

receiving and making effective use of the knowledge offered for the improved performance of their SME. Also, 15 participants recorded their involvement in the process with a periodic frequency of **less than a month**

Trust is a major factor in the development of Absorptive Capacity through building of quality relationships and knowledge exchange. 1 participant reported lack of trust in the source of knowledge. The remaining 59 participants reported they had trust and strong confidence on the sources of the knowledge and that they have a reliable mentor within the SME's social network they can approach for succor in the face of challenges

Taking cognizance of Absorptive Capacity development through quality relationships and knowledge exchange within the SME sector, the final phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) was assessed using the questionnaire. All the participants except 6 **either agreed or strongly agreed** that the motivation to participate in the process is that process should be effective in improving the SME's operational efficiency, solving problem, or provide innovative idea that will lead to development of another products or services. All the participants except 1 (one) participated in the Absorptive Capacity development to improve exchange of knowledge and to cultivate and strengthen quality relationships.

There are different methods of engaging in exchange of knowledge; the internet provides an alternative direct physical engagement. The questionnaire required the participants to rate the preferred method of Absorptive Capacity development, social media is the most rated method for Absorptive Capacity development. From the sample size of 60 participants, 14 participants indicated their preference for the daily usage of social media. Online discussion forums method was the least rated method of knowledge exchange preferred by the owners of SME's. From the sample size of 60 participants, 17 declared that the method is not applicable.

Extroverts and introverts engage socially in different ways, in examining the perception of SME owners as regard their personality, the feedback obtained revealed that most of the participants are extroverts. The

statistics shows that 18 participants see them as very sociable and accommodating. Out of 51 respondents, 12 participants indicated they do not enjoy much of talking, 19 participants preferred not to be exposed socially, 15 participants are not always comfortable in midst of strangers.

When responding to questions regarding the scale mutual agreement, 3 participants indicated lack of interest in helping other SME owners. The other participants **either agreed** or **strongly agreed** to being interested in helping other people, being accessible to other SME owners and being empathetic with other SME owners. The results exhibited the influence of personality on Social Exchange Theory (SET).

A meticulous person is careful and diligent in actions, being meticulous earned a good rating in respect of the owners' personality traits among the participants. 42 participants are considered being orderly, showing level of preparedness and doing things appropriately. This attributes were scaled at either agree or strongly agree. The remaining participants portrayed the attributes of being carefree and disorderliness.

Participants that are emotionally stable provided a scale for measuring the participant's potential stress absorbing level, the results indicated that 49 out of 60 participants were typically relaxed, 35 do not struggle with feeling depressed, and 29 are not easily worried by business challenges and stress. Contrastingly, 12 participants agreed or strongly agreed to be worried by business challenges and stress, 4 participants agreed or strongly agreed to highly temperamental, 7 participants agreed or strongly agreed to being an imitant.

Innovative SME owners are often times better able to create ideas and view issues differently, the measure of clear imagination is rated high with 49 out of 60 participants viewing themselves as having a clear imagination. Viewing issues differently was measured and scaled, 46 participants believed they are quick in assimilating innovative ideas. Reflection was also classed as very important, 46 participants agreed or strongly agreed to spending time on reflection.

The qualifying question for the interview session or focus group discussion concluded the questionnaire. A total of 36 participants were willing to participate in either an interview or the focus group. Invitations were sent to the 36 participants who agreed to participate.

4.2.2 Interviews

The data collected from the interviews were detailed and qualitative in respect of the perception of service sector SME owners on how the challenges confronting development of Absorptive Capacity is being curtailed. 8 female and 12 male SME owners participated in the interview session. The unstructured questions served as the guidelines for the conversations among these SME owners to exchange personal experiences and perceptions about Absorptive Capacity development.

4.2.2.1 Participant Demographics

Demographic questions of the questionnaire were designed to be all inclusive in order to protect the identity of the participants. The interview participants consisted of 8 female and 12 SME owners. From the questionnaire, out of the 36 respondents who expressed interest on the interview selection part of the process, 20 were selected (8 female and 12 male). Identification data such as age, years of service, and the actual line of business were not disclosed in this research. Time range, age range, and general industry labels were used in presenting the demographic data for this study. Table 8 below presents the demographic data for the interview participants.

Table 8: Demographic Data – Interview Participants

Identifier	Gender	Participant Age(years)	Industry	Number Employees	of Tenure (years)
NS002I	M	45-54	Digital Products	0-5	1-5
NS008I	F	45-54	Branding Consultant	0-5	6-10
NS005I	F	45-54	Virtual Assistant	0-5	1-5
NS004I	F	45-54	Alternative Healing	0-5	10-15
NS003I	M	25-34	Nutrition	0-5	1-5
NS001I	M	45-54	Real Estate	6-10	6-10
NS006I	F	65+	Travel Agent	0-5	1-5
NS0007	F	45-54	Promotional Products	0-5	11-15
NS009I	M	65+	Publishing and Branding	0-5	11-15
NS010I	F	55-64	Branding and Design	0-5	20+
NA0001I	M	55-64	Masters	0-5	1-5
NA0002I	M	25-34	Nutrition	6-10	1-5

			Computer		
NA003I	M	65+	and Scientific	6-10	20+
			Equipment		
			Consulting		
NA004I	M	45-54	Advertising Agency	0-5	11-15
NA005I	M	45-54	Entertainment	0-5	11-15
NA006I	M	45-54	Law Firm	6-10	16-20
NA007I	F	45-54	Bail Bonds	0-5	1-5
NB0001I	M	45-54	Fleet Management	0-5	1-5
NB002I	M	45-54	Game Development	0-5	1-5
NB003I	F	45-54	Music and	0-5	20+
			DrumTherapy		

The participants of the interview session that has a minimum of five years' experience as an SME owner is made up of 4 female and 6 male. 13 participants are within the age range of 45 years to 54years. 2 participants were below the age of 35, and 5 participants were over the age of 54. From the age range of 45 years to 54 years, there 3 female and 5 male participants that has more than five years of experience as an SME owner.

20 SME owners within the service sector participated in the unstructured interview session while 6 owners out of this 20 went on to take part in the unstructured focus group discussion. The general code provided confidentiality for participants. An aggregate code of NA001I is used to represent the first SME's owner in

the sample that would be engaged in the interview session (NA for Nigerian- American Chamber of Commerce), however, alphabet “F” (F=Focus Group) will be used in place of the alphabet “I” (I=Interview) where focus group discussion is involved. Table 9 below provides the summary of the data collated from the different primary sources.

Table 9: Summary of Data Sources

Source	Unique Participants Descriptive Data	
Questionnaire	60	60 questionnaires
SME’s Owner Interview Session	20	20 unstructured interview sessions
Focus Group Discussion	6	1 focus group discussion

4.2.2.2 Narrative summary of Interview data collected

The questionnaire was designed to elicit data and also served as a sampling method to identify the interview session participants and the focus group participants. In addition, it provides demographic and baseline data in respect of Absorptive Capacity development and personality traits. The un-structured interview protocol was designed to obtain detailed and quality data from the owners of the SMEs. The participants shared how they had been involved in Absorptive Capacity development and the benefits that had accrued through the process for the growth and enhanced performance of the SME’s. The unstructured interview protocol was also designed to collate quality and reliable data in respect of building quality relationships with other SME owners. The participants shared individual experiences on how relationships have contributed to the success of Absorptive Capacity development and strategies in building and strengthening quality relationships.

The interviews were conducted with the aid of Zoom.com, the online execution of the interview sessions made the time schedule to be flexible and a perfect fit into the participants work schedule. Zoom.com

provided the facility to record the session with the consent of the SME owners. The flexibility in scheduling helped in reducing the stress involves in planning interview session, it also enhanced the level of preparedness of the SME owners thereby leading to provision of more reliable and quality responses. The time management is an essential issue for the SME owners, therefore with the flexibility of the time schedule the participating ratio was highly encouraging.

Each of the interview sessions is completed within a time limit of between 15minutes to 60minutes; this produced an average of seven pages of single-spaced transcribed data per interview (see Table 8). The recommended standard duration for interviews is no more than 45minutes to 60 minutes (Yin, 2014).

The apportioned time frame for the interview is sufficient to produce the required text needed to carry out thorough examination of the process that is being focused by the study. A much longer duration may deter individuals from participating, redundancy in data may also occur with longer interview sessions.

Table 10: Length of Interviews and Transcripts

Participant	Audio Length – Minutes	Transcribed
NS002I	31	9
NS008I	40	7
NS005I	23	5
NS004I	40	10
NS003I	18	5
NS001I	34	7
NS006I	25	6
NS0007	60	13
NS009I	25	6
NS010I	40	9
NA0001I	34	9
NA0002I	42	9
NA003I	25	6
NA004I	22	6
NA005I	15	5

NA006I	34	8
NA007I	26	6
NB0001I	25	6
NB002I	21	5
NB003I	42	9
Average	31	7

4.2.3 Focus group

The focus group discussion succeeded in collating quality and reliable rich data in respect of the perception of SME owners on the influence of quality relationships and knowledge exchange for the development of Absorptive Capacity. The participants were selected from the questionnaire respondents who had expressly indicated their interest to partake in the focus group discussion, none of the focus group discussants participates in the interview session. The focus group discussants are comprised of 5 female and 1 male SME's owners. The unstructured questions served as the guideline for the focus group discussion.

4.2.3.1 Participant Demographics

The following data were generated from the responses received from the questionnaire in respect of SME owners that express their desire to participate in the focus group discussion. The sample size is made up of 5 female and 1 male owners of service sector SMEs. From the data collated, 3 female and 1 male participants are within the age range of 45years to 54 years old, 1 female participant is above the age of 65years, 1 female participant fall within the age range of 25years to 34years. In addition to the demographic date, 3 female participants had garnered work experience in excess of 10years (see Table 9 for details).

Table 11: Demographics of Focus Group Participants

Identifier	Gender	Participant Age (years)	Industry	Number of Employees	Tenure(years)
NS007F	F	45-54	Promotional Products	0-5	10-15
NS004F	F	45-54	Alternative Healing	0-5	10-15
NB002F	M	45-54	Game Development	0-5	1-5
NB003F	F	45-55	Music and Drum Therapy	0-5	1-5
NA003F	F	65+	Computer & Scientific Equipment Consulting	0-5	20+
NS003F	F	25-34	Nutrition	0-5	1-5

4.2.3.2 Narrative Summary of Focus Group Data Collected

The focus group discussion in respect of the above array of data took a maximum of 45minutes; the transcription of the data into print produced 9.5 pages of single-spaced transcribed data. The goal of the focus group discussion is to obtain quality and reliable data in respect of the importance of participating in Absorptive Capacity development through the quality relationships and knowledge exchange and it benefits to the growth and success of the SME's. The responses collected from the focus group discussion provided answers to research questions relating to how Absorptive Capacity is developed through external knowledge

exchange and cultivating relationships and its contribution to the success and enhanced performance of SMEs.

The focus group commenced with a brief discussion on maintaining confidentiality, participants were advised to keep every facts of discussion within the privacy of the group. The focus group questions did not expose the SMEs owners and the business to risk the Non-disclosure terms. The focus group discussion helped establishing an enabling environment in which the SME owners bare their mind truthfully and realistically without holding back important facts. In the course of the focus group discussion, each participant was given a pseudonym for ease of conversation. Upon completion of the focus group discussion, aggregate code was assigned to each participant. In addition, follow-up questions on responses provided by the participants lead to collection of detailed data that are helpful to the study. The use of follow-up questions helps in ensuring that all 6 participants contributed usefully to the discussion.

A code cloud created from the frequency of codes reflects how many times a code appeared in the focus group transcript (see Appendix R). The more frequent codes include advice to the SME owners, advice for business operations, and advice participation methods. The listed codes imply that the participants highlighted the preferred methods of engaging in external exchange of knowledge, and either providing advice or receiving advice as per the operational procedure of the SMEs more frequently than other topics during the focus group session.

The focus group provided informative descriptions that revealed factors that influenced successful development of Absorptive Capacity. The factors were very evident and presented through codes such as the importance of mentoring, the importance of establishing quality relationships within social network of SMEs, it also expatiates on how external advice can assist in improving the growth and performance of the SMEs. The responses provided by participant helps in answering Research Question 1 (RQ 1), Research Question 2 (RQ 2), and Research Question 3 (RQ3).

4.3 Data Analysis Procedures

4.3.1 Analysis of data.

The research questions serves as guide for the data analysis process, this section presents the dynamics of the data analysis process. The data analysis did not include any modifications to the procedures presented in Chapter 3. The first section will focus on analyzing the data collated from the questionnaire while the later part of the section will analyze the data from the interview and focus group transcripts.

The questionnaire served two primary purposes in this study. The first purpose was to screen participants to determine eligibility for interviews and the focus group. Demographic data was collected from the participants to identify the industry, age, number of employees and years of experience of the participant. The demographic data helped in selecting a diversity of participants for interviews and the focus group. The varying degree of the perspectives from a diverse sampling helped the reliability and quality of the data used in answering the research questions.

Candidates were asked to participate in an interview or the focus group. SurveyMonkey.com provided a listing of participants with the demographic data. The listed participants received an invitation to participate either in an interview session or the focus group discussion. Yin's five phases of analysis provided direction to the thematic data analysis. Yin's five-phase cycle enabled the data analysis process to be inductive coding with semantic themes. The five phases presented data analysis in a nonlinear cycle consisting of compiling data, disassembling data, reassembling data, interpreting data, and conclusions (Yin, 2014). The conceptual approach to data analysis was through the perceptiveness of both the Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET). Absorptive Capacity Theory provided conceptual focus as to how individuals acquire, transfer, and capitalize on knowledge exchange to develop absorptive capacity. SET establishes the social guidelines for how quality relationships provide reliable fundamentals for mutual exchange of knowledge.

The ability to repeat a study with a different sampling increases the reliability of the research. Yin's five phases of analysis provided the framework to guide the thematic analysis. Yin (2014) defines the five phases of analysis as:

- ❖ **Compiling:** Compiling is the act of creating an organized database in preparation for analysis.
- ❖ **Disassembling:** This is the process in which data are coded and organized in more than one view to create new perspectives.
- ❖ **Reassembling:** This is the process of classifying and summarizing data to discover its patterns.
- ❖ **Interpreting:** This is process whereby collected data are triangulated to provide meaning for answering research questions.
- ❖ **Concluding:** This is the final phase of the cycle, it is involved with the answering of the research questions.

The purpose of using thematic analysis for this study is basically to identify the patterns and quality of experience of the individual SME owners, which would provide meaning and depth in answering the research questions. A thematic analysis allowed the examination of the themes and its significant to the process (Braun & Clarke, 2006). To set up the codes, an inductive approach was used as against the use of an established codebook. The inductive coding allowed themes to emerge from the interview and focus group data.

4.3.2 Data Preparation

The disassembling phase of the analysis process commenced with the reading of the transcripts. The disassembling of the data includes identifying interview and focus group participants from the questionnaire, the first coding, second and third coding of the transcripts, summarizing and categorizing codes, and identifying emerging themes. The following sections outline the data analysis process.

Data preparation begins immediately the questionnaires stage is concluded, the questionnaire served two purposes, the demographic data is summarized using SurveyMonkey.com's question summary reporting tool, and the summarized data is later downloaded into a spreadsheet for further review.

The query selection tool in SurveyMonkey.com helped in the creation of list of positive responses. The list provides the researcher with email addresses that facilitates the sending of invitation to the SME owners that had expressed their willingness to participate in the interview session and the focus group discussion.

The second objective of the questionnaire helps in establishing the participant's perception about Absorptive Capacity development and the general approach to external knowledge exchange. These questions ensured the potential participants in the interview session and focus group discussion had prior experience on Absorptive Capacity development. SurveyMonkey.com provided summary of the report in respect of the responses from each participant and for the questions. The summary data was downloaded into Microsoft-Excel package; this was used in describing the questionnaire data. The thematic analysis data collated from the interview, focus group data, and individual participant responses were reviewed using SurveyMonkey.com to complement the research analysis process.

The request to participate in an interview or focus group was the second primary function of the questionnaire.

Trint.com is used in transcribing the focus group discussion and the interview sessions recordings. Each transcription was read and reviewed thoroughly based on the audio recording file. The researcher forward

transcribed copy of the audio recording file of the interview and focus group discussion to the participants through electronic mailing system for member checking. The Participants did not provide further feedback on the transcripts, the absence of feedback may be attributed to the fact that clarifications for this purpose are required during the actual interview and focus group.

The actual transcription process involves the uploading of the audio recording file from Zoom.com into Trint.com's online transcription service; the transcription service provided a Microsoft Word document. The files containing the processed data are stored in an external hard disk drive for secure storage. The assigned aggregate code is used to replace the participant's name in the transcript. Also, general label is used to replace any particular specific identity of the participants, identity such as company names and location; this is part of the privacy protection for data scrubbing. Transcriptions were uploaded into MaxQDA immediately the data scrubbing is concluded. It is worthy to note that MaxQDA is software designed specifically for qualitative analysis, MaxQDA provided a platform that helped in identifying and organizing code for easy management. The coding of transcripts commenced immediately the data is uploaded into MaxQDA platform. Coding involved an iterative process for the upload of each transcript.

4.3.3 Coding

The iterative or repetitive nature of coding provides the researcher and the participants with the opportunity to read transcripts multiple times. Having access to read the transcripts multiple times after coding a new transcript provided a slightly different perspective at times. In most cases, referencing audio file during the coding process ensured proper understanding of the context. Important sections of the first transcript provided the framework for the initial codebook. The evolving nature of the codebook made the iterative process compulsory for thorough analysis. Subsequent reading help to fine tune the initial codebook, the refined codebook provided the foundation for the thematic analysis.

An inductive approach to coding was adopted as against a theoretical approach. Themes were linked to the data collected in interviews and the focus group (Braun & Clarke, 2006). A theoretical approach involves

coding specifically for the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2006) while inductive approach on the other hand provides quality and reliable data which provides answer to the research questions.

Coding commenced immediately after completion of the transcription of the first interview session. Iterative reading of the text revealed important characteristics that helped form the initial codes. The initial codes were generated from the statements that revealed the participant reliance on trust and the strength of the established relationship before seriously considering the development of Absorptive Capacity. Proof-reading the transcript multiple times helped align the codes and reduce redundancy as seen in Table 12 below. The initial transcript was read until new codes did not emerge.

Table 12: Interview Coding Results

Interviews	Number of Codes
NS001I	32
NS003I	28
NS004I	44
NS005I	22
NS006I	30
NS007I	27
NS008I	34
NS009I	36
NS010I	66
NA001I	28
NA002I	36
NA003I	24
NA004I	20
NA005I	28
NA006I	39
NA007I	31
NB001I	28
NB002I	33

NB003I	31
Focus Group	48

An inductive coding approach was applied for the analysis process, coding will be iteratively carried out until saturation was achieved. Saturation occurs at the point where new codes emerge from the data (Yin, 2014). The second reading of interview number 17 did not produce new codes. The interview and focus group transcripts generated 60 initial codes; the initial codebook (see Appendix S) comprised of codes that emerged from reading the transcripts and taking note significant features.

Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) was used in identifying codes, identifying the topics of Absorptive Capacity development, knowledge exchange, acquiring, and transferring knowledge to the organization. Codes such as “methods of developing Absorptive Capacity, the challenges in absorptive capacity, and seeking knowledge are examples of codes that emerged from using ACT as part of the framework. Codes including trust and reciprocity emerged as part of the Social Exchange Theory (SET) framework. Table 13 illustrates the example in respect of coding.

Table 13: SME's Owners Coding Examples

Interview Question	Code	Quote
What challenge have you confronted in using external knowledge for either improving operations or developing innovation? (RQ1 and RQ2)	Challenges in Absorptive Capacity	"Just trying to learn the process, I tried to create time to learn how to get the process fit your process and to follow workflow chart process."
How have you overcome some of these challenges? (RQ1 and RQ2)	The challenges –Strategies	"I consistently listen to personal development and podcast that talk to a wide variety of people who've had got to be resilient and go through many challenges in order to get to where they want to be, the best solution for overcoming challenges is a lot more challenges."

The second reading of the transcripts produced a precise codebook, second thorough reading of the transcripts helped identify redundant codes. One example of redundancy is the initial code meet up and type of social interaction. The second reading re-classified the segment of coded meet up as type of social interaction. The other activity during the second reading involved evaluating codes with less than 10 coded segments. The codes were reviewed and merged with other codes for proper alignment with the purpose of the study.

A final line by line review of the coded segments arranged by code presented a focused view of the data. Analyzing the codes by segment created greater clarity to similarities in responses. Themes began to emerge by grouping the segments by code. Viewing the coded segments by code rather than by participant placed responses in the appropriate context for the next phase of analysis as demonstrated in Table 14.

Table 14: Example of Coded Segments Organized by Code

DocumentName	Code	Segment
NS003I	Receiving Knowledge\Most impactful	“The establishment of quality relationship with other owners of SME’s in my neighbourhood, gives me the courage that common challenges facing the industry can be jointly surmounted. It assured me that there is existent of a big umbrella that can be very during a stormy period of the business.”
NS004I	Receiving Knowledge\Most impactful	“My main target is to find means to reduce my general overhead expenses drastically and bring my business back to profitability level”.
NS009I	Receiving Knowledge\Most impactful	“I am a member of an SME social network in my state, one of the leader of the network suggested to the members that it very important that the members read a forwarded e-mail, I did and I have been able to implemented parts of the strategies contained in the mail. The implementation of some of the suggested policies had bring about improvement to my business.”

The last step in disassembling data is concerned with the organization of the codes into similar groups based on theoretical constructs. Organizing the codes into categories based on shared characteristics produced the final codebook and initiated the thematic analysis, categorizing the codes helps in identifying the potential relationships (Saldana, 2016). The categories included personality, relationship, challenges in Absorptive Capacity, and methods of knowledge exchange, receiving knowledge, and approaches towards knowledge-sharing opportunities, topics, and participation. Appendix U demonstrates the results of categorizing codes and the final codebook which contained 39 codes.

4.3.4 Developing Thematic Network

The last step in the disassembling phase involved summarizing the codes in preparation for thematic analysis. Summary create a perspective of the coded segments (Yin, 2014). The summary of the coded segments provided the fundamental basis for the thematic network. A thematic network is the technique used in conducting the thematic analysis. The use of tools like the thematic network facilitates the organization and presentation of the analysis (Attride-Stirling, 2001). According to Attride-Stirling (2001) “thematic networks aim is to x-ray the understanding of an issue or its significance of an idea, rather than to reconcile conflicting definitions of a problem”. The thematic network is made up of three classifications of themes.

The approach taken in the thematic analysis was semantic rather than latent. The themes that emerged in a semantic approach is based on the explicit meaning of the data (Braun& Clarke, 2006). The latent approach goes beyond describing the data to theorizing the underlying meaning. The semantic themes emerged in three tiers consisting of basic, organizing and global themes.

The first classification is the basic themes, basic themes are the lowest order themes which emerge from the text (Attride-Stirling, 2001). This meaning was conveyed to the higher-level themes through the basic themes. Basic themes should be read within context of the other basic themes for detail meanings to be comprehended (Attride-Stirling,2001). The organizing theme is represented by the basic themes.

The second phase of developing the network includes organizing the basic themes which shared uniformity in topic to form the organizing themes. The organizing theme is more abstract than basic themes. The organizing themes present a summary of the main ideas represented by multiple basic themes (Attride-Stirling, 2001). Organizing themes were classified based on similar attributes to form overall themes.

The highest level of the thematic network is overall themes. The overall themes present what the text as a whole reveal regarding the analysis (Attride-Stirling, 2001). The lower level themes were summarized and presented at a macro level. Overall themes are both the summary and interpretation of the analyzed text (Attride-Stirling, 2001). The main and most important part of the thematic network are the overall themes. Overall themes provided comprehensive answers to the research questions, appendix T presents the thematic network for this study. The final thematic review of the research resulted in the 39 coded segments which were summarized into 25 basic themes. The 25 basic themes were further grouped into seven organizing themes. Five overall themes provided the macro level summary of this study.

In transitioning from code to basic theme, codes were grouped by similar characteristics. For example, the codes advice – business value, advice – business operations, and types of knowledge created a basic theme of challenges being faced by SME owners. The participants' responses presented the types of advice required or given in Absorptive Capacity development process. The responses generated the three codes relating to business advice, business operations, and types of knowledge. All three codes represent distinct challenges confronting SME's in Nigeria. Challenges, such as technology trends or brand imaging. The basic theme focused on the challenges faced by SME owners, this is identified in the codes listed in the example.

The transition from basic themes to organizing themes presented seven emerging organizing themes, the seven organizing themes created more focus on the theoretical constructs of how owners of the service sector SMEs participates in the development of Absorptive Capacity, what motivates participation in Absorptive Capacity development, challenges faced by SME's owners in participating in Absorptive Capacity development, the impact of absorptive capacity on the SME's performance, influence of quality relationships in absorptive capacity development, the influence of personality, and how relationships are cultivated.

The grouping of the organizing themes resulted in the emergence of five overall themes (see Appendix T). The overall themes comprised of engaging in Absorptive Capacity, participating in knowledge exchange, factors influencing the development of Absorptive Capacity, influences of the SME's owners' personality, and cultivating relationships. The overall themes bring alignment of the coded segments of the participants' responses to the research questions through the framework of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET).

4.3.5 Describe and Explore Thematic Network

The thematic networks facilitated the interpretation of the original text in providing further description of the data further. The basic theme, organizing theme, and the overall themes provided the basis for reading the original transcripts. The thematic network is useful in interpreting the data; an example of data interpretation was more pronounced with the overall theme by engaging in the development of Absorptive Capacity. The thematic network of engaging in absorptive capacity development consists of three organizing themes and eleven basic themes (see Appendix T).

Engaging in the development of absorptive capacity summarized the exploration of SME's owners' personal perceptions and experiences in engaging in the process. The individual experiences includes how the participants engage in Absorptive Capacity development, knowledge exchange activities, preferred methods of developing in absorptive capacity, and what challenges prevent the SME's owners from participating in absorptive capacity development.

4.3.6 Thematic Network Summary

The thematic network helped in the identification of the themes which emerged from the data. As illustrated above, basic themes were summarized into organizing themes; the basic themes were subsequently grouped into organizing themes. The overall themes emerged from the grouping of the organizing themes. Each layer of the thematic network illustrates the main themes of the research study.

4.3.7 Interpreting Patterns

The third phase of Yin's five phases of analysis is reassembling data. The process of reassembling data involved merging the results created in the thematic network into a complete story (Yin, 2014). The results section contains a summary of each thematic network. The overall theme of engaging in the development of absorptive capacity was built around the organizing themes of how the owners' service sector of the SME's engaged in the process, the motivational factors that influence participation in the process, and challenges in participating in the process.

Table 13 demonstrates the thematic network for engaging absorptive capacity development, interpreting the process of developing absorptive capacity in relation to ACT, reflected knowledge was more easily absorbed into the SMEs when factors such as the knowledge being relevant to current goals and the existence of previous experience on absorptive capacity within the industry's social network. The last step in interpreting data involved connecting the thematic network back to the research questions. The development of absorptive capacity with the SMEs social network provides the answers to the research questions (RQ1 and RQ2)

Table 15: Thematic Network for Engaging in Exchange of Knowledge

Basic themes	Organizing Themes	Overall Themes
Direct physical participation in Exchange of knowledge	How do SME owners	Engaging in Exchange of Knowledge
is preferred, but technology enables social media	Engage in	
to be more convenient.	Exchange of Knowledge	
SME owners must engage in knowledge exchange		
with specific goals.		
An individual's personality is an Important factor	Motivational factors	
in motivating the individual to participate.	In engaging	
	In knowledge exchange	
Previous experiences with exchange of		
Knowledge Impact the current approach.		
Participating in knowledge exchange		
opportunities is influenced by quality relationships.		
Scarce and limited resources affects	Challenges being confronted	
absorptive capacity development	in participating in	
The content of the capacity	knowledge exchange	
must be relevant		

4.3.8 Trustworthiness

The fourth phase of Yin's five phases of analysis is interpretation, this includes establishing trustworthiness. Triangulation is one method of establishing trustworthiness, the triangulation of data sources helps in ensuring that data collected is reliable and is of good quality in nature provides thorough answers to the research questions (Yin, 2014). Member checking is the second method used in establishing trustworthiness.

Member checking is the process of having the participant confirms the accuracy of the transcription. The third method used in establishing trustworthiness is keeping the audit trail of the process. The following sections discuss the steps taken to establish trustworthiness. Improved trustworthiness helped in ensuring that the study is in line with the criteria set for credibility by reporting accurate data from the participants. Every effort to ensure trustworthiness was taken.

4.3.9 Triangulation

Triangulation is a strategy to assess the validity of a study by merging data from various sources. Triangulation allows the assessment of data from multiple viewpoints through a single lens of observation (Yin, 2014). The ability to merge data from separate sources and answer the research questions through the theoretical framework demonstrates the validity and reliability of data (Yin, 2014). A questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group established the triangulation for this study.

The questionnaire, interviews, and focus group provided different perspectives of engaging the topics of Absorptive Capacity, Exchange of Knowledge and cultivating quality relationships with other service sector SME owners. The questionnaire provides the participants with an opportunity to present personal view on the topic and consider personal perspectives. The self-reflection helped establish a frame of mind for the participant to engage in either an interview session or focus group discussion. The interview and focus group encouraged the participant to express their individual experiences in Absorptive Capacity development, exchange of knowledge and cultivating quality relationships, which generates reliable and quality data for the study.

Data collected from the questionnaire and interviews were corroborated to the overall themes of engaging in the development of Absorptive Capacity and its influence on the personality of SME owners. The questionnaires provided additional insight for the interview and focus group data. For example, the self-perceptions of personality type bring about clarity to the responses in respect of the participation in Absorptive Capacity development. The results section presents the finding in detail.

The results of the analysis of the quality data demonstrated the importance of triangulation in qualitative research. Interviews and the focus group supported the overall themes of engaging Absorptive Capacity development, contributory factors to Absorptive Capacity development, and influences on the personality of SME owners. Where the interview participants consistently presented time and trust as challenges in participating in Absorptive Capacity development, the focus group presented individual experiences in curtailing some of the challenges presented in the interviews. Collectively, the multiple data collection methods employed corroborated the individual results of each method. The Individual method of data collection employed provides detailed insights.

The interview and the focus group transcript were individually coded, the result of the coding was the ability to merge the sources of data to form a clearer picture of the phenomenon of knowledge exchange and relationship quality towards the development of absorptive capacity. The ability to accomplish the combination of data from the various sources confirmed the validity of data through triangulation. The results from the triangulation of the data were very thorough and sufficient to provide clear answers to the research questions.

4.3.10 Member Checking

Member checking is used in validating trustworthiness of the process, the transcripts were member checked by the focus group and interview participants. Birt et al. (2016) defined member checking as the process of having the participant proof-read and confirm the accuracy of the transcribed data. Member checking provides a solid foundation for qualitative research's reliability and trustworthiness through having a verbatim transcript of the discussion.

Member checking occurred in two different ways; it can be carried out by the participants through clarification of the responses provided during the course of the interview and the focus group. Asking for clarity presented an opportunity to explain the discussion topic. The second method adopted for member checking involved sending a copy of the transcript to the participants for review and clarification and additional comments. Member checking help ensure the validity of the data. Participants did not report any inaccuracies in audio transcriptions.

4.3.11 Audit trail

Audit trail provides adequate and proper documentation for the research process from inception to conclusion. Audit trails in qualitative research facilitate the replication of the study using a different sample (Cope, 2014). The ability to replicate the study increases integrity of the researcher and research work executed. An audit trail provides the opportunity for the researcher to review the process and the influences of the data collection and analysis steps (Cope, 2014). The ability to review activities throughout the entire process established trustworthiness.

4.4 Results

The final phase of qualitative analysis is the concluding phase. According to Yin(2014), concluding answers the research question and identifies future research. The study presents the answers to the research questions through the results as well as suggested future research.

The results are presented in three parts; this section discussed the results of the data analysis for each research question. Secondly, a discussion of the results for the questionnaire presents the data according to the technique being used as a recruitment tool and asupplement to the interviews and focus group. Lastly, a thematic analysis of interviews and the focus group provides the details of the individual participants' experiences in Absorptive Capacity development, knowledge exchange and quality relationships.

4.4.1 Research Questions

As mentioned above, the first section in the discussion ofthe results are the research questions. The questions were designed to examine the contributory factors for the development of Absorptive Capacity through quality relationships and knowledge exchange among SME owners for growth and enhanced performance of SMEs. Research Question1 (RQ1) provided the participants perceptionsof Absorptive Capacity development through exchange of knowledge and relationship quality.

RQ2 guided the research to examine the strategies to initiate and improve the exchange of knowledge process. Methods for improving relationship quality with other SME owners were identified through the guidance of Research Question 3. (RQ 3).

Data analysis was conducted with the aid of thematic analysis; the thematic network answered the research questions. The following discussion details the thematic network and the connection to the research questions.

- ❖ **RQ1: Thematic network.** RQ1: How do SME owners perceive exchange of knowledge and relationship quality with other SME's as aiding the development of absorptive capacity?

The overall theme that emerged provides answer to RQ1. The overall theme is made up of two organizing themes which was on how owners' of SMEs engage in exchange of knowledge and the motivational factors that contribute to participation in such exchange of knowledge (see Appendix T). The participants discussed the preferred methods for engaging in exchange of knowledge, direct physical interaction was the most preferred method of exchange and collaborating with other SME's owners in the informal settings. However, challenges such as time and the ability to step away from business operations activities posed a great challenge for involvement in knowledge exchange, therefore online engagement provide the solution to the challenge. The direct physical engagement made the knowledge exchange experience more personal and meaningful.

Formal knowledge exchange experiences offered through professional organizations provide established capacity exchange with specific goals. Professional organizations targeted specific topics and goals for the participants, the participants who were apprehensive in engaging in exchange of knowledge are more confident in well structured professional knowledge exchange activities. The methods of engaging in knowledge exchange emphasized on the first step of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) which is involved in identifying knowledge sources and the understanding the knowledge exchanged.

The second step of the Absorptive Capacity Theory is the acquisition of knowledge; the discussions from the participants identified the second organizing theme which was based on the motivational factors for engaging in the knowledge exchange process. The organizing theme summarized the experiences that are shared by the owners of SMEs by engaging in knowledge exchange. Empirical research has shown that different personality traits types are motivated by different factors (Bencsik, Machova, & Hevesi, 2016). The participants' self-perception of their personality influenced how exchange of knowledge is carried out.

Participants who viewed themselves as being opened and willing to connect with others were more willing to engage in the process of exchange of knowledge. Participants discussed trust as a factor in examining the value of knowledge exchange. The personality influenced the cultivation of quality relationships with other owners of SMEs. For example, participants consistently discussed trust when talking about quality relationships and the self-perception of their personality type. Participants shared experiences of having received wrong information provided intentionally to negatively impact the business operations which caused apprehension in how knowledge acquisition. Consistently trust was a motivational factor in knowledge acquisition.

- ❖ **RQ2: Thematic network.** RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs?

Research Question 2 explored the exchange of knowledge in details by identifying the strategies the participants employed to initiate and improve knowledge exchange . The ability to absorb knowledge differs for everyone. The two overall themes which contributed to answering RQ2 were engaging in exchange of knowledge as well as knowledge exchange factors of Absorptive Capacity (see Appendix T). The discussions of how the participants perceived the ability to absorb knowledge and the influence of relationships in Absorptive Capacity development includes the strategies employed by the owners of SME's in initiating and improving knowledge exchange.

The first overall theme for participating in exchange of knowledge is made up of two organizing themes. The first organizing theme presents the challenges in engaging in exchange of knowledge, the basic themes is presented by the scarcity and availability of limited resources which hindered Absorptive Capacity development, content of the knowledge must be relevant, and an individual's perception of value in the exchange of knowledge must be presented (see Appendix T). Owners of the service sector SMEs in the study

are confronted with challenges of inadequate personnel to cover business operations and to attend direct physical knowledge exchange engagement activities. Other owners' of SMEs are confronted with challenges of limited time to be available to participate in the process. With the frequent knowledge exchange process being an informal arrangement, spending time on irrelevant content was another code which emerged from the discussions.

The strategy the participants identified to curtail the challenges of limited resources includes finding alternative methods of engagement in knowledge exchange process. Technology offers alternatives method for participating in exchange of knowledge, participants identified podcasts, blogs and social media platforms as ways to take advantage of technology to participate in exchange of knowledge.

Technology also provided the means to filter the relevance of the contents the participants exchanged by using the internet to research knowledge exchange activities to determine whether the program will be beneficial to the participants. The strategies helped in improving the first and second phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT). Improving the ability to absorb knowledge within the first two phases increases the chances of transferring the knowledge back to the SMEs for effective implementation.

Strategies to improve participation in knowledge exchange is the second organizing theme. Having positive experiences with previous knowledge exchange activities motivates participants to develop strategies to cope with the social impacts of knowledge exchange activities. Consistent approach to participating in exchange of knowledge provides the opportunity for cultivating quality relationships which in turn increased the consistency in participating in knowledge exchange activities. The social impacts of engaging other owners' of SMEs improved the knowledge exchange experience for the participants. The success in the strategy improves with consistency.

The second overall theme was knowledge exchange factors of absorptive capacity. This overall theme consisted of one organizing theme (see Appendix T). The organizing theme is exchange of knowledge impacts on success of SMEs. The first basic theme is negative experience of knowledge exchange and its

effects on the participation in process. Receiving misleading information and spending time with individuals who were not mutually engaging in exchange of knowledge creates negative experiences which hindered participation in future activities.

Positive experience about Absorptive Capacity development activities helps in strengthening the relationships. The positive experiences provided the participants with access to other ideas and resources which helps in the introduction of innovation. Cultivating quality relationships helps minimize the negative experiences of participants. Quality relationships built trust which in turn creates positive experiences in Absorptive Capacity development activities.

❖ **RQ3: Thematic network:** RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners?

Research Question 3 (RQ3) explored how owners of SMEs cultivate quality relationships with other owners. The mutual exchange between individuals influenced the success of Absorptive Capacity development; the evaluation of the quality relationships among owners of the SME's provides insights to challenges, strategies, and benefits of these relationships.

The first overall theme which contributed to answering Research Question 3 is relationship factors of Absorptive Capacity development. Appendix T presents the overall theme of credible relationship as a factor of Absorptive Capacity development which is comprised of one organizing themes. The organizing theme of the role of quality relationships in Absorptive Capacity development provided answers to Research Question 3. Participant's ability to share good intentions by cultivating quality relationships reduced challenges in Absorptive Capacity development. Quality relationships cultivate trust; recommendations made by trusted sources reduced the challenges in respect of identifying relevant content and avoiding knowledge exchange engagements that don't offer such. Participating in Absorptive Capacity development opportunities is influenced by establishment of quality relationships. The frequency of engaging in Absorptive Capacity development improves through cultivation of quality relationships within the industry's network. Participants

appreciate the time to connect with other owners of SME's by resolving to attend knowledge exchange activities and making it a regular and consistent act.

A mentor is an important resource for every individual owner of SME. Cultivating quality relationships provides the opportunities for mentorship. The mentorships provide support system and accountability for owners of SMEs. Accountability helps in developing consistent personal habits for the owners of SMEs. Support system provides a mentor to serve as someone to share with during difficult time of the SMEs business life. Being a mentor created the opportunity to help the business activities of the mentee. The mutual participation in the relationship strengthened the success of Absorptive Capacity development. Quality relationships strengthened the Absorptive Capacity development process.

The second overall theme is the influences of the SME owners personality (see Appendix T). The organizing theme is the personality types that influenced quality relationships and knowledge exchange. The basic theme is the personality type which influence how quality relationships are established and cultivated. Participants who are self-identified as being a introverts discussed the difficulty in meeting new people. Introversion was measured using the scales of the Big Five Model (see Appendix W). Intentional actions such as setting goal for making new introduction are a common strategy to surmount social inhibitions. Introversion had the potential to hinder cultivation of quality relationships evenwhen cultivating relationships is important to the success of SME's.

Cultivating quality relationships is the third overall theme on how the participants connected with other owners of the SME's. The overall theme is made up of the organizing theme in respect of methods used to cultivate quality relationships with other owners of SMEs. Challenges confronting owners of SMEs in connecting with other owners are time and trust.

One important strategy shared by the participants is summarized by the basic theme of being consistent and desirable in meeting other owners who have common goals and values. Consistency was different for individual owners of the SME's, some participants are comfortable with a monthly telephone call, while

others preferred having coffee time meeting for a few minutes on weekly basis. Intentionally, being consistent in meeting people who shared common goals and values is what helped relationships to grow. Common goals provide the ability to be sincere and interested in the other person. Identifying and working together provide the opportunity for owners of SMEs within a locality to work together for the benefits and success of the business.

Quality relationships tend to strengthened trust. The second basic theme is trust, this is the result of established relationships and it improves the Absorptive Capacity development experience.

The last basic theme is relationships; relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the otherperson. A relationship is when individuals mutually engage each other and develop an understanding of being a owner of SME which exist without competition. Trust is when the other owners of SME's owners improve the cultivation of quality relationships. A perceived threat discussed by the participants is the fear of receiving misinformation. Time and consistency in connecting with each other built trust in the development of Absorptive Capacity experiences. Cultivating quality relationships with other small business owners is an intentional act for the participants.

4.4.2 Analysis of Questionnaire Data

The second section in the discussion of the results covers the initial collection of data. The questionnaire serves as the initial point of contact with the participants. The data served two purposes for this study. First, the questionnaire is used as a method of selecting participants for interviews and the focus group. The second purpose the questionnaire is that the data collected provide corroboration with the data gathered from interview session or focus group discussions. The responses help inexplaining the participants' approaches towards Absorptive Capacity development, knowledge exchange and cultivating quality relationships with insights of the participant's self-perception of personality type.

Demographic data

Two sets of data were used to select owners of SMEs who met the criteria for the study. Demographic data enabled the selection of owners with different age, years of experience, number of employees and industries. The questionnaire prompted the participants to participate in either an interview or the focus group. The responses provided a list of owners of SMEs to be contacted for interview or focus group participation.

The demographic data reflected that the participants represent 21 different industries. The industries include travel agent, sports equipment sales, office equipment repair, real estate, junk removal, auctions, property investment, direct marketing, crafts, law, financial, business consulting, insurance, video production, marketing, restaurant, virtual assistant, bail bondsman, pharmaceuticals, and non-profit organization. The participants represent a variety of industries to provide a broader perspective into the study.

The top three categories of years of experience as owners of SME's were 1year to 5years, 10years to 15years, and 20years and above. A total of 24 participants had 1year to 5 years of experience, 11 participants has 10years to 15years of experience, 9 participants has 20years and above years of experience, 6 participants has between 5years to 10years of experience, 4 participants has between 10years to 20years of experience.

The age demographic presented an interesting pattern. Participants who are between 45years to 54 years of age represent the largest class of the sample as shown in Table 16 below, this followed by class age boundary of 35years to 44 years, this is also closely followed by the class age boundary of 55years to 64years. The class boundary of 25 years- 34years has lowest number of participants.

Table 16: Years of Experience as an SME Owner

Answer Choices	Responses
25-34	5
35-44	16
45-54	20
55-64	10
65+	9

The demographic data representing the number of employees in service sector SMEs is presented as follows; 45 of the participants had between 1 to 5 employees, 6 participants has between 5 to 10 employee, 5 participants had between 10 to 15 employees, 4 participants employed 20 employees or more employees.

The questionnaire prompted participants to participate in an interview or focus group which resulted in a selection pool of 60 participants.

4.4.3 Personality, Exchange of Knowledge and Relationships

The findings from the questionnaire in respect of personality, exchange of knowledge and quality relationships provide preliminary insight for interview and focus group discussion. The questionnaire prompted participants to rate their involvement in exchange of knowledge. Questions collected the self-perceptions of exchange of knowledge, the importance of knowledge exchange , frequency of engagement in

knowledge exchange , and methods of engagement. The responses provided detail insight into the knowledge exchange process of the participants. The following is general overview of the participants' responses.

The participants were asked to rate the frequency of receiving and using knowledge. Receiving and using knowledge from sources within the locality network has the highest ratings, sources of knowledge from within the industry's social network was rated second. A total of 17 participants make use of knowledge received from other owners of SMEs within the locality at a frequency of more than once a week.

In giving knowledge, participants were asked to rate the frequency at which others received and used knowledge from the participant. A frequency of once a month rated higher with 14 participants out of the 60 participants indicating that other owners of SMEs received and used knowledge shared by the participant. Frequency period of more than once a week was the second highest rated frequency with 11 out of 60 sharing knowledge within the community.

Trust rated high among the participants, Trust is measured based on a scale of strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, strongly agree and n/a. Having trust in the source of knowledge is ranked with 29 participants out of 60 participants agreed trust in the source of knowledge was important. The measure of strongly agree reflected 16 participants out of 60 participants strongly relied on trust when engaging in exchange of knowledge. When faced with a challenge, 25 participants strongly agreed and 19 agreed that they have a trusted individual to consult.

There are indications that some of the participants have preference for group few numbers of participants during knowledge exchange engagement, the fewer number of participants in the group made the engagement more personal and lively for the SME owners. The improvement in the engagement frequency made knowledge exchange more beneficial and successful.

From the survey, 21 participants from the total of 60 participants preferred a group size of 5 or less 15 participants are comfortable with a group size of between 6 participants to 10 participants, 6 participants

preferred group consisting of 20 participants or more. Knowledge Exchange process at the neighborhood level recorded smaller number of participants.

Knowledge Exchange activities were measured between engagements within the industry's social network at the neighborhood level. 17 participants expressed their preference for engagement in knowledge exchange activities within the neighborhood level, 17 participants agreed while 15 participants strongly agreed to participate in knowledge exchange within industry's social network at the neighborhood level, 23 participants agreed and 10 participants strongly agreed. The larger percentage of the relationship consummated during the knowledge exchange process were made at the neighborhood network level.

Information about the basic motivational incentives for engaging in knowledge exchange among owners of SMEs was obtained by asking the participants to rate the measures of knowledge exchange level of importance, by rating the process as important, as enjoyable, as helpful in cultivating quality relationships, as a means to display competency, as the builder of trust. The measures were scaled on strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, strongly agree and *n/a*. All measures resulted in at least 35 out of 60 participants strongly agreeing to the measure being a motivational factor except for displaying their level of competency to other participants. The highest rated motivation is that knowledge exchange is important with 34 participants strongly agreed. Only 22 participants believed knowledge exchange process is an opportunity to display competency among other SME owners.

The primary objective for participating in knowledge exchange process include for improved performance, development and acquisition of innovative idea to facilitates creation of improved products and better services, building of quality relationship, and to solve a specific operational or managerial problem. A total of 60 participants responded to the question, from the survey, most participants believed that the purpose of engaging in exchange of knowledge process is to build quality relationships. From the sample size of 60 participants, 42 participants strongly agreed and 17 agreed.

Some set of participants confirmed that the purpose of engaging in exchange of knowledge is for improved performance, this set of participants believed that participants engaged in the process to discover ways to improve performance within the SME's. A total of 30 participants strongly agreed and 17 participants agreed.

The participants were presented with six methods of participating in knowledge exchange . The question measured the frequency of using email, blogs, social media, online discussion forums, direct physical meetings, and online tele-conferencing. From the sample size of 60 participants, blogs was the least rated with 18 participants selecting not applicable (n/a), online discussion forums is rated next to blogs with 17 participants selecting n/a, daily usage of online teleconferencing is also rated with 15 participants selecting n/a, social media platform is rated with 14 participants selecting n/a, direct physical meeting on weekly basis recorded the highest ratings with 15 participants out of the sample size of 60 selecting n/a.

The Five Factor Model provided the measures for the personality traits of the participants. The questionnaire measured the participants' self -perceptions of extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and intellect/ imagination. The measures were scaled on strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, strongly agree, and n/a.

The baseline for extroversion was obtained by asking the participants to place their personal lifestyle on rating scale, the measure are based on being comfortable around other people, often starting conversations, not talking a lot, not like being the center of attention, and being quiet around strangers. The measure of the participants personal lifestyle revealed that 18 participants out of 60 participants neither agreed nor disagreed. Another 13 participants selected agreed and 5 strongly agreed in the rating.

Feeling comfortable around others is rated the highest among the participants. Out of the 60 participants, 26 agreed and 19 strongly agreed to being comfortable around other participants.

The measuring rating scale ranges from the lowest value of -12 to the maximum of +12, with -12 indicating an extreme introvert and +12 indicating an extreme extrovert. 9 participants recorded the score that ranges

between -4 to -1, 15 participants had a score that ranges between +1 to +8, 1 participant scored +10 and another participant score +11

To measure agreeableness, the participants rated their self-perceptions of being interested in other people, sympathizing with the feelings of others, taking time for others, not being interested in others, not being interested in other peoples' problems, and not feeling concern for others. The measures were scaled strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, strongly agree, and not applicable (n/a). The result of the survey revealed that out of 60 participants, 3 participants agreed not to be really interested in others SME's business, 2 participants agreed to not being interested in other peoples' business challenges, and only 1 participants strongly agreed to feeling little concern for others. The other participants selected either agree or strongly agree for being interested in others, sympathizing with the feelings of others, and taking time for others.

The range for the score totals for agreeableness ranged from -12 to +12, with -12 indicating an extreme introvert and 12 indicating an extreme extrovert. 1 participant had a score of -4, 2 participants had the score that ranges between +1 to +3, 7 participants scored between +6 to +9, 16 participants scored between +10 to +12 depicting high level of agreeableness.

The participants were asked to rate self-perceptions of being conscientious. The measures included being prepared, discharging responsibilities promptly, excited about taking order and directives, handling items carelessly, making mess of things, being forgetful and absent minded. The measures were scaled strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, strongly agree, and not applicable (n/a). The results of always being prepared shows that 27 participants out of the 60 participants agreed, 11 participants strongly agreed. The participants that agreed to possess the attribute of discharging responsibilities promptly are 17, 17 participants neither agreed nor disagreed. The measure in respect of being excited for taking order and directives indicated that 25 agreed to this attribute while 17 strongly agreed.

The range for the score totals for conscientiousness ranged from -12 to +12 with, -12 indicating an extreme introvert and +12 indicating an extreme extrovert. A total of 13 participants had the score that ranges between -4 to +2, 1 participant had the score of +4, 11 participants had the score that ranges between +6 to +11.

Emotional stability was measured through self-perceptions rating of being relaxed most of the time, seldom feeling bored, not easily bothered by things, worry about things, get upset easily, and get irritated easily. The measures were scaled strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree or disagree, agree, strongly agreed, and not applicable (n/a). The overall results indicated the 60 participants who responded to the self-perceptions rating gave conscientiousness high rating. The result revealed that 31 participants agreed to being relaxed most of the time, 25 participants agreed to seldom feeling bored, 10 participants strongly agreed to seldom feeling bored. The measure of I am not easily bothered by things revealed that 23 participants agreed and 10 participants neither agreed nor disagreed.

The range for the score totals for emotional stability ranged from -12 to +12, with -12 indicating an extreme introvert and +12 indicating scale rating depicting the case of an extreme extrovert. The score totals were fairly distributed within the range of -3 to 10 with 2 or 3 participants in each of the score bracket.

The final factor of personality traits measured is intellect or imagination. The factor was measured by having a clear imagination, quick to understand things, spending time to reflect on issues, not interested in abstract ideas, having difficulty in imagining things, and avoid complex people. The measures were scaled strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, strongly agree, and not applicable (n/a). For the survey, spending to reflect on issues had the highest rating in the participants' self-perceptions rate, 20 participants agreed and 26 participants strongly agree 32 participant 32 agreed and 14 strongly agreed to quick understanding things. 20 participants agreed and 19 participants strongly agreed to have a clear imagination.

The range for the score totals for intellect or imagination ranged from -12 to +12, with -12 indicating an extreme introvert and 12 indicating an extreme extrovert. From the survey, 8 participants had scores that

range between 0 to +5, 11 participants had scores between +6 to +9, and 7 participants had scores between +10 to +12.

4.4.4 Analysis of Interview Data: Thematic analysis

The last section of the results discusses the analysis of the interview and focus group data. The patterns of the participants' discussions were identified using a thematic analysis. The process included Yin's five phases of analysis to guide the analysis process. Interview session and focus group transcripts were coded, codes were organized, the organized codes were then summarized to develop the thematic network. The thematic network informed the participants' response to the research questions.

Inductive coding was used to initially assess the collected data, the coding process involved reading and re-reading the transcripts to discover the meanings of the codes (Saldana, 2016). Organizing the themes emerged through axial coding which identified relationships between the codes. The summarized organizing codes resulted in five overall themes emerged from the study forming the answers to the research questions. The organizing themes were grouped and summarized based on uniformities.

The five themes include engaging in knowledge exchange, participating in exchange of knowledge, factors of absorptive capacity, influence of the personality of the SME owner and building of quality relationships. The following sections present the details in respect of the development of the five overall themes.

4.4.4.1 Overall Theme 1: Exchange of Knowledge Engagement

The purpose of Research Question 1 is to examine the factors contributing to the success of Absorptive Capacity development for SMEs. Research Question 1 provided the framework to identify factors based on the SME owners' perception on the importance of engaging in exchange of knowledge towards the Absorptive Capacity development process. As presented in Appendix T, the overall theme of engaging in Absorptive Capacity development is comprised of two organizing themes which include the followings:

- 1) How does a service sector SME owner engage in exchange of knowledge for development of

absorptive capacity?

- 2) Motivational factors in knowledge exchange participation.

The organizing theme of how do the owners of SMEs engage in knowledge exchange also identified the participants' preferred methods of engaging in knowledge exchange towards Absorptive Capacity development. The organizing theme summarized two basic themes:

- 1) Direct physical participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development is preferred.
- 2) Professional organizations provide exchange of knowledge with specific goals.

The organizing theme for motivational factors that influence participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process is made up of the basic theme of the individual SME owners' personality. The personality of the SME owners is a major factor in motivating the individual SME owner to participate in the process. These basic themes provide the understanding through the experiences shared by the owners of the SME for engaging in exchange of knowledge towards Absorptive Capacity development.

How does owners SME owners engage in Exchange of Knowledge For Absorptive Capacity Development

One of the major factors that influence participation of service sector SME's participation in exchange of knowledge emerged from the interview sessions which involved the delivery method of knowledge exchange opportunities. Technology advancement has succeeded in providing added resources for connecting and networking with people. Podcasts, blogs, social media, and email make knowledge exchange more convenient and easy. In addition, a direct physical interaction is another potent method of engagement.

Direct Physical Participation in Knowledge Exchange is Preferred

The interview participants who preferred direct physical participation for exchange of knowledge opted for this method for numerous reasons. First, participant NA006I stated “. . . in attending webinars or video conferencing, it made me to be watching through my telephone set. Though engagement through direct physical participation difficult considering the schedule,” Direct physical participation creates a level of engagement with the activity that certain people need for the event to feel successful. Direct physical engagement in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development is far more than serving as a means of accountability in paying attention.

The level of engagement in external exchange of knowledge offered the SME owners the opportunity to connect on a personal level. The personal connection introduces the importance of cultivating quality relationships. The personal connections establish openness and trust, which enables the SME owners to seek external assistance within the industry’s social network at the neighborhood level. Question 2.4 of the interview guide (see Appendix J) required the participants to highlight the impacts of knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development. Participant tagged NB003I highlighted the impact of direct physical participation in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development as providing the opportunity to be in close contact with in similar situations and not being afraid to ask for help. Identifying how to move beyond barriers and discover success is important.

Professional organizations provide exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity Development with Specific Goals

The participants proposed knowledge exchange opportunities that focused on a specific goal and formally structured opportunity increase the perceived value of the opportunity. The groups and professional member organizations offer specific goals and topics; the structure of these processes provides the owners of service sector SME’s with confidence in the quality of knowledge to be exchanged thereby increasing the perceived

value. The participant tagged NB002I confirmed his participation in the process because it provides structure and consistent accountability among members of the group. Group Engagement of knowledge exchange requires the owners of SMEs to be intentional in actions. The participant tagged NB001I stated, "I've arranged an early morning telephone call to request the know the number of people present, I do this every time, so there is consistency. We do a daily call where we hold each other accountable." Technology aids the creation of consistency and intentionality.

Technological advancement provides another good method of engagement that add to the perceived value, consistency, and intentions for the owners of the SME's. The participants indicated technology provided the benefits of convenience and more exposure to sources of knowledge. Podcasts provided NS007I the ability to listen to the experts who would not be heard if the only option is direct physical participation. **NS004I stated, "We have seven locations right now... we get together once a month via Zoom."** Facebook and other social media platforms provided participant NS006I with faster responses to questions.

The opportunities to engage external knowledge development is abundant, owners of SMEs must be able to identify the method of engagement which best fit their current situation. The theme of engaging in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development partially provided the required answer to Research Question (RQ 1) by presenting the experience of individual owners of SMEs by identifying the sources of the knowledge to be exchanged. The identification of the source of the knowledge to be exchanged explained the first phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). The emphasis on the benefits of direct physical interaction further provided details answer to Research Question 1 as well as creating the foundation for Research Question 3 (RQ 3) with regards to building of quality relationships. Direct physical interaction is one of the methods being used in participating in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities. Participants elucidated on other methods used in participating in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process.

Motivational Factors To Participate In Exchange of Knowledge

Consideration is given to the personality of individual SME owners in respect of successful knowledge exchange for the development of Absorptive Capacity. The participants completed a self-evaluation of the major personality traits in the questionnaire. The interview questions provide detailed and reliable data in respect of the influence of personality of individual owners of SME's.

The influence of the participants' personalities are seen in the responses to interview question 3.2, which focused on participants' motivating factors for engaging in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities (see Appendix J). The responses indicated that the motivating factor for participating in exchange of knowledge is derived from having interest in other SME owners. The general theme in the participants sampling is presented in Table 17. Table 17 presents a common desire to help other owners of SMEs .

Table 17: Personality as a Motivational Factor

Participant	Response	Perception of Personality
NB004I	<p>“For example, in knowledge exchange, I have to remember to take a step back and let the other person run the meeting if it's their meeting.”</p>	Aggregable, interested in people, imaginative
NS003I	<p>“So, I'm not a crazy extrovert. I haven't yet gone on like Facebook live where I get nervous.”</p>	Doesn't talk a lot, sympathizes with others, likes structure, relaxed and imaginative
NS004I	<p>“I don't like people asking for me to get out of my little zone here with my little introvert environment”</p> <p>“But when it comes down to who I'm actually sharing or bringing into what I call the inner circle it's become very selective.”</p>	Quiet, sympathizes with others, likes structure
NS0010I	<p>“When I go to a conference, I don't work them the way I should because I'm intimidated even now when I'm older and experienced.”</p>	Comfortable around people, interested in people, and is reflective

The desire to help others presented a challenge for participants who exhibited an extroverted personality. The participant with code NA008I was identified as an extrovert with a score of 4 based on questionnaire result. The desire to help others compelled the participant to contribute meaningfully during the conversations. The participant is aware of this habit and during the interview session, the participant shared the need for being self-constraint as to not dominate a conversation. This participant's personality on the questionnaire was rated as being strongest in aggregable, interested in people, and imaginative. The imaginative nature and interest in people appear to be the compelling force for participant NB003I to have a dominant personality in Absorptive Capacity development activities. The need to help other owners of SMEs is also an essential attribute for participants that are not extrovert. For example, participant with code NB002I responded to the interview question with, ““So, I'm never an extreme extrovert. I prefer Facebook or other online network as against direct physical interaction.”

NB002I stated, ““However, when there is need to exchange capacity with other owners of SME, I am very selective in doing that, I prefer old allies”

Both individual participants identified as being owners of service sector SMEs directly relate with people who need help.

Personality has great influenced on exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development. This was reported by participants during the interview session. The responses received depicts that the desire to help other owners of SME's motivates both introverts and extroverts to participate in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities. Table 15 presents the results of the sampling of responses and perceptions of personality which demonstrates the findings. Interviews generated the responses. The questionnaire generated self-perceptions of the individual personality.

4.4.4.2 Overall theme 2: Participating in Knowledge Exchange

Participating in exchange of knowledge emerged as the second theme from the data collected. The data from the interview sessions discussion revealed the challenges and strategies of the SME owners in engaging in knowledge exchange. The responses provided insight as to what challenges and strategies the owners of the SME's employed in managing the business' operations by engaging in exchange of knowledge activities.

The thematic network for overall theme 2 is comprised of two organizing themes. The first organizing theme in respect of the challenges confronted by owners of SMEs in participating in knowledge exchange activities is summarized with the following basic themes:

- 1) Limited resources affect Absorptive Capacity development.
- 2) Relevancy of the Content
- 3) The individual's perceptions about the benefit for participation.

The organizing theme of strategies adopted for the improvement of participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities is made up of the following two basic themes:

- 1) Current Approach is influenced by Previous Experiences.
- 2) The knowledge exchange experience is improved by Socializing.

Challenges in participation in Knowledge Exchange

The challenges confronted by engaging in exchange of knowledge opportunities lower the Absorptive Capacity development of service sector SME owners. The challenges confronted by participating in external exchange of knowledge emerged as an organizing theme of the overall theme – participating in exchange of knowledge. The organizing theme is comprised of two basic themes which is made up of resources availability and content relevancy.

Limited resources hinder absorptive capacity

The challenges the participants highlighted include how limited resources affects Absorptive Capacity. Question 4.4 in the interview guide (see Appendix J) is fashioned out to elicit data and facts from the participants to identify an appropriate number of external exchange of knowledge opportunities to participate on monthly basis. The participants presented the influences on the frequency of participation.

Participants NA003I, NS003I, NA006I, and NB002I identified availability of time as one of the factor that affects participation in direct physical exchange of knowledge activities. Time is known to be a very scarce resource for owners of service sector SMEs. Participant with code NS003I reported that, “Yeah, I would probably like to participate more often; however, my work schedule is very tight. You know. My absence at work will affect the work rate, my employees require close monitoring and supervision for optimal performance.”

The technological advancement has helped in curtail the effects of inadequate time and the desire to engage in external exchange of knowledge activities. The preferred frequency of participation for participant with code NS003I is daily. The technological advancement encouraged participant with code NS003I to participate in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development through podcasts and other social media content to take advantage of engaging other owners of SMEs in exchange of knowledge. Another good method of external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development that encouraged higher frequency rate of engagement for participant with code NA003I is 5 minutes telephone call on daily basis. The participant with code NS003F reported that all the time in the day had been scheduled for business operation, therefore use of telecommunication technology become a valuable tool in external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development process.

The participant with NB002I revealed that time is major challenges that affect the frequency of participation. The participant is willing to participate in the exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities more than once a week. The time constraints of having a family and responsibilities at home

prevented more SME owners to participate frequently in external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities.

Time is reported to be the most important challenge affecting the frequency rate of participating in external knowledge exchange activities. The participant with code NB002I identified lack of local opportunity and inadequate time to travel in order to participate in programs as an important factor affecting frequency of participation. The participants with code NA006I in contrast to the position of participant with code NA005I reported that

“I, travel to participate in activities multiple times on a monthly basis with high expectation of acquiring innovative idea that will help in improving the operational performance of my business activities.”

Inadequate time is not the only challenges the technological advancement has helped curtail. The lack of office coverage presented a similar challenge, which participant with code NS003I has been able to identify. The lack of the ability to leave the business to attend direct physical exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities presented a challenge that affect the desire to participate. The participant NS005I noted that absence from the office, result in clients not being able to relate properly with the employees of the SME. The participant with code NS003I reported similar challenge that affect participation in knowledge exchange activities due to the demand created by operational needs. Technology provided an alternative method to engaging in external Absorptive Capacity development activities.

Relevancy of the Content

Another major challenge to participating in external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities extended beyond the availability of resources. The importance of knowledge exchange served as a factor in considering the allocation of adequate time for participation. The content quality serves as an incentive for engaging in knowledge exchange. Participant with code NA003I has over 20 years of experience; this revealed that participation in external knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development depends basically on the subject of discussion. Participant NA003I stated that: “If

you're going to develop a concept for group of SME owners, this require enormous background work and a lot of time had to be invested into it, you will have to take your time to understand the basic need of the group, the product or service before going ahead to announce you out to render assistance to other owners”

Knowledge exchange for the sake of engaging other SME owners did not motivate the participant to dedicate time to carry out the enormous background work required to identify and understand the need of the owners of SMEs within the industry’s social network. Participant with code NA003I concluded that the focus on revenue generation is rated the most important benefit of external knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development.

Individual SME Owners Perceptions on the Value of Participating in the Process

Participant with code NS004I presented a slightly distinct experience on the perception of SME owners about the benefits of engaging in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development. The participant (NS004I) reported his observations about individual SME owners’ lack of interest in engaging in the process as it relates to health and medical status of the participants. The reported observations by NS004I indicated apprehension of the participants as it relates to the quality of the of the information shared. The perceptions of the participants, according to the observation reported by NS04I, prevented the ability to be opened and transparent with the subject presented in the engagement. The responses of the participants established the influence of the perceived value of the subject presented in the knowledge exchange process.

The themes that emerge from the overall theme of participating in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development were classified into the challenges in participating in knowledge exchange process and the strategies to improve participation in the process. The participants’ responses provided details insights from the individual SME owners’ experiences, which provided additional information for Research Question 2 (RQ2). The data collected from the questionnaire helped in establishing a guideline for the interview responses by providing data which include years of experience in the SME business. The

demographic data helped in providing detail understanding of the participants' responses. The shared experiences are illustrated by the transition within Absorptive Capacity Theory by seeking knowledge which tends to improve the innovative ability within the SMEs.

Strategies to Improve Exchange of Knowledge Participation

Participant discussions provided two basic themes which identified strategies to improve participation in knowledge exchange process. The strategies provided insights as to why the participants participate in knowledge exchange activities more frequently than other SME owners. Previous experiences and socialization were the factors identified which influence participation in exchange of knowledge.

Prior Experiences Influence Current Approach

Previous experience about the process influence participation in future engagement, the results from the questionnaire indicated that 4 participants employed 5 employees or less. It was added that the time allocated for engaging in the process jeopardizes potential revenue of the SMEs. The quality and expected benefits of the knowledge exchange process must be able to motivate the SME owners' to participate. Participant with code NB002I provided insights into a previous experience of the participants as a motivator.

Knowledge exchange process have provided participant NB002I with social exposure by meeting other owners'. Participant NB002I indicated he made some consultation at the instance of the questionnaire. Participant NB002I main motive for participating in knowledge exchange is to afford him the opportunity to enlarge the list of his potential clients' base. NB002I reported that "I have been asked recently by many people about my membership of any business network group and the reasons of my membership, my response has always been that I'm a member of a great business network and there are great business opportunities for members, I'm there to learn."

The participation in knowledge exchange process improves based on previous experiences and the quality of the content being offered. The previous experiences for participating also improve the motivation for engaging in the process.

The Knowledge Exchange Experience Is Improved By Socializing

Establishment of quality relationships is also a motivating factor for the SME owners for engaging in external exchange of knowledge process. The process of digging deep into the details of Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity reveals dependence on trust and quality relationships in respect of the responses. Some sub-sector of service sector SMEs such as personal coaching and well-being, make use of Knowledge exchange events as primary method of operation.

Participant with code NS003I is a consultant who focuses on the client's overall well-being. Quality relationships bring about credibility. Without proven credibility, NS003I would not consider participating in any Knowledge exchange events. NS003I stated that, "sometimes I'm not bothered about participating in any of the process, at times I do participate. Majorly what move me into participating depend on my respect level for the individual and the quality of the supposed capacity to be exchange." Other service sector SME owners shared the same opinion.

Participant with code NA007I noted that "there are numerous cheat and opportunist in the industry, therefore, one really need to weigh the quality of the relationship one has within the industry's network" An established quality relationship helped in building credibility of the source of the capacity, which in turn motivates owners of service sector SMEs to participate in the Knowledge exchange process. Individual SME owners are motivated to participate in the Knowledge exchange process by different motivators.

4.4.4.3 Overall Theme 3: Knowledge Exchange factors of absorptive capacity.

Factors of absorptive capacity emerged as the third overall theme from the interview data. One of the organizing themes of Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity is that it impacts the growth of the business. The basic themes summarized by the organizing theme included:

- 1) Negative Knowledge exchange experiences hinder participation in knowledge exchange process.
- 2) Positive Knowledge exchange experiences helps in strengthening business performance and growth.

The codes which discussed the Knowledge exchange factors of absorptive capacity highlight the attempt of SME owners to absorb knowledge from external source.

Exchange of Knowledge Impacts the Business

Absorptive Capacity represents the participants' attempts to capitalize on external source of knowledge exchange. Interview and focus group participants presented the challenges confronting SME owners' in absorbing knowledge from external sources. The individual experience of SME owners' experience attempt to implement advice from other SME owners are confronted by varying levels of difficulty.

Negative Knowledge Exchange Experience Hinders Participation In Exchange of Knowledge

It is assumed that SME owners relied on internal source knowledge for their success. Participant with code NB003I reported the challenge in respect of the above mentioned assumption by stating that, "When I commenced the business newly, I was cheated at various times." NB003I commented most SMEs succeed as a result of the strong financial ability of the SME owners. The participant (NB003I) further submitted that the struggle to succeed in business affects the ability to trust knowledge from an external source.

Trusting the source of knowledge emerged as a code for participants, NS003I shared his experience about the knowledge he received from other female SME owner who intentionally offered bad advice on certain operational strategies. Participant with code NS010I reported similar experience in the first year of entering

into the business he maintained that competitors would intentionally offered wrong information to distract your smooth activities and potential sales. Participants (NB004I and NA007I) are very apprehensive in receiving knowledge which could help the business grow.

Misguided information is not always intentional; participant with NS003I shared the experience when he newly commenced business, the participant was not very certain about the quantity of material required to be ordered at the inception, the participant (NS003I) approached another SME owner in similar business to inquire about the material to be purchased, the advice provided mislead the participant into purchasing excess quantity of the material. The advice provided by the other SME owner was based on market location and personal experience of the adviser. Therefore, the misguided information on material quantity to purchase was not intentional; however, participant (NS003I) always exercises an apprehension on whose advice to be followed.

The personal experience of participant with code NS001I was similar but from a different perspective, the participant's (NS001I) response to the interview question brought attention to the need to be familiar with the relevant statutory regulations. The participant was asked to engage in exchange of knowledge around the topic of demographic data of clients. Participant NS001I noted that demographic data within the financial industry cannot be shared by the lender, the statutory regulations restricted the finance practitioners from exchanging knowledge in respect of their client's activities, this in turn restricted participation in the Knowledge exchange opportunities for participant NS001I.

Positive Knowledge Exchange Experience Helps In Strengthening Operation

Another barrier to absorptive capacity for participants is lack of proper understanding. Participant with code NA003I identified that technology is another great challenge to proper understanding and implementation of Knowledge. The primary focus of the business is computer and scientific equipment consulting but the implementation of the technology required to stay competitive in the industry presents different challenge. The participant (NA003I) revealed that, "I have been able to discover that I needed some level of education

on new trend in market, I need to sharpen my marketing skill. The current trend is quite different with what I am used to". The technology presented challenges due to its impacts on the society.

Lack of resources is a broader category of codes that represented challenges in absorptive capacity for the participants. Previous themes highlighted the importance of inadequate time for some owners of SMEs as result of busy work schedule. Time is an essential resource which hindered participant NS007I from learning more about streamlining technology idea to fit into current operational requirements. The participant stated that, "allocating the time to learn the new technology in order to be in tune with the current trend that fit into today operational system and to follow the operation flowchart seamlessly." The decision to pursue the learning of new technology resulted in fulfilling obligations of the day to day operations.

Two participants emphasized that lack of capital is a challenge to absorb knowledge fully. Participant with code NS003I presented a unique situation by stating that, " the main challenge in starting up as SME owner is the lack of investment, also I'm not very good in social networking, I have this great business idea that need funding to take off." The responses to the questionnaire by this participant reflect a more introverted creative personality.

NB002I presented two challenges to absorptive capacity, the first challenge highlighted by participant NB002I is the lack of capital to effectively implement strategies gained from external knowledge. The other challenge is the apprehension in engaging in building quality relationships that can help source for adequate capital.

Participant with code NS011I expressed similar experience in respect of lack of adequate capital for effective commencement and take-off of the SME business operation. Lack of adequate capital prevented the participant from being able to pay for an office space for the business take-off, thereby using a section of the home as take off point. Making use of the home location presented an additional challenge in attracting high net-worth clients for the business, paucity of fund also affected the purchase and acquisition marketing tools and devices to enhance sales and revenue generation.

The coded segments highlighted above reflect that Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development has both positive and negative impacts on businesses. The ability of the SMEs to absorb knowledge depends on numerous factors. The participants identified trust, lack of resources, poor marketing, the pressure to succeed, and mis-information or ill-advice as factors that personally influenced the ability to absorb and capitalize on the knowledge. Building of quality relationships with other owners of SME's created positive experiences in Knowledge exchange for participants NS0011I and NS0014I.

4.4.4.4 Overall Theme 4: Quality Relationship As A Factor For Absorptive Capacity Development

The quality and reliable data collected from the participants helped in identifying the transition of Knowledge exchange through the phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory with serious emphasis on the impact of quality relationships. The organizing theme for this theme is made up of the role of quality relationships in absorptive capacity development. The basic themes summarized by the organizing theme included:

- 1) Established Relationships influence engagement in Knowledge exchange activities.
- 2) Knowledge Exchange obstacles are reduced by relationships established intentionally.
- 3) A mentor is an important resource for every SME owner.
- 4) Mentees should also try as much as possible to provide mentorship for others.

Previous discussion of the report has highlighted ways in which quality relationships influenced other factors of Knowledge exchange and Absorptive Capacity Theory. The discussion of coding will begin the transition from the theoretical framework of ACT to the theoretical framework of SET.

Established Quality Relationships Affects Participation In Knowledge Exchange Opportunities

SET was evident in the participants' responses. Question 6.6 in the interview guideline (see Appendix J) requires the participants to share personal perceptions about the importance of quality relationships for engaging in Knowledge exchange opportunities. Participant with code NB003I best presented his the

sentiment by stating that, “building quality relationship has assisted thus far.” The revelations of NS004I and NS005I confirmed that quality relationship is very essential in order to have trust on the shared knowledge.

NA004I expressed similar view regarding the importance of trust and quality relationships when engaging in Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity. The experience of individual owners of the SME’s placed participant NA004I in a position where information is fact-checked where relationship is not existence. The non-existence of quality relationship resulted into lack of trust in exchanged knowledge.

The interview question highlighted another interesting factor that influenced building of quality relationships. The established relationships influenced participation in Knowledge exchange. The influence of credible relationship brings about the desire to participate in the process. In the interview, participant NS007I shared his experience in respect of a specific relationship with other SME owners. The response included the statement, “I know him personally,. I know his character. So anytime I get a chance to participate in a program with him, I do not hesitate.” The established relationship served as a major factor for NS007I to participate in Knowledge exchange process. The relationship is criteria to determine the importance of the opportunity. The influence of qualityrelationships presented a slightly different perception for participant 006I.

Knowledge Exchange Obstacles Are Reduced By Relationships Established Intentionally

Building quality relationships with other SME owners within the industry’s social network helped in reducing the challenges of the knowledge exchange process. Participant NA006I explained during the interview session his relationship with another SME owners who are married couple in the network. The network attached high values to personal development and self-improvement. The influence of quality relationship motivated participant NS007I to change his perception about Knowledge exchange engagement. Participants NS007I stated that:

“initially when I started participating in capacity development program, training and others, at times I left very disappointed and plan to quit the idea. The idea of quitting made some members of the network to be unhappy because the attached high value to the process, therefore I quit the idea of quitting. So, your peers, your coach, or your partners can encourage you about participating in a program if they value it so greatly, this will ensure benefitted from the process. Then when you want to get lazy, they push through.”

The responses of the participants confirmed that the influence of quality relationships can motivate individual SME owners to make personal changes. The personal changes bring about attitudinal change which helps in bringing clarity in focus for decision making.

Mentorship is an Important Resource for Every SME’s Owner

Relationships with other SME owners were a common theme among the participants in the research study. The importance of quality relationships was aggregated by participant NA002I who stated that, “relationship means mean so much to me when it comes Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process, I have my trust on few owners of the SME, believe me I seldom to ask questions or raised queries.” One specific relationship discussed in the interview was a mentor/ mentee relationship between SME owners.

A mentor/ mentee relationship established a professional relationship that helped certain participants to engage in external exchange of knowledge successfully. Participants shared experiences from the views of the mentor/mentee relationship. The basic motivation factor for being a mentor for participant NB003I is to encourage individuals who are struggling with their business. Awareness of other owners of SMEs served as a motivator for participant NB003I to be available to participate in exchange of knowledge with other SME owners that are confronting serious challenges in their business activities. The awareness of others served as a motivator for participant NA007I, who stated that, “I’m good at either perceiving that there is a challenge or just seeing that there is an opportunity to improve on a system.” Other participants gave more formal approaches to mentoring.

The more formal approaches presented specific types of knowledge exchanged with the mentee. The type of knowledge participant NB002I shared with the mentee relates to managerial skills. Participant NS0010I mentored owners of SME on brand imaging. Participant NA007I focused on marketing strategies for mentoring purpose. Helping other owner of the SME to build self-confidence is a subject that participant NB003I will like to coach as a mentor.

Mentees Should Also Try as Much as Possible to Provide Mentorship for Others

The interview session discussions that evolved into mentoring occurred organically. Mentoring and being a mentee created detail definition of the role of the Social Exchange Theory within the process of Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity. Participant NA002I set the tone for the subject of being a mentee by stating that, “Nobody is island of knowledge, if you're trying to do it alone, you're setting yourself up for failure.” Participant NS007I recommends that one of the first necessary actions that should be taken by a new owner of SME is to appoint a good business coach and a good accountant. Both provide the guidance in establishing a solid foundation for the new business to grow. Strategically engaging others is important first step.

The need for a good coach kept participant NS0010I from succeeding in business. During the interview, participant NS0010I shared the experience of struggling with the initial start-up capital required for the business. The participant had little experience in starting a business or in getting the required help. Participant NS0010I registered for a marketing seminar offered by a community organization where she met other SME owners with experience in the same line of business operations. The quality relationship evolved into the new acquaintance being a coach for NS010I. The coach advised participant NS010I to make strategic changes in pricing and the services being rendered, this bring about improved performance and success of her business.

The group was asked to share advice to new SME owners in respect of mentor/mentee relationships. Participant NA009I provided advice, “Never be afraid to ask questions.” Participant NS0012I, a SME

business coach, stated that, “I would just say be opened, be receptive to new idea.” Mentoring provides SME owners with the opportunity to learn from the experience of other SME owners.

Theme 4, quality relationship as a contributive factor for absorptive capacity development, this provided the required answer to Research Question 3. The factors discussed in this section identify challenges that are confronted by SME owners in the phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory. The discussions, which presented quality and reliable data that transitioned to the thematic analysis from Absorptive Capacity Theory into Social Exchange Theory. The influence of quality relationships became apparent in the open-ended discussion of the participants.

4.4.4.5 Overall theme 5: Relationship Building

The discussions led into strategies adopted for the cultivation of quality relationships for SME owners. The reliable data provided by the participants strengthened the theoretical framework of the Social Exchange Theory. This overall theme summarized the organizing theme methods used to build quality relationships. The organizing theme emerged from the following three basic themes:

- 1) Being consistent in meeting SME owners who share common goals and values.
- 2) Trust is the end result of established quality relationships and improves the development of Absorptive Capacity.
- 3) Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person.

Consistency in Meeting People who Share Common Goals and Values

A simple statement generalized the response of the interview sessions; this provides an answer in respect of the questions on how to build quality relationships. This is simplified by stating that, being intentional in getting to know the other person on a personal level cultivated strong and quality relationships. The experience shared by individual SME owners conveyed the message.

Consistency in meeting SME owners that share common goals and values intentionality emerged as an important strategy used among the participants in terms of strategies to cultivate quality relationships. It should be noted that most of the SME owners who participated in the research recognized time as a scarce resource, the cultivation of quality relationships required the participants to be desirable in reaching out to other SME owners.

Many of the participants stated the need to meet outside of the business in an informal and casual setting. Participants like NS005I and NS007I, stated that an activity as simple as meeting for coffee or going out to lunch play a major role in establishing quality relationships.

Trust is The Result of Established Credible Relationships to Enhance the Knowledge

Another strategy identified by participants includes reciprocation of business. Participant NA003I established credible relationships by sending referrals to other SME owners. Participant NS001I actively engage with other SME owners within the local community. Participant NS001I will pay a little more to a local SME owner to cultivate credible relationships, as against engaging with chain retail provider. The reciprocation established loyalty which in turn helped in building trust between the SME owners. The improved trust helped in the development of Absorptive Capacity for the SME owners in respect of benefits of the process.

Relationships are Best Cultivated by Showing Interest in the Other Person

The third strategy that emerged from the interview session is the volunteering in the local community. Participant NS007I used volunteering in the community as a way for the community to get to know his team. Volunteering provided the community with extra help to meet a need as well as extra help in establishing an identity with other SME owners who volunteered. The volunteer work demonstrated by participant NS007I social responsibility to the community. The activity increased participant NS007I brand awareness within the

community and among other SME owners. The act of reciprocating business and meeting for coffee or lunch is not enough.

Participant NS007I shared, “My philosophy about the other owners of SME’s is authenticity” According to participant NS009I, authenticity occurs by sitting and getting to know the other person. Participant NS009I revealed that getting to know the other person helped in identifying how to help the person to be better. Understanding the person helped in understanding the personality. Participant NS009I stated that, “Because, as I take my time to understand more about the personality of the people I'm working with, that creates that quality relationship.” Quality relationships provide better support for each other without being offensive.

The value of quality relationships goes unrealized until an actual time of need. Participant NB001I shared a very personal experience in the interview which illustrates the impact of cultivating quality relationships. Participant NB001I revealed that at the inception of the business and going head-to-head with the large business corporations. Relationships were cultivated with local competitors who were small business owners to create competition against the large corporations.

The increase in business for the competitors resulted in an increase in business for participant NB001I. Later in the year later, the participant experienced a personal tragedy, the Small business owners, with whom participant NB001I had cultivated relationships came together to help the business continue operations. Friendships superseded the fear of competition which helped participant NB001I keep the business opened to SME owners within the local community.

The theme for building quality relationships illustrated strategies to improve absorptive capacity for the SME owners. Cultivating strong relationships requires intentional acts to know the other person authentically. The time invested in cultivating relationships could potentially pay big dividends in a time of need and hardship. The discussions and the experience shared by individual SME owner strongly demonstrated Social Exchange Theory. The quality and reliable data gathered from the interview sessions provided greater understanding of Research Question 3.

4.4.4.6 Overall theme 6: Influences of the SME Owner's Personality

The influence of the individual SME owner's personality toward the approaches to exchange of knowledge and credible relationships were very clear in the responses of the participants. The influences of the SME owners' personality emerged as the sixth overall theme. The type of personality that influences quality relationships and exchange of knowledge served as the organizing theme. The basic theme from the coded text is individual SME owners' personality influences how easily quality relationships are built and nurtured.

Personality Type Influences How Relationships are Built and Nurtured

Relationship is a powerful two way strategy for SME owners. However, not all participants attach the same importance to quality relationships. Participant NB002I's responses illustrated the influence of personality on cultivating quality relationships. The self-perception of the individual SME owner on personality was confirmed by the response provided by participant NB002I on the questionnaire. Participant NB002I self-identified as an introvert with a score of 3 (see Appendix W). The response to interview question 6.2 (see Appendix J) revealed that participant NB002I avoids social network and building relationships due to being "really uncomfortable." Participant NB002I further stated that, "I hardly ask for help because I hate that idea." The participant described the state of the business at the time of the interview as very critical and requires capital for corporate restructuring and business re-launch. The problem of being an introvert has prevented participant NB002I from intentionally engaging in building quality relationships.

Participant NB002I avoid participating in knowledge exchange and relationships, therefore not having access to the benefits. Participant NS004I, who also self-identified as an introvert with a score of 6, explained the approach adopted for engaging in exchange of knowledge for absorptive capacity process (see Appendix W). The initial approach was to "stand in the corner and ponder on, 'Who do I talk to?'" Participant NS004I did not allow his personality to stop him from engaging in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process compared to NB002I. The participant set personal goals to meet other SME owners at knowledge exchange programs.

The approaches for exchange of knowledge for participants with similar personalities as participant NS004I were analogous. Participant NS004I said he will “attend conferences and meetings, other knowledge exchange events but will stand far off to the side due to the fact he is feeling being intimidated.” The participant shared how the feelings of introversion hindered his participation in the knowledge exchange process. Participant NS004I also stated that, “Despite feeling intimidated, I always try as much as possible to participate so as to benefit from the program, therefore I considered it useful for me.” Participant NA002I avoids establishing relationships with individuals who were not authentic.

The extroverted participants portrayed a different approach towards the exchange of knowledge. Participant NB003I stated that, “In knowledge exchange, I have always step backward and let the other person preside over the meeting if it's their meeting.” The extroverted personalities represented in the study explained always willing to seek help at all time.

The participant’s personality influenced building of quality relationships. Participating NS010I builds relationships with only selected group of people. Participant NS010I preferred approach for engaging in Knowledge exchange is a reserved one which revealed how the participant builds quality relationships. In contrast to participant NS004I, other extroverted participants pursued opportunities to build and nurture relationships. The desire to help other people motivates participant NS006I to cultivate quality relationships. The participants’ personalities influenced Knowledge exchange and building of quality relationships in similar ways.

The quality and reliable data collected in this study revealed common code of trust. Trust is the end result of building quality relationships. Trust is the factor that added value to Knowledge exchange experiences. Participant NS003I place premium on advice received from established relationships far above advice from strangers. According to participant NS007I, business is not simply business – business is relationships. Relationships and trust mean everything to participant NA003I who questions the motives of strangers. Participant like NB003I, need high level of trust to be opened and share freely. Cultivating quality

relationships with local SME owners resulted in trust which allowed NB002I to receive help with operations during the time of need.

The influences of the SME owner's personality strongly illustrated Social Exchange Theory (SET).

The quality and reliable data revealed that even when the success level of the SME is also an important factor, the SME owner's personality still have some level of influence on the approach for cultivating quality relationships. Certain types of personality cultivate quality relationships and engage in Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development more easily than other personality types. Trust is an essential factor that strengthened intentional acts of cultivating quality relationships.

4.4.5 Analysis of Focus Group Data: Thematic analysis

This section of the results discusses the analysis of the focus group data. The patterns of the participants' discussions were identified using a thematic analysis. The process included Yin's five phases of analysis to guide the analysis process. The focus group session transcripts were coded, codes were organized, the organized codes were then summarized to develop the thematic network. The thematic network informed the participants' response to the research questions.

Inductive coding was used to initially assess the collected data, the coding process involved reading and re-reading the transcripts to discover the meanings of the codes (Saldana, 2016). Organizing the themes emerged through axial coding which identified relationships between the codes. The summarized organizing codes resulted in five overall themes emerged from the study forming the answers to the research questions. The organizing themes were grouped and summarized based on uniformities.

The five themes include engaging in knowledge exchange, participating in exchange of knowledge, factors of absorptive capacity, influence of the personality of the SME owner and building of quality relationships. The following sections present the details in respect of the development of the five overall themes.

4.4.5.1 Overall Theme 1: Exchange of Knowledge Engagement

The purpose of Research Question 1 is to examine the factors contributing to the success of Absorptive Capacity development for SMEs. Research Question 1 provided the framework to identify factors based on the SME owners' perception on the importance of engaging in exchange of knowledge towards the Absorptive Capacity development process. As presented in Appendix T, the overall theme of engaging in Absorptive Capacity development is comprised of two organizing themes which include the followings:

- 1) How does a service sector SME owner engage in exchange of knowledge for development of absorptive capacity?
- 2) Motivational factors in knowledge exchange participation.

The organizing theme of how do the owners of SMEs engage in knowledge exchange also identified the participants' preferred methods of engaging in knowledge exchange towards Absorptive Capacity development. The organizing theme summarized two basic themes:

- 1) Direct physical participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development is preferred.
- 2) Professional organizations provide exchange of knowledge with specific goals.

The organizing theme for motivational factors that influence participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process is made up of the basic theme of the individual SME owners' personality. The personality of the SME owners is a major factor in motivating the individual SME owner to participate in the process. These basic themes provide the understanding through the experiences shared by the owners of the SME for engaging in exchange of knowledge towards Absorptive Capacity development.

How does owners SME owners engage in Exchange of Knowledge For Absorptive Capacity Development

One of the major factors that influence participation of service sector SME's participation in exchange of knowledge emerged from the interview sessions which involved the delivery method of knowledge exchange opportunities. Technology advancement has succeeded in providing added resources for connecting and networking with people. Podcasts, blogs, social media, and email make knowledge exchange more convenient and easy. In addition, a direct physical interaction is another potent method of engagement.

Direct Physical Participation in Knowledge Exchange is Preferred

Direct physical participation creates a level of engagement with the activity that certain people need for the event to feel successful. Direct physical engagement in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development is far more than serving as a means of accountability in paying attention.

The level of engagement in external exchange of knowledge offered the SME owners the opportunity to connect on a personal level. The personal connection introduces the importance of cultivating quality relationships. The personal connections establish openness and trust, which enables the SME owners to seek external assistance within the industry's social network at the neighborhood level. Participant tagged NB003F highlighted the impact of direct physical participation in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development as providing the opportunity to be in close contact with in similar situations and not being afraid to ask for help. Identifying how to move beyond barriers and discover success is important.

Professional organizations provide exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity Development with Specific Goals

The participants proposed knowledge exchange opportunities that focused on a specific goal and formally structured opportunity increase the perceived value of the opportunity. The groups and professional member organizations offer specific goals and topics; the structure of these processes provides the owners of service

sector SME's with confidence in the quality of knowledge to be exchanged thereby increasing the perceived value. The participant tagged NB002F confirmed his participation in the process because it provides structure and consistent accountability among members of the group. Group Engagement of knowledge exchange requires the owners of SMEs to be intentional in actions.

Technological advancement provides another good method of engagement that add to the perceived value, consistency, and intentions for the owners of the SME's. The participants indicated technology provided the benefits of convenience and more exposure to sources of knowledge. Podcasts provided NS007F the ability to listen to the experts who would not be heard if the only option is direct physical participation. **NS004F stated, "We have seven locations right now... we get together once a month via Zoom."** Facebook and other social media platforms provided participant NS006I with faster responses to questions.

The opportunities to engage external knowledge development is abundant, owners of SMEs must be able to identify the method of engagement which best fit their current situation. The theme of engaging in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development partially provided the required answer to Research Question (RQ 1) by presenting the experience of individual owners of SMEs by identifying the sources of the knowledge to be exchanged. The identification of the source of the knowledge to be exchanged explained the first phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). The emphasis on the benefits of direct physical interaction further provided details answer to Research Question 1 as well as creating the foundation for Research Question 3 (RQ 3) with regards to building of quality relationships. Direct physical interaction is one of the methods being used in participating in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities. Participants elucidated on other methods used in participating in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process.

Motivational Factors To Participate In Exchange of Knowledge

Consideration is given to the personality of individual SME owners in respect of successful knowledge exchange for the development of Absorptive Capacity. The participants completed a self-evaluation of the

major personality traits in the questionnaire. The focus group questions provide detailed and reliable data in respect of the influence of personality of individual owners of SME's.

The influence of the participants' personalities are seen in the responses to focus group questions which focused on participants' motivating factors for engaging in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities. The responses indicated that the motivating factor for participating in exchange of knowledge is derived from having interest in other SME owners.

The desire to help others presented a challenge for participants who exhibited an extroverted personality. The participant with code NA008F was identified as an extrovert with a score of 4 based on questionnaire results. The desire to help others compelled the participant to contribute meaningfully during the conversations. The participant is aware of this habit and during the group session, the participant shared the need for being self-constraint as to not dominate a conversation. This participant's personality on the questionnaire was rated as being strongest in aggregable, interested in people, and imaginative. The imaginative nature and interest in people appear to be the compelling force for participant NB003F to have a dominant personality in Absorptive Capacity development activities. The need to help other owners of SMEs is also an essential attribute for participants that are not extrovert. For example, participant with code NB002I responded to the interview question with, ““So, I'm never an extreme extrovert. I prefer Facebook or other online network as against direct physical interaction.”

NB002F stated, ““However, when there is need to exchange capacity with other owners of SME, I am very selective in doing that, I prefer old allies”

Both individual participants identified as being owners of service sector SMEs directly relate with people who need help.

Personality has great influenced on exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development. This was reported by participants during the interview session. The responses received depicts that the desire to help

other owners of SME's motivates both introverts and extroverts to participate in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities.

4.4.5.2 Overall theme 2: Participating in Knowledge Exchange

Participating in exchange of knowledge emerged as the second theme from the data collected. The data from the focus group discussion revealed the challenges and strategies of the SME owners in engaging in knowledge exchange. The responses provided insight as to what challenges and strategies the owners of the SME's employed in managing the business' operations by engaging in exchange of knowledge activities.

The thematic network for overall theme 2 is comprised of two organizing themes. The first organizing theme in respect of the challenges confronted by owners of SMEs in participating in knowledge exchange activities is summarized with the following basic themes:

- 1) Limited resources affect Absorptive Capacity development.
- 2) Relevancy of the Content
- 3) The individual's perceptions about the benefit for participation.

The organizing theme of strategies adopted for the improvement of participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities is made up of the following two basic themes:

- 1) Current Approach is influenced by Previous Experiences.
- 2) The knowledge exchange experience is improved by Socializing.

Challenges in participation in Knowledge Exchange

The challenges confronted by engaging in exchange of knowledge opportunities lower the Absorptive Capacity development of service sector SME owners. The challenges confronted by participating in external exchange of knowledge emerged as an organizing theme of the overall theme – participating in exchange of knowledge. The organizing theme is comprised of two basic themes which is made up of resources availability and content relevancy.

Limited resources hinder absorptive capacity

The challenges the participants highlighted include how limited resources affects Absorptive Capacity.

Participants NA003F and NS003F identified availability of time as one of the factor that affects participation in direct physical exchange of knowledge activities. Time is known to be a very scarce resource for owners of service sector SMEs. Participant with code NS003F reported that, “Yeah, I would probably like to participate more often; however, my work schedule is very tight. You know. My absence at work will affect the work rate, my employees require close monitoring and supervision for optimal performance.”

The technological advancement has helped in curtail the effects of inadequate time and the desire to engage in external exchange of knowledge activities. The preferred frequency of participation for participant with code NS003F is daily. The technological advancement encouraged participant with code NS003F to participate in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development through podcasts and other social media content to take advantage of engaging other owners of SMEs in exchange of knowledge. Another good method of external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development that encouraged higher frequency rate of engagement for participant with code NA003F is 5 minutes telephone call on daily basis. The participant with code NS003F reported that all the time in the day had been scheduled for business operation, therefore use of telecommunication technology become a valuable tool in external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development process..”

Inadequate time is not the only challenges the technological advancement has helped curtail. The lack of office coverage presented a similar challenge, which participant with code NS003F has been able to identify. The lack of the ability to leave the business to attend direct physical exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities presented a challenge that affect the desire to participate. Technology provided an alternative method to engaging in external Absorptive Capacity development activities.

Relevancy of the Content

Another major challenge to participating in external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities extended beyond the availability of resources. The importance of knowledge exchange served as a factor in considering the allocation of adequate time for participation. The content quality serves as an incentive for engaging in knowledge exchange. Participant NA003F stated that: “If you're going to develop a concept for group of SME owners, this require enormous background work and a lot of time had to be invested into it, you will have to take your time to understand the basic need of the group, the product or service before going ahead to announce you out to render assistance to other owners”

Knowledge exchange for the sake of engaging other SME owners did not motivate the participant to dedicate time to carry out the enormous background work required to identify and understand the need of the owners of SMEs within the industry's social network. Participant with code NA003F concluded that the focus on revenue generation is rated the most important benefit of external knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development.

Individual SME Owners Perceptions on the Value of Participating in the Process

Participant with code NS004F presented a slightly distinct experience on the perception of SME owners about the benefits of engaging in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development. The participant (NS004F) reported his observations about individual SME owners' lack of interest in engaging in the process as it relates to health and medical status of the participants. The reported observations by NS004F indicated apprehension of the participants as it relates to the quality of the of the information shared. The perceptions of the participants, according to the observation reported by NS004F, prevented the ability to be opened and transparent with the subject presented in the engagement. The responses of the participants established the influence of the perceived value of the subject presented in the knowledge exchange process.

The themes that emerge from the overall theme of participating in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development were classified into the challenges in participating in knowledge exchange process and the strategies to improve participation in the process. The participants' responses provided details insights from the individual SME owners' experiences, which provided additional information for Research Question 2 (RQ2). The data collected from the questionnaire helped in establishing a guideline for the focus group responses by providing data which include years of experience in the SME business. The demographic data helped in providing detail understanding of the participants' responses. The shared experiences are illustrated by the transition within Absorptive Capacity Theory by seeking knowledge which tends to improve the innovative ability within the SMEs.

Strategies to Improve Exchange of Knowledge Participation

Participant discussions provided two basic themes which identified strategies to improve participation in knowledge exchange process. The strategies provided insights as to why the participants participate in knowledge exchange activities more frequently than other SME owners. Previous experiences and socialization were the factors identified which influence participation in exchange of knowledge.

Prior Experiences Influence Current Approach

Previous experience about the process influence participation in future engagement, the results from the questionnaire indicated that 4 participants employed 5 employees or less. It was added that the time allocated for engaging in the process jeopardizes potential revenue of the SMEs. The quality and expected benefits of the knowledge exchange process must be able to motivate the SME owners' to participate. Participant with code NB002F provided insights into a previous experience of the participants as a motivator.

Knowledge exchange process have provided participant NB002F with social exposure by meeting other owners'. Participant NB002F indicated he made some consultation at the instance of the questionnaire. Participant NB002F main motive for participating in knowledge exchange is to afford him the opportunity to enlarge the list of his potential clients' base. NB002F reported that "I have been asked recently by many

people about my membership of any business network group and the reasons of my membership, my response has always been that I'm a member of a great business network and there are great business opportunities for members, I'm there to learn.”

The participation in knowledge exchange process improves based on previous experiences and the quality of the content being offered. The previous experiences for participating also improve the motivation for engaging in the process.

The Knowledge Exchange Experience Is Improved By Socializing

Establishment of quality relationships is also a motivating factor for the SME owners for engaging in external exchange of knowledge process. The process of digging deep into the details of Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity reveals dependence on trust and quality relationships in respect of the responses. Some sub-sector of service sector SMEs such as personal coaching and well- being, make use of Knowledge exchange events as primary method of operation.

Participant with code NS003F is a consultant who focuses on the client’s overall well-being. Quality relationships bring about credibility. Without proven credibility, NS003F would not consider participating in any Knowledge exchange events. NS003F stated that, “sometimes I’m not bothered about participating in any of the process, at times I do participate. Majorly what move me into participating depend on my respect level for the individual and the quality of the supposed capacity to be exchange.” Other service sector SME owners shared the same opinion.

4.4.5.3 Overall Theme 3: Knowledge Exchange factors of absorptive capacity.

Factors of absorptive capacity emerged as the third overall theme from the focus group data. One of the organizing themes of Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity is that it impacts the growth of the business. The basic themes summarized by the organizing theme included:

- 1) Negative Knowledge exchange experiences hinder participation in knowledge exchange process.
- 2) Positive Knowledge exchange experiences helps in strengthening business performance and growth.

The codes which discussed the Knowledge exchange factors of absorptive capacity highlight the attempt of SME owners to absorb knowledge from external source.

Exchange of Knowledge Impacts the Business

Absorptive Capacity represents the participants' attempts to capitalize on external source of knowledge exchange. Interview participants presented the challenges confronting SME owners' in absorbing knowledge from external sources. The individual experience of SME owners' experience attempt to implement advice from other SME owners are confronted by varying levels of difficulty.

Negative Knowledge Exchange Experience Hinders Participation In Exchange of Knowledge

It is assumed that SME owners relied on internal source knowledge for their success. Participant with code NB003F reported the challenge in respect of the above mentioned assumption by stating that, "When I commenced the business newly, I was cheated at various times." NB003F commented most SMEs succeed as a result of the strong financial ability of the SME owners. The participant (NB003F) further submitted that the struggle to succeed in business affects the ability to trust knowledge from an external source.

Trusting the source of knowledge emerged as a code for participants, NS003F shared his experience about the knowledge he received from other female SME owner who intentionally offered bad advice on certain operational strategies.

Positive Knowledge Exchange Experience Helps In Strengthening Operation

Another barrier to absorptive capacity for participants is lack of proper understanding. Participant with code NA003F identified that technology is another great challenge to proper understanding and implementation of Knowledge. The primary focus of the business is computer and scientific equipment consulting but the implementation of the technology required to stay competitive in the industry presents different challenge.

Lack of resources is a broader category of codes that represented challenges in absorptive capacity for the participants. Previous themes highlighted the importance of inadequate time for some owners of SMEs as result of busy work schedule. Time is an essential resource which hindered participant NB005F from learning more about streamlining technology idea to fit into current operational requirements. The participant stated that, “allocating the time to learn the new technology in order to be in tune with the current trend that fit into today operational system and to follow the operation flowchart seamlessly.” The decision to pursue the learning of new technology resulted in fulfilling obligations of the day to day operations.

Two participants emphasized that lack of capital is a challenge to absorb knowledge fully. Participant with code NS003F presented a unique situation by stating that, “ the main challenge in starting up as SME owner is the lack of investment, also I'm not very good in social networking, I have this great business idea that need funding to take off.” The responses to the questionnaire by this participant reflect a more introverted creative personality.

4.4.5.4 Overall Theme 4: Quality Relationship As A Factor For Absorptive Capacity Development

The quality and reliable data collected from the participants helped in identifying the transition of Knowledge exchange through the phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory with serious emphasis on the impact of quality relationships. The organizing theme for this theme is made up of the role of quality relationships in absorptive capacity development. The basic themes summarized by the organizing theme included:

- 1) Established Relationships influence engagement in Knowledge exchange activities.
- 2) Knowledge Exchange obstacles are reduced by relationships established intentionally.
- 3) A mentor is an important resource for every SME owner.
- 4) Mentees should also try as much as possible to provide mentorship for others.

Previous discussion of the report has highlighted ways in which quality relationships influenced other factors of Knowledge exchange and Absorptive Capacity Theory. The discussion of coding will begin the transition from the theoretical framework of ACT to the theoretical framework of SET.

Established Quality Relationships Affects Participation In Knowledge Exchange Opportunities

SET was evident in the participants' responses. The focus group discussions requires the participants to share personal perceptions about the importance of quality relationships for engaging in Knowledge exchange opportunities. Participant with code NB003F best presented his the sentiment by stating that, "building quality relationship has assisted thus far." The revelations of NS004F confirmed that quality relationship is very essential in order to have trust on the shared knowledge.

Knowledge Exchange Obstacles Are Reduced By Relationships Established Intentionally

Building quality relationships with other SME owners within the industry's social network helped in reducing the challenges of the knowledge exchange process. The network attached high values to personal

development and self-improvement. The influence of quality relationship motivated participant NS007F to change his perception about Knowledge exchange engagement. Participant NS007F stated that:

“initially when I started participating in capacity development program, training and others, at times I left very disappointed and plan to quit the idea. The idea of quitting made some members of the network to be unhappy because the attached high value to the process, therefore I quit the idea of quitting. So, your peers, your coach, or your partners can encourage you about participating in a program if they value it so greatly, this will ensure benefitted from the process. Then when you want to get lazy, they push through.”

The responses of the participants confirmed that the influence of quality relationships can motivate individual SME owners to make personal changes. The personal changes bring about attitudinal change which helps in bringing clarity in focus for decision making.

The focus group questions attempted to stimulate deeper thought on quality relationships for focus group discussion. Questions 3.1 and 3.2 in the Focus Group guidelines (see Appendix L) asked the group participants to highlight the importance and benefits of building quality relationships with other owners of the SME's. Participants NS003F and NS004F contributed to the discussion on how other SME owners provided advice, which helped prevent error. Participant NS0003F elucidate on the importance of having reliable partner which helped in maintaining focus on achieving current goals. An established quality relationship created the opportunity for participant NS004F to express their suggestions about the current state of operations within the industry without the suggestions being regarded as offensive and knowing that the other SME owners was sincere in providing constructive feedback.

Mentorship is an Important Resource for Every SME's Owner

One specific relationship discussed in the focus group was a mentor/ mentee relationship between SME owners.

A mentor/ mentee relationship established a professional relationship that helped certain participants to engage in external exchange of knowledge successfully. Participants shared experiences from the views of the mentor/mentee relationship. The basic motivation factor for being a mentor for participant NB003F is to encourage individuals who are struggling with their business. The awareness of others served as a motivator for participant NA003F, who stated that, "I'm good at either perceiving that there is a challenge or just seeing that there is an opportunity to improve on a system." Other participants gave more formal approaches to mentoring.

The more formal approaches presented specific types of knowledge exchanged with the mentee. The type of knowledge participant NB002F shared with the mentee relates to managerial skills. Helping other owner of the SME to build self-confidence is a subject that participant NB003F will like to coach as a mentor.

Mentees Should Also Try as Much as Possible to Provide Mentorship for Others

The focus group discussed mentoring as an important part of the business model. For example, participant NS004F started the personal coaching business out of a identified need for leadership mentoring within church administration.

Participant NS004F built a viable business around coaching owners of SMEs on building a solid foundation for success with the business plan. The business models for participant NS003F and NA003F emerge from being a mentor to clients on health and nutrition. Mentoring, as illustrated by the participants' responses, occurred either through the voluntary engagement of other SME owners or through a formal professional engagement of clients.

Theme 4, quality relationship as a contributive factor for absorptive capacity development, this provided the required answer to Research Question 3. The factors discussed in this section identify challenges that are confronted by SME owners in the phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory. The discussions, which presented quality and reliable data that transitioned to the thematic analysis from Absorptive Capacity Theory into Social Exchange Theory. The influence of quality relationships became apparent in the open-ended discussion of the participants.

4.4.5.5 Overall theme 5: Relationship Building

The discussions led into strategies adopted for the cultivation of quality relationships for SME owners. The reliable data provided by the participants strengthened the theoretical framework of the Social Exchange Theory. This overall theme summarized the organizing theme methods used to build quality relationships. The organizing theme emerged from the following three basic themes:

- 1) Being consistent in meeting SME owners who share common goals and values.
- 2) Trust is the end result of established quality relationships and improves the development of Absorptive Capacity.
- 3) Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person.

Consistency in Meeting People who Share Common Goals and Values

A simple statement generalized the response of the focus group sessions; this provides an answer in respect of the questions on how to build quality relationships. This is simplified by stating that, being intentional in getting to know the other person on a personal level cultivated strong and quality relationships. The experience shared by individual SME owners conveyed the message.

Consistency in meeting SME owners that share common goals and values intentionality emerged as an important strategy used among the participants in terms of strategies to cultivate quality relationships. It should be noted that most of the SME owners who participated in the research recognized time as a scarce resource, the cultivation of quality relationships required the participants to be desirable in reaching out to other SME owners.

Many of the participants stated the need to meet outside of the business in an informal and casual setting. 2 Participants stated that an activity as simple as meeting for coffee or going out to lunch play a major role in establishing quality relationships.

Trust is The Result of Established Credible Relationships to Enhance the Knowledge

Another strategy identified by participants includes reciprocation of business. Participant NA003F will pay a little more to a local SME owner to cultivate credible relationships, as against engaging with chain retail provider. The reciprocation established loyalty which in turn helped in building trust between the SME owners. The improved trust helped in the development of Absorptive Capacity for the SME owners in respect of benefits of the process.

Relationships are Best Cultivated by Showing Interest in the Other Person

The third strategy that emerged from the focus group session is the volunteering in the local community. Participant NS007F used volunteering in the community as a way for the community to get to know his team. Volunteering provided the community with extra help to meet a need as well as extra help in establishing an identity with other SME owners who volunteered. The volunteer work demonstrated by participant NS007F social responsibility to the community. The activity increased participant NS007F brand awareness within the community and among other SME owners. The act of reciprocating business and meeting for coffee or lunch is not enough.

The theme for building quality relationships illustrated strategies to improve absorptive capacity for the SME owners. Cultivating strong relationships requires intentional acts to know the other person authentically. The time invested in cultivating relationships could potentially pay big dividends in a time of need and hardship. The discussions and the experience shared by individual SME owner strongly demonstrated Social Exchange Theory. The quality and reliable data gathered from the interview sessions provided greater understanding of Research Question 3.

4.4.5.6 Overall theme 6: Influences of the SME Owner's Personality

The influence of the individual SME owner's personality toward the approaches to exchange of knowledge and credible relationships were very clear in the responses of the participants. The influences of the SME owners' personality emerged as the sixth overall theme. The type of personality that influences quality relationships and exchange of knowledge served as the organizing theme. The basic theme from the coded text is individual SME owners' personality influences how easily quality relationships are built and nurtured.

Personality Type Influences How Relationships are Built and Nurtured

Relationship is a powerful two way strategy for SME owners. However, not all participants attach the same importance to quality relationships. Participant NB002F's responses illustrated the influence of personality on cultivating quality relationships. The self-perception of the individual SME owner on personality was confirmed by the response provided by participant NB002F on the questionnaire. Participant NB002F self-identified as an introvert with a score of 3 (see Appendix W). Participant NB002F further stated that, "I hardly ask for help because I hate that idea." The participant described the state of the business at the time of the interview as very critical and requires capital for corporate restructuring and business re-launch. The problem of being an introvert has prevented participant NB002F from intentionally engaging in building quality relationships.

Participant NB002F avoid participating in knowledge exchange and relationships, therefore not having access to the benefits. Participant NS004F, who also self-identified as an introvert with a score of 6,

explained the approach adopted for engaging in exchange of knowledge for absorptive capacity process (see Appendix L). The initial approach was to “stand in the corner and ponder on, ‘Who do I talk to?’” Participant NS004F did not allow his personality to stop him from engaging in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process compared to NB002F. The participant set personal goals to meet other SME owners at knowledge exchange programs.

The approaches for exchange of knowledge for participants with similar personalities as participant NS004F were analogous. Participant NS004F said he will “attend conferences and meetings, other knowledge exchange events but will stand far off to the side due to the fact he is feeling being intimidated.” The participant shared how the feelings of introversion hindered his participation in the knowledge exchange process. Participant NS004F also stated that, “Despite feeling intimidated, I always try as much as possible to participate so as to benefit from the program, therefore I considered it useful for me.” Participant NA002I avoids establishing relationships with individuals who were not authentic.

The extroverted participants portrayed a different approach towards the exchange of knowledge. Participant NB003F stated that, “In knowledge exchange, I have always step backward and let the other person preside over the meeting if it's their meeting.” The extroverted personalities represented in the study explained always willing to seek help at all time.

The quality and reliable data collected in this study revealed common code of trust. Trust is the end result of building quality relationships. Trust is the factor that added value to Knowledge exchange experiences. Participant NS003F place premium on advice received from established relationships far above advice from strangers. According to participant NS007F, business is not simply business – business is relationships. Relationships and trust mean everything to participant NA003F who questions the motives of strangers. Participant like NB003F, need high level of trust to be opened and share freely. Cultivating quality relationships with local SME owners resulted in trust which allowed NB002F to receive help with operations during the time of need.

The influences of the SME owner's personality strongly illustrated Social Exchange Theory (SET).

The quality and reliable data revealed that even when the success level of the SME is also an important factor, the SME owner's personality still have some level of influence on the approach for cultivating quality relationships. Certain types of personality cultivate quality relationships and engage in Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development more easily than other personality types. Trust is an essential factor that strengthened intentional acts of cultivating quality relationships.

4.6 Summary

Chapter 4 described the data collected through a questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group. Multiple data sources increased the validity, reliability and credibility through triangulation. The five phases of the analysis presented by Yin assisted in returning to the original research questions and the theoretical frameworks for supporting the study.

The first phase consisted of collecting and transcribing the collected data. MaxQDA provided the platform for organizing and coding the transcribed data. The interview and focus group transcriptions were member checked for accuracy. Transcribed documents were uploaded into the software.

The disassembling process, Phase 2, involved multiple iterations of reading and coding the transcripts to ensure codes and themes accurately emerged. The initial open coding generated 60 initial codes (see Appendix S). Subsequent reading, coding, and organizing data resulted in 37 codes in the final codebook. Phase 2 concluded with organizing codes into similar groups. The grouping created the foundation for the thematic network used to answer the research questions.

Phase 3 is comprised of reassembling data according to the organization of codes into similar groups. The grouping of codes produced the organizing themes. Organizing codes provided a broader classification of

general codes. Organizing themes were grouped and summarized into overall themes. The overall themes represent the foundation that supports the network of all codes.

Establishing the trustworthiness of the data occurred in Phase 4 – interpreting.

Triangulation, member checking, and an audit trail established trustworthiness. The questionnaire, interview, and a focus group provided triangulation for the study. Transcripts were sent to participants for member checking after transcription. An audit log was kept throughout the process for future replication of the study. Repeatability of the research study improves the trustworthiness and credibility of this study.

The fifth phase – conclusions – provided the description of the results aligned with the theoretical framework and research questions along with suggested future research. The following lists the basic themes which provide answers to each research question as discussed above (see Appendix T):

- ❖ RQ1: How do SME owners perceive exchange of knowledge and relationship quality with other SME's as aiding the development of absorptive capacity?
 - 1) Direct physical participation in the process of Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development is preferred, but technology enable participation through the social media to be more convenient.
 - 2) Professional organizations provide established Knowledge exchange programs with specific goals.
 - 3) Individual SME owners' personality is highlighted as a major motivating factor that motivates SME owners to participate in knowledge exchange programs.

RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs?

- 1) Limited and inadequate resources affect knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity.
- 2) Relevancy of the Content.
- 3) Individual SME owners' perceptions of value in knowledge exchange engagement..

- 4) Previous experiences of the SME owners influence the approach adopted in participating in Knowledge exchange activities.
- 5) The Knowledge experience is improved by Socializing.
- 6) Engagement in knowledge exchange is affected by negative experiences.
- 7) Business operations are strengthened by previous positive experience.

RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners?

- 1) Established quality relationships affects participating in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development.
- 2) Establishing quality relationships intentionally limit the challenges of knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process.
- 3) Mentorship is identified as an important resource for every SME's owner.
- 4) Mentees should also try as much as possible to provide mentorship for others.
- 5) Personality type affects how quality relationships are built and nurtured.
- 6) Consistency in meeting people who share common goals and values .
- 7) Trust is the end result of established quality relationships and improves the knowledge exchange experience.
- 8) Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person.

Overall theme 1 within the thematic network is engaging in exchange of knowledge. Individual participants shared personal experiences and described the approach and methods of engaging in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development. The responses provided beneficial insights in respect of how SME owners seek advice to improve the performance and growth of the SMEs. Different methods work for different individuals. This bring the role of personality to the front burner. An individual's personality is a motivational factor for participating in Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development. The

response comprising the theme of engaging in Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity illustrated the first phase of the Absorptive Capacity Theory.

Participating in Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity emerged as the overall theme 2. The theme summarized challenges and strategies for participating in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process. Factors such as limited resources, relevant content, and individual's perception of value, previous experience and socializing influenced knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity. The transition of responses into participation introduced Social Exchange Theory into the theoretical framework. Participating in Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity expanded Absorptive Capacity Theory's phase of acquiring knowledge in a technology developed society.

Knowledge Exchange factors of Absorptive capacity as presented in the overall theme 3, is very significant in identifying the challenges confronting SME owners ability to absorb knowledge as well as the strategies to improve absorptive capacity. Contributive factors for the development of Absorptive Capacity are primarily centered around previous experience in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development.

Previous negative experiences influence continued participation in future knowledge exchange programs while previous positive experiences strengthened the participants' perception of the value and benefits of participating in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process.

Overall theme 4 identified quality relationship as contributive factor of knowledge exchange for development of absorptive capacity. Establishment of quality relationships influenced participation in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process. Establishing quality relationships with other SME owners is an intentional act. Some participants have developed mentor relationships to help with accountability in achieving goals and objectives. Mentees should not discount their experiences; therefore, mentees should consider being a mentor to other SME owner to help other businesses to grow.

Overall theme 5 emerged as building of quality relationships; this overall theme established the importance of building quality relationships with other SME owners. The participants presented strategies and benefits

personally experienced as SME owner. The responses affirmed Social Exchange Theory (SET) and expand the theory. Today's society is more technology-driven, thereby facilitating the building of quality relationships in various ways using numerous means.

The influence of the personality of the SME's owners is presented in the overall theme 6, this concluded the process of merging codes into similar groups. The participant's personalities were evident throughout the discussion. The approach adopted for knowledge exchange, how the participants engaged in exchange of knowledge, and how the participants build credible relationships revealed the personality of the individual SME's owner. Personality influenced how knowledge is absorbed and transferred to the SME's, this is the last two phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory. Personality also influenced relationships with other SME owners, this further expatiates Social Exchange Theory (SET).

Four limitations emerged in the research; the first limitation encountered in the study is the inability of some SME owners to complete the questionnaire. 10 SME owners started the answering of questionnaire but failed to complete the process. It is worthy to note that inability of some SME owners to fully answer the questionnaire did not pose any shortcoming to the study.

The potential for bias in questions presented for the interview guidelines created another limitation to the study. The researcher designed the interview and focus group guidelines and the research questions. An expert panel was deployed to assist in improving and refining the research instruments. In addition pilot test was carried out to assist in streamlining the interview and focus group guidelines; however, the potential for bias exists when the researcher designed the questions used for collection of data.

The third limitation involved focus group participants losing grip of the topic of discussion by providing response that is out of context. The focus group guidelines assisted in keeping the topics on track. There is slight possibility for existence of irrelevant responses during the course of the conversation because of fluidity nature of the discussion.

The focus group presented the limitation of six participants. The basic assumption for the research is that the individual experiences of the six participants represented the much larger population of service sector SME owners in Nigeria. The cumulative experiences of a smaller group may not fully represent the quality and reliable data that a larger sample size would have produced.

Chapter 5 contains a comprehensive summary and conclusions of this study. A detailed discussion of the research and analysis of the outcomes are also presented.

Chapter 5: Discussions of Research Findings

5.1 Introduction and Summary of Study

The main purpose of this qualitative descriptive study is to examine how the owners of the service sector SMEs in Nigeria perceived the development of Absorptive Capacity through the contribution of credible relationships and exchange of knowledge with other SME's owners within the industry's social network.

The research attempts to examine the experience of individual SME owners regarding exchange of knowledge and credible relationship as well as its effects on successful development of Absorptive Capacity. Exchange of Knowledge and credible relationships with other SME owners provide a resource that facilitates the performance and improve the success rate of service sector SMEs in Nigeria

Small and Medium Enterprises play a major role in the growth and development of the Nigerian economy. The growth of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria increased significantly between the period of year 2010 and 2014. The 2014 Annual Survey of Nigerian's Entrepreneurs released by Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS) reported a total of 28.8 million Small and Medium Enterprises operating in Nigeria. The SME's provide employment opportunities for more than 56.8 million teeming population in Nigeria. Hence, the success of service sector SME's and the owners cannot be overemphasized.

There are three well-structured research questions that provide the guidelines for this qualitative descriptive study. The first research question established the primary objective of the study in respect of the contribution of credible relationships and exchange of knowledge among owners of service sector SMEs towards the development of Absorptive Capacity. The study through the second research question examined the challenges confronting SME owners in the bid to initiate and/or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs. The effects of personality and credible relationships on the development of Absorptive Capacity were examined through the third research question.

Questionnaire, interview session, and focus group discussion are the multiple sampling method and source of primary data collected for the purpose of the study. The use of multiple primary source of data collection provided improves the quality and reliability of the data collected for the success of the research study.

The research questions are:

- ❖ RQ1: How do SME owners' perceived exchange of knowledge and the strength of the relationship with other SME's owners as facilitating the development of Absorptive Capacity?
- ❖ RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs?
- ❖ RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain credible relationships with other SME's owners?

A thematic analysis of the transcripts generated from the interview sessions and the focus group discussions provided a qualitative and descriptive conclusion for the study. Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) provided the framework for Research Question 1 (RQ1) and Research Question 2 (RQ2), Cohen & Levinthal supported the fact that ACT provided the foundation for applying all required phases of the theory for knowledge absorption. In addition to the Absorptive Capacity Theory, Social Exchange Theory (SET) is another important theory that supported the theoretical foundation for the research study. Peter Blau (1986) presented the model for the effective exchange of information between individuals. Both theoretical foundations (ACT and SET) provided the approach for structuring the data analysis.

The findings of the research study was elaborately discussed and presented in the chapter. The chapter begins with a summary of the findings; this is followed by the conclusive part of the analysis. The chapter presents the discussion of the results of the research study in relation to the outcomes of previous research.

5.2 Summary of Findings

5.2.1 Research questions.

The research questions examined the process Absorptive Capacity development through the contribution of credible relationships and exchange of knowledge among the owners of service sector SMEs. The interviews and focus group were analyzed using a thematic analysis, the thematic analysis resulted in the coded segments grouped into basic themes, and the basic themes were organized into organizing themes. The organizing themes were summarized and grouped by overall themes. The research questions were successfully answered by the basic theme,

Research Question 1: Summary

- ❖ RQ1: How do SME owners' perceived exchange of knowledge and relationship quality with other SME's as facilitating the development of absorptive capacity?

The research question provided the general overview of the Absorptive Capacity development and credible relationships among owners of SMEs. The general overview resulted in a proper understanding of the process. The summary of the basic theme that provides the required answers to the research questions is as follows:

- 1) Direct physical participation in exchange of knowledge is more preferred; however technology advancement enables social media to be the most convenient means of participation in Absorptive Capacity development process.
- 2) Professional organizations provide embarked on capacity exchange with targeted goals.
- 3) An individual's personality is identified as a factor in motivating individual to participate in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development.

Research Question 2: Summary

- ❖ RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in the bid to initiate and or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs owners?

Participants discussed personal challenges being faced in their efforts to initiate or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs owners..

Participation in exchange of knowledge should not be restricted to only seminars, conferences or direct physical interactions. The discussions in respect of the response for Research Question 2 as to the strategies employed by participants to improve exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development provide detailed answers for Research Question 1.

The following are the summary of the basic themes that answered Research Question 2:

- 1) Inadequate resources affect exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development.
- 2) Content of the knowledge exchange program must be relevant
- 3) Individual's perceptions of the SME's owners about the importance of the process have great effects on the level of participation.
- 4) Previous experience of the participants about the knowledge development process had impact on the current participation approach.
- 5) The knowledge exchange process is improved by Socializing.
- 6) Engagement in knowledge exchange is hindered by participant's negative experiences.
- 7) Engagement in knowledge exchange is bolstered by participant's positive experiences.

Research Question 3: Summary

❖ RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain credible relationships with other SME's owners?

The final research question examined the strategies the participants adopted in cultivating credible relationships with other SME owners, cultivating and maintaining credible relationships provides mentorship and provision of support services. A summary of the general codes which provides answers to Research Question 3 are:

- 1) Knowledge exchange is greatly improved by credible relationships.
- 2) Carefully cultivating credible relationships helps in curtailing the challenges confronting exchange of knowledge.
- 3) Every SME owner needs a mentor for self development and success of the business.
- 4) Mentees should also endeavor to take up role of a mentor at their level of capacity.
- 5) Cultivating credible relationship is greatly influenced by Personality types.
- 6) Consistency in meeting people who share common goals and values.
- 7) Trust is the result of established credible relationships and it improves Absorptive Capacity development process.
- 8) Credible relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in other person.

5.2.2 Questionnaire

The questionnaire employed for the purpose of this research study served two main roles; the questionnaire was designed for data collection. In addition it was used for the selection of the qualified SME owners for either the interview sessions or to participate in the focus group discussion.

The data collected with the aid of the questionnaire assist in complementing the responses from the interviews and focus group. The participants were asked to rate their self-perceptions on Absorptive Capacity development through credible relationships and exchange of knowledge among SME owners, and their personality type.

Table 16: Participant Demographics

Demographic	Number of Participants
Industries	16
Years of Experience	
1year to 5years	9
5years to 10years	1
10years to 15years	5
15years to 20years	2
20years and above	3
Employees	
0 to 5 employees	16
5 to 10 employees	4
Age	
18 years to 24 years	1
25years to 34 years	1
45years to 54years	12
55 years to 64years	3
65years and above	3

The questionnaires were served on 60 SME owners, and the responses were received, individual responses provided insights into the discussions. The interview participants' selection process took place among 20 questionnaire participants. Table 16 above presents the breakdown of the selected participants by demographic.

The participants' self-perceptions about absorptive capacity development through quality relationship and exchange of knowledge among owners of SME's and their personality complement the discussion of individual experiences. Participants who self-identified as introverts found motivation to participate in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development process, extroverted participants recognized the need to not dominate the engagement discussion. One participant that was identified as an introvert did fail to participate in the cultivation of quality relationships and exchange of knowledge even at the detriment of business poor performance.

5.2.3 Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis provides the opportunities for thorough examination of individual's experience of SME's owners about their participation in Absorptive Capacity development. Five overall themes emerged from the data analysis; the themes include engagement in Exchange of Knowledge, participating in exchange of knowledge, Absorptive Capacity factors, credible relationships development, and impacts of the SME owner's personality.

5.2.4 Overall Theme 1: Exchange Of Knowledge Engagement

The purpose of RQ1 was to explore the factors of development of absorptive capacity. Through Research Question 1, a framework was provided to identify the SME owner perceptions of critical factors before engaging in the development of Absorptive Capacity. Q1 provided the framework to identify factors the SME's owner perceived as important in engaging in external knowledge. As shown in Appendix T, the overall theme of engagement in exchange of knowledge comprised of two organizing themes which are:

- 1) How do SME owners engage in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development?
- 2) Factors that motivates SME owners to participate in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development.

The organizing theme that focus on how SME's owners engage in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development has succeeded in identifying the preferred methods of participating in the process. The organizing theme summarized two basic themes:

- 1) Direct physical participation in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development is preferred.
- 2) Professional organizations provide exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development with the targeted goals and objectives.

The organizing theme for motivational factors in respect of exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development participation is comprised of the basic theme of an individual SME owners' personality as a major factor that motivates SME owners to participate. These basic themes provide detailed understanding through the experiences shared by the participants in the course of participating exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities.

How do SME owners engage in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development?

There are several notable methods that can be adopted for participating in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development, out of all options, the direct physical method engagement is the most preferred method of participation. However, technology such as podcasts, blogs, social media, and email provided an alternative method of participation; this is identified to be more convenient.

Direct Physical Method of Participation in Exchange of Knowledge for Absorptive Capacity Development is Preferred

The interview participants preferred direct physical method of participation in exchanging knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development for numerous reasons; direct physical participation exposed the participants to a more personal engagement and relationships. In addition, direct physical participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development helps in building openness and trust; it also encourages making personal connections which in turn enabled the participant to seek help for specific issues. The comments and reports by some of the participants in respect of their experience and benefits by engaging in direct physical participation are stated below:

participant NS006I stated “. . . in attending webinars or video conferencing, it made me to be watching through my telephone set Though engagement through direct physical participation difficult considering the schedule,”

Participant tagged NA001I highlighted the impact of direct physical participation in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development as providing the opportunity to be in close contact with owners in similar situations and not being afraid to ask for help. Identifying how to move beyond barriers and discover success is important.

Professional Organizations Provide Knowledge Exchange for Absorptive Capacity Development with Targeted Goals

Participants preferred exchange of knowledge opportunities for absorptive capacity development program that focused on targeted goals and objectives, a well formally structured capacity development process enhanced the perceived value and importance of the process.

Professionally organized knowledge exchange program such as a mastermind group, professional member organizations, and trade union presents the targeted goals and topics. The structure and format of this type of program helps in building confidence about the quality of the process and resulted in an improved perception of the importance of the process. The report stated is provided by one of the participants in respect of the influence of professionally organized capacity development program with the targeted goals:

The participant tagged NA004I confirmed his participation in the process because it provides structure and consistent accountability among members of the group.

Motivational Factors of Knowledge Exchange for Absorptive Capacity Development

Individual SME owner personality should be considered regarding successful exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity Development. The participants rated the self-perceptions of their personality in the questionnaire. The interview questions provided detailed examination of the influence individual's personality.

A desire to help others posed some level of challenges for some participants; the participants should be cautious and exercise some level of self-restraint not to be dominating every conversation. The approach is necessary so that other participants would not be apprehensive to engage in conversation.

Personality influenced the knowledge exchange experience for the participants.

Both introverts and extroverts participants have the mindset of rendering assistance to other SME's owners which is the main benefit of engaging in exchange of knowledge for absorptive capacity development. The

primary objective of engaging in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development is to meet other SME owners and share advice and suggestions to overcome the burning issues.

A broader definition of knowledge exchange and knowledge management is important; “knowledge is the careful harmonization of contextual information with experience (Ramayah, Yeap, & Ignatius, 2013)”. Knowledge management encompass the identification of knowledge sources, accessing the knowledge, assimilation , transfer, and effective utilization of the knowledge to enhance SME growth and development (Ramayah et al., 2013; Schenkel, Farmer, & Maslyn, 2019). As stated by Ramayah et al., 2013, knowledge exchange is the principal factor of knowledge management. They further stated, “...knowledge exchange can be referred to as the exchange of knowledge between at least two parties in a reciprocal process allowing reshaping and sense-making of the knowledge in the new context” . Effective exchange of knowledge is a form of mutual exchange.

Knowledge exchange is very beneficial to SME owners. Through knowledge exchange, owners of service sector SMEs improve the performance and profitability of SMEs, it also help in sustaining the growth of the business while also encouraging building of credible relationship with other SME owners to create innovative ideas (Turner & Endres, 2017). Owners of SMEs are more likely to benefit from multiple sources of knowledge including family and friends, educational institution, collaboration with other SMEs within the industry’s network (Howard, Steensma, Lyles,& Dhanaraj, 2016).

Knowledge brings about creativity, efficiency, and self-development. Cerezo, et al. (2019) in their study explained that it’s very important to know the difference between self-perceived knowledge and objective knowledge. They also found that how an individual perceive knowledge may be different from the perception of another individual. The knowledge an individual believes he has is known as self-perceived knowledge while managerial or technical training and experience is known as objective knowledge (Cerezo, et al., 2019).

He found that objective knowledge does not always encourage acceptance of an idea, self-perceived knowledge is receptive and willing to accept an idea (Cerezo, et al., 2019). The level of confidence an individual has about his knowledge strengthens his creativity and self-development.

Creativity and self-development stimulates innovation and invention. Research has shown that an individual who innovates possess high level of creativity and self-development as creative self-efficacy is a byproduct of the knowledge of an individual's knowledge (Bei and Yidan 2016) . They further postulated that increased knowledge implies that there is an increase in creative self-efficacy resulting into an increase in innovative ideas (Bei & Yidan, 2016). Bei and Yidan (2016) developed hypothesis which confirm that knowledge exchange among employees increases innovation while carrying out research on creative self-efficacy and innovation

5.2.5 Overall Theme 2: Participating in Knowledge Exchange for Absorptive Capacity Development

Participating in exchange of knowledge for absorptive capacity development process emerged as the second overall theme from the collected data. The data from interview sessions and the focus group discussion presents the challenges and benefits targeted by the SME owners in engaging in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development. The responses provided insight as to what challenges and benefits the SME owners are targeting to achieve for participating in knowledge exchange activities for the growth and improved performance of business.

The thematic network for the overall theme is comprised of two organizing themes. The first organizing theme highlights the challenges for participating in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development, the basic theme is summarized as follows:

- 1) Inadequate resources impacts Absorptive Capacity development.
- 2) There must be relevancy to the Content.
- 3) An individual SME owner's perceptions of the importance and benefits

The organizing theme focused on the strategies adopted for improving exchange of knowledge, the organizing theme is made up of two basic themes:

- 1) Current approach is influenced by prior experiences.
- 2) Knowledge exchange experience is enhanced by Socializing.

Challenges in Knowledge Exchange Engagement

Challenges to exchange of knowledge reduce absorptive capacity. Knowledge exchange engagement challenges appeared as an organizing theme of the overall theme. The organizing theme is made up of two basic themes consisting of inadequate resources and content relevancy.

Inadequate Resources affect Absorptive Capacity Development

Inadequate resources is a major challenge that affects absorptive capacity development, time availability is a factor that affects ability to participate in direct physical capacity development activities, time is a very scarce and limited resource that hindered the participants from participating in the knowledge exchange process, however technology advancement had provides the facilities and platform that has helped the participants to conveniently participate in exchange of knowledge process with limited time resources.

Apart from the time scarcity challenge, technology has also helped in combating other challenges affecting the process, this includes lack of office coverage. Direct physical participation in knowledge exchange process is affected by the inability of the participant to leave the work space. Technology provides an alternative method for participating in the knowledge exchange process.

Relevancy of the Content

Inadequate resources is not the only challenge inhibiting participation in external exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development process, the content and relevance of knowledge is another important challenge that the participants considered when deciding to engage in the activity or not.

The quality of the content serves as a motivating factor to engage in exchange of knowledge. The content must be focused in providing solution to a prominent business problem or as an idea for innovation.

Engagement Value Perception by Participant

The participants discussed the importance of the perceived importance of engaging in knowledge exchange activities. Lack of perceived importance of the process may prevent the ability of the participant to be open and transparent during the process. The responses of the participants established the influence of the perception of the importance in knowledge exchange opportunities.

Strategies to Increase Knowledge Exchange Engagement

Two general themes were discovered from Participant discussions which identified the strategies to improve engagement in exchange of knowledge through which explanatory reasons were provided for the frequency of participants engagement in knowledge exchange activities. Previous experiences of the process and socializing were factors which motivates the participants in continuous engagement in exchange of knowledge.

Current Approach is influenced by Previous Experience

Previous experience about a knowledge exchange event influence participation in future engagement. Substantial amount of revenue could be lost due to time taken away from the business. The knowledge exchange event must have high value to motivate the SME owner to participate. The previous experiences in knowledge exchange influenced continued participation based on the quality of the content.

The Knowledge Exchange Experience is Improved by Socializing

Established credible relationships motivate participants to engage in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development, the attempt to be thorough and detailed on exchange of knowledge experience reveals reliance on trust and credible relationships in the responses. Some SME owners make use of knowledge exchange activities as primary method of operation.

Credibility is built through cultivating of credible relationships; the confidence to mutually participate in knowledge depends on the credibility of the source of knowledge. An established quality relationship helped in building credibility in the source of knowledge and motivates the SME owners to participate.

The owners of service sector SMEs are motivated to participate in the development of Absorptive Capacity through the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge exchange as the desire to remain competitive increased (Silva, Rocha Dacorso, Barreto Costa, & Di Serio, 2016). Development of Absorptive Capacity through external exchange of knowledge is therefore a reflection of internal knowledge exchange; as internal knowledge exchange aids the setting of the precedent to pursue the exchange of external knowledge. Sawang & et al., 2016 stated that organization learning (OL) is referred to as the exchange of knowledge within the context of SMEs. The process of organization learning depends on the skills and experiences of the organizational members to bolster the SME'S overall performance (Sawang & et al., 2016). This method of group learning will be greatly advantageous and effective if the learning experience is designed to meet the participant's needs (Ramezani & Ava, 2017). Business consultancy which offers learning opportunities for the owners of service sector SMEs appears to be better effective to deliver educational content thereby encouraging innovation by taking cognizance of the participant's needs (Sawang & et al., 2016). Internal exchange of knowledge has the benefit of designing knowledge exchange experiences to meet the need of the owners of SME's, external knowledge exchange on the other hands provides other form of benefits for service sector SME owners. External knowledge exchange expanded the access to resources for the organization.

Prior study has evaluated the impacts of external knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships for the development of Absorptive Capacity. In 2016 Sawang & et al. carried another study which further supported the previous research which established that SME's owners that engage in exchange of knowledge externally experience higher success levels compared to non-participants. By engaging in learning collectively and exchange of knowledge externally, participants are better able to detail real life skills and experiences in a less formal setting with other SME owners (Sawang & et al., 2016). When SME owners

participate in the knowledge exchange experience, information are shared in a manner to improve the profitability of the SMEs within the local market and how to collaborate with other SME owners within the industry through social networking (Turner & Endres, 2017).

The two main knowledge forms are explicit and tacit. Olaniran, 2017 classified knowledge gained from experience as Tacit Knowledge. An example of Tacit knowledge was presented by Turner and Endres (2017) as the live and realistic experiences the much experienced owners of the SMEs shared with the new entrant in the industry and the less experienced owners. The process of exchanging tacit knowledge increased the self-efficacy and creativities of the owners the SME's (Wipawayangkool & Teng, 2016). In spite of the fact that, self-efficacy is a motivating factor required in engaging in mutually beneficial knowledge exchange, it is worthy of note that, individuals are not solely motivated by self-efficacy to share their knowledge (Wipawayangkool & Teng, 2016). Mutual exchange is often the motivating factor for beneficial and successful exchange of knowledge, particularly tacit knowledge.

The study carried by Olaniran in 2017 presented the barriers that hinder effective exchange of tacit knowledge. He first and foremost said, personal values can impede the desires of the SME's owners not to engage in tacit knowledge exchange . Personal values consist of the personality traits with the disposition that is incompatible with cultural or knowledge superiority where a lower value is placed on one culture by another (Olaniran, 2017). The perception of SME owners involved in the knowledge transfer will hinder the development of Absorption Capacity (Olaniran, 2017).

Secondly, Olaniran discovered that the dearth of quality relationships in the industry social networking can prevent the transfer of tacit knowledge. Lastly, he said the culture of individual organization can led to conflict as tacit knowledge is transferred. Lack of team cohesion creates resistance to innovative ideas and differing perception.

Further to the technological advancement, SMEs need to embrace development of Absorptive Capacity as nucleus part of their operational routine and procedures. Identifying the success factors, as well as the

challenges is the first step to developing Absorptive Capacity process. However, the SMEs will be required to take a step further by building credibility relationships and effective implementation of knowledge (Asiedu, 2015). To adequately support development of Absorptive Capacity, management of the service sector SMEs must be ready to construct facilities and create conducive environment that encourages and enables the employees' of the SMEs development process (Asiedu, 2015). The success of developing Absorptive Capacity process commenced with the strong support from the management and subsequently drop down to the employees'.

5.2.6 Overall Theme 3: Knowledge sharing factors of Absorptive Capacity

Contributive factors that influence absorptive capacity development emerged as a third overall theme from the interview and focus group data. One organizing theme of knowledge exchange impacts the business; the basic themes summarized by the organizing theme include the following:

1) Negative experience about exchange of knowledge affects participation in knowledge exchange activities. The quotations, reports and statements of some participants in respect of their negative experience about knowledge exchange are stated below:

Trusting the source of knowledge emerged as a code for participants, NA004I shared his experience about the knowledge he received from other female SME owner who intentionally offered bad advice on certain operational strategies. Participant with code NS007I reported similar experience in the first year of entering into the business he maintained that competitors would intentionally offered wrong information to distract your smooth activities and potential sales. Participants (NA004I and NS007I) are very apprehensive in receiving knowledge which could help the business grow.

Misguided information is not always intentional; participant with NB003I shared the experience when he newly commenced business, the participant was not very certain about the quantity of material required to be ordered at the inception, the participant (NB003I) approached another SME owner in similar business to inquire about the material to be purchased, the advice provided mislead the participant into purchasing excess quantity of the material. The advice provided by the other SME owner was based on market location and personal experience of the adviser. Therefore, the misguided information on material quantity to purchase was not intentional; however, participant (NB003I) always exercises an apprehension on whose advice to be followed.

2) Positive experience about knowledge exchange helps in strengthening business operations. The comments and quotations of some participants in respect of positive experience as it strengthened participation is as follows:

The participant (NB009I) revealed that, “I have been able to discover that I needed some level of education on new trend in market, I need to resharpen my marketing skill. The current trend is quite different with what I am used to”. The technology presented challenges due to its impacts on the society.

The codes which are made up contributive factors that influence development of Absorptive Capacity demonstrated the organization attempts to absorb the external source of knowledge.

Knowledge Exchange Affects the Business

Absorptive Capacity developments represent the participants’ attempts to capitalize on external knowledge exchange. Interview and focus group participants presented challenges confronted in absorbing knowledge from external sources. The individual experiences of participants’ attempt to implement advice from other SME owners reflected varying degrees of difficulty.

Negative Knowledge Exchange Experiences Hinder Participation

Having trust on the source of knowledge is very important for participants, participants who received misleading information may develop apprehension and might not make effective use of important information provided in future that can lead to the growth of the SME. Regardless of the intention behind the information, misguided advice will discourage future participation in exchange of knowledge.

Positive Experiences of Knowledge Exchange Helps in Strengthening the Operations

Positive experiences in knowledge exchange generated the opportunities to overcome inadequate resources. Inadequate funds prevented one participant from being able to start a new business in an actual office space as opposed to the home. The poor business location presented a challenge in attracting high net worth and credible clients. The participant reached out to the industry’s network at his local community level and the required assistance was provided.

The discussions reflect that exchange of knowledge have both positive and negative impacts on businesses. Knowledge absorption is influenced by many factors such as trust, inadequate resources, previous misguided advice offered, marketing, and the pressure to succeed.

“Managers may not be naturally inclined to embrace knowledge sharing. The knowledge possessed by an individual represents his/her personal asset which helps create a competitive advantage (Rajput & Talan, 2017). The concept of willingly sharing knowledge may be difficult for certain individuals. Personality traits influence the process of knowledge sharing and the ability of the individual to absorb knowledge. The influence of the individual’s personality cannot be discounted in the knowledge sharing process. In a study conducted on knowledge sharing among educators, the individual’s personality traits contribute to an individual’s propensity to share knowledge (Zhang, Zhou, & Zhang, 2016). The individuals who were more agreeable, conscientious, and extroverted participated more often in the knowledge sharing process (Quan, Di, & Lan, 2015; Rajput & Talan, 2017; Zhang et al., 2016). The research on the influence of personality traits supports prior research which suggested effective knowledge sharing is dependent upon the participant’s willingness to share individual experiences (Sawang et al., 2016). In establishing knowledge sharing practices, the personality traits of the participants cannot be discounted. Each personality type was motivated to participate in knowledge sharing in diverse ways. Effective knowledge sharing is a mutual exchange between participants. Although all five personality traits have unique contributions to the knowledge sharing process, agreeableness has the greater positive contribution (Quan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2016). The openness and willingness to exchange experiences and ideas is important for 58 knowledge sharing to result in innovative ideas (Quan et al., 2015). Building trust between partners in a relationship is a key factor when trying to increase openness in sharing. Trust, within the framework of SET, grows from one of two roots. First, trust can grow from developing a close personal relationship (Blau, 1986). Second, trust can grow from the mutual exchanges (Blau, 1986). Within relationships and SET, the principle of reciprocity states that participants will receive mutual contributions to the relationship

(Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Lioukas and Reuer (2015) proposed that as each participant contributes to the knowledge sharing process because of seeking a mutual benefit rather than fulfilling a self-serving intention and trust will grow. Initially, trust begins within mutual exchanges. Lioukas and Reuer (2015) concluded that trust does not exist automatically because of social exchanges. Time cultivates trust. Over time, individuals build rapport through continual positive interactions. As individuals establish rapport with each other, trust grows out of the formation of close personal relationships (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Prior interactions and commitments within the alliance create a history of alliance members by which trust can exist through caring about the other member(s). This type of affect-based trust will help strengthen the alliance, enabling knowledge sharing to occur more naturally (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). As exchanges occur, feelings begin to form creating a deeper connection in the alliance. Even within close relationships, boundaries naturally exist. Lioukas and Reuer (2015) showed that certain boundaries exist within affect-based trust among business owners. The research suggested that when business owners are in less direct competition, the affect-based trust will be stronger (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Trust will form more easily when business owners are not directly competing for the same shares within the market, and through less fear over revealing competitive advantages exists (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). The identification of such boundaries is important when seeking to form relationships with other business owners. Individuals approach trust through the filters of his/her personality traits. Understanding the influence of personality helps unravel the mystery in building relationships. An individual's personality contributes to an individual's approach to placing trust in others and allowing trust to strengthen relationships (Rajput & Talan, 2017). Trust, quality relationships, and understanding of the role personality plays in knowledge sharing will help increase the absorptive capacity of the participants. Trust enabled individuals to be more open in the knowledge sharing process." The personality traits which comprise the Big Five Model include extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and intellect. Extroversion is the tendency of the individual to be sociable, adventurous, energetic, and assertive (Zvolensky, Taha, Bono, & Goodwin, 2015). Agreeableness is the ability to feel comfortable around

others and the ability to be compliant and cooperative (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Conscientiousness is the tendency to be self-aware, self-disciplined, and organized (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Emotional stability encompasses the ability to evaluate and express emotion (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Intellect is the desire for innovative learning, creativity, and new ideas (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Personality traits are the unique expressions of the individual.

5.2.7 Overall Theme 4: Quality Relationship factors of Absorptive Capacity

The quality and reliable data collected from the participants helped in the identification and transition of Absorptive Capacity development through the phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) with strong emphasis on the impact of quality relationships. The organizing theme is comprised of the influence of credible relationships in Absorptive Capacity development.. The basic themes summarized by the organizing theme include:

- 1) Participating in Absorptive Capacity development opportunities was influenced by established credible relationships.
- 2) Intentionally establishing credible relationships helps in curtailing the challenges confronting Absorptive Capacity development.
- 3) A mentor is an important resource for SME's owners.
- 4) Mentees should also serves as mentor for other SME''s owner at their capacity level.

Prior discussion of the results has highlighted ways in which quality relationships influenced Absorptive Capacity development as it relates to Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT). The discussion of coding will commence with the transition from the theoretical framework of (ACT) to the theoretical framework of Social Exchange Theory (SET).

Participating in Absorptive Capacity development process is influenced by established credible relationship, the established credible relationships helped in strengthening the trust and confidence of the participants in the capacity development process. Building of credible relationships is essential for the ability to trust the shared knowledge. Trusting the source of knowledge increased confidence in participating in the Absorptive Capacity development process, increased and improved Absorptive Capacity development stimulate innovation.

A Mentor is an Important Resource for SME Owner

Relationships with other SME owners are an important theme among the participants in the study. The importance of credible relationships was observed through the discussions of accountability and finding solutions to problems. One specific type of relationship discussed in the study is the mentor/ mentee relationship.

The motivation to be a mentor is the interest in rendering assistance to other SME owners that struggling with their SME business activities. Mentorships is considered as being informal, when an owner of the SME is aware of the needs of others who have challenges in their business. On other hand, a formal mentorship is when specific needs of the SME is being handled by a professional business coach.

Mentees Should Consider Being a Mentor

The focus group discussed mentoring as a part of the business model. Mentoring can occurred either through the voluntary engagement of other people or through a formal professional engagement of clients. Mentoring created more definition of the role of Social Exchange Theory (SET) within the activity of Absorptive Capacity development. Both the ACT and SET provides the guidance in establishing a solid foundation for the growth of the SME business. Strategically engaging others is important.

Mentoring provided opportunity to help other SME owners, the owners of newly established SMEs struggles with the business take-off or commencement. Mentoring provided the opportunity to listen to what the much experienced SME owners have experienced while trying to stability and grow their business. Mentoring results in improving the success and improved performance of the SME.

Theme 4, quality relationship as contributive factors to the development absorptive capacity provided answers to Research Question 3 (RQ 3).

The discussions identified the challenges confronting the SME owners in the phases of ACT. The discussions presented quality and reliable data which is transitioned through the thematic analysis from ACT into SET.

“The principle of reciprocity according to Social Exchange Theory (SET) asserted that participants will receive mutual contributions from the relationship (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Lioukas and Reuer (2015) proposed that as each participant contributes to the development of Absorptive Capacity through the strength of the relationships and knowledge exchange process because of seeking a mutual benefit rather than fulfilling a self-serving intention and trust will grow. Originally, trust begins with mutual exchanges. The study carried out by Lioukas and Reuer (2015) concluded that trust does not exist automatically because of social exchanges. Trust is cultivated over time.

Over time, individuals build strong and credible relationships through continual positive interactions among the owners of SMEs. As individuals established rapport with each other, trust grows out of the formation of close personal relationships (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Previous interactions and commitments within the social network create historical details of synergy between owners of the SMEs thereby leading trust. Trust can exist through caring about the other member(s), this type of affect-based trust will help strengthened the alliance and encourage development of Absorptive Capacity through quality relationships and knowledge exchange which will occur naturally (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). As exchanges occur, affections begin to grow thereby creating a strong connection in the alliance.

Building credible relationships cannot break the natural boundaries that exist among owners of SMEs. Lioukas and Reuer (2015) study showed that there exist certain boundaries within affect-based trust between owners of SMEs. The research suggested that when business owners are in less direct competition, the affect-based trust will be stronger (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Trust will grow more easily when owners of SMEs are not directly competing for the market shares; also through less fear there exists competitive advantages (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). The identification of such boundaries is important when seeking to form relationships with other owners of SMEs.

The influence of personality traits helps to uncover the challenges in building credible relationship. An individual's personality traits contribute to individual's approach to placing trust on others and allowing trust to strengthen relationships (Rajput & Talan, 2017). Trust, quality relationships, and understanding of the role personality plays important role in developing Absorptive Capacity which help to increase the knowledge exchange of the participants. Trust enabled individuals to be more opened in the knowledge exchange process.

The personality trait which is made up of the Big Five Model includes extroversion, agreement, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and intellect.””

Extroversion is the tendency of the individual owner of the SME's to be sociable, adventurous, energetic, and assertive (Zvolensky, Taha, Bono, & Goodwin, 2015).

Agreement is the ability to feel at ease around other owners of the SME's and the ability to be compliant and cooperative (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Conscientiousness is the ability to be self-aware, self-disciplined, and organized (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Emotional stability is involved with the ability to assess and express emotion (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Intellect is the desire for innovative learning, creativity, and new ideas (Zvolensky et al., 2015).

Personality trait is the distinct expressions of the individual.

5.2.8 Overall Theme 5: Cultivating Quality Relationships

The discussions developed into strategies that are employed in cultivating credible relationships for the SME owners. The quality and reliable data provided by the participants strengthened the theoretical framework of SET. This overall theme summarized the organizing theme methods used in cultivating credible relationships. The organizing theme emerged from the following three basic themes:

- 1) Consistency in meeting people with similar goals and values.
- 2) Trust is the result of established relationships and improves the Absorptive Capacity development experience.
- 3) Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person.

Consistency in meeting people with similar goals and values, a simple statement sums up the interview responses, which provides answer to the questions on how to cultivate credible relationships.

Intentionality in getting to know other SME owners cultivated credible relationships. A simple phone call can help in the establishment and strengthening of credible relationships. The individual experiences shared by the participants corroborate this fact

Intentionality was a common topic when discussing strategies to cultivate credible relationships. Cultivating credible relationships required the participants to be intentional in connecting with other SME owners. Most of the participants preferred meeting outside of the business in an informal, casual setting. Participants stated that an activity as simple as meeting for coffee or going out to lunch play important role in establishing credible relationships.

Trust is the result of established relationships and improves the Absorptive Capacity development experience. The reciprocation of business was another strategy identified by participants in cultivating credible relationships, relationships are strengthened by sending referrals to other SME's owners. The

reciprocation established loyalty and built trust between SME owners. The overall effect results in improved Absorptive Capacity development.

Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person business activities. The third strategy that emerged in the interviews is volunteering in the local community. Volunteering in the community provided an opportunity for the community to get to know the SME owners and the team personally. Volunteering provided the community with extra help to meet a need, through meeting this need, the community will develop a greater awareness of the SME services and brand. The data generated in the interviews successfully provides answers to Research Question 3 (RQ3).

The motivation to establish credible relationships varies among owners of SMEs. The literature review earlier pointed it out that owners of SMEs will establish credible relationships for knowledge exchange. However, there are other factors that may encourage the owners of SME's to seek and establish quality relationships.

By having good understanding of the motivational factors, owners of SMEs can form alliance towards developing quality and meaningful relationships with other SME's owners.

“Cultivating credible relationships with other owners of SMEs provide connections with other owners of SME's who face similar challenges previously. Absorptive Capacity process creates more than an opportunity to learn new concepts. The involvement of the owners of the SMEs in external knowledge exchange creates an intangible asset known as social capital. Social capital is the product of cultivating relationships which add value to the owners of the SMEs that participates in the process (Moyes, Ferri, Henderson, &Whittam, 2015).

Social capital enables owners of SMEs to take advantage of the resources to increase innovation and improve the efficiency in the operations of the SMEs (Moyes et al., 2015). The bridge which connects owners of the SMEs to collaborate and form alliance in the exchange of resources is trust (Moyes et al., 2015; Yoo et al., 2016). Social capital is a dynamic process through which owners of the SMEs recognized the potential in

developing credible relationships (Moyes et al., 2015). Owners of SMEs are encouraged to develop credible relationships with other SME owners to basically to create social capital.

The literature review has successfully identified other factors which influenced SME owners to develop credible relationships in order create opportunities to learn (Silva et al., 2016). Man-pil et al. (2017) stated conscientiousness and agreeableness were two of the personality traits exhibited by managers which influenced building of credible relationship and organizational learning.

It should be noted that agreeableness is the only personality traits found to directly impact performance (Man-pil et al, 2017). As owners of SME's are being careful and vigilant in their relationships with other SME owners and seek to develop strong and credible relationships, the potential for the development of Absorptive Capacity improves (Man-pil et al., 2017). Relationships strengthened the development of Absorptive Capacity.

Cultivating credible relationships with other SME's owners is important to increase the knowledge base within the SMEs (Silva et al., 2016). To be innovative, SME owners need to embrace learning (Bei & Yidan, 2016; Silva et al., 2016). Development of Absorptive Capacity creates opportunity for informal learning (Bei & Yidan, 2016; Silva et al., 2016). Through developing quality relationships, mutual exchange of knowledge becomes seamless (Bei & Yidan, 2016; Silva et al., 2016). Cultivating credible relationships with other SME owners is a continuous process built on trust. Successfully engaging in external knowledge exchange depends on trust, credible relationships, and learning.

The market situation is very dynamic, therefore the market conditions shift periodically, and the relationships will need to be re-aligned for the owners of SMEs to benefit from knowledge relevant to prevalent market conditions (Silva et al., 2016). For an SME owner who is well motivated to develop credible relationships for the development of Absorptive Capacity, the process of re-aligning relationships become very fluid and dynamic (Silva et al., 2016). However, the owners of SME who is less motivated to strengthen the relationships, the process of re-aligning the relationships will be retrogressive and static (Silva et al., 2016).

It is worthy of note that not all relationships consummated by the SME's owners directly relate to business activities of the SMEs."

5.2.9 Overall Theme 6: Influence of the SME Owner's Personality

The influence of the individual SME owners' personality in respect of their approaches to Absorptive Capacity development through the contribution of quality relationship and knowledge exchange are clear and obvious in the responses of the participants. The influences of the SME owner personality emerged as the sixth overall theme. Personality types that influence relationships and exchange of knowledge served as the organizing theme. The basic theme from the coded text is the individual's personality and its influence on building of quality relationships.

The Type of Personality Influences How Relationships are Established and Cultivated

Relationship is a powerful two-way tool for SME owners. For the introverted participant, the cultivation of credible relationships is avoided due to the type of personality. The challenge of being an introvert prevents him from intentionally engaging in cultivating credible relationships.

Another participant who also self-identified as an introvert discussed setting goals to motivate her participation in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development process, the participant set personal target to meet and relate with other SME owners at knowledge exchange programs.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) was illustrated through the influences of the SME owners' personality, the quality and reliable data revealed that the success of the business is factor that improves the personality of the owners that influences the approach for cultivating credible relationships. Different personality types cultivate credible relationships and engage in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development easily than other personality types.

As hypothesized by Rajput & Talan, 2017, SME managers may not be motivated naturally to support development of Absorptive Capacity. The intellectual capacity that an individual possess is his/her personal asset which aids the creation of competitive advantage for the individual. The idea of desire and willingness to exchange knowledge may be taxing and difficult for some set of individual SME's owners.

Personality traits influence the process of developing Absorptive Capacity and the ability of the individual to exchange knowledge. The influence of the individual's personality cannot be de-emphasized in the process of developing Absorptive Capacity. In a research conducted on Absorptive Capacity development among educational instructors, the individual's personality traits contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity (Zhang, Zhou, & Zhang, 2016). Quan, Di, & Lan, 2015; Rajput & Talan, 2017; Zhang et al., 2016 further said that individuals who exercise higher levels of extroversion, conscientiousness and were more agreeable will freely participate better in the process.

The study on personality traits influence is in agreement with prior research which suggested that effective exchange of knowledge is a function of the willingness of the participant to share their individual experiences (Sawang et al., 2016). In developing Absorptive Capacity through quality relationships and knowledge exchange process, the personality traits of the participants cannot be discounted. There exist different ways each individual will be motivated to participate in the process.

“The influence of the individual's personality cannot be discounted in the knowledge sharing process. In a study conducted on knowledge sharing among educators, the individual's personality traits contribute to an individual's propensity to share knowledge (Zhang, Zhou, & Zhang, 2016). The individuals who were more agreeable, conscientious, and extroverted participated more often in the knowledge sharing process (Quan, Di, & Lan, 2015; Rajput & Talan, 2017; Zhang et al., 2016). The research on the influence of personality traits supports prior research which suggested effective knowledge sharing is dependent upon the participant's willingness to share individual experiences (Sawang et al., 2016). In establishing knowledge sharing practices, the personality traits of the participants cannot be discounted. Each personality type was motivated to participate in knowledge sharing in diverse ways. Effective knowledge sharing is a mutual exchange between participants. Although all five personality traits have unique contributions to the knowledge sharing process, agreeableness has the greater positive contribution (Quan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2016). The openness and willingness to exchange experiences and ideas is important for 58 knowledge sharing to

result in innovative ideas (Quan et al., 2015). Building trust between partners in a relationship is a key factor when trying to increase openness in sharing. Trust, within the framework of SET, grows from one of two roots. First, trust can grow from developing a close personal relationship (Blau, 1986). Second, trust can grow from the mutual exchanges (Blau, 1986). Within relationships and SET, the principle of reciprocity states that participants will receive mutual contributions to the relationship (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Lioukas and Reuer (2015) proposed that as each participant contributes to the knowledge sharing process because of seeking a mutual benefit rather than fulfilling a self-serving intention and trust will grow. Initially, trust begins within mutual exchanges. Lioukas and Reuer (2015) concluded that trust does not exist automatically because of social exchanges. Time cultivates trust. Over time, individuals build rapport through continual positive interactions. As individuals establish rapport with each other, trust grows out of the formation of close personal relationships (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Prior interactions and commitments within the alliance create a history of alliance members by which trust can exist through caring about the other member(s). This type of affect-based trust will help strengthen the alliance, enabling knowledge sharing to occur more naturally (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). As exchanges occur, feelings begin to form creating a deeper connection in the alliance. Even within close relationships, boundaries naturally exist. Lioukas and Reuer (2015) showed that certain boundaries exist within affect-based trust among business owners. The research suggested that when business owners are in less direct competition, the affect-based trust will be stronger (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). Trust will form more easily when business owners are not directly competing for the same shares within the market, and through less fear over revealing competitive advantages exists (Lioukas & Reuer, 2015). The identification of such boundaries is important when seeking to form relationships with other business owners. Individuals approach trust through the filters of his/her personality traits. Understanding the influence of personality helps unravel the mystery in building relationships. An individual's personality contributes to an individual's approach to placing trust in others and allowing trust to strengthen relationships (Rajput & Talan, 2017). Trust, quality relationships, and understanding of the role personality plays in knowledge

sharing will help increase the absorptive capacity of the participants. Trust enabled individuals to be more open in the knowledge sharing process.” The personality traits which comprise the Big Five Model include extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and intellect. Extroversion is the tendency of the individual to be sociable, adventurous, energetic, and assertive (Zvolensky, Taha, Bono, & Goodwin, 2015). Agreeableness is the ability to feel comfortable around others and the ability to be compliant and cooperative (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Conscientiousness is the tendency to be self-aware, self-disciplined, and organized (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Emotional stability encompasses the ability to evaluate and express emotion (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Intellect is the desire for innovative learning, creativity, and new ideas (Zvolensky et al., 2015). Personality traits are the unique expressions of the individual.

Development of Absorptive Capacity involves strength of the relationships and the knowledge exchanged based on mutual exchange between participants. It should be noted that all five personality traits have its distinct contribution to the development of Absorptive Capacity process; agreement between the participants contribute positively to the process (Quan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2016). Another important contributory factor in the development of Absorptive Capacity through quality relationships and knowledge exchange to bring forth innovative ideas is willingness and openness to exchange experience (Quan et al., 2015). Building trust and confidence between partners in a relationship is another important contributory factor that must be considered in the development of Absorptive Capacity when trying to imbibe the habit of openness in sharing.

5.3 Summary

This research work examine how service sector SME owners in Nigeria perceived Absorptive Capacity development through contributive factor of credible relationship and exchange of knowledge with other SME owners within the industry's social network. The analysis of the quality and reliable data collected in this study resulted in five themes. The themes include:

- 1) Engaging in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development
- 2) Participating in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development
- 3) Factors of Absorptive Capacity development
- 4) Influences of the SME owners personality
- 5) Cultivating credible relationships

The theoretical frameworks of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET) corroborated the results of this research study. The results demonstrated the influencing factors of the Absorptive Capacity. The factors of Absorptive Capacity identified through the individual experiences of the SME owners played a vital role in the participants' approach for Absorptive Capacity development.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) was evident through the participants' responses in that the individual experiences revealed the cultivation of credible relationships depend on mutual exchange.

CHAPTER 6: RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

6.1 Introduction

The emerging economies of the world and the economies of the developing countries such as Nigeria depend principally on the efficiency and performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) as its engine for growth and development. SMEs remained the engine for growth and development because it is the largest employer of labor and basically employ indigenous technology by harnessing local raw materials. SME's in Nigeria is characterized by dynamism, innovations, efficiency, and their size and organizational structure encourage quick decision-making process.

In a developing economy like Nigeria, owing to the essential feature and characteristics of the SMEs, the large chunk of the productive activities (formal and informal) are carried out in the SME sector. A growing and productive SME sector depicts improvement in the country's Gross Domestic Product. This also implies efficient and optimal utilization of the active workforce for the country, it also bring about growth and contribution to the GDP and an improvement in the growth of the real sector of the economy. The unemployment rate of the teeming young population will reduce and will also curb the brain-drain problem. The efficiency of the SME's will have a multiplier effect on the economy, it will assist the government in the proper implementation of Import-Substitution policy which will help greatly to correct the country's imbalance term of trade thereby resulting in surplus balance of payment. It will also help in improving the foreign reserve balance of the country thereby strengthening the Naira.

Globally, the government bureaucracy and policies are being designed to benefit and create conducive environment for the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), the government had realized that the SMEs are the tonic required for economic development and a veritable means of reducing the national economic burden. Presently in Nigeria, all the tiers of government and government parastatals are making frantic effort to create conducive atmosphere for smooth running and productive activities of the SME's, the Finance Bill

of 2020 was passed and assented to lessen the tax exposure of the SME, the statutory stamp duties, the incorporation fee, and the timing for registration of new business had been reviewed favorably to the benefit of the SME's. This policies and government directives tend to promote the growth and sustenance of SMEs.

The definition of Small and Medium businesses varies distinctively depending on the country and the perspective of the scholars providing the definition of the terms. In Nigeria, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are generally referred to as enterprises with up to 500 employees. According to the [Ministry of Industry, Trade, and Investment](#), Nigeria has well over 37.07 million Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), and they employed more than 84 percent of the Nigeria total workforce. In addition, the ministry pointed out that the SMEs in the country generates about 48.5 percent of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and also account for almost 7.27 percent of the country's exports.

Meanwhile, the ability of a business entity to be prepared and positioned to take advantage of innovation, invention, technological and scientific breakthrough, comprehend and implement effectively and profitably is essential to good entrepreneurial abilities. This essential entrepreneurial quality (or rather set of abilities) was considered an organizational Absorptive Capacity. The general belief is that Absorptive Capacity development is connected to a set of company's procedures and operational processes which form the bedrock of the company's technological advancement acquisition which they seems to have comprehended, mastered and effectively implement and become very proficient on the skill acquired. The company will embark on Internal Research and Development (R&D) to sharpen and fine tune the acquisition. Investment on Research and Development is one of the important indicators for the measurement of the level of Absorptive Capacity in any given SME as one of the variables of measurement, increase the Absorptive Capacity of a company, this implies that a company's investment in Research and Development (R&D) is proportional to its level of Absorptive Capacity development.

One of the factors contributing to the increasing success of SMEs is the development of Absorptive Capacity. In line with the study conducted by Turner and Endres (2017), Absorptive Capacity development and effective implementation of acquired innovative idea in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) through the network of numerous stakeholders in the sector was largely classified as very essential.

Absorptive Capacity is the ability to recognize the importance of innovation through technological and scientific breakthrough, comprehend such innovation and implement it in a brilliant way and also make it an essential part of the organization's process, procedure, practice and policy (Cohen and Levinthal 1989, 1990; Zahra and George 2002).

One of the center-point of this study was how service sector SME cope with the challenges of Absorptive Capacity development. Skills acquired through Absorptive Capacity development are only beneficial when SMEs implement effectively to solve existing organizational problems which later had a resultant effect in improving current condition progressively.

Absorptive Capacity development posed a great challenge to service sector SMEs thereby hindering the sector in benefiting from technological advancement and managerial development (Yoo, Sawyerr, & Tan, 2016).

The major obstacle impeding the development of Absorptive Capacity in the service sector SMEs are inadequate resources (man, material and financial) effective implementation and efficient utilization of the acquired innovative idea (Yoo & et al., 2016). The readiness of SMEs to embrace innovative idea comes with its attendant limitations (Yoo & et al., 2016).

The study is concerned with the contribution of Absorptive Capacity development to the success of service sector SME's in Nigeria.

6.2 Summary of The Research

This research work examine how service sector SME owners in Nigeria perceive Absorptive Capacity development through contributive factors of quality relationship and exchange of knowledge with other SME's owners within the industry's social network. The analysis of the quality and reliable data collected in this study resulted in five overall themes. The themes include:

- 1) Engaging in Knowledge Exchange
- 2) Participating in Exchange of knowledge
- 3) Factors of Absorptive Capacity development
- 4) Influences of the SME's owners personality
- 5) Building quality relationships

The theoretical frameworks of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET) complemented the results of this research study. The results demonstrated the influencing factors of the Absorptive Capacity. The factors of absorptive capacity identified through the individual experiences of the SME owners played a vital role in the participants' approach for Absorptive Capacity development.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) was evident through the participants' responses in that the individual experiences revealed the cultivation of quality relationships depend on mutual exchange.

There are three well-structured research questions that provide the guidelines for this qualitative descriptive study. The first research question established the primary objective of the study in respect of the contribution of quality relationships and exchange of knowledge among the owners of service sector SMEs to the development of Absorptive Capacity. The study carried out the detailed evaluation of the challenges SME owners face while trying to initiate knowledge exchange through the second research question. The effects of

personality and quality relationships on the development of Absorptive Capacity were examined through the third research question.

Questionnaire, interview session, and focus group discussion are the multiple sampling method and source of primary data collected for the purpose of the study. The use of multiple primary source of data collection provided improves the quality and reliability of the data collected for the success of the research.

6.3 Achieving Research Objectives

The aim of the qualitative descriptive research study is to examine how owners' of SMEs perceived knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationships within the SMEs industry's network contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity amongst service sector SMEs in Nigeria.. The research objectives include:

- 1) Gain a deeper understanding of small business owners' experiences with knowledge sharing and perceptions of relationships with other small business owners through a questionnaire, interviews, and a focus group
- 2) Identification of existing small business owners' strategies to develop absorptive capacity through perceptions of knowledge sharing and the quality of relationships.
- 3) Expand current research by exploring how small business owners utilize knowledge sharing which is a form of collective learning as a tool for the small business owner to achieve success.
- 4) Recommend a framework on how small business owners leverage resources such as time and technology to cultivate impactful relationships with other small business owners.
- 5) Contribute to Absorptive Capacity Theory and Social Exchange Theory as well as also advice policy makers and SME owners on the development of absorptive capacity for service sector SMEs.

Each of the first three objectives has been addressed in chapters 4 and 5. These 2 Chapters looked at the first three research objectives with specific reference to the SMEs in the services sector. The fourth and Fifth objective was addressed in chapter 6, which focused on contributions of the research ,both theory and practical.

The following research questions provided the required guidelines for this study:

- ❖ RQ1: How does SME owners' perception of knowledge exchange and quality of relationships with other SME's aid the development of absorptive capacity?
- ❖ RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve knowledge sharing with other SMES?
- ❖ RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners?

RQ1 is the major focus of this study which also underpins RQ2 and RQ3. RQ1 was very useful in understanding how the ability of SME owners in absorbing and transferring knowledge back into the business affects the development of absorptive capacity. RQ1 also provided personal insights into participant perception of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship with other SME owners which helped to understand how knowledge exchange and quality of relationships affects the development of absorptive capacity.

RQ2 was helpful in describing approaches deployed by SME owners towards improving the capitalization of knowledge exchange opportunities. SME owners that were interviewed came from differing backgrounds with varying personalities which helped to get a broader image of the many obstacles being faced in the process of knowledge exchange as well as the different approaches SME owners use in tackling these obstacles.

An in-depth understanding of factors affecting the development of absorptive capacity will reveal other factors besides perception of knowledge exchange. Strength of the relationships is another factor that affects the absorptive capacity development for SME owners. RQ3 was instrumental in exploring how quality of relationship with other SME owners affect the development of Absorptive Capacity by enabling the collection of data on the impactful nature of relationships as well as approaches used by SME owners to initiate and/or develop relationships with other SME owners.

RQ1 and RQ2 are both connected to the Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT). Through RQ1, data was collected which showed how each participant in the study identify opportunities to engage in knowledge exchange. RQ2 on the other hand delved into the ability to transfer knowledge back to the organization as well as the attendant obstacles. Between RQ1 and RQ2, an image is created of the perception of knowledge exchange by each participant as well as approaches deployed to tackle knowledge exchange challenges towards the development of Absorptive Capacity.

RQ1 and RQ3 on the other hand are linked to the Social Exchange Theory (SET). Strength of the relationships is another highly influential factor in the development of Absorptive Capacity. SET made it possible to examine how each participant navigates the process of cultivating relationships. Through Research Question 1 (RQ 1), strength of the relationships are considered to be very essential in the building of trust in respect of the sources of the knowledge to be exchanged. Research Question 3 (RQ 3) provided different experiences of the SME owners in deploying resources such as technology and time to develop relationships with other SME owners. The Social Exchange Theory provided the background for the elucidation of individual experiences from RQ1 and RQ3.

Collectively; RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3 jointly filled the long existing void in the literature. This vacuum in literature was identified as exploring how small business owners' perception of knowledge exchange and the strength of the relationship contribute to the development of Absorptive Capacity (Olaniran, 2017; Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). By using the three research which were the signal board for the research study, individual experience of the SME's owners were elicited in respect of Absorptive Capacity development through knowledge exchange and dependable relationships.

The following lists the basic themes which provide answers to each research question as discussed above as well as form a framework on how small business owners leverage resources such as time and technology to cultivate impactful relationships with other small business owners. :

❖ **RQ1: How do SME owners perceive exchange of knowledge and relationship quality with other SME's as aiding the development of absorptive capacity?**

- 1) Direct physical participation in the process of Knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development is preferred, but technology enable participation through the social media to be more convenient.
- 2) Professional organizations provide established Knowledge exchange programs with specific goals.
- 3) Individual SME owners' personality is highlighted as a major motivating factor that motivates SME owners to participate in knowledge exchange programs.

RQ2: What challenges do SME owners face in a bid to initiate and/or improve exchange of knowledge with other SMEs?

- 1) Limited and inadequate resources affect knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity.
- 2) Relevancy of the Content.
- 3) Individual SME owners' perceptions of value in knowledge exchange engagement..
- 4) Previous experiences of the SME owners influence the approach adopted in participating in Knowledge exchange activities.
- 5) The Knowledge experience is improved by Socializing.
- 6) Engagement in knowledge exchange is affected by negative experiences.
- 7) Business operations are strengthened by previous positive experience.

RQ3: How do SME owners develop and maintain quality relationships with other small business owners?

- 1) Established quality relationships affects participating in knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development.
- 2) Establishing quality relationships intentionally limit the challenges of knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity process.
- 3) Mentorship is identified as an important resource for every SME's owner.
- 4) Mentees should also try as much as possible to provide mentorship for others.
- 5) Personality type affects how quality relationships are built and nurtured.
- 6) Consistency in meeting people who share common goals and values .
- 7) Trust is the end result of established quality relationships and improves the knowledge exchange experience.
- 8) Relationships are best cultivated by showing interest in the other person.

6.4 Contribution to The Research

“This study is one of only a handful of studies that has been constructed purposely to explore the internal processes leading to the enhancement of ACAP, specifically, for SMEs, operating in the services sector. The contribution is, therefore twofold, in that, the study aims to address gaps that are evident in the literature, by tailoring an ACAP model pertinent to firms, which evidence the characteristics of SMEs in terms of size, agility, leadership characteristics and resource limitations, and also, because the model has been designed specifically for firms that operate in the services sector, where the ACAP literature published so far, is limited.

This study is also somewhat unique in that it focuses on development of absorptive capacity amongst service sector SMEs in Nigeria, where dedicated literature is even more scant. It also contributes directly by qualitatively testing existing ACAP models in use in the different service sector SMEs and attempted to construct a comprehensive ACAP framework for small and medium sized firms operating in the SMEs operating in this sector as well as to assist in the enhancement of innovation. Consequently, it offers valuable insights and guidance on the optimization of resources and capabilities of firms to match internal competences with competitiveness implications for SMEs operating in these industries.”

The data collected from the participants contributed to filling the vacuum left by the previous research. Turner and Endres (2017) a renowned scholar recommended that future research studies should include research of the SME owners in multiple industries. Based on this recommendation, the SME owners who participated in this research represented many parts of the service sector, it includes marketing, consulting, publishing, financial management, health coaching, travel, and holistic coaching. Contributions of the stakeholders from different part of the sector play a pivotal role in understanding the perception of service sector owners of the SME on Absorptive Capacity development through the contribution of quality relationships and knowledge exchange within the social network of the industry.

The relevance of the content of Absorptive Capacity development program stimulates active participation thereby resulting in successful development of Absorptive Capacity among the service sector SMEs in Nigeria.

Sawang & et al. (2016) recommended that future research study should focus on individual SME's owner's experience with the knowledge gained, including the resources required for the acquisition of the knowledge. The participants' responses which provides answers to Research Question 1 (RQ1) identified technology and time as two major resources impeding the participation of SME's owners in Absorptive Capacity development process.

Also, quality relationships contributed greatly to the Absorptive Capacity development of individual SME owners.

Yoo et al. (2016) suggested that future research should x-ray how quality relationships and relational capital influence Absorptive Capacity development. The participants' responses in respect of the factors that influence Absorptive Capacity development through quality relationships and knowledge exchange complements the previous research by contributing qualitative data that affirmed the previous quantitative research. The individual experiences helps in creating a literature that enhanced the performance and growth of the service sector SME's. The participants' responses provides answers to Research Question 2 (RQ 2), the responses also provided the factors that contributes to knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development.

The personality of individual SME's owners' contributes to participation in Absorptive Capacity development process through quality relationships and knowledge exchange among the SME's owners within the industry's social network. The need for future research study as suggested by Olaniran (2017), includes the identification of personality traits of individual SME owners that express willingness and readiness to participate in Absorptive Capacity development process. The data collected provides answers to Research Question 3 (RQ 3) by identifying how certain personality types engaged in Absorptive Capacity

development process through cultivation of credible relationships and knowledge exchange. The participants' responses presented the strategies used by the participants to curtail the challenges and impediments generated by personality traits.

The research study provides several brilliant contributions and idea, this includes theoretical, practical and future implications. The sections below discuss each of the contributions in details.

6.4.1 Theoretical Contributions

6.4.1.1 Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT)

Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) served as the general theoretical construct for this study, the theoretical concept of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) was propounded by Cohen and Levinthal (1990). ACT provides substantive definition for the results of the research study. The two major phases of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) provide insights into Absorptive Capacity development process.

ACT consists of two major phases – The Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC) and Realized Absorptive Capacity (RAC) (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC) involves the processes of identifying potential sources of knowledge and its acquisition. The data analysis produced two significant themes (see Appendix T) which demonstrated the concept of Potential Absorptive Capacity (PAC). The interview sessions and focus group discussions produced detailed reports of techniques adopted by the participants to identify sources of knowledge. The techniques adopted in identifying sources of knowledge includes recommendations by SME owners, following the steps of individual SME owners based on their reputation and level of success in the industry, internet surfing and browsing with specific topics in mind.

The influence of Social Exchange Theory (SET) presented additional details that emerge in the course of the data analysis as the participants identified quality relationships and social exchange as factors that influenced participation in Absorptive Capacity development process.

The second process within Absorptive Capacity Theory is the acquisition of knowledge, knowledge acquisition process involves lengthy period of time. The results, as presented in Chapter 4, presented time as a scarce resource for SME owners; this is identified as one of the great challenges in knowledge acquisition. Participants that preferred direct physical participation in Absorption Capacity development process will have to invest much of their time into the process while the participants that preferred a more convenient ways of participation in the process will relied on technology and other internet based and online sources of

knowledge acquisition.. The use of technology and direct physical interaction presented the importance of Absorptive Capacity development.

The methods adopted in knowledge acquisition helped in expanding the concept of ACT in line with the evolution of technology which has helped in facilitating accessibility to convenient Absorptive Capacity development process. The options that are available to the SME owners through technology and online resources were absent at time Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) is conceptualized.

The success of innovation depends on effective implementation of the acquired knowledge into the SME's operations.

The third process of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) is knowledge transfer through effective implementation of the acquired knowledge (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). The participants presented several factors that influenced participation in Absorptive Capacity development process. Personal factors influencing Absorptive Capacity development at this stage include the ability to understand technology, lack of desire to engage in irrelevant topics, Absorptive Capacity development topics, and inadequate time to engage the topic on a personal level to broaden understanding.

The method adopted taken by participants include intentionally avoiding some topics of Absorptive Capacity development process or delegating other participants within the network to attend the program. Another important factor identified from the interview session to impacts the SME owners participation in Absorptive Capacity development is the ability to harmonize the newly acquired knowledge with the SME's goals and operations. One of the participants that participated in the interview session shared his experience for implementing a change in operations because of the knowledge acquired through the knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development program he had attended earlier. The participants reported that inability to properly harmonize the newly acquired knowledge with the goals of the SME distracted the subsequent participation of the participant in Absorptive Capacity development process. Lack of focus by the participant caused the SME to experience reduction in productivity.

The research study broadens the theoretical framework of ACT. The literature review presented the growth and importance of SME's to the development and growth of the Nigeria economy. The technological advancement created the window of opportunity for individual SME's owners to source and acquires knowledge that will enhance the performance and success of the SME's operational activities. The dependence on the use of technology by the participants presented techniques and strategies which help in improving the capacity absorption. Technology provides the participants with a more convenient ways of participating in Absorptive Capacity development process where challenges such as time constraints, inadequate resources and the irrelevant Absorptive Capacity development topics were present. The individual participant experience in respect of strategies adopted which leveraged on technology to engage in Absorptive Capacity development activities by the SME's owners deepened the concept of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT).

6.4.1.2 Social Exchange Theory (SET)

The second theoretical framework that provides support for this research study is Social Exchange Theory (SET). Social Exchange Theory (SET) provides a framework that identifies how individuals interact with each other (Blau, 1986). The experiences shared by individual participants exhibited the principles of Social Exchange Theory (SET) in action.

The principle of Social Exchange Theory (SET) identified mutual respects and interest shared among the participants serves as the foundation in cultivating credible relationships. One of the themes (see Appendix T), that emerged from the interview sessions and focus group discussions reveals that cultivating quality relationships is a result of intentionally being consistent in meeting people who share common goals and visions. The relationships between participants created an opportunity to get familiarized and know each other more personally. The strength of the relationships between the SME's owner bring about trust among the owners.

The trust aspect of relationship is another important factor identified by Social Exchange Technology. Blau (1986) suggested that as individual SME owners trust each other, the mutual exchange of ideas and knowledge becomes easier. Consistency in participating in Absorptive Capacity activities over time builds trust (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Data collected in this research study revealed high frequency of trust in the response provided by the participants in respect of knowledge engagement for Absorptive Capacity development engagement. Several participants indicated that without trust; capacity development process engagement will be impossible

Throughout the process of data collections and analysis, evidence of the support provided by Social Exchange Theory (SET) is very obvious and crystal clear. The SME owners that participated in the research the study exhibited the principles of SET through the collective experiences of the individual SME owners' about Absorptive Capacity development activities. This study supports trust and mutual engagement as important contributive factor for the success of Absorptive Capacity development process.

6.4.2 Future Contributions

The basis of the future implications of the qualitative descriptive research study is based on the finding of this study. Although the research study includes the description of various experiences of SME owners in Absorptive Capacity development process through quality relationships and exchange of knowledge with other SME owners, in spite of elaborate qualitative description, there exist some limitations in respect of the research study. The sample size used in the study is made up of small number of service sector SME owners in Nigeria. The sampling helped to cover the vacuum left behind by previous research study by focusing on the SME industries in the sampling (Turner & Endres, 2017). In addition, repeating the study in other regions with varying population densities would help improve the probability of improved general results for the SME industries.

Another important future implication to be taken into cognizance from this study is that 22 out of the 26 interview and focus group discussion participants employed not more than 5 employees. The examination of the process through SME businesses with larger number of personnel should be a consideration for future research. Previous research identified inadequate resources as a limiting factor in participating in Absorptive Capacity development process (Yoo et al., 2016), time and manpower was identified as the major resources required participating in direct physical exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development process, SME's owners with larger number of personnel would also expand the generalizations from this study.

6.5 FRAMEWORK FOR SMALL BUSINESS OWNERS

In examining the perception of SME owners on the contributions of quality relationships and knowledge exchange to the development of Absorptive Capacity, several practical implications emerged from the results of this study from which a framework was developed. The ability to absorb knowledge positively impacts the success of the SME's (Kuhn & Galloway, 2013). Trust was identified as a factor influencing knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development (Muhammad & Sadia, 2016). The following recommendations provide strategic direction for consideration by SME owners which can help to improve the Absorptive Capacity development and the quality of relationships.

The results of the study suggested that participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process is an important activity in the SME owners' schedule. Previous research suggested that examining the SME owner's experience with the resources used in the acquisition of knowledge (Sawang & et al., 2016). The results revealed that direct physical method of engagement in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process is the most preferred method by the participants. However, technology and online resources availed the participants with opportunity to engage in exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development process where there are difficulties and challenges like scarcity of time and inadequate personnel limiting the adopting of direct physical method of participation.

Scarcity of time has been identified as a major challenge impeding the SME's owners from participating in the knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process and benefiting from the activities. The current market conditions influence the relevancy of knowledge (Silva et al., 2016). The discussions revealed two methods used by the participants, one of the strategies helped in selecting relevant topics for exchange of knowledge for the Absorptive Capacity development process; this is successfully carried by relying on recommendations of the stakeholders in the SME industry. The second identified strategy is the adoption of online resources such as social media and podcasts to have more control over selecting relevant knowledge exchange development topics and contents. The identification of the best method of engaging in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process and the selection of relevant content will

improve the level of participation by the SME's owners; this is in support of the first phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory. This will further help the SME's owners improve the owners ability to identify relevant sources of knowledge and improve effective implementation of the knowledge.

Previous research study identified trust as a contributive factor to the successful development of Absorptive Capacity. Knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development depends on trust (Blau, 1986; Olaniran, 2017).

Social Exchange Theory (SET) postulated that cultivating quality relationships through mutual exchanges build trust (Blau, 1986). The participants discussed trust as being an important factor for accepting knowledge and innovative idea from other SME owners. The desires to accept knowledge is the second phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory. Strategies to improve trust include cultivating quality relationships with other SME's owner's small. Intentionally engaging other SME owners creates the possibility for development of quality relationship. Cultivating quality relationships can be as simple as making a phone call or having a lunch with other SME's owners. Other strategies that can be adopted in cultivating quality relationships is making referrals which exhibited mutual respect and sense of belongings with other SME's owners. The act of cultivating quality relationships must be intentional and consistent in order to strengthen trust and confidence of SME's owner to participate in Absorptive Capacity development process. The overall effects of cultivating quality relationships which further strengthen trust and confidence results in the improvement to the second phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT).

The third phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory is the effective implementation of the acquired knowledge within the SME for improved performance. Inadequate resources are a major constraint that can impede effective implementation of the acquired innovative idea from the Absorptive Capacity development process. The challenge of inadequate resources focused on the importance of social capital, social capital is the potential value in cultivating relationships (Moyes et al., 2015). One of the strategies adopted in the acquiring knowledge is to form partnership with the SME's owners that are much experienced and strength in a specific area of the SME's operations. One of the participants confirmed that a lack of understanding of

the acquired knowledge delay effective implementation of the acquired knowledge. Cultivating quality relationships increase the number of contacts who can assist with the implementation of the acquired idea. Quality relationships with SME's owners can bring about opportunity to trade skills or services.

Capitalizing on exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity is the fourth phase of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT), the ability to create new products or improve on the existing operational system and procedure through innovation is the positive return on investment (ROI) in respect of Absorptive Capacity development process. To improve the Absorptive Capacity of this phase, the participants identified that having a mentor helped with accountability and provide quick resolution of operational and other business challenge. Mentoring has been recognized to be very to the success of the SME's (Grose, 1974). The accountability helped to keep focus on primary goals and objectives, while having mentor to discuss challenges in implementation helped with adjusting strategies to achieve goals.

Quality relationships is very essential to Absorptive Capacity development process, to achieve the primary goals and objective of the SME seamlessly require the SME owners to cultivate quality and welcoming relationships with other SME owners within the industry's social network (Man-pil et al., 2017). The approach and system for initiating and cultivating quality relationships varies for individual SME owners and their peculiar situation. The objective is to be intentional in and consistent in cultivating quality relationships with other SME owners.

6.6 Research Limitations

The research study have some area of strength, firstly, the interview sessions is made up of 20 participants who are SME owners with more than one year business experience. The interview session participants sample size is formed from the combination of different array of personality types as well as individuals who participated in Absorptive Capacity development process at regular interval and those that seldom participating in the process. Previous quantitative research did not recognized the different personalities. The different experiences of the participants provided broader insights by examining the experience of the individual SME owners that participate in the Absorptive Capacity development through cultivating quality relationships and exchange of knowledge among SME owners. As a result, the reliable and quality data collected through this qualitative descriptive study expanded the scope of previous quantitative research.

The other strength and competitive advantage of the study includes the use of multiple sources of data which provided triangulation for the study. Triangulation contributed towards the trustworthiness, validity, and credibility of the study (Yin, 2014). This system adopted in the research study allows comparison of the interview and focus group responses to the questionnaire responses, this provide an insight that motivates SME owners for participating in Absorptive Capacity development process.

The notable weakness of this study is the sample size of the SME owners in comparism to general population size of SME owners in Nigeria. A total of 60 SME owners were contacted and served with the questionnaire, only 51 completed the process by fully completing the questionnaire. A different sampling method would strengthen this study by involving more SME owners and different combination of personality types.

The primary source of the SME owners listing for the research study is another worthy weakness to the research. The service sector SME's that are enlisted on the membership register of two Chambers of commerce (Nigeria-British Chamber of Commerce, and Nigeria-America Chamber of Commerce) and the National Association of Small and Medium Enterprises (NASME) were used as the primary source for the listing and sampling of the SME's owners that are selected in the research study. The adopted strategies and

perceived influences of Absorptive Capacity development may be different among the SME owners in the local community network. Involving SME owners that are non-members of the two chambers of commerce (NBCC and NACC) and the SME owners association (NASME) would have probably provide deeper insights into personal perceptions of Absorptive Capacity development among SME's owners. Different environments may influence the importance placed on Absorptive Capacity development among SME owners.

Apart from the influence of quality relationships and exchange of knowledge on Absorptive Capacity development, one of the participants identified absence of relevant topics as another factor that hinders their participation in the knowledge exchange for absorptive capacity development process. The influence of the topics that was identified was not within the scope of this research study, however it should be considered for the overall success of knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities. Other important factors excluded from the scope of this research study were the frequency of knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development. The qualifications and experience of the knowledge provider are also factors also contribute to the success of knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development.

6.7 Recommendations For Future Research and Practice

The sections below presents the recommendations for future research study and practice based on the findings of this study. Future research addresses considerations to widen the results generated from this study. Future practice presents recommendations that will improve the Absorptive Capacity development of service sector SME owners through quality relationships and Exchange of knowledge among SME owners within the industry's social network.

6.7.1 Recommendations for Future Research

Previous research on Absorptive Capacity development presents the need to extend this research to service sector SME owners in Nigeria. The identified void in the existing literatures and the need to examine the importance of Absorptive Capacity development through credible relationships and exchange of knowledge among SME's owners (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). Previous research recommends that future research should include the study of how knowledge exchange and relational capital influence Absorptive Capacity development (Yoo et al., 2016).

The research study attempts to address the void identified in the previous research studies. To properly address this inadequacy, this created opportunities for future research to further examine factors influencing Absorptive Capacity development amongst SME owners.

A qualitative descriptive research study helped in addressing the void in the research study by examining the experience of individual SME owners. In view of the importance of the Small and Medium Enterprises for the growth and development of Nigeria economy, further probe into how Absorptive Capacity development is influenced by cultivating credible relationships and exchange of knowledge is required in order to employ the appropriate strategies to stimulate improved performance and the survival rate of SMEs in Nigeria. This research study is based on the theoretical framework of Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET). Absorptive Capacity Theory identifies four phases of absorbing knowledge (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). The individual SMEs owners must identify the source of the knowledge acquired by the

individual, the source of the knowledge transferred to the SME's, and later transformed into innovation (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). Combination of both theories (ACT and SET) provided the foundation for the evaluation of the process in respect of the influence of cultivating quality relationships and exchange of knowledge on the success of Absorptive Capacity development. Understanding the basic principles of the ACT and SET theories is essential for SME owners.

The research study is executed to satisfy two main goals in terms of expanding the theoretical framework. Firstly, the targeted goal of the study is to expand Absorptive Capacity Theory through the examination of how SMEs adapted to the various challenges of knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development process.

The second goal of the study is to add value to the Social Exchange Theory through the examination of the SME owner's perceptions about quality relationship as it contributes to Absorptive Capacity development experiences.

The results generated from the current research highlights approaches to be adopted for future research, previous research focused mainly on quantitative research in respect of knowledge exchange and credible relationships. The qualitative descriptive nature of the research study serves as the foundation for future research on the topics of Absorptive Capacity development and credible relationships.

Another good suggestion for the future research includes the sampling of other geographic regions, particularly SME owners in the sub-urban and rural communities. Rural communities present different challenges than urban areas. Most of the participants in the current research study travelled to neighboring towns to participate in the direct physical exchange of knowledge for Absorptive Capacity development activities. Evaluating the preferred method of participating in exchange of knowledge when there are limited opportunities will expand the practical applications of the study for SME owners.

Future researchers can also consider it necessary to examine other factors of Absorptive Capacity development. An emerging code in the current research indicated that the relevance of topic content

influenced participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities. The other influencing factors include the qualifications and experience of the presenters and the frequency of the activities. Future research should explore these and other factors that influence successful development of Absorptive Capacity.

The third necessary consideration for future research includes the effect of shifting from direct physical participation in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities to an online forum. The online forum could be any available internet platform such as social media, online teleconferencing, chat rooms, or discussion forums. If society faced a situation where social and physical contact is limited or restricted, the exploration of alternatives delivery method should be harnessed.

Finally, future researchers may consider evaluating the direct benefits of Absorptive Capacity development engagement for the SME owners through quality relationships and knowledge exchange. Current research focused on factors influencing the absorption of knowledge and approaches adopted by SME owners to cultivate quality relationships with other SME's owners within the industry's social network. Evaluating how Absorptive Capacity development stimulates innovation, aids the problem-solving ability, and improves customer relationships would expand future practices and help SME owners in achieving success.

The SME owners and researchers should consider two important recommendations for future practice. Firstly, the study emphasized the importance of knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development as a learning resource for SME owners. Limited time and financial resources to participate in formal learning is a major challenge for SME owners from learning opportunities which are affordable and available to large organizations. Identifying the right method of participating in knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities provides the SME owners access to knowledge and it increases the success rate of the SME. Understanding the factors that influence the absorption of knowledge facilitates the ability of the SME owners to identify, acquire, and transfer knowledge into the business activities of the SMEs. Based on the collective experience of individual SME owners presented in this research study, SME owners should actively pursue participating in Absorptive Capacity development.

The SME owners' personality in cultivating credible relationships presents another consideration for future practice. Cultivating credible relationships is an important practice for SME owners; the practice is laden with challenges in the form of time constraints and the fear of unhealthy competition. On the other hand, the cultivation of quality relationships builds trust. Trust presents the opportunities for SME owners to pursue common goals within the industry's social network at community level. Cultivating quality relationships with other SME owners lower the isolation tendency and the feeling of being alone in the business activities. The ability to connect with SME owners with much experience and passed through similar challenges helps in providing step by step approach to overcome the challenges confronting the SME's.

6.7.2 Recommendations for Future Practice

The results of this research study presented numerous recommendations that will be useful for future practice. Chapter 1 introduced the importance of Absorptive Capacity development through the contribution of cultivating quality relationships and knowledge sharing. Previous quantitative research emphasized the importance of Absorptive Capacity development. The research study produced a void in the literatures, the void was identified and this facilitates the evaluation of the contribution of knowledge exchange and credible relationships in the development of Absorptive Capacity among SME's owners (Sawang & et al., 2016; Turner & Endres, 2017; Yoo et al., 2016). Executing qualitative descriptive research study to x-ray the factors contributing to the Absorptive Capacity development through exchange of knowledge and cultivation of credible relationships among service sector SMEs in Nigeria helped to connect the missing link.

The questionnaire, in depth interviews and the focus group discussions help in broadening previous research. Absorptive Capacity Theory (ACT) and Social Exchange Theory (SET) bring about the development of the research questions. This study provides recommendations for future research and future practice to expand this study.

Given the results of this qualitative descriptive study, the researcher recommends that SME owners are required to understand the influence of effective knowledge exchange and cultivating quality relationships on the development of Absorptive Capacity. The SME owners should identify relevant knowledge exchange for Absorptive Capacity development activities at regular interval for participation in order to engage other SME owners. The findings of this study suggest that SME owners should endeavor to identify current goals and challenges within the SME. By identifying organizational goals, the owner can easily identify relevant Absorptive Capacity development activities that are useful for the achievement of the current goals and challenges.

The findings further suggest that SME owners should not only discover ways to acquire knowledge but to also give and transfer knowledge. Social Exchange Theory (SET) complements the findings by providing the

foundation that social exchanges are mutual. The mutual investment into the relationship, over time, builds credible relationships in the future. Absorptive Capacity development activities provide the SME owners with an opportunity to learn from the experience of individual SME owners.

Another recommendation for SME owners is to be intentional in cultivating quality relationships. Quality relationships strengthen development of Absorptive Capacity, the intentionality of cultivating quality relationships, regardless of whether the act is a phone call, text message, or meeting for lunch helps in building trust between individual SME owners.

Lastly, it is recommended that SME owners should diligently consider participating in Absorptive Capacity development knowledge exchange activities. The fear of protecting trade secrets should not impede the SME owners from benefiting from the Absorptive Capacity development activities through effective knowledge exchange and cultivation of quality relationships. All participants in the study recognized the benefits of Absorptive Capacity development with other SME owners. The larger percentage of the participants consistently participates in Absorptive Capacity development because of the benefits discussed in this study. Participating in Absorptive Capacity development frequently resulted in building of quality relationships with other SME owners.

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Appendix A.**Site Authorization Letters***Letter sent from researcher*

Hi,

My name is Olakunle Jamiu Agboola a doctoral student at the University of West Scotland, under the direction of Dr. Lucy Lu, working towards my Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) degree.

My research work is based on the perception of the owners of service sector SME's in Nigeria towards the development of Absorptive Capacity through the contributory factor of quality relationships and knowledge exchange within the industry's social network.

I write to seek your permission to avail me with your latest industry directory to enable me identify and contact stakeholders in the SME industry to complete a questionnaire to facilitate the completion of my research work on the perception of owners of the service sector in the development of Absorptive Capacity through strengthening of quality relationship among the owners of SMEs and effective exchange of knowledge within the industry's social network. I am seeking to engage 20 distinct owners of the service sector SMEs for this purpose.

I look forward to your favorable consideration and prompt response. Should you require further clarification please do not hesitate to contact me.

Thank you.

Yours faithfully,

Olakunle Jamiu Agboola

National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME)

XXXXXX <XXXXXX@Nasme.com>

Thu 1/06 , 10:28 AM Olakunle Jamiu Agboola

Mr. Agboola,

We will be glad to avail you our latest directory for the purpose of your study, we do not charge for the directory.

We wish you the very best and successful completion of the research.

Thank you.

Yours faithfully,

For: National Association of Small and Medium Scale (NASME)

Executive Vice President

Nigeria British Chamber of commerce

XXXXXX <XXXXXXXX@nbcc.com> Mon 3/6, 9:27 AM

Olakunle Jamiu Agboola

Hi Olakunle,

You are welcome to utilize our business directory.

Sincerely,

XXXXXXXX@nbcc.com

Nigeria American Chamber of Commerce

XXXXXX <XXXXXX@nacc.com> Thu 1/10,

10:28AM Olakunle Agboola

Hi Olakunle

Please feel free to utilize the Nigeria American chamber of commerce website Member

Search for your study.

Good luck to you on your study.

My best,

Appendix B.
Ethics Approval Letter

Appendix C.

Informed Consent: Questionnaire

This form gives you information to consider when deciding to participate in this study. This form records the consent of those who agree to participate in the study.

RESEARCH

Olakunle Agboola, a Doctoral student in the School of Business and Creative Industries, University of West Scotland , has invited your participation in a research study.

STUDY PURPOSE

The purpose of the research is to look at how SME owners' perception of knowledge exchange and quality of relationships with other SME's aid the development of absorptive capacity in Service Sector SMEs in Nigeria?

ELIGIBILITY

You are eligible to participate in this research if you:

- 1) Own a small business
- 2) Participate in learning opportunities with other small business owners
- 3) Build relationships with other small business owners

You are not eligible to participate in this research if you

- 1) Are not a small business
- 2) Do not participate in knowledge exchange with other small business owners
- 3) Do not build relationships with other small business owners

DESCRIPTION OF RESEARCH ACTIVITY

If you decide to participate, then as a study participant you will be asked to:

1. Complete a survey
2. Share experiences relating to experiences in learning activities with other small business owners
3. Share experiences relating to relationships with other small business owners

Participants may skip questions if necessary.

Approximately 60 subjects will be participating in this research study.

RISKS

If you decide to participate in this research study, then you may face some risks such as:

1. Sharing negative experiences with other small business owners To

decrease the impact of these risks, you can:

1. Skip any question in the process
2. Stop participation at any time
3. Refuse to answer any question

BENEFITS

If you decide to participate direct benefits to you are:

1. Receive a copy of the results once results are published If you

decide to participate indirect benefits to you are:

1. Gain insights as to what other small business owners are doing to capitalize on learning opportunities
2. Learn more about external sources of information to better support your business

ANONYMITY

All information collected in this study is anonymous unless disclosure is required by law. What you say and how you answer the questions in this survey cannot be connected to you. The results of this research study may be used in reports, presentations, and publications. The researchers will not identify you. In order to maintain anonymity of your records, Olakunle Agboola will...

Create the survey to be an anonymous survey. By doing so, no personally identifying data will be collected including names, locations, addresses, ipaddresses, or other identifying data.

The people who will have access to your responses are:

1. Olakunle Agboola, Doctoral Student
2. Dr. Lucy Lu, Dissertation Supervisor
3. Other members of the doctoral process at University of West Scotland as needed.

I will secure your information with these steps:

1. Create the questions to be anonymous
2. Not collect any identifying participant data.
3. Keep your data for 3 years.
4. Delete electronic data and destroy paper data after 3 years.

WITHDRAWAL PRIVILEGE

It is ok for you to decline to participate in this research study. Even if you say yes now, you are free to say no later, and stop participating at any time, there will be no penalty to you.

If you decide to stop participation, you may do so by: Answering “I wish to withdraw” in the last question read then exit the online survey at any time. If so, I will not use the information I gathered from you.

Your decision will not affect your relationship with the researcher or University of West Scotland or otherwise cause a loss of benefits to which you might otherwise be entitled.

I may stop your participation, even if you did not ask me to, if: The survey results become focused on negative experiences in either learning opportunities or relationships with other small business owners.

COST AND PAYMENTS

There is no financial cost to you as a participant in this study, nor is there payment for your participation.

COMPENSATION FOR INJURY OR ILLNESS

If you agree to participate in the study, then your consent does not waive any of your legal rights. However, no funds have been set aside to compensate you in the event of injury.

VOLUNTARY CONSENT

Any questions you have concerning the research study or your participation in the study, before or after your consent, will be answered by Olakunle Agboola,

This form explains the nature, demands, benefits and any risk of the research study. By clicking "I Agree" you confirm that you are 18 years or older, understand the content of this form, and agree to participate in this study.

Appendix D.

Informed Consent: Interviews

This form provides information to consider when deciding to participate in this study. This form records the consent of those who agree to participate.

RESEARCH

Olakunle Agboola, who is a doctoral learner in the College of Business University of West Scotland, has invited you to take part in a research study.

STUDY PURPOSE

The first purpose of this study is to explore how small business owners take part in exchange of knowledge. The second purpose is to explore the benefits of relationships with other small business owners.

ELIGIBILITY

You may take part in this study if you:

1. Own a small business
2. Participate in exchange of knowledge
3. Build relationships with other small business owners

You may not take part in this study if you

1. Are not a small business
2. Do not take part in knowledge exchange
3. Do not build relationships with other small business owners

DESCRIPTION OF RESEARCH ACTIVITY

If you decide to take part, then you will be asked to:

1. Schedule an interview online using Zoom.com
2. Share experiences relating to exchange of knowledge
3. Share experiences relating to relationships with other small business owners

You may skip questions if necessary. 12 - 15 small business owners will take part in the interviews.

RISKS

If you choose to take part in this study, then you may face some risks such as:

1. Sharing negative experiences with other small business owners To decrease the risks, you can:

1. Skip any question in the process
2. Stop participation at any time
3. Refuse to answer any question

BENEFITS

If you decide to take part, direct benefits to you are:

1. Receive a copy of the results once results are published If you decide to participate indirect benefits to you are:

1. Get ideas on what other small business owners are doing to benefit from knowledge sharing
2. Learn more about sources of information to help your business

ANONYMITY

All information collected will be anonymous unless disclosure is required by law. Your answers to the questions in this study cannot be connected to you. The results may be used in reports, presentations, and publications. You will not be identified. In order to maintain anonymity, Olakunle Agboola will...

Assign each interviewee a unique identification number. No personal data will be collected including names, locations, addresses, ip addresses, or other identifying data.

The people who will have access to your responses are:

1. Olakunle Agboola, doctoral learner

2. Dr. Lucy Lu, Dissertation Supervisor
3. Other members of the doctoral process at University of West Scotland as needed

I will secure your information with these steps:

1. Create the questions to be anonymous
2. Not collect any identifying participant data.
3. Keep your data for 3 years.
4. Delete electronic data and destroy paper data after 3 years.

WITHDRAWAL PRIVILEGE

It is ok for you to decline to participate in this research study. Even if you say yes now, you are free to say no later, and stop participating at any time, there will be no penalty to you.

If you decide to stop participation, you may do so by: Answering “I wish to withdraw” in the last question read then exit the survey at any time. If so, I will not use the information I gathered from you.

Your decision will not affect your relationship with the University of West Scotland or cause a loss of benefits to which you might be entitled.

I may stop your participation, even if you did not ask me to, if: The question results become focused on negative experiences in either learning opportunities or relationships with other small business owners.

COST AND PAYMENTS

There is no financial cost to you as a participant in this study. There is no payment for your participation.

COMPENSATION FOR INJURY OR ILLNESS

If you agree to participate in the study, then your consent does not waive any of your

legal rights. However, no funds have been set aside to compensate you in the event of injury.

VOLUNTARY CONSENT

Any questions you have concerning the study or your participation, before or after your consent, will be answered by Olakunle Agboola at kunleagboola@live.com.

This form explains the nature, demands, benefits and any risk of the project. By signing this form, you agree to assume any risks involved. Remember, your part is voluntary. You may choose not to take part. You may withdraw your consent and discontinue your part at any time without penalty or loss of benefit. In signing this consent form, you are not waiving any legal claims, rights, or remedies. A copy of this form will be offered to you for your record purpose.

Your signature below indicates that you consent to take part in the above study.

_____ Subject's

Signature Printed Name Date

"I certify that I have explained to the above individual the nature and purpose, the potential benefits and possible risks associated with participation in this research study, have answered any questions that have been raised, and have witnessed the above

signature. These elements of Informed Consent conform to the Assurance given by University of West Scotland to protect the rights of human subjects. I have provided (offered) the subject/participant a copy of this signed consent document."

Signature of Investigator _____

Date _____

Appendix E.

Informed Consent: Focus Group

This form provides information to consider when deciding to participate in this study.

This form records the consent of those who agree to participate.

RESEARCH

Olakunle Agboola, who is a doctoral student at the University of West Scotland, has invited you to take part in a research study.

STUDY PURPOSE

The first purpose of this study is to explore how small business owners take part in knowledge exchange. The second purpose is to explore the benefits of relationships with other small business owners.

ELIGIBILITY

You may take part in this study if you:

1. Own a small business
2. Participate in exchange of knowledge
3. Build relationships with other small business owners

may not take part in this study if you

1. Are not a small business
2. Do not take part in knowledge exchange
3. Do not build relationships with other small business owners

DESCRIPTION OF RESEARCH ACTIVITY

If you decide to take part, then you will be asked to:

1. Schedule a focus group online using Zoom.com
2. Share experiences relating to exchange of knowledge with other business owners
3. Share experiences relating to relationships with other small business owners

You may skip questions if necessary. 7 – 10 small business owners will take part in the focus group.

RISKS

If you choose to take part in this study, then you may face some risks such as:

1. Sharing negative experiences with other small business owners To decrease the risks, you can:

1. Skip any question in the process
2. Stop participation at any time
3. Refuse to answer any question

BENEFITS

If you decide to take part, direct benefits to you are:

1. Receive a copy of the results once results are published If you decide to participate indirect benefits to you are:

1. Get ideas on what other small business owners are doing to benefit from knowledge exchange
2. Learn more about sources of information to help your business

ANONYMITY

All information collected will be anonymous unless disclosure is required by law. Your answers to the questions in this study cannot be connected to you. The results may be used in reports, presentations, and publications. You will not be identified. In order to maintain anonymity, Olakunle Agboola will...

Assign each focus group member a unique identification number. The identification number will be used to label participant responses. No personal data will be collected including names, locations, addresses, or other identifying data.

The people who will have access to your responses are:

1. Olakunle Agboola, doctoral learner
2. Dr. Lucy Lu, Dissertation Supervisor
3. Other members of the doctoral process at University of West Scotland as needed

I will secure your information with these steps:

1. Create the questions to be anonymous
2. Not collect any identifying participant data.
3. Keep your data for 3 years.
4. Delete electronic data and destroy paper data after 3 years.

WITHDRAWAL PRIVILEGE

It is ok for you to decline to participate in this research study. Even if you say yes now, you are free to say no later, and stop participating at any time, there will be no penalty to you.

If you decide to stop participation, you may do so by: Answering “I wish to withdraw” in the last question read then exit the online survey at any time. If so, I will not use the information I gathered from you.

Your decision will not affect your relationship with the University of West Scotland or cause a loss of benefits to which you might be entitled.

I may stop your participation, even if you did not ask me to, if: The question results become focused on negative experiences in either learning opportunities or relationships with other small business owners.

COST AND PAYMENTS

There is no financial cost to you as a participant in this study. There is no payment for your participation.

COMPENSATION FOR INJURY OR ILLNESS

If you agree to participate in the study, then your consent does not waive any of your

legal rights. However, no funds have been set aside to compensate you in the event of injury.

VOLUNTARY CONSENT

Any questions you have concerning the study or your participation, before or after your consent, will be answered by Olakunle Agboola, [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

This form explains the nature, demands, benefits and any risk of the project. By signing this form, you agree to assume any risks involved. Remember, your part is voluntary. You may choose not to take part. You may withdraw your consent and discontinue your part at any time without penalty or loss of benefit. In signing this consent form, you are not waiving any legal claims, rights, or remedies. A copy of this form will be offered to you to keep for your records.

Your signature below indicates that you consent to take part in the above study.

_____ Subject's

Signature Printed Name Date

"I certify that I have explained to the above individual the nature and purpose, the potential benefits and possible risks associated with participation in this research study, have answered any questions that have been raised, and have witnessed the above signature. These elements of Informed Consent conform to the Assurance given by the University of West Scotland to protect the rights of

human subjects. I have provided (offered) the subject/participant a copy of this signed consent document."

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

Appendix G.

Questionnaire: Pilot or Pre-Field Test

Knowledge Exchange

Knowledge Exchange Among Small Business Owners

The purpose of this questionnaire is to explore how business owner view knowledge exchange

2. To what extent have you:

Never	Less than once a month	Once a month	Never than once a month	Once a week	N/A
-------	------------------------	--------------	-------------------------	-------------	-----

Received knowledge from other small business owners within your community?

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Used knowledge from other small business owners within your community?

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Received knowledge from other small business owners within your industry?

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Used knowledge from other small business owners within your industry?

3. To what extent have other small business owners _____

Never Less Once a Never Once a N/A
 than than month than once week
 once a a a month
 month

in your community received knowledge from you?

in your community used knowledge from you?

in your industry received knowledge from you?

in your industry received knowledge from you?

4. To what extent do you agree with the following?

Strongly Disagree Neither Agree Strongly N/A
 disagree agree or agree
 disagree

I trust the information I received from my external sources is

trustworthy

I trust the source of information I seek

If I face a challenge, I have another small business owner who will give me reliable advice

Small business owners with whom I share knowledge do not try to deceive me for their own profit

5. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following:

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither agree or disagree Agree Strongly agree N/A

in your community received knowledge from you?

in your community used knowledge from you?

6. On average, how many small business owners do you collaborate with on a monthly basis?

- 0-10
- 10-30
- 30-50

- o 50+

7. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I am an active participant in knowledge sharing activities within my community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Most of my connections with other small business owners are within my community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8. I participate in knowledge sharing because _____

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
Knowledge sharing is important	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge sharing is enjoyable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge sharing helps establish relationships with other small business owners	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I want others to think I am	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

competent

Sharing knowledge builds respect
with other small business owners

9. I participate in knowledge sharing because _____

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither Agree Strongly N/A
disagree agree or agree
disagree

I want to improve the performance
of my small business

I need to innovate my product or
service

Knowledge sharing helps establish
relationships with other small
business owners

I have a specific issue I need help
resolving

10. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I feel that I have enough experience to share knowledge with other small business owners	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have multiple methods of being able to share knowledge (for example, in a person , social media, chat forums, podcasts, etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have sufficient time to engage in knowledge sharing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11. Which methods of knowledge sharing do you use?

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Blogs | <input type="checkbox"/> Online teleconference |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Wiki | <input type="checkbox"/> Face to face meetings |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Facebook | <input type="checkbox"/> LinkedIn |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Twitter | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | |

Others (please specify)

12. How often do you participate in knowledge sharing using:

	Less than a month	Once a month	Weekly	Multiple times a week	Daily	N/A
Email	<input type="radio"/>					
Blogs	<input type="radio"/>					
Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
Online discussion forums	<input type="radio"/>					
Face to Face meetings	<input type="radio"/>					
Online teleconferencing	<input type="radio"/>					

13. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
Frequent knowledge sharing is	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

important

My closest colleagues think

knowledge sharing is important

My closest colleagues value mutual

participation in knowledge sharing

Perceptions of Personality

Please rate your perception of personality

14. Extroversion:

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither Agree Strongly N/A
disagree agree or agree
disagree

I am the life of the party

I feel comfortable around people

I often start conversations

I don't talk a lot

I don't like to draw attention to
myself

I am quiet around strangers

15. Agreeableness:

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither agree or disagree Agree Strongly agree N/A

I am interested in people

I sympathize with others feelings

I take time out for others

I am not really interested in others

I am not interested in other people's problems

I feel little concern for others

16. Conscientiousness:

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither agree or disagree Agree Strongly agree N/A

I am always prepared

I get shores done right away

I like order

I have my belongings around

I make a mess of things	<input type="radio"/>					
-------------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I often forget to put things back in their proper places	<input type="radio"/>					
---	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

17. Emotional Stability:

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
----------------------	----------	---------------------------------	-------	-------------------	-----

I am relaxed most of the time	<input type="radio"/>					
-------------------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I seldom feel blue	<input type="radio"/>					
--------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I am not easily bothered by things	<input type="radio"/>					
------------------------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I worry about things	<input type="radio"/>					
----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I get upset easily	<input type="radio"/>					
--------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I get irritated easily	<input type="radio"/>					
------------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

18. Intellect or Imagination:

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
----------------------	----------	---------------------------------	-------	-------------------	-----

I have a vivid imagination	<input type="radio"/>					
----------------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I am quick to understand things	<input type="radio"/>					
---------------------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I spend time reflecting on things	<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I am not interested in abstract ideas

I have difficulty imagining things

I tried to avoid complex people

Appendix H.

Questionnaire: Post-Field Test

Knowledge Exchange

Knowledge Exchange Among Small Medium Enterprises Owners

The purpose of this questionnaire is to explore how business owners view knowledge sharing.

2. To what extent have you:

Never	Less than once a month	Once a month	Never than once a month	Once a week	N/A
-------	------------------------	--------------	-------------------------	-------------	-----

Received knowledge from other small business owners within your community?

Used knowledge from other small business owners within your community?

Received knowledge from other small business owners within your industry?

Used knowledge from other small business owners within your industry?

3. To what extent have other small business owners _____

Never Less Once a Never Once a N/A
 than than month than once week
 once a a a month
 month

in your community received knowledge from you?

in your community used knowledge from you?

in your industry received knowledge from you?

in your industry received knowledge from you?

4. To what extent do you agree with the following?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I trust the information I received from my external sources is trustworthy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust the source of information I seek	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If I face a challenge, I have another small business owner who will give me reliable advice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Small business owners with whom I share knowledge do not try to deceive me for their own profit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. On the average, how many small business owners do you collaborate with on a monthly basis?

- 0-10
- 10-30
- 30-50

- o 50+

6. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I am an active participant in knowledge sharing activities within my community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Most of my connections with other small business owners are within my community	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. I participate in knowledge sharing because _____

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
Knowledge sharing is important	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge sharing is enjoyable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Knowledge sharing helps establish	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

relationships with other small
business owners

I want others to think I am
competent

Sharing knowledge builds respect
with other small business owners

8. I participate in knowledge sharing because _____

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neither Agree Strongly N/A
disagree agree or agree
disagree

I want to improve the performance
of my small business

I need to innovate my product or
service

Knowledge sharing helps establish
relationships with other small
business owners

I have a specific issue I need help

resolving

9. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I feel that I have enough experience to share knowledge with other small business owners	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have multiple methods of being able to share knowledge (for example, in a person , social media, chat forums, podcasts, etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have sufficient time to engage in knowledge sharing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. How often do you participate in knowledge sharing using:

Less than a month	Once a month	Weekly	Multiple times a week	Daily	N/A
-------------------	--------------	--------	-----------------------	-------	-----

Email	<input type="radio"/>					
Blogs	<input type="radio"/>					
Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
Online discussion forums	<input type="radio"/>					
Face to Face meetings	<input type="radio"/>					
Online teleconferencing	<input type="radio"/>					

11. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
Frequent knowledge sharing is important	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My closest colleagues think knowledge sharing is important	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My closest colleagues value mutual participation in knowledge sharing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Perceptions of Personality

Please rate your perception of personality

12. Extroversion:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I am the life of the party	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel comfortable around people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often start conversations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't talk a lot	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't like to draw attention to myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am quiet around strangers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

13. Agreeableness:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I am interested in people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I sympathize with others feelings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I take time out for others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not really interested in others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I am not interested in other people's problems

I feel little concern for others

14. Conscientiousness:

Strongly Disagree Neither Agree Strongly N/A
disagree agree or
disagree

I am always prepared

I get shores done right away

I like order

I have my belongings around

I make a mess of things

I often forget to put things back in their proper places

15. Emotional Stability:

Strongly Disagree Neither Agree Strongly N/A
disagree agree or
disagree

I am relaxed most of the time

I seldom feel blue

I am not easily bothered by things	<input type="radio"/>					
I worry about things	<input type="radio"/>					
I get upset easily	<input type="radio"/>					
I get irritated easily	<input type="radio"/>					

16. Intellect or Imagination:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	N/A
I have a vivid imagination	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am quick to understand things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I spend time reflecting on things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not interested in abstract ideas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have difficulty imagining things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I try to avoid complex people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Interview and Focus Group

Please indicate if you would be willing to participate in either an interview conducted online or be a number focus or be a group with 7 to 10 other small business owners.

17. Would you be willing to participate in an interview?

Yes

No

18. Would you be willing to participate in an online focus group?

Yes

No

Contact Information

Thank you for your willingness to participate in either an interview or focus group. Please complete the contact information below. Your information will be used ONLY for contacting you to schedule the next session.

19. Contact Information

Name:

Address:

Phone Number:

Appendix I.**Interview Protocol: Pilot or Pre-Field Test****Interview Guide and Protocol*****Interview Questions:***

Date: _____ Time _____

Notes to interviewees:

Thank you all for your participation. I know your time is very valuable and I appreciate you all for allowing me to interview you for my dissertation project. I am confident your input will be extremely useful in helping me further understand strategies used to capitalize on external knowledge exchange and professional relationships with other small business owners to develop absorptive capacity.

Confidentiality of all responses is guaranteed.

The session will be audio recorded and transcribed for accuracy and analysis purposes. The participants may choose to not any of the questions posed by the researcher.

Approximate length of interview: No more than 45 minutes.

Introduction

1.1 Could you describe your small business?

1.2 Is your product complimentary or competitive within the market?(e.g.

Spotify is complimentary to Uber)

1.3 What does knowledge sharing mean to you?

2. Knowledge sharing in the small business sector

Knowledge sharing is the exchange of knowledge such as skills, expertise or ideas

2.1 Within the past year, how have you participated in exchange of knowledge with other small business owners?

2.2 What was the topic of the knowledge exchange activities?

2.3 What did you learn from the knowledge sharing activities?

2.4 How did you learn about the opportunity to participate in the knowledge exchange activities?

3. Recognizing the value in knowledge exchange

The value of knowledge exchange is filtered through past experiences, knowledge, and evaluation against current goals of the organization.

3.1 How do you determine what knowledge exchange activities have potential value to your small business?

3.2 How does your prior knowledge influence your participation in knowledge exchange activities?

3.3 What factors prompt you to participate in a knowledge exchange activity?

(e.g. market trends, customer expectations, customer feedback, local market conditions, invitation to participate)

3.4 What methods of knowledge exchange delivery motivate you to participate?

(e.g. online, close geographic proximity, promoted by a certain organization, social)

3.5 What criteria do you use to determine the sources of knowledge exchange ? (e.g. past experience, tacit knowledge, formal or informal exchange, established relationships)

3.6 How do you prioritize searching for knowledge exchange opportunities?

3.7 Are there factors which prevent you from participating in knowledge exchange opportunities? (e.g. source of the knowledge, alliance participation, prior knowledge)

4. Acquiring external knowledge

Acquiring external knowledge is the firm's ability to identify sources of external knowledge and acquire external knowledge. (Potential Absorptive Capacity)

4.1 What type of knowledge do you seek the most? (e.g. Tacit or explicit, technical, or non-technical, specific solutions to problems, any knowledge that could potentially benefit the firm)

4.2 How do you search for knowledge exchange opportunities? (e.g. informally through other small business owners, through other organizations, through professional organizations)

4.3 What systematic methods for acquiring external knowledge do you have in place?

4.4 What channels do you learn about external exchange of knowledge?

(e.g. social media, other small business owners, trade publications, suppliers, customers, small business alliances)

4.5 What is a reasonable number of knowledge exchange opportunities for your firm to participate? (e.g. once a month, once quarter)

4.6 Why would your organization not participate more often?

4.7 What factors motivate you to acquire external knowledge?

4.8 How do relationships with other small business owners influence your external knowledge acquisition?

4.9 How does innovation initiatives influence your external knowledge acquisition?

5. Capitalizing on external knowledge

Capitalizing on external knowledge is transferring the knowledge to the firm to improve the current operations and/or product.

5.1 What knowledge have you used in either improving operations or developing innovation within your firm?

5.2 What challenges have you faced in using external knowledge for either improving

operations or developing innovation? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of prior knowledge, lack of internal enthusiasm)

5.3 How have you overcome some of these challenges?

5.4 What external knowledge have you tried to use that ended up not being successful?

5.5 What indicators could have prevented the lack of success in using the external knowledge?

6. Role of professional relationships in knowledge exchange

Relationships with other small business owners provide a great resource for external knowledge sharing.

6.1 How do you perceive the influence of your personality in establishing professional relationships?

6.2 How do you cultivate relationships with small business owners in the local community?

6.3 How do you cultivate relationships with small business owners outside of the local community? (e.g. within your specific industry)

6.4 What level of interaction between small business is ideal for you? (e.g. casually, weekly, monthly)

6.5 What is your perception of the importance for small business owners within the local community to engage in knowledge sharing?

6.6 How does an established relationship influence your participation in knowledge sharing?

6.7 What indicators could have prevented the lack of success in using the external

knowledge?

7. Conclusion

7.1 How do you think knowledge exchange has influenced your firm?

7.2 Would you like to add any concluding remarks about knowledge exchange that would be beneficial to new small business owners?

Thank you for your time and cooperation.

Appendix J.

Interview Protocol: Post-Field Test

Interview Guide and Protocol

Interview Questions:

Date: _____ Time _____

Notes to interviewees:

Thank you for your participation. I know your time is very valuable and I appreciate the opportunity to interview you for my dissertation project. I am confident your input will be extremely useful in helping me further understand strategies used to capitalize on external knowledge exchange and professional relationships with small business owners.

Confidentiality of all responses is guaranteed.

The session will be audio recorded and transcribed for accuracy and analysis purposes. You may choose to not answer any of the questions posed by the researcher or to stop at any time.

The questions will begin with knowledge exchange and transition to capitalizing on knowledge and conclude with professional relationships.

The approximate length of the interview will be no more than 45 minutes.

1. Introduction

1.1 Could you describe your small business?

1.2 How long have you been a small business owner?

1.2 Why did you decide to become a business owner?

2. Knowledge Exchange in the small business sector

Knowledge exchange is the exchange of knowledge such as skills, expertise, or ideas

2.1 What does the term knowledge exchange mean to you?

2.2 Within the past year, how have you participated in knowledge exchange with other small business owners?

2.3 What was the topic of the knowledge exchange activities?

2.4 What was most impactful for you regarding the knowledge exchange activities?

2.5 How did you learn about the opportunity to participate in the knowledge exchange activities?

3. Recognizing the value in exchange of knowledge

The value of knowledge exchange is filtered through past experiences, knowledge, and evaluation against current goals of the organization.

3.1 How do you determine what knowledge exchange activities have potential value to your small business?

3.2 What factors motivate you to participate in an external knowledge exchange activity? (e.g. prior knowledge, type of knowledge, need for innovation, market trends, customer expectations, solution to a problem, local market conditions, invitation to participate)

3.3 What criteria do you use to determine the sources of knowledge exchange? (e.g. past experience, tacit knowledge, formal or informal exchange, established relationships)

3.4 How do you prioritize searching for knowledge exchange opportunities?

3.5 Are there factors which prevent you from participating in knowledge exchange opportunities? (e.g. source of the knowledge, alliance participation, prior knowledge)

4. Acquiring external knowledge

Acquiring external knowledge is the firm's ability to identify sources of external knowledge and acquire external knowledge. (Potential Absorptive Capacity)

4.1 What type of knowledge do you seek the most? (e.g. Tacit or explicit, technical, or non-technical, specific solutions to problems, any knowledge that could potentially benefit

the firm)

- 4.2 What systematic methods for acquiring external knowledge do you have in place?
- 4.3 What factors of knowledge exchange motivate you to participate? (e.g. online, close geographic proximity, other small business owners, trade publications)
- 4.4 What is a reasonable number of knowledge exchange opportunities for your firm to participate? (e.g. once a month, once quarter)
- 4.5 Why would your team not participate more often?
- 4.6 How do relationships with other small business owners influence your external knowledge acquisition?

5. Capitalizing on external knowledge

Capitalizing on external knowledge is transferring the knowledge to the firm to improve the current operations and/or product.

- 5.1 How does innovation initiatives influence your external knowledge acquisition?
- 5.2 What knowledge have you used in either improving operations or developing innovation within your firm?
- 5.3 What challenges have you faced in using external knowledge for either improving operations or developing innovation? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of prior knowledge, lack of internal enthusiasm)
- 5.4 How have you overcome some of these challenges?
- 5.5 What external knowledge have you tried to use that ended up not being successful?
- 5.6 What indicators could have prevented the lack of success in using the external knowledge?

6. Role of professional relationships in knowledge exchange

Relationships with other small business owners provide a great resource for external knowledge exchange.

- 6.1 How do you perceive the influence of your personality in establishing professional relationships?
- 6.2 How do you cultivate relationships with small business owners in the local community?
- How do you cultivate relationships with small business owners outside of the local community? (e.g. within your specific industry)
- 6.3 What level of interaction between small business is ideal for you? (e.g. casually, weekly, monthly)

6.4 What is your perception of the importance for small business owners within the local community to engage in knowledge exchange?

6.5 How does an established relationship influence your participation in knowledge exchange?

7. Conclusion

7.1 Would you like to add any concluding remarks about knowledge exchange that would be beneficial to new small business owners?

Thank you for your time and cooperation.

Appendix K.

Focus Group Guide: Pilot or Pre-Field Test

Focus Group Instrument and Protocol

Focus Group Session Questions:

Date: _____

Time: _____

Total Number of Participates: _____

Number of New Participates: _____

Number of Returning Participates: _____

Notes to interviewees:

Thank you all for your participation. I know your time is very valuable and I appreciate you all for allowing me to interview you for my dissertation project. I am confident your input will be extremely useful in helping me further understand strategies used to capitalize on external knowledge exchange and professional relationships with other small business owners.

Confidentiality of all responses is guaranteed.

The session will be audio recorded and transcribed for accuracy and analysis purposes. The

participants may choose to not any of the questions posed by the researcher.

Approximate length of interview: No more than 60 minutes.

8. Knowledge Exchange in the small business sector

Knowledge exchange is the sharing of knowledge such as skills, expertise, or ideas

8.1 Within the past year, how have you participated in knowledge exchange with others small business owners?

8.2 How did you learn about the opportunity to participate in the knowledge exchange activities?

9. Capitalizing on external knowledge

Capitalizing on external knowledge is transferring the knowledge to the firm to improve the current operations and/or product.

9.1 What knowledge have you used in either improving operations or developing innovation within your firm?

9.2 What challenges have you faced in using external knowledge for either improving operations or developing innovation? (e.g. lack of resources, lack of prior knowledge, lack of internal enthusiasm)

9.3 How have you overcome some of these challenges?

9.4 What external knowledge have you tried to use that ended up not being successful?

9.5 What indicators could have prevented the lack of success in using the external knowledge?

10. Role of professional relationships in knowledge sharing

Relationships with other small business owners provide a great resource for external knowledge exchange.

10.1 How do you perceive the influence of your personality in establishing professional relationships?

10.2 How do you cultivate relationships with small business owners in the local community?

10.3 How do you cultivate relationships with small business owners outside of the local community? (e.g. within your specific industry)

10.4 What level of interaction between small business is ideal for you? (e.g. casually, weekly, monthly)

- 10.5 What is your perception of the importance for small business owners within the local community to engage in knowledge exchange?
- 10.6 How does an established relationship influence your participation in knowledge exchange?
- 10.7 What indicators could have prevented the lack of success in using the external knowledge?

11. Conclusion

- 11.1 How do you think knowledge exchange has influenced your firm?
- 11.2 Would you like to add any concluding remarks about knowledge exchange that would be beneficial to new small business owners?

Closing:

Thank you again for your time today. Please do not hesitate to contact me with any further information or concerns you have regarding my project or our conversation.

Appendix L.

Focus Group Guide: Post-Field Test

Focus Group Instrument and Protocol

Focus Group Session Questions:

Date: _____

Time: _____

Total Number of Participants: ____ _

Welcome

Olakunle Agboola will serve as the moderator for the focus group session. The session will be recorded using the Zoom.com interface.

Topic

Our topic is to explore how small business owners capitalize on knowledge exchange. The focus group is intended to collect experiences in knowledge exchange and establishing relationships with other small business owners.

The results will be used for helping identify how small business owners can engage knowledge exchange to improve overall success rates of small businesses.

You were selected as a result of your responses to the questionnaire.

Guidelines

1. No right or wrong answers, only differing points of view
2. We're recording, one person speaking at a time
3. We're on a first name basis
4. You don't need to agree with others, but you must listen respectfully as others share their views

Rules for cellular phones

We ask that you turn off your phones. If you cannot and if you must respond to a call, please do so as quietly as possible and rejoin us as quickly as you can.

My role as moderator will be to guide the discussion Talk to each other Notes to participants:

Thank you all for your participation. I know your time is very valuable and I appreciate you all for allowing me to interview you for my dissertation project. I am confident your input will be extremely useful in helping me further understand strategies used to capitalize on external knowledge exchange and professional relationships with other small business owners.

Confidentiality of all responses is guaranteed.

The session will be audio recorded and transcribed for accuracy and analysis purposes. The participants may choose to not answer any of the questions posed by the researcher.

Approximate length of the focus group: No more than 45 minutes.

Knowledge exchange in the small business sector

Knowledge exchange is the sharing of knowledge such as skills, expertise, or ideas

1. What does knowledge exchange mean to you?
2. How important is it for you to engage in knowledge exchange with others outside of your business?
3. What is your preferred method of knowledge exchange?

Capitalizing on external knowledge

Capitalizing on external knowledge is transferring the knowledge to the firm to improve the current operations and/or product.

1. What are the benefits of knowledge exchange for you?
2. How has participating in knowledge exchange improved your business?
3. What prevents external knowledge from being useful?
4. Tell me about a time when you had limited resources (such as time, money, or experience), but found ways to implement an idea you had heard?

Role of professional relationships in knowledge exchange

Relationships with other small business owners provide a great resource for external knowledge exchange.

1. What value do you place on relationships with other small business owners?
2. How have other small business owners contributed to your success in your business?
3. How have you contributed to the success of another small business owner?

Conclusion

1. What is the best advice you could give a new small business owner regarding knowledge exchange and professional relationships?
2. Would you like to add any concluding remarks that may not have been covered in the discussion?

Closing:

Thank you again for your time today. Please do not hesitate to contact me with any further information or concerns you have regarding my project or our conversation.

Appendix M.

16 Step Process Map

Step 1	Project approval from University of West Scotland
Step 2	Identify small business owners through local chambers of commerce and contact via email per UWS approved procedure to participate in the survey. Allow two weeks for a response to participate.
Step 3	<p>Destroy identifying information of small business owners who did not participate.</p> <p>Assign unique identifier to participants.</p> <p>Master list will be kept separate from all other data files in a locked safe.</p> <p>The master list will be the only means to identify participants.</p>
Step 4	Once surveys are complete, select 20 participants to conduct interview based on survey responses
Step 5	Begin conducting interviews using Zoom.
Step 6	After completion of the interview, the raw media file will be transcribed.
Step 7	Begin focus group selection process
Step 8	Begin conducting focus group using Zoom.
Step 9	After completion of the focus group, the raw media file will be transcribed.

Step 10	<p>Transcript of each interview will be presented to corresponding participants for member checking.</p> <p>The participant will be informed this will provide opportunity forhim/her to edit, clarify, or delete any comments.</p>
Step 11	<p>Transcript of the focus group will be presented to the participants for member checking.</p> <p>The participant will be informed this will provide opportunity forhim/her to edit, clarify, or delete any comments.</p>
Step 12	<p>Focus group and interview scripts will be loaded into MaxQDA.</p> <p>Thematic data analysis will be used.</p> <p>.</p>
Step 13	<p>Thematic analysis will be conducted on interview and focus group independently first.</p>
Step 14	<p>Notations will be made throughout the analysis process that highlight trends in knowledge sharing, innovations which resulted</p>

	from knowledge exchange, and how the small business owner values relationships with other small business owners.
Step 15	Once complete, both sets of transcripts will be merged into MaxQDA for a thematic analysis to identify commonalities.
Step 16	Revise/ complete analysis. Complete results write-up. Archive all data for 3 years. Destroy any personal information belonging to the participants and all data after 3 years.

Appendix N.**Invitation for Interview**

Dear xxxx,

Thank you for taking part in a research study by Olakunle Agboola, a doctoral student at the University of West Scotland. This study will explore how small business owners perceive their knowledge exchange and professional relationships contribute to the development of absorptive capacity.

Details of the research are attached to this email. The informed consent must be signed before taking part in the interview.

The private interview contains open-response questions. The 60-minute interview will be audio recorded. All information obtained in this study is private. The results of this study may be presented or used in reports or publications. You will not be identified. All data obtained for this study will be stored on a password-protected computer. After 3 years of completion of this study, all data will be destroyed.

Please respond with a date and time for the interview that is convenient for you.

Questions regarding the research study may be sent to Olakunle Agboola

at Personal details withheld.

Thank you in advance for your help,

Olakunle Agboola

Appendix O.
Invitation for Focus Group

Dear xxxxx,

Thank you for taking part in a research study by Olakunle Agboola, a doctoral student at the University of West Scotland. This study will explore how small business owners perceive knowledge exchange and professional relationships contribute to development of absorptive capacity.

Details of the research are attached to this email. The informed consent must be signed before taking part in the interview.

The focus group is designed to be confidential. The focus group contains open-response questions. The 60-minute interview will be audio recorded. All information obtained in this study is private. The results of this study may be presented or used in reports or publications. You will not be identified. All data obtained for this study will be stored on a password-protected computer. After 3 years of completion of this study, all data will be destroyed.

Using the link below, please specify a date and time convenient for you to participate in the focus group.

<http://www.signupgenius.com/xxxxx>

Questions regarding the research study may be sent to Olakunle Agboola at

████████████████████

Personal details withheld.

Thank you in advance for your help,

Olakunle Agboola

Appendix P.
Invitation for Questionnaire

Dear xxxxx,

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study by Olakunle Jamiu Agboola, a doctoral student at the University of West Scotland. This study will explore how small business owners perceive knowledge exchange and professional relationships as contributing to the development of absorptive capacity.

Details of the research are attached to this email. The informed consent will be provided on page 1 of the questionnaire. You may select “I agree” to proceed with the questionnaire or “I disagree” to exit and not take the questionnaire.

The questionnaire is designed to be confidential. The questionnaire contains rating questions which will establish your involvement in knowledge sharing. Additionally, you will be asked to rate your perception of your personality. The questionnaire will take no more than 10 minutes.

All information obtained in this study is private. The results of this study may be presented or used in reports or publications. You will not be identified. All data obtained for this study will be stored on a password-protected computer. After 3 years of completion of this study, all data will be destroyed.

Questions regarding the research study may be sent to Olakunle Jamiu

Agboola at [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Thank you in advance for your help,

Olakunle Agboola

Appendix R.

Focus Group Code Cloud

Figure R1. Focus group code cloud

Appendix S.

Initial Codes

Table S1.

Initial Codes

Codebook - List of Initial Codes from Interviews and Focus		
Group		
Personality	Receiving Knowledge	Face to Face
Personality Influence on knowledge sharing	Unsuccessful Advice	Time
Type	Type of social interaction	Introvert
Reason for being a small business owner	Approach toward knowledgesharing events	Extrovert
Relationship	Expectations	Avoid interaction
Influence on knowledge sharing	Frequency	Participate Monthly
Ways to cultivate	Results	Participate Weekly
Frequency in cultivating	Topics	Blog
Recommendations	Podcast	Warm Referrals
Benefits	Innovate Operations	Business Town Ordinances

Priorities	Increase Business Value	Meetup
Personality influence on relationships	Mastermind	Go get coffee
Trust	Problem Solving	Phone call
Challenges in Absorptive Capacity	Improving operations	Go out for drinks
Methods of knowledge sharing	Memberships	Business coach
Challenges	Participation	Reciprocate business
Mentoring	Challenges - Participation	Always being alone
Receiving Knowledge	Knowledge Definition	Sharing Helping others
Giving Knowledge	Seeking Knowledge	Trust is everything
Relationships are everything	Social Media	Always research validity of information

Appendix T.

Thematic Network

Table T1.

Thematic Network

General Themes	Organizing Themes	Overall Themes	RQ1	RQ 2	RQ 3
How do small business owners	Face to face	Engaging knowledge exchange		X	
participation	in knowledge				
is preferred	exchange				
Professional organizations					
provide knowledge					
exchange with					
specific goals.					
An individual's personality is a	Motivational factors	in knowledge			

factor in exchange
 motivating the participation
 individual to
 participate.

Limited	Challenges in	Participating in	knowledge	
resources	participating in	sharing		
hinder	knowledge exchange			X
absorptive				
capacity				
Content must				
be relevant				
An individual's				
perceptions of				
value in				
participation.				
Prior	Strategies to			
experiences	improve			
influence	knowledge			
current	exchange			
approach.	Participation			
Socializing	improved			
the knowledge				
Exchange				
Experience				

General	Organizin	RQ	RQ	R	
Theme	gThemes	Global Themes	1	2	Q
s					3
Negative knowledge exchange experience shinder participation in knowledge sharing	Knowledge Exchange impacts the business	Knowledge Sharing Factors of Absorptive Capacity		X	
Positive knowledge exchange experience s helps strengthen business operations.					
Participating in knowledge exchange	Role of relationships in knowledge	Relationship Factors of Absorptive Capacity			X

opportunities Exchange

was

influenced by

established

relationships.

Intentionall

y

establishing

relationships

reduces

obstacles in

knowledge

exchange.

A mentor is

an important

resource for

every small

business

owner.

Mentees

should

consider

being a

mentor.

Being Methods used to Cultivating relationships

consistent in cultivate
meeting relationships with
people who small business
share owners
common goals
and
values.

X

Trust is the
result of
established
Relationships

General	Organizin		RQ	RQ	R
Theme	gThemes	Global Themes	1	2	Q
s					3

and improves

the knowledge

exchange

experience.

Relationships

are best

cultivated by

showing

interest in the

other person.

Personality Personality types Influences of the Small Business Owner's

type influences Personality

influences relationships and

X

how knowledge

relationships sharing

are established

and cultivated.

Appendix U.
Codebook with Categories

Table U1.

Codebook with Categories

Codebook from Interviews and Focus Group	
Personality	Approach toward knowledge exchange events
Personality - Strategy for strengthening	Approach - Deepen perspectives
Influence on relationships	Approach - Expand resources
Reason for being a small business owner	Warm referrals
Personality Influence on knowledge exchange	Memberships
Type	Improving operations
Relationship	Problem Solving
Influence on knowledge exchange	Operational goals influence on knowledge sharing
Ways to cultivate	Topics
Frequency in cultivating	Advice - Business value
Relationships – Strategies	Advice - Business operations
Benefits	Types of knowledge
Priorities	Type – Marketing
Personality influence on relationships	Type – Operations

Trust	Type – Technical
Challenges in Absorptive Capacity	Participation
Challenges – Strategies	Participation – Methods
Methods of knowledge exchange	Participation – Selection
Challenges	Participation – Frequency
Mentoring	Participation – Motivation
Mentoring - Receiving Knowledge	Participation – Challenges
Mentoring - Giving Knowledge	
Receiving Knowledge	
Type of social interaction	
Most impactful	
Unsuccessful Knowledge exchange	

Appendix V.**Expert Panel**

The following individuals reviewed the interview and focus group guide:

Dr. Osoba, DBA

- Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun State , Nigeria

- Focus – consumer behavior

Dr. F D., Ph.D.

- Olabisi Onabanjo University

- Focus – sociology, criminal justiceDr.

D. S., Ph.D.

- Olabisi Onabanjo University

- Focus – Qualitative research, History of Science

Appendix W.
Personality Scores

Table W1.

Extroversion

Extroversion							
n							
Respondent ID	I am the life of the party	I feel comfortabl e around people	I often start conversations	don't talk a lot	I like to draw attention to myself	I am quiet around stranger s	Score
NS014F	4	4	4	2	3	4	3
NS013F	4	5	5	1	2	1	10
NS012F	2	2	3	4	3	4	-4
NS011F	5	5	5	2	1	1	11
NS010I	3	3	3	4	4	2	-1
NS009I	2	4	4	5	3	3	-1
NS007I	5	4	4	2	1	2	8
NS006I	3	4	4	2	2	3	4
NS005I	2	2	4	3	4	5	-4
NS004I	4	4	4	2	2	2	6

NS003I	3	4	2	4	3	4	-2
NS002I	3	4	4	1	3	1	6
NS001I	3	4	3	4	3	4	-1
NB009F	2	4	2	1	2	4	1
NB008F	3	4	4	2	4	2	3
NB007I	4	5	4	2	4	2	5
NB006I	4	4	4	2	2	3	5
NB005I	3	4	5	2	2	2	6
NB004I	2	4	4	4	4	4	-2
NB003I	4	4	4	2	3	2	5
NB002I	3	5	5	1	4	1	7
NB001I	1	4	4	4	4	4	-3
NA004I	4	4	4	2	4	2	4
NA003I	4	5	3	2	3	3	4
NA002I	4	4	3	3	2	3	3
NA001I	3	4	4	2	3	3	3

Table W2.

Agreeableness

Agreeableness							
s							
Respondent tID	I sympathize with others' feelings			I am not interested in other people's problems			Score
	I am interested in others' feelings	I take time for others	I am not really interested in others	I am not interested in other people's problems	I feel little concern for others		
NS014F	4	5	5	1	1	1	11
NA013F	4	3	4	1	3	1	6
NS012F	4	5	4	1	1	1	10
NS011F	5	5	5	1	1	1	12
NS010I	5	5	5	1	1	1	12
NS009I	5	4	5	1	1	1	11
NS007I	5	5	5	1	2	1	11
NS006I	5	5	5	1	2	1	11
NS005I	4	5	4	1	1	1	10
NS004I	4	5	5	4	3	1	6
NS003I	4	1	4	2	3	1	3

NS002I	4	4	4	2	2	2	6
NS001I	4	4	4	2	2	1	7
NB009F	5	5	5	1	1	1	12
NB008F	5	5	4	1	1	1	11
NB007I	5	5	5	2	2	1	10
NB006I	5	4	4	1	1	1	10
NB005I	4	5	5	1	1	1	11
NB004I	3	2	2	4	4	3	-4
NB003I	5	5	5	2	1	1	11
NB002I	5	5	4	2	3	2	7
NB001I	5	5	5	2	2	2	9
NA004I	5	4	4	1	2	1	9
NA003I	5	5	5	1	2	1	11
NA002I	4	5	5	1	1	1	11
NA001I	4	3	4	3	4	3	1

Table W3.

Conscientiousness

Conscientiousness								
Respondent ID	I get I am chores always done prepared right away			I leave I I like my order belongin gs around		I make a mess of things	I often forget to put things back in their proper place	Score
	NS014F	5	4	3	3	2	3	
NS013F	4	3	5	3	1	2	6	
NS012F	2	4	4	4	4	4	-2	
NS011F	4	3	4	5	5	2	-1	
NS010I	5	3	3	4	4	4	-1	
NS009I	4	3	3	4	3	2	1	
NS007I	2	1	5	4	4	4	-4	
NS006I	4	4	4	2	2	2	6	
NS005I	4	4	5	1	1	2	9	
NS004I	4	3	5	2	3	1	6	
NS003I	4	3	5	2	2	1	7	

NS002I	3	2	4	4	3	3	-1
NS001I	5	5	4	2	1	1	10
NB009F	4	2	4	4	2	2	2
NB008F	2	2	5	3	2	2	2
NB007I	4	4	4	5	5	5	-3
NB006I	2	2	4	4	4	4	-4
NB005I	4	4	4	1	1	1	9
NB004I	3	3	4	3	2	3	2
NB003I	5	5	5	2	1	1	11
NB002I	4	3	4	3	3	4	1
NB001I	4	3	5	1	2	1	8
NA004I	5	4	4	2	1	2	8
NA003I	5	4	5	1	1	1	11
NA002I	2	2	2	2	2	2	0
NA001I	4	4	5	3	2	4	4

Table W4.

Emotional Stability

Emotional Stability							
Respondent ID	I am relaxed most of the time	I seldom feel blue	I am not easily bothered by things	I worry about things	I get upset easily	I get irritated easily.	Score
NS014F	4	4	4	2	2	6	
					2		
NS013F	4	4	3	1	3	4	
					3		
NS012F	4	4	3	3	3	1	
					4		
NS011F	4	4	4	3	2	5	
					2		
NS010I	4	4	4	3	2	5	
					2		
NS009I	5	4	5	2	1	10	

						1	
NS007I	5	5	4	5	3		3
						3	
NS006I	4	4	4	1	2		7
						2	
NS005I	4	4	2	2	3		2
						3	
NS004I	4	4	3	3	3		2
						3	
NS003I	5	3	3	1	1		7
						2	
NS002I	2	2	2	2	4		-3
						3	
NS001I	4	4	3	4	2		3
						2	
NB009F	4	2	4	4	3		-1
						4	
NB008F	5	2	4	2	2		5
						2	
NB007I	4	4	4	2	2		6
						2	
NB006I	2	2	4	4	2		0
						2	
NB005I	4	3	4	3	2		4
						2	

NB004I	4	5	3	2	2		4
						4	
NB003I	5	5	5	3	2		9
						1	
NB002I	4	3	4	2	1		6
						2	
NB001I	4	3	2	4	4		-3
						4	
NA004I	4	5	4	3	3		4
						3	
NA003I	4	4	4	2	1		8
						1	
NA002I	4	5	4	2	1	1	9
NA001I	3	3	2	3	3	4	-2

Table W5.

Intellect or Imagination

	Intellect or Imagination						
	I have a vivid imagination	I am quick to understand things	I spend time reflecting on things	I am not interested in abstract ideas	I have difficulty imagining things	I try to avoid completing people	Score
NS014F	3	4	4	3	2	2	4
NS013F	3	4	5	4	3	3	2
NS012F	5	2	4	2	1	2	6
NS011F	5	4	4	3	2	2	6
NS010I	3	5	5	1	2	1	9
NS009I	5	4	5	1	1	1	11
NS007I	5	4	5	4	3	1	6
NS006I	3	3	4	4	3	3	0
NS005I	3	4	5	3	3	3	3
NS004I	5	4	5	1	1	1	11

NS003I	5	4	3	3	1	3	5
NS002I	4	4	5	1	2	3	7
NS001I	5	4	4	2	2	2	7
NB009F	4	4	5	2	2	2	7
NB008F	3	3	5	2	3	3	3
NB007I	5	5	5	2	1	1	11
NB006I	4	4	4	2	1	1	8
NB005I	4	5	5	2	2	4	6
NB004I	4	4	2	1	1	3	5
NB003I	5	5	5	1	1	2	11
NB002I	4	4	5	2	2	2	7
NB001I	4	2	5	3	2	2	4
NA004I	5	5	4	2	1	1	10
NA003I	5	5	5	1	1	1	12
NA002I	5	4	5	2	1	1	10
NA001I	5	4	4	2	2	2	7

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACAP

Absorptive Capacity